

Selfie Expressions With Factorial, Fibonacci and Triangular Values¹

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Abstract

Selfie expressions are written in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. This work brings expressions where one side with factorial, and other side with Fibonacci and/or with triangular numbers having same digit's order. This we have done in different ways. One expressions with Factorial, Fibonacci and Triangular values. Second, expressions with Factorial and Fibonacci values. Third, expressions with Factorial and Triangular numbers. Forth, expressions with Fibonacci sequence and Triangular numbers. The operations used are addition, subtraction and multiplication.

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¹It is revised and combined version author's previous works <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a114.pdf> [8], <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a122.pdf> [9] and <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a123.pdf> [10] done in 2017.

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1 Selfie Expressions

Selfie expressions are very much similar to **selfie numbers**. Selfie numbers are represented by its own digits by use of some operations, while **selfie expressions** are the expressions where both sides have same digits, not necessarily same operations on both sides, i.e., **same digits equality expressions**. Below are different ways of expressing equalities with same digits on both sides:

• **Multiplicative Equalities**

$$abcd... \times efgh... = cbad... \times gfhe.. \quad \forall a,b,c,d,e,... \in \mathbb{N}_+. \tag{1}$$

• **Power and Addition**

$$a^b + c^d + ... = ab + cd + ..., \quad \forall a,b,c,d,.. \in \mathbb{N}. \tag{2}$$

• **Factorial and Power**

$$a! \times b! + (c! + d!) \times e! + \dots = a^a + b^b - c^c \times (d^d - e^e) + \dots, \quad \forall a, b, c, d, e, \dots \in \mathbb{N}_+, \text{ etc.} \quad (3)$$

$$a! \times b! + (c! + d!) \times e! + \dots = a^c + (b^d - c^a) \times d^e - e^b + \dots, \quad \forall a, b, c, d, e, \dots \in \mathbb{N}_+, \text{ etc.} \quad (4)$$

We observe that the (4) is different from the (3) in right side of the expression. In case (3), the power of digits is same as of bases. In case of (4), it is not necessary that the power is same as of digits, but is a permutation of same digits as of bases. See below more general way.

$$(a!, b!, c!, \dots) = (a^a, b^b, c^c, \dots)$$

$$(a!, b!, c!, \dots) = (a, b, c, \dots)^{(a, b, c, \dots)}.$$

The first expression is simplified form of (3) and the second expression is similar to (4).

Let us explain one by one, the idea of above four **selfie expressions**, i.e., (1)-(4).

1.1 Multiplicative Selfie Equalities

This subsection brings results based on the expression (1). By **multiplicative selfie equalities**, we understand that there are equalities, where each side is separated by operation of multiplications having same digits on both sides, not necessarily in same order. There are many ways of writing these kind of numbers explained in following subsections.

1.1.1 First Type

In this case, we have multiplicative equalities with equal number of digits on both sides and also in each multiplicative factor. The operation of multiplications is with number and its reverse forming a palindromic-type expression. For example, Based on idea of expressions are written in such a way that numbers formed by same digits multiplied by its reverse are equal to another group of multiplicative factors with same digits but of different numbers. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned} \diamond 37468 \times 86473 &= 47386 \times 68374 \\ \diamond 37596 \times 69573 &= 39756 \times 65793 \\ \diamond 39648 \times 84693 &= 48396 \times 69384 \\ \diamond 45495 \times 59454 &= 49545 \times 54594 \\ \diamond 46069 \times 96064 &= 64096 \times 69046 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \diamond 120024 \times 420021 &= 210042 \times 240012 \\ \diamond 102204 \times 402201 &= 201402 \times 204102 \\ \diamond 130026 \times 620031 &= 260013 \times 310062 \\ \diamond 120036 \times 630021 &= 210063 \times 360012 \\ \diamond 102306 \times 603201 &= 201603 \times 306102 \end{aligned}$$

1.1.2 Second Type

The second case is similar to first one, having the same number of digits in each multiplicative factor but not forming a palindromic-type expression. For example,

$$\diamond 2017 \times 3404 = 1702 \times 4034$$

$$\diamond 2017 \times 6808 = 1702 \times 8068$$

$$\diamond 1729 \times 3584 = 1792 \times 3458$$

$$\diamond 1729 \times 3854 = 1927 \times 3458$$

$$\diamond 1729 \times 4358 = 2179 \times 3458$$

$$\diamond 1729 \times 4732 = 2197 \times 3724$$

$$\diamond 1729 \times 5438 = 2719 \times 3458$$

$$\diamond 1729 \times 5781 = 1927 \times 5187$$

1.1.3 Third Type

The third case is similar to second one, but there is no rule with order of digits. Only thing is that on both sides of the equality sign, there are same digits

There are many numbers, but we have written only those with more than one equality sign. See below examples,

$$\diamond 162 \times 8064 = 216 \times 6048 = 648 \times 2016$$

$$\diamond 162 \times 8073 = 207 \times 6318 = 702 \times 1863$$

$$\diamond 17 \times 35945 = 35 \times 17459 = 395 \times 1547$$

$$\diamond 176 \times 7469 = 194 \times 6776 = 776 \times 1694$$

$$\diamond 18 \times 39879 = 189 \times 3798 = 378 \times 1899$$

$$\diamond 18 \times 41553 = 54 \times 13851 = 513 \times 1458$$

$$\diamond 1782 \times 43956 = 2178 \times 35964 = 3564 \times 21978 = 4356 \times 17982$$

$$\diamond 18 \times 2830464 = 486 \times 104832 = 1404 \times 36288 = 3024 \times 16848$$

$$\diamond 18 \times 5204736 = 162 \times 578304 = 3456 \times 27108 = 4518 \times 20736$$

$$\diamond 198 \times 179982 = 297 \times 119988 = 1188 \times 29997 = 1782 \times 19998$$

$$\diamond 198 \times 339966 = 396 \times 169983 = 1683 \times 39996 = 3366 \times 19998$$

$$\diamond 2 \times 12089121 = 11 \times 2198022 = 222 \times 108911 = 1221 \times 19802$$

Due to large quantity of numbers, we worked only with double or higher equality signs. Some times these expressions with single equality are famous as **vamp numbers**. For more numbers of this kind refer author's work [11].

1.2 Powers and Addition

Following the idea of expression (2) the author wrote the numbers **2017** [6] and **1729** [7] as:

$$\mathbf{2017} := 4^4 + 41^2 + 77^0 + 79^1 = 44 + 412 + 770 + 791$$

$$:= 1^4 + 44^2 + 77^0 + 79^1 = 14 + 442 + 770 + 791$$

$$:= 2^4 + 2^8 + 4^2 + 12^3 + 180^0 = 24 + 28 + 42 + 123 + 1800$$

$$:= 1^1 + 3^6 + 5^4 + 5^4 + 6^2 + 180^0 = 11 + 36 + 54 + 54 + 62 + 1800$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1729 &:= 2^7 + 40^2 + 130^0 &= 27 + 402 + 1300 \\
 &:= 2^6 + 40^2 + 64^1 + 66^0 &= 26 + 402 + 641 + 660 \\
 &:= 1^6 + 41^2 + 46^1 + 84^0 &= 16 + 412 + 461 + 840
 \end{aligned}$$

Below are more examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
 81 &:= 2^3 + 2^6 + 3^2 &= 23 + 26 + 32 & \quad 266 &:= 4^2 + 9^2 + 13^2 &= 42 + 92 + 132 \\
 99 &:= 2^3 + 3^3 + 4^3 &= 23 + 33 + 43 & \quad 286 &:= 6^2 + 9^2 + 13^2 &= 62 + 92 + 132 \\
 121 &:= 2^3 + 2^6 + 7^2 &= 23 + 26 + 72 & \quad 306 &:= 8^2 + 11^2 + 11^2 &= 82 + 112 + 112 \\
 170 &:= 2^6 + 5^2 + 9^2 &= 26 + 52 + 92 & &:= 9^2 + 9^2 + 12^2 &= 92 + 92 + 122 \\
 246 &:= 2^2 + 11^2 + 11^2 &= 22 + 112 + 112 \\
 &:= 5^2 + 5^2 + 14^2 &= 52 + 52 + 142
 \end{aligned}$$

In the above examples, the equality expressions are formed by three terms on both sides, while the numbers 2017 and 1729 are with **different terms expressions**. More detailed study can be seen at author's work [15]. In these works, instead of using only positive sign, both positive and negative signs are used. For more study on numbers refer historical work [1, 2, 3].

1.3 Factorial and Power

Recently, author [16] worked on results arising due to (3) and (4). This we have done in three different ways. One without any repetition of digits. The second we have done with repetition of digits. Third with permutable powers. Both sides of the equality are with the operations as, addition, subtraction, and multiplication along with composite relation. See below some examples in each case:

1.3.1 Different Digits

$$\begin{aligned}
 144 &:= (2! - 1!) \times 3! \times 4! &= -2^2 \times (1^1 + 3^3) + 4^4 \\
 147 &:= 1! + 2! + 3! \times 4! &= -1^1 - 2^2 \times 3^3 + 4^4 \\
 148 &:= (1! + 4!) \times 3! - 2! &= 1^1 \times 4^4 - 3^3 \times 2^2 \\
 152 &:= 2! + 3! \times (1! + 4!) &= 2^2 \times (-3^3 + 1^1) + 4^4 \\
 286 &:= (-1! + 3! \times 4!) \times 2! &= -1^1 + 3^3 + 4^4 + 2^2 \\
 287 &:= -1! + 2! \times 3! \times 4! &= 1^1 \times 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4 \\
 288 &:= 1! \times 2! \times 3! \times 4! &= 1^1 + 2^2 + 3^3 + 4^4
 \end{aligned}$$

1.3.2 Repetition of Digits

$$\begin{aligned}
 108 &:= 2! \times (3! + 4! + 4!) &= 2^2 \times 3^3 + 4^4 - 4^4 \\
 &:= 3! \times (3! + 3! \times 2!) &= (3^3 + 3^3 - 3^3) \times 2^2 \\
 &:= -5! + 2! \times (5! - 3!) &= (5^5 + 2^2 - 5^5) \times 3^3 \\
 &:= (-3! + 5!) \times 2! - 5! &= 3^3 \times (5^5 + 2^2 - 5^5) \\
 &:= (2! \times 3! + 3!) \times 3! \times 1! &= (2^2 + 3^3 - 3^3) \times 3^3 \times 1^1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= (1! \times 1! + 2!) \times 3! \times 3! = (-1^1 - 1^1 + 2^2) \times (3^3 + 3^3) \\ &:= (1! \times 3! + 3! + 3!) \times 3! = 1^1 \times 3^3 + 3^3 + 3^3 + 3^3 \\ &:= (4! + 3! \times 1! + 4!) \times 2! = (4^4 + 3^3 \times 1^1 - 4^4) \times 2^2 \\ &:= (-3! + 5! \times 1!) \times 2! - 5! = (5^5 \times 1^1 + 3^3 - 5^5) \times 2^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{1008} &:= ((4! - 2!) \times 4! - 4!) \times 2! = (4^4 - 2^2 - 4^4 + 4^4) \times 2^2 \\ &:= (2! + 2! + 4!) \times 3! \times 3! = 2^2 \times (-2^2 + 4^4) - 3^3 + 3^3 \\ &:= (2! - 1! + 3!) \times 3! \times 4! = -2^2 + (1^1 + 3^3) \times 3^3 + 4^4 \\ &:= 2! \times (2! \times (5! + 5!) + 4!) = 2^2 \times (-2^2 - 5^5 + 5^5 + 4^4) \end{aligned}$$

1.3.3 Permutable Power

In the above two subsections powers on left side are the same as of bases, below are examples, where powers permutations of bases:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3648} &:= 1! \times 6! + (2! + 5!) \times 4! = (1^5 + 6^2) \times 2^6 + 5^1 \times 4^4 \\ &:= 1! \times 6! + (5! + 2!) \times 4! = (1^4 \times 6^2 + 5^1) \times 2^6 + 4^5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3649} &:= 1! + 4! \times (2! + 5!) + 6! = 1^4 + 4^5 + 2^6 \times (5^1 + 6^2) \\ \mathbf{3690} &:= (1! + 2! + 5!) \times (3! + 4!) = (1^2 + 2^1) \times (5^3 + 3^4 + 4^5) \\ \mathbf{3744} &:= (1! \times 3! + 5!) \times 4! + 6! = (1^6 \times 3^5 + 5^3 + 4^4) \times 6^1 \\ \mathbf{3745} &:= 1! + (3! + 5!) \times 4! + 6! = 1^6 + (3^5 + 5^3 + 4^4) \times 6^1 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3840} &:= (1! \times 4! + 2! + 3!) \times 5! = (1^4 + 4^3) \times (2^1 + 3^2) + 5^5 \\ &= 1^4 \times 4^3 \times (2^5 + 3^1 + 5^2) \\ &:= 1! \times 5! \times (4! + 2!) + 6! = (1^5 + 5^1) \times 4^4 + 2^6 \times 6^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4320} &:= (2! - 1!) \times 3! \times 6! = (-2^3 - 1^2 + 3^6) \times 6^1 \\ &= 2^1 \times (1^6 + 3^2) \times 6^3 \\ &:= (2! - 1!) \times 7! - 6! = (2^7 - 1^6 - 7^1) \times 6^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4326} &:= 3! \times (2! - 1! + 6!) = (3^6 - 2^3) \times 1^2 \times 6^1 \\ \mathbf{4332} &:= 1! \times 3! \times (2! + 6!) = (1^2 + 3^6 - 2^3) \times 6^1 \\ \mathbf{4608} &:= 3! \times (4! \times 2! + 6!) = 3^3 \times 4^4 - 2^6 \times 6^2 \\ \mathbf{4800} &:= 1! \times 7! - 2! \times 5! = (-1^7 + 7^1) \times 2^5 \times 5^2 \\ \mathbf{5050} &:= 2! \times (3! - 1!) + 7! = (2^7 - 3^3) \times (1^1 + 7^2) \\ \mathbf{5058} &:= (2! + 1!) \times 3! + 7! = 2^1 \times (-1^2 + 3^7 + 7^3) \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [16].

2 Fibonacci and Triangular Values

This section brings definition and idea of **Fibonacci and Triangular Values**. Also connections with **selfie numbers** are given in with some examples

Later these sequences are used to extend **selfie expressions** with some basic operations.

2.1 Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature [4, 5]. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Initial values of Fibonacci sequence are given by

$F(1) := 1$	$F(8) := 21$	$F(15) := 610$
$F(2) := 1$	$F(9) := 34$	$F(16) := 987$
$F(3) := 2$	$F(10) := 55$	$F(17) := 1597$
$F(4) := 3$	$F(11) := 89$	$F(18) := 2584$
$F(5) := 5$	$F(12) := 144$	$F(19) := 4181$
$F(6) := 8$	$F(13) := 233$	$F(20) := 6765, \text{ etc,}$
$F(7) := 13$	$F(14) := 377$	

Below are examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence** values:

$235 := 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5))$	$63 := 3 \times F(F(6))$
$256 := 2^5 \times F(6)$	$882 := 2 \times F(8) \times F(8)$
$4427 := (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7))$	$1631 := F(13) \times (6 + 1)$
$46493 := F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3$	$54128 := 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5))$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [14].

2.2 Selfie Numbers with Triangle Numbers

The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2)$$

Initial values of triangular sequence are given by

$T(1) := 1$	$T(8) := 36$	$T(15) := 120$
$T(2) := 3$	$T(9) := 45$	$T(16) := 136$
$T(3) := 6$	$T(10) := 55$	$T(17) := 153$
$T(4) := 10$	$T(11) := 66$	$T(18) := 171$
$T(5) := 15$	$T(12) := 78$	$T(19) := 190$
$T(6) := 21$	$T(13) := 91$	$T(20) := 210, \text{etc.}$
$T(7) := 28$	$T(14) := 105$	

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** with **Triangular numbers**. See below:

$1069 := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$	$874 := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$
$1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$	$0105 := 50 + T(10)$
$2887 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$	$1155 := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$
$4965 := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$	$1224 := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$
$4999 := 49 + T(99)$	$2418 := T(81) - T(42)$
$99545 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$	$99632 := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$
$99546 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6$	$99633 := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's work [12]. Similar kind of work with **binomial coefficients** can be seen in Taneja [13].

As a consequence of definitions of F and T , the following results are obvious. These are limited up to four terms.

$F(1) + F(2) = F(3)$	$T(5) + T(6) = T(8)$
$F(2) + F(3) = F(4)$	
$F(3) + F(4) = F(5)$	$T(1) + T(2) + T(3) = T(4)$
$F(4) + F(5) = F(6)$	$T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) = T(7)$
$F(5) + F(6) = F(7)$	$T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) = T(8)$
$F(6) + F(7) = F(8)$	
	$(-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) = T(5)$
$F(1) + F(3) + F(5) = F(6)$	
$F(3) \times F(6) + F(5) = F(8)$	$T(1) + T(5) = T(3) + T(4)$
$F(5) + F(6) + F(8) = F(9)$	$T(5) + T(9) = T(3) \times T(4)$
$T(3) + T(5) = T(6)$	

2.3 Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci and Triangular Values Together

In [17] author studied numbers represented by **Fibonacci sequence** values and **Triangular numbers** together. See below examples in digit's order and reverse order of digits:

$$1446 := (-1 + F(4)) \times (F(4) + 6!) = (1 + 4! \times T(4)) \times 6$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1448 &:= -1 + F(4!)/(4 \times 8) &= -1 + T(T(T(4))) - T(T(4)) - T(8) \\
 1456 &:= F(1 + F(4!)) \times (5! - F(6)) &= (1 + T(T(4))) \times (5 + T(6)) \\
 7874 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(8)) \times (7 + 4!) &= 7! - T(T(8)) + 7! - T(T(T(4))) \\
 7920 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(9) - 2 + 0 &= -7! + (9!/T(T(T(2)) + 0!)) \\
 7942 &:= (T(T(7)) - T(9)) \times (4! - 2) &= F(F(7)) \times F(9) + F(F(F(4)!)) - F(2) \\
 8085 &:= F(8) + 08!/5 &= (T(8) - 0!) \times T(T(8) - T(5)) \\
 8317 &:= 8!/3! + F(17) &= T(8) \times T(T(T(3))) + 1^7 \\
 8856 &:= (F(8 + 8) + 5!) \times F(6) &= T(8) \times (T(8) + 5) \times 6 \\
 8972 &:= F(F(8)) - F(9 + 7) \times 2 &= 8 \times T(T(9)) - T(7) + (T(T(2)))! \\
 9243 &:= -9 \times 2 + F(F(F(4)!))\sup3 &= 9 \times (2^{T(4)} + 3) \\
 9244 &:= F(9)\sup2 \times F(F(4!)) - 4 &= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 \\
 0169 &:= F(9) \times (6 - 1) - 0! &= (T(T(9)) - T(6))/T(T(1 + 0!)) \\
 0176 &:= F(6) \times (F(7 + 1) + 0!) &= -T(T(6)) + T(T(7)) \times 1 + 0! \\
 0234 &:= F(4 + 3\sup2) + 0! &= 4 \times T(3) + T(20) \\
 0244 &:= F(4)\sup{F(4)+2} + 0! &= 4! + T(4) + T(20) \\
 3024 &:= (F(4)\sup2)!/(-0! + 3!)! &= 4! \times T(T(2)) \times T(T(03)) \\
 3045 &:= (5! + 4! + 0!) \times F(F(3!)) &= T(5 + 4!) \times (0! + T(3)) \\
 3165 &:= -5 \times 6! + F(-1 + F(F(3!))) &= T(5) \times T(T(6)) - T((1 + 3)!) \\
 3276 &:= F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times 2) \times 3! &= T(6 + 7) \times T(2\sup3) \\
 3297 &:= -7 + F(9 \times 2) + 3!! &= (T(7 + 9) + T(T(T(2)))) \times T(T(3)) \\
 3303 &:= 3!! - 0! + F(3 \times 3!) &= T((3 + 0!)!) + T(T(T(T(3))))/3 \\
 3304 &:= F(4! - 03!) + 3!! &= T(4!) + 0! + T(T(T(T(3))))/3 \\
 3325 &:= 5 \times (-F(2 + F(3!)) + 3!!) &= 5 \times (-T(T(-2 + T(3))) + T(3)!)
 \end{aligned}$$

In this work our aim is to extend the results similar to **selfie expressions** given in section 1.3. This we have done by replacing right side expressions of power either with Fibonacci sequence values, or with Triangular numbers or with both. The results are limited up to 5 terms expressions, using only the values of $F(1), \dots, F(9)$ and/or $T(1), \dots, T(9)$ with same digit order as of section 1.3

3 Factorial-Fibonacci-Triangular Selfie Expressions

In this section, we shall give equality expressions with factorial, Fibonacci sequence values and triangular numbers in the same expression, where the main digits follows the same order. We have very few results. See below examples,

3.1 Two-Terms Expressions

$$2 := 1! \times 2! = F(1) + F(2) = -T(1) + T(2)$$

3.2 Three-Terms Expressions

$$3 := -1! - 2! + 3! = F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) = -T(1) \times T(2) + T(3)$$

$$4 := -1! \times 2! + 3! = F(1) + F(2) + F(3) = T(1) - T(2) + T(3)$$

3.3 Four-Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &:= (1! - 3!) \times 4! + 5! = F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) - F(5) = T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(5) \\ &:= 4! \times (1! - 3!) + 5! = F(4) \times F(1) + F(3) - F(5) = T(4) - T(1) + T(3) - T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &:= 1! + 3! \times 5! - 6! = -F(1) \times F(3) - F(5) + F(6) = T(1) + T(3) + T(5) - T(6) \\ &:= -6! + 3! \times 5! + 1! = F(6) - F(3) - F(5) \times F(1) = -T(6) + T(3) + T(5) + T(1) \end{aligned}$$

$$6 := -(1! + 2!) \times 3! + 4! = F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(4) = -T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12 &:= -1! \times 2! \times 3! + 4! = (F(1) + F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) = -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) + T(4) \\ &:= 3! \times (-2! + 4!) - 5! = -F(3) - F(2) + F(4) \times F(5) = T(3) \times (-T(2) - T(4) + T(5)) \\ &:= 3! \times (2! + 5!) - 6! = -F(3) + F(2) + F(5) + F(6) = T(3) \times T(2) + T(5) - T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$18 := 3! \times (-1! + 4!) - 5! = F(3) + F(1) + F(4) \times F(5) = -T(3) - T(1) + T(4) + T(5)$$

$$22 := -2! + 4! \times 3! - 5! = F(2) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(5)) = T(2) + T(4) - T(3) + T(5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24 &:= 3! \times 5! + 4! - 6! = F(3) \times (F(5) + F(4)) + F(6) = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(4) - T(6)) \\ &:= -1! \times 5! + 4! \times 3! = (-F(1) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(3) = (-T(1) + T(5) - T(4)) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$25 := 1! + 3! \times 4! - 5! = (F(1) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) = (T(1) - T(3)) \times (T(4) - T(5))$$

$$30 := (1! + 4!) \times 3! - 5! = (F(1) + F(4) + F(3)) \times F(5) = -T(1) + T(4) + T(3) + T(5)$$

$$120 := 5! \times (1! + 3!) - 6! = F(5) \times (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(6) = T(5) - (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(6)$$

3.4 Five-Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &:= (-1! + 2! - 3!) \times 4! + 5! = (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(4) - F(5)) = (T(1) + T(2) + T(3) - T(4)) \times T(5) \\ &:= (1! - 2!) \times 3! \times 5! + 6! = F(1) + F(2) - F(3) \times F(5) + F(6) = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(5) - T(6)) \\ &:= ((1! - 3!) \times 4! + 5!) \times 6! = (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(5) - F(6)) = (T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\ &:= ((1! - 3!) \times 4! + 5!) \times 7! = F(1) \times F(3) - F(4) \times F(5) + F(7) = (T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\ &:= ((1! - 3!) \times 4! + 5!) \times 8! = (F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) - F(5)) \times F(8) = (T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(5)) \times T(8) \\ &:= ((1! - 3!) \times 4! + 5!) \times 9! = (F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) - F(5)) \times F(9) = (T(1) + T(3) - T(4)) \times T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= -2! \times 4! \times 5! + 7! + 6! = (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(5) - F(7) + F(6)) = (T(2) + T(4) + T(5) - T(7)) \times T(6) \\ &:= (-2! \times 4! + 3!) \times 5! + 7! = (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(3) + F(5) - F(7) = T(2) - T(4) - T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= (-2! + 1! - 3!) \times 6! + 7! = (F(2) + F(1) - F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(7) = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(3) + T(6) - T(7)) \\ &:= (-5! + 2! \times 4!) \times 7! + 9! = F(5) \times F(2) - F(4) \times F(7) + F(9) = (T(5) + T(2) + T(4) - T(7)) \times T(9) \\ &:= -7! \times 5! + 3! \times 8! + 9! = F(7) - F(5) - F(3) \times F(8) + F(9) = T(7) \times (T(5) - T(3) + T(8) - T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := 4! \times 5! + (2! - 3!) \times 6! & = (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(2) - F(3)) + F(6) & = (T(4) - T(5)) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(6) \\
 & := 8! \times (3! - 4!) + 2! \times 9! & = F(8) \times (F(3) - F(4) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = (-T(8) + T(3) + T(4) \times T(2)) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1} & := -1! + 2! - 3! \times 5! + 6! & = F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(5) - F(6) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5) - T(6)) \\
 & := 1! + (2! + 3!) \times 7! - 8! & = (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(3) + F(7)) - F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(7) - T(8) \\
 & := 1! + 3! \times (5! + 6!) - 7! & = -F(1) + F(3) - F(5) - F(6) + F(7) & = -T(1) - T(3) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2} & := (1! + 3!) \times 6! + 2! - 7! & = -(F(1) + F(3) + F(6)) \times F(2) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(2) - T(7) \\
 & := (1! - 3!) \times 4! + 2! + 5! & = F(1) + F(3) + F(4) + F(2) - F(5) & = -T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(2) + T(5) \\
 & := 1! \times 2! + 3! \times 5! - 6! & = (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(3) - F(5) + F(6)) & = -T(1) + T(2) - T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := 2! + (5! + 6!) \times 3! - 7! & = F(2) \times F(5) + F(6) + F(3) - F(7) & = T(2) \times T(5) - T(6) + T(3) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{3} & := 1! + 2! + 3! \times 5! - 6! & = F(1) + F(2) - F(3) - F(5) + F(6) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(5) - T(6) \\
 \mathbf{4} & := (1! + 5!) \times 3! - 2! - 6! & = (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(2) - F(6) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(3) + T(2) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{6} & := (-1! + 4! - 2!) \times 3! - 5! & = -(F(1) + F(4)) \times F(2) + F(3) \times F(5) & = -T(1) + T(4) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) \\
 & := (-1! + 2! - 5!) \times 3! + 6! & = (F(1) + F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) - F(6) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(5) - T(3)) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{8} & := (1! + 5!) \times 3! + 2! - 6! & = -F(1) - F(5) + F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(6)) & = -T(1) - T(5) + T(3) - T(2) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{10} & := (1! - 3!) \times (4! - 2!) + 5! & = F(1) + F(3) + F(4) - F(2) + F(5) & = (T(1) - T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(2) - T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{11} & := -1! + (-2! + 4!) \times 3! - 5! & = -F(1) - F(2) + F(4) + F(3) \times F(5) & = (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) + T(3) - T(5) \\
 & := -1! + 3! \times (2! + 5!) - 6! & = -F(1) - F(3) + F(2) + F(5) + F(6) & = -T(1) - T(3) + T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{12} & := (1! \times 4! - 2!) \times 3! - 5! & = F(1) + F(4) + F(2) + F(3) + F(5) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) - T(3) - T(5) \\
 & := -(2! + 5!) \times 3! + 4! + 6! & = -(F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) + F(4) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(3) - T(4)) - T(6) \\
 & := (2! + 5! + 6!) \times 3! - 7! & = -F(2) - F(5) - F(6) + F(3) \times F(7) & = (T(2) - T(5)) \times (T(6) + T(3) - T(7)) \\
 & := 1! \times 3! \times (5! + 2!) - 6! & = (F(1) + F(3)) \times (-F(5) + F(2) + F(6)) & = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) - T(2) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{13} & := 1! - (2! - 4!) \times 3! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(3) + F(5) & = -T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(3) + T(5) \\
 & := 1! + 3! \times (2! + 5!) - 6! & = (F(1) \times F(3) - F(2)) \times F(5) + F(6) & = T(1) - T(3) - T(2) \times (T(5) - T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{14} & := (1! + 3!) \times (2! + 6!) - 7! & = (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) - F(7) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 \mathbf{16} & := (-1! + 4!) \times 3! - 2! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(4)) \times (-F(3) + F(2) + F(5)) & = T(1) \times T(4) - T(3) - T(2) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{18} & := (1! + 2! + 5!) \times 3! - 6! & = (F(1) + F(2) - F(5)) \times (F(3) - F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(5) - T(3) - T(6) \\
 & := (1! + 4! - 2!) \times 3! - 5! & = F(1) \times F(4) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times (-T(2) + T(3)) - T(5) \\
 & := -3! \times (1! + 5!) + 4! + 6! & = (F(3) + F(1)) \times (-F(5) + F(4) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(5) + T(4) - T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{20} & := (1! + 4!) \times (2! - 3!) + 5! & = (F(1) + F(4)) \times (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) & = -T(1) + T(4) \times T(2) + T(3) - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{21} & := -1! - 2! + 3! \times 4! - 5! & = F(1) - (F(2) - F(3) - F(4)) \times F(5) & = -T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{22} & := -1! \times 2! + 3! \times 4! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(3) \times F(4) + F(5)) & = T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 & := -2! - 3! \times 5! + 4! + 6! & = F(2) + F(3) - F(5) + F(4) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(4) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{23} & := -1! - 3! \times 5! + 4! + 6! & = -F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) \times (-F(4) + F(6)) & = T(1) + T(3) - T(5) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := 1! - 2! + 3! \times 4! - 5! & = -F(1) - F(2) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) & = T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(4) + T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{24} & := 1! \times 3! \times 5! + 4! - 6! & = F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(4)) + F(6) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(5) + T(4) - T(6)) \\
 & := (-1! \times 3! + 2!) \times 4! + 5! & = (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(2) \times (F(4) + F(5)) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 & := (1! + 3!) \times 6! + 4! - 7! & = (F(1) + F(3)) \times (-F(6) + F(4) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(3) - T(6) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := (2! + 3!) \times 7! + 4! - 8! & = -(F(2) + F(3)) \times F(7) + F(4) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(7) + T(4) - T(8)) \\
 & := 3! \times (5! + 6!) + 4! - 7! & = -F(3) - F(5) - F(6) + F(4) \times F(7) & = T(3) + T(5) + T(6) + T(4) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{25} & := 1! + 3! \times 5! + 4! - 6! & = F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(4) + F(6) & = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(4) - T(6)) \\
 & := -1! + 2! + 3! \times 4! - 5! & = (F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) - T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{26} & := 1! \times 2! + 3! \times 4! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(3) + F(4) \times F(5)) & = -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\
 & := 4! + 2! + 3! \times 5! - 6! & = (F(4) + F(2) - F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(6)) & = -T(4) + T(2) \times (T(3) - T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{27} & := 1! + 2! + 3! \times 4! - 5! & = F(1) + F(2) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) & = -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{28} & := (1! + 4!) \times 3! - 2! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(3) \times F(2) + F(5)) & = -T(1) - T(4) - T(3) + T(2) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{30} & := -(1! + 2!) \times (3! + 4!) + 5! & = (F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) - T(2) - T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 & := 3! \times (1! + 5!) + 4! - 6! & = (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(5) - F(4) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(4) - T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{32} & := (1! + 4!) \times 3! + 2! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(5)) & = -T(1) + (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(2) - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{34} & := (1! + 3!) \times (4! - 2!) - 5! & = -F(1) + (F(3) \times F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(4) - T(2)) - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{35} & := -1! + (2! + 4!) \times 3! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(2) + F(4) + F(3)) \times F(5) & = T(1) + T(2) + T(4) + T(3) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{36} & := (1! \times 4! + 2!) \times 3! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(4)) \times (-F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) & = -(T(1) - T(4)) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \\
 & := (2! + 5!) \times 3! + 4! - 6! & = (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) + F(4) \times F(6) & = -T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{42} & := (1! + 2! + 4!) \times 3! - 5! & = (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(5)) & = -T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{46} & := -2! + (1! + 3!) \times 4! - 5! & = F(2) + (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(3)) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{48} & := (1! - 3! + 2!) \times 4! + 5! & = (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(4) \times F(5)) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(2) - T(4) + T(5)) \\
 & := 2! \times 4! + 3! \times 5! - 6! & = (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(3) \times F(5) + F(6) & = (-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := (3! + 1!) \times (4! - 5!) + 6! & = (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(5) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(4)) + T(5) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{50} & := (1! + 3!) \times 4! + 2! - 5! & = ((F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) & = T(1) - T(3) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{60} & := -1! \times 2! \times (3! + 4!) + 5! & = (F(1) + F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(5) & = (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(3) \times (T(4) - T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{96} & := (1! + 3!) \times 5! - 4! - 6! & = ((F(1) + F(3)) \times F(5) - F(4)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(4) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{120} & := (-1! + 2! - 3!) \times 5! + 6! & = (F(1) \times F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 & := (2! + 3!) \times 7! + 5! - 8! & = F(2) \times F(3) + F(7) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(7) - T(5) - T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{132} & := -3! \times (2! + 5! - 4!) + 6! & = F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) & = (T(3) - T(2) - T(5)) \times (T(4) - T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{144} & := 1! \times 3! \times (4! + 5!) - 6! & = (F(1) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(5)) \times F(6) & = (-T(1) \times T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 & := (2! - 3!) \times (4! + 5!) + 6! & = (F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(5)) \times F(6) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(4) - T(5) + T(6)) \\
 & := 3! \times (4! + 6! + 5!) - 7! & = (-F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) \times (F(5) + F(7)) & = T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(6) - T(5) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{150} & := (1! + 4! + 5!) \times 3! - 6! & = F(1) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(3) + F(6)) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(3) - T(6) \\
 \mathbf{168} & := (1! + 3!) \times (4! + 6!) - 7! & = -F(1) + (F(3) + F(4) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(6)) \times T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 192 &:= -2! \times (4! \times 3! + 5!) + 6! &= (-F(2) + (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(2) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5)) - T(6) \\
 216 &:= (2! + 3!) \times 5! - 4! - 6! &= (-F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(6) &= -T(2) - T(3) + T(5) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 240 &:= (5! - 4!) \times (1! - 3!) + 6! &= F(5) \times F(4) \times F(1) \times F(3) \times F(6) &= T(5) \times (-T(4) - T(1) + T(3) + T(6)) \\
 264 &:= (2! + 3!) \times 5! + 4! - 6! &= (F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(6) &= (T(2) + T(3) + T(5)) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \\
 288 &:= 2! \times ((5! + 4!) \times 3! - 6!) &= (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(3) \times F(6) &= T(2) + T(5) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 480 &:= -2! \times 5! - 6! \times 3! + 7! &= (-F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) \times (F(3) + F(7)) &= T(2) + T(5) - T(6) \times (T(3) - T(7)) \\
 576 &:= -3! \times (4! + 6!) \times 1! + 7! &= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times (-F(1) + F(7)) &= T(3) + T(4) + (T(6) - T(1)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 600 &:= -5! - 3! \times 6! \times 1! + 7! &= F(5) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times (-F(1) + F(7)) &= -T(5) + T(3) + T(6) \times (T(1) + T(7)) \\
 &:= -5! + 6! \times (2! + 3!) - 7! &= F(5) \times F(6) \times F(2) \times (F(3) + F(7)) &= T(5) \times (T(6) - T(2) - T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 624 &:= -3! \times 6! + 4! - 5! + 7! &= (-F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= -T(3) + T(6) \times T(4) + T(5) \times T(7) \\
 720 &:= -5! \times 4! + 7! - 2! \times 6! &= F(5) \times (F(4) + F(7)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) &= -T(5) + (T(4) + T(7) - T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 864 &:= 4! + 5! + 7! - 3! \times 6! &= F(4) \times (F(5) + F(7)) \times F(3) \times F(6) &= T(4) \times T(5) + (T(7) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 960 &:= -3! \times 6! + 5! \times 2! + 7! &= F(3) \times F(6) \times F(5) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) &= -T(3) + T(6) \times (T(5) + T(2) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 1560 &:= -(3! - 1!) \times 6! + 5! + 7! &= (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(6) \times F(5) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times (T(1) - T(6)) \times (T(5) - T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 3.1. *There are only three values, when factorial, power and triangular numbers are equal with same digit's order.*

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &:= 1! = 1^1 &&= T(1) \\
 3 &:= 1! + 2! = -1^1 + 2^2 &&= T(1) \times T(2) \\
 2760 &:= (-1! + 5! + 2! - 3!) \times 4! = -1^1 + 5^5 - 2^2 \times 3^3 - 4^4 &&= (T(1) + T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Selfie Expressions with Selected Operations

4.1 Positive Sign

Below are few examples of **factorial-triangular selfie expressions** only with positive sign.

$$\begin{aligned}
 6 &:= 3! = T(3) \\
 \\
 7 &:= 1! + 3! = T(1) + T(3) \\
 \\
 9 &:= 1! + 2! + 3! = T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) \\
 18 &:= (1! + 2!) \times 3! = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) \\
 36 &:= 3! \times 2! + 4! = T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \\
 150 &:= 3! + 4! + 5! = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 37 &:= 1! + 3! \times 2! + 4! = T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \\
 78 &:= (1! + 2!) \times 4! + 3! = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 90 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (3! + 4!) = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) \\
 150 &:= 1! \times 3! + 4! + 5! = T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 151 &:= 1! + 3! + 4! + 5! = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 168 &:= 2! \times 1! \times 4! + 5! &= T(2) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 300 &:= 2! \times (3! + 5! + 4!) &= T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(5) + T(4)) \\
 960 &:= 1! \times 6! + 2! \times 5! &= (T(1) + T(6) \times T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 2160 &:= 2! \times 6! + 3! \times 5! &= (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) \times T(5) \\
 1008 &:= (2! \times 3!) \times 4! + 6! &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 174 &:= 3! \times 1! + 2! \times 4! + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(2)) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 198 &:= (2! + 1!) \times 4! + 3! + 5! &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(4) \times T(3)) + T(5) \\
 270 &:= 1! \times 3! + 4! + 2! \times 5! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) + T(5)) \\
 271 &:= 1! + 3! + 4! + 2! \times 5! &= T(1) + T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) + T(5)) \\
 276 &:= 3! \times (4! + 2!) \times 1! + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) + T(1) + T(5)) \\
 294 &:= 2! \times (4! \times 1! + 5!) + 3! &= (T(2) + T(4) + T(1)) \times (T(5) + T(3)) \\
 295 &:= 1! + 3! + 2! \times (5! + 4!) &= (T(1) + T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(5) + T(4) \\
 300 &:= 2! \times (3! \times 1! + 4! + 5!) &= (T(2) + T(3) + T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 301 &:= 1! + 2! \times (4! + 3!) + 5! &= T(1) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3) \times T(5)) \\
 385 &:= 1! + 3! \times 4! + 2! \times 5! &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 390 &:= 4! + 3! + (2! + 1!) \times 5! &= T(4) \times (T(3) \times (T(2) + T(1)) + T(5)) \\
 420 &:= (1! + 4!) \times 2! \times 3! + 5! &= (T(1) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 450 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (3! + 4! + 5!) &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 456 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 2! \times 4! + 5! &= T(1) \times T(3) + (T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 540 &:= 2! \times ((4! + 1!) \times 3! + 5!) &= (T(2) \times T(4) \times T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 576 &:= 2! \times (4! \times (3! + 1!) + 5!) &= (T(2) \times T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 756 &:= 1! \times 3! \times 2! + 4! + 6! &= (T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 757 &:= 1! + 3! \times 2! + 4! + 6! &= T(1) + (T(3) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 768 &:= 2! \times 4! + 3! \times 1! \times 5! &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 810 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (4! + 3!) + 6! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 966 &:= 3! + 5! \times 1! \times 2! + 6! &= T(3) + T(5) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 972 &:= (3! \times 1! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! &= T(3) + (T(1) + T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1008 &:= 6! + 4! \times 3! \times 2! \times 1! &= T(6) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(2) \times T(1) \\
 1009 &:= 6! + 4! \times 3! \times 2! + 1! &= T(6) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(1) \\
 1590 &:= 4! + 5! + 3! + 2! \times 6! &= T(4) \times (T(5) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6))) \\
 1710 &:= 2! \times (5! + 6!) + 3! + 4! &= (T(2) \times T(5) + T(6) \times T(3)) \times T(4) \\
 1728 &:= 3! \times (4! \times 2! + 5!) + 6! &= (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 1968 &:= 2! \times (5! + 6! + 4! \times 3!) &= (T(2) + T(5) \times T(6) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 2160 &:= 1! \times 3! \times 5! \times 2! + 6! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 2161 &:= 1! + 3! \times 5! + 2! \times 6! &= T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 2166 &:= 3! \times (1! + 5!) + 2! \times 6! &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6))) \\
 2286 &:= 3! + 6! \times (1! + 2!) + 5! &= (T(3) \times T(6) + T(1)) \times (T(2) + T(5)) \\
 2448 &:= 2! \times (5! + 4!) \times 3! + 6! &= (T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(4) + T(3) \times T(6)) \\
 3168 &:= 2! \times (3! \times (4! + 5!) + 6!) &= T(2) \times T(3) + (T(4) \times T(5)) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3840 &:= 1! \times 5! \times (4! + 2!) + 6! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 3888 &:= (5! + 2! \times 3!) \times 4! + 6! &= (T(5) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 3960 &:= 5! \times (1! + 4! + 2!) + 6! &= T(5) \times (T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 4320 &:= 1! \times 5! \times (4! + 3!) + 6! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 5040 &:= 5! \times (3! \times 2! + 4!) + 6! &= (T(5) + T(3) + T(2)) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 5100 &:= (3! + 4! \times 1!) \times 2! + 7! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 5220 &:= (3! + 4!) \times 2! + 7! + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) + T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 5310 &:= 3! + 2! \times 5! + 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 5760 &:= 3! \times ((5! \times 1!) \times 2! + 6!) &= T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 5905 &:= 5! + 4! + 1! + 6! + 7! &= T(5) + T(4) \times (T(1) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 5916 &:= 3! \times (4! + 2!) + 6! + 7! &= T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 6048 &:= (5! + 4!) \times 2! + 6! + 7! &= (T(5) \times (T(4) + T(2)) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 6516 &:= (3! + 6!) \times 2! + 7! + 4! &= T(3) + T(6) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \times T(4) \\
 7560 &:= (1! + 2! + 3!) \times (5! + 6!) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(5) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 12240 &:= (7! + 3! \times 5!) \times 2! + 6! &= (T(7) + T(3)) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 13104 &:= 7! \times 2! + (3! + 5!) \times 4! &= T(7) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5) \times T(4)) \\
 25200 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 4! \times 5! + 7! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 30240 &:= 4! \times (5! + 6!) + 2! \times 7! &= T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \times T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 725760 &:= 8! \times 3! + 4! \times 7! + 9! &= (T(8) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(7)) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

4.2 Multiplication with Fibonacci and Triangular Numbers

We have few examples when all the terms with Fibonacci or triangular numbers are with multiplication sign.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1} &:= -1! + 2! = F(1) \times F(2) \\
 \mathbf{1560} &:= (1! - 4!) \times 5! - 6! + 7! = F(1) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times F(6) \times F(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{6} &:= 1! \times 3! = T(1) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{18} &:= (1! + 2!) \times 3! = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2700} &:= (1! + 4!) \times (5! - 2! \times 3!) = T(1) \times T(4) \times T(5) \times T(2) \times T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{25200} &:= (1! + 3!) \times 4! \times 5! + 7! = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{181440} &:= (3! - 2! + 4!) \times 7! + 8! = T(3) \times T(2) \times T(4) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{453600} &:= (2! + 5! - 4!) \times 7! - 8! = T(2) \times T(5) \times T(4) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{816480} &:= 3! \times (2! \times 8! - 7!) + 9! = T(3) \times T(2) \times T(8) \times T(7) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1360800} &:= (4! - 2!) \times (7! + 8!) + 9! = T(4) \times T(2) \times T(7) \times T(8) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{4082400} &:= (3! + 5!) \times (8! - 7!) - 9! = T(3) \times T(5) \times T(8) \times T(7) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

5 Factorial-Fibonacci Selfie Expressions

In this case we have very few examples, as we considered factorial and Fibonacci values equality expressions following the same order of digits on both sides of the equalities. Numbers appearing in section 5 are not included here.

5.1 Two-Terms Expressions

$$1 := -1! + 2! = F(1) \times F(2)$$

5.2 Four-Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned} 2 &:= 2! + 3! \times 5! - 6! &= F(2) \times F(3) \times F(5) - F(6) \\ 6 &:= (1! + 5!) \times 3! - 6! &= F(1) - F(5) + F(3) + F(6) \\ 10 &:= -(1! + 3!) \times 2! + 4! &= F(1) + (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(4) \\ &:= 4! - 2! \times (1! + 3!) &= (F(4) + F(2) + F(1)) \times F(3) \\ 24 &:= (-3! + 2!) \times 4! + 5! &= (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(5)) \\ 26 &:= 2! + 3! \times 4! - 5! &= F(2) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) \\ 36 &:= -5! + (2! + 4!) \times 3! &= (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

5.3 Five-Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned} 36 &:= (1! \times 2! + 4!) \times 3! - 5! &= F(1) + (F(2) + F(4) \times F(3)) \times F(5) \\ &:= 4! + (2! + 5!) \times 3! - 6! &= (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) + F(3) \times F(6) \\ 37 &:= 1! + 3! \times (4! + 2!) - 5! &= F(1) + F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \\ 42 &:= (4! + 2! + 1!) \times 3! - 5! &= F(4) \times (F(2) + F(1)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) \\ 46 &:= 2! \times (4! \times 3! - 1! - 5!) &= F(2) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(5) \\ 48 &:= (1! + 3!) \times (4! - 5!) + 6! &= (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(5) + F(6)) \\ &:= 4! \times 2! + 5! \times 3! - 6! &= (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) \times F(3) + F(6) \\ &:= 4! \times (2! + 1! - 3!) + 5! &= F(4) \times (F(2) + (F(1) + F(3))) \times F(5) \\ 50 &:= 2! \times (3! \times 4! + 1! - 5!) &= ((F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(1)) \times F(5) \\ 60 &:= -(3! + 4!) \times 2! \times 1! + 5! &= (F(3) \times F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(5) \\ 96 &:= -4! + 5! \times (1! + 3!) - 6! &= (F(4) \times F(5) + F(1)) \times (-F(3) + F(6)) \\ 120 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 6! + 5! - 7! &= (F(1) - F(3) \times F(6)) \times (F(5) - F(7)) \\ &:= (3! + 2! - 1!) \times 5! - 6! &= (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(1) \times F(5) \times F(6) \\ &:= 5! + 8! - (3! + 2!) \times 7! &= (F(5) \times F(8) + F(3)) \times F(2) + F(7) \\ &:= -7! \times (2! + 3!) + 8! + 5! &= F(7) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(8) \times F(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$142 := 3! \times (4! + 5!) - 2! - 6! = -F(3) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 144 &:= (1! \times 4! + 5!) \times 3! - 6! = (F(1) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(6) \\ &:= (6! + 4! + 5!) \times 3! - 7! = F(6) \times F(4) \times (-F(5) - F(3) + F(7)) \\ &:= (4! + 5!) \times (2! - 3!) + 6! = (F(4) + F(5) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 146 &:= 3! \times (4! + 5!) + 2! - 6! = F(3) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(6) \\ 192 &:= -2! \times (3! \times 4! + 5!) + 6! = (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) \\ 216 &:= -4! + 5! \times (3! + 2!) - 6! = F(4) \times (F(5) \times F(3) - F(2)) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 240 &:= (-1! + 3!) \times (4! - 5!) + 6! = (F(1) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times F(6) \\ &:= 7! + (3! + 2!) \times (5! - 6!) = (F(7) \times F(3) - F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 288 &:= (3! + 1!) \times (5! + 4!) - 6! = F(3) \times (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(6) \\ &:= 4! \times ((5! + 2!) \times 3! - 6!) = F(4) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 576 &:= -3! \times (6! + 4!) \times 1! + 7! = F(3) \times F(6) \times F(4) \times (-F(1) + F(7)) \\ &:= -4! - 5! + 7! - 3! \times 6! = -F(4) + F(5) \times (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(6) \\ &:= 7! \times 1! - (4! + 6!) \times 3! = (F(7) - F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times F(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 598 &:= -2! - 5! - 6! \times 3! + 7! = ((F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) - F(3)) \times F(7) \\ 599 &:= -1! - 5! + 7! - 3! \times 6! = -F(1) + F(5) \times (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(6) \\ 600 &:= -1! \times 5! + 7! - 3! \times 6! = F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(6) \\ 601 &:= 1! - 5! + 7! - 3! \times 6! = F(1) + F(5) \times (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(6) \\ 624 &:= -3! \times 6! - 5! + 4! + 7! = (-F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(4)) \times F(7) \\ 672 &:= -3! \times 6! - 4! \times 2! + 7! = F(3) \times F(6) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(7)) \\ 702 &:= (1! - 6!) \times 3! - 4! + 7! = (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times F(4) \times F(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 720 &:= (2! \times 5! + 6!) \times 3! - 7! = (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) \times (F(3) + F(7)) \\ &:= -(3! + 4!) \times 5! + 7! - 6! = (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) \times F(6) \\ &:= -2! \times 6! - 5! \times 4! + 7! = (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(5) \times (F(4) + F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 744 &:= (4! - 6!) \times 3! + 7! - 5! = F(4) \times F(6) \times (F(3) \times F(7) + F(5)) \\ 816 &:= -4! + 5! - 3! \times 6! + 7! = (F(4) + F(5)) \times (-F(3) + F(6) \times F(7)) \\ 864 &:= -3! \times 6! + 4! + 5! + 7! = F(3) \times F(6) \times F(4) \times (F(5) + F(7)) \\ 960 &:= 5! \times 2! + 7! - 3! \times 6! = F(5) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) \times F(3) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1440 &:= 4! \times 5! \times 2! - 7! + 6! = F(4) \times F(5) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) \\ &:= 1! \times 7! - 4! \times 5! - 6! = (-F(1) + F(7)) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1560 &:= (1! - 4!) \times 5! - 6! + 7! &= F(1) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times F(6) \times F(7) \\
 &:= (7! - 6! \times 3!) \times 2! + 5! &= F(7) \times F(6) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(5) \\
 &:= 7! + (1! - 3!) \times 6! + 5! &= F(7) \times (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(5) \\
 1680 &:= -5! \times (4! - 2!) + 7! - 6! &= F(5) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) \\
 9240 &:= 8! - 5! - 6! - 7! \times 3! &= F(8) \times F(5) \times F(6) \times (F(7) - F(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

6 Factorial-Triangular Selfie Expressions

In this case we have examples of factorial and triangular selfie expressions with positive and negative signs, where the digits follows the same order on both sides. The example given in section 4.1 are also written again to have a complete list.

6.1 Single-Term Expressions

$$6 := 3! = T(3)$$

6.2 Two-Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned}
 5 &:= -1! + 3! = -T(1) + T(3) \\
 6 &:= 1! \times 3! = T(1) \times T(3) \\
 7 &:= 1! + 3! = T(1) + T(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

6.3 Three-Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned}
 8 &:= 1! \times 2! + 3! &= -T(1) + T(2) + T(3) \\
 9 &:= 1! + 2! + 3! &= T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) \\
 10 &:= (-1! + 3!) \times 2! &= T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \\
 12 &:= 1! \times 2! \times 3! &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= -2! \times 3! + 4! &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \\
 17 &:= -1! - 3! + 4! &= T(1) + T(3) + T(4) \\
 18 &:= (1! + 2!) \times 3! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) \\
 27 &:= 1! + 4! + 2! &= (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) \\
 28 &:= -2! + 3! + 4! &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \\
 36 &:= 3! \times 2! + 4! &= T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \\
 42 &:= 2! \times 4! - 3! &= (-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 90 &:= -3! + 5! - 4! &= (-T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 108 &:= -3! \times 2! + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5)) \\ 150 &:= 3! + 4! + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \end{aligned}$$

6.4 Four-Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned} 11 &:= -1! - 2! \times 3! + 4! &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \\ 13 &:= 1! - 2! \times 3! + 4! &= -T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(4) \\ 14 &:= (1! - 3!) \times 2! + 4! &= T(1) + T(3) - T(2) + T(4) \\ 15 &:= -1! - 3! + 4! - 2! &= (T(1) - T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) \\ 16 &:= -1! \times 2! - 3! + 4! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \\ 18 &:= (1! - 2!) \times 3! + 4! &= -T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(4) \\ 19 &:= -1! + 2! - 3! + 4! &= T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(4) \\ 20 &:= 1! \times 2! - 3! + 4! &= T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(4) \\ 21 &:= 1! + 4! + 2! - 3! &= (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) - T(3) \\ 27 &:= -1! - 2! + 3! + 4! &= -T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \\ 28 &:= -1! \times 2! + 3! + 4! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \\ 29 &:= 1! - 2! + 3! + 4! &= T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \\ 30 &:= (-1! + 2!) \times 3! + 4! &= (-T(1) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) \\ 31 &:= -1! + 2! + 3! + 4! &= T(1) - (T(2) - T(3)) \times T(4) \\ 32 &:= 1! \times 2! + 3! + 4! &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \\ 33 &:= 1! + 4! + 2! + 3! &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times (-T(2) + T(3)) \\ 34 &:= 2! \times (-1! - 3! + 4!) &= (T(2) + T(1)) \times T(3) + T(4) \\ 35 &:= -1! + 3! \times 2! + 4! &= -T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \\ 36 &:= 1! \times 2! \times (4! - 3!) &= (-T(1) - T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\ 37 &:= 1! + 3! \times 2! + 4! &= T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \\ 40 &:= -3! + 2! \times (-1! + 4!) &= (T(3) - T(2) + T(1)) \times T(4) \\ 41 &:= -1! - 3! + 2! \times 4! &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(4)) \\ 42 &:= -1! \times 3! + 2! \times 4! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(4)) \\ 43 &:= 1! + 2! \times 4! - 3! &= (T(1) - T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\ 48 &:= -(2! + 1!) \times 4! + 5! &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(4)) + T(5) \\ 48 &:= 2! \times (3! \times 4! - 5!) &= T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(5) \\ 53 &:= -1! + 3! + 4! \times 2! &= (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(2) \\ 56 &:= 2! \times (1! + 4!) + 3! &= -T(2) - T(1) + T(4) \times T(3) \\ 58 &:= (-1! + 3! + 4!) \times 2! &= T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(2) \\ 60 &:= -2! \times (4! + 3!) + 5! &= -T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) \\ 62 &:= 2! \times (1! + 3! + 4!) &= T(2) - T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) \\ 70 &:= -(4! + 1!) \times 2! + 5! &= T(4) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\ 72 &:= -2! \times 1! \times 4! + 5! &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(4) + T(5)) \\ 78 &:= (1! + 2!) \times 4! + 3! &= (T(1) \times T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$89 := -1! - 4! - 3! + 5! = -T(1) + T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(5))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 90 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (3! + 4!) = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) \\ &:= -1! \times 3! + 5! - 4! = (-T(1) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$91 := 1! - 4! - 3! + 5! = T(1) + T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(5))$$

$$98 := 2! - 4! \times 1! + 5! = (T(2) - T(4)) \times (T(1) - T(5))$$

$$100 := (3! - 2!) \times (1! + 4!) = (T(3) + T(2) + T(1)) \times T(4)$$

$$101 := -1! - 4! + 3! + 5! = T(1) + T(4) + T(3) \times T(5)$$

$$102 := -(2! + 1!) \times 3! + 5! = -T(2) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5)$$

$$107 := -1! - 3! \times 2! + 5! = -T(1) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5))$$

$$108 := 1! \times 5! - 2! \times 3! = (T(1) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times T(3)$$

$$109 := 1! - 3! \times 2! + 5! = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5))$$

$$114 := (1! - 2!) \times (-5! + 3!) = (T(1) + T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3)$$

$$120 := (1! - 2! + 3!) \times 4! = (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) \times T(4))$$

$$126 := -3! \times (1! - 2!) + 5! = (T(3) + T(1)) \times (T(2) + T(5))$$

$$132 := -2! \times 3! + 4! + 5! = -T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)$$

$$134 := (1! + 3!) \times 2! + 5! = -T(1) + (T(3) + T(2)) \times T(5)$$

$$143 := 1! + 5! + 4! - 2! = (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(2)$$

$$144 := 3! \times (4! + 5!) - 6! = (-T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(6))$$

$$146 := 1! \times 2! + 4! + 5! = -T(1) - T(2) + T(4) \times T(5)$$

$$147 := 1! + 2! + 4! + 5! = -T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) \times T(5)$$

$$149 := -1! + 3! + 4! + 5! = -T(1) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5))$$

$$150 := 1! \times 3! + 4! + 5! = T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5))$$

$$:= 3! \times (-1! + 2! + 4!) = (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(2) \times T(4)$$

$$151 := 1! + 3! + 4! + 5! = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5))$$

$$162 := (1! + 4! + 2!) \times 3! = (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(3)$$

$$168 := 2! \times 1! \times 4! + 5! = T(2) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5)$$

$$168 := 2! \times 3! \times 4! - 5! = T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)$$

$$170 := (4! + 1!) \times 2! + 5! = T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(2) + T(5))$$

$$:= 2! + (3! + 1!) \times 4! = (T(2) \times T(3) - T(1)) \times T(4)$$

$$174 := 3! + 4! \times 2! + 5! = -T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(5))$$

$$180 := 2! \times (3! + 4!) + 5! = T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5)$$

$$186 := 2! \times (5! - 4!) - 3! = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(3)$$

$$190 := 2! \times (5! - 1! - 4!) = (T(2) + T(5) + T(1)) \times T(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 194 &:= (1! + 5! - 4!) \times 2! &= -T(1) + T(5) \times (T(4) + T(2)) \\
 210 &:= 2! \times 5! - 4! - 3! &= (T(2) \times T(5) - T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 \\
 240 &:= (-1! + 3!) \times 4! + 5! &= (T(1) \times T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= (3! - 1!) \times 2! \times 4! &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 252 &:= (1! \times 5! + 3!) \times 2! &= (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) \times T(2) \\
 270 &:= 2! \times 5! + 3! + 4! &= T(2) \times (T(5) - T(3)) \times T(4) \\
 300 &:= 2! \times (3! + 5! + 4!) &= T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(5) + T(4)) \\
 \\
 360 &:= (-1! - 2! + 3!) \times 5! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(5) \\
 &:= 6! - (1! + 2!) \times 5! &= (T(6) \times T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 432 &:= 3! \times (5! - 4! \times 2!) &= (-T(3) + T(5) \times T(4)) \times T(2) \\
 456 &:= (3! - 2!) \times 5! - 4! &= T(3) + T(2) \times T(5) \times T(4) \\
 468 &:= -(3! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! &= T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 486 &:= -2! \times 5! + 3! + 6! &= (T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 528 &:= 2! \times (4! - 5!) + 6! &= T(2) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 588 &:= 3! \times (2! - 4!) + 6! &= (T(3) \times T(2) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 600 &:= -5! - 6! \times 3! + 7! &= F(5) \times F(6) \times (F(3) + F(7)) \\
 624 &:= (-3! + 2!) \times 4! + 6! &= -T(3) + (T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 630 &:= 3! + 4! - 5! + 6! &= T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 693 &:= -1! - 4! - 2! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(6) \\
 714 &:= -(1! + 6!) \times 3! + 7! &= T(1) \times T(6) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 750 &:= 3! \times (1! + 5!) + 4! &= (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(5) \times T(4) \\
 756 &:= 2! \times (4! - 3!) + 6! &= (T(2) \times T(4) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 840 &:= -3! \times 6! + 5! + 7! &= (-T(3) + T(6) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 960 &:= 1! \times 6! + 2! \times 5! &= (T(1) + T(6) \times T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 1008 &:= (2! \times 3!) \times 4! + 6! &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 2160 &:= 2! \times 6! + 3! \times 5! &= (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) \times T(5) \\
 3612 &:= 2! \times (3! - 6!) + 7! &= (T(2) + T(3) \times T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 5040 &:= -(1! + 3!) \times 7! + 8! &= (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(7) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

6.5 Five-Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 &:= (2! \times 4! - 5!) \times 7! + 9! &= (T(2) + T(4) + T(5) - T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= 9! \times 2! + 8! \times (3! - 4!) &= (-T(9) + T(2) + T(8) + T(3)) \times T(4) \\
 &:= 6! + 7! - 2! \times 4! \times 5! &= (T(6) - T(7) - T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 1 &:= 7! \times (2! + 3!) + 1! - 8! &= T(7) + T(2) + T(3) \times T(1) - T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21 &:= 3! \times 4! - 1! - 2! - 5! &= -T(3) + T(4) - T(1) + T(2) + T(5) \\
 22 &:= 1! \times 3! \times 4! - 5! - 2! &= T(1) + T(3) - (T(4) - T(5)) \times T(2) \\
 25 &:= 1! + 4! + 3! \times 5! - 6! &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\
 26 &:= 4! \times 1! \times 3! + 2! - 5! &= -T(4) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(5) \\
 27 &:= 1! + 4! \times 3! + 2! - 5! &= (T(1) \times T(4) - T(3)) \times T(2) + T(5) \\
 32 &:= 2! + 3! \times (4! + 1!) - 5! &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) - T(1) - T(5) \\
 34 &:= (1! + 3!) \times (-2! + 4!) - 5! &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (-T(2) + T(4)) - T(5) \\
 35 &:= -1! - 5! + 3! \times (2! + 4!) &= T(1) + T(5) + T(3) + T(2) + T(4) \\
 36 &:= 2! \times (3! \times (-1! + 4!) - 5!) &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times (-T(1) - T(4) + T(5)) \\
 37 &:= 1! + (4! + 2!) \times 3! - 5! &= T(1) \times T(4) - T(2) \times (T(3) - T(5)) \\
 42 &:= (1! + 4! + 2!) \times 3! - 5! &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \\
 46 &:= 2! \times (3! \times 4! - 1! - 5!) &= -(T(2) - T(3)) \times T(4) + T(1) + T(5) \\
 47 &:= -1! + 2! \times (3! \times 4! - 5!) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) + T(5) \\
 48 &:= (1! + 2! - 3!) \times 4! + 5! &= T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 49 &:= 1! - (5! - 3! \times 4!) \times 2! &= T(1) - T(5) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) \\
 50 &:= 2! - 5! + (1! + 3!) \times 4! &= T(2) \times T(5) + T(1) - T(3) + T(4) \\
 54 &:= 3! - (1! + 2!) \times 4! + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(5)) \\
 58 &:= -(1! + 3! + 4!) \times 2! + 5! &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(2) - T(5) \\
 59 &:= -1! - 2! \times (4! + 3!) + 5! &= -T(1) - T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 60 &:= 1! \times 5! - 2! \times (3! + 4!) &= (T(1) \times T(5) - T(2) - T(3)) \times T(4) \\
 61 &:= 1! - (3! + 4!) \times 2! + 5! &= T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(5) \\
 62 &:= (1! + 3!) \times (2! + 4!) - 5! &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(4)) - T(5) \\
 64 &:= -(1! + 4!) \times 2! - 3! + 5! &= T(1) + (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 65 &:= -1! - 3! - 2! \times 4! + 5! &= (-T(1) + T(3) + T(2)) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 66 &:= -1! \times 4! \times 2! - 3! + 5! &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times (-T(2) - T(3) + T(5)) \\
 67 &:= -2! \times 4! - 3! + 1! + 5! &= T(2) + (T(4) - T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 68 &:= -2! \times (4! - 1!) - 3! + 5! &= T(2) - T(4) - (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 71 &:= -1! + (2! + 3!) \times 4! - 5! &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) \\
 72 &:= 1! \times 4! \times (2! + 3!) - 5! &= (T(1) + T(4) - T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T(5)) \\
 73 &:= 1! + (2! + 3!) \times 4! - 5! &= T(1) - T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) \\
 76 &:= -(1! + 4!) \times 2! + 3! + 5! &= -T(1) - T(4) - T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 77 &:= -2! \times 4! - 1! + 3! + 5! &= -(T(2) + T(4)) \times T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 78 &:= -1! \times 2! \times 4! + 3! + 5! &= T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(5) \\
 79 &:= 1! - 2! \times 4! - 3! + 5! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(3)) + T(5) \\
 80 &:= 3! + (1! - 4!) \times 2! + 5! &= (T(3) - T(1)) \times (T(4) + T(2)) + T(5) \\
 82 &:= -(1! + 3!) \times 2! - 4! + 5! &= T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 83 &:= -1! - 4! - 2! \times 3! + 5! &= -T(1) \times T(4) + T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 84 &:= -1! \times 2! \times 3! + 5! - 4! &= T(1) + T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(4) \\
 85 &:= 1! - 2! \times 3! - 4! + 5! &= (T(1) + T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) - T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86 &:= 2! \times (1! - 4! + 3!) + 5! &= -T(2) - T(1) + T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(5)) \\
 87 &:= -1! - 2! - 4! - 3! + 5! &= -T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(5)) \\
 88 &:= -1! \times 2! - 4! - 3! + 5! &= T(1) - T(2) - T(4) \times (T(3) - T(5)) \\
 89 &:= 1! - 2! - 3! - 4! + 5! &= -T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\
 90 &:= (1! - 2!) \times 4! - 3! + 5! &= (-T(1) + T(2) + T(4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 91 &:= -1! - 3! - 4! + 2! + 5! &= T(1) + T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) - T(5)) \\
 92 &:= 1! \times 2! - 3! - 4! + 5! &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4) + T(5)) \\
 93 &:= 1! + 2! - 3! - 4! + 5! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4) + T(5)) \\
 94 &:= 2! \times (-1! + 5!) - 3! \times 4! &= (T(2) + T(1)) \times (T(5) + T(3)) + T(4) \\
 95 &:= -1! - 3! \times 4! + 2! \times 5! &= (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(5) \\
 96 &:= -1! \times 4! \times 3! + 2! \times 5! &= (-T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(2)) + T(5) \\
 97 &:= 1! - 4! \times 3! + 2! \times 5! &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5)) \\
 98 &:= (1! + 5!) \times 2! - 3! \times 4! &= (T(1) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times T(3) - T(4) \\
 99 &:= -1! - 2! - 4! + 3! + 5! &= (T(1) + T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(5) \\
 100 &:= -1! \times 2! + 3! - 4! + 5! &= (T(1) - T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 102 &:= (1! - 2!) \times 4! + 3! + 5! &= -T(1) + T(2) + T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 103 &:= 2! - 1! - 4! + 3! + 5! &= T(2) \times T(1) + T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 104 &:= 1! \times 2! + 3! - 4! + 5! &= -T(1) + (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(5) \\
 105 &:= 1! + 2! + 3! - 4! + 5! &= (T(1) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(5) \\
 106 &:= (-1! + 3!) \times 2! - 4! + 5! &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(4)) + T(5) \\
 108 &:= 2! \times 3! \times 1! - 4! + 5! &= T(2) \times T(3) \times (T(1) - T(4) + T(5)) \\
 109 &:= 1! + 5! + 3! \times 2! - 4! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(2) + T(4) \\
 110 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 2! - 4! + 5! &= (T(1) - T(3)) \times (T(2) - T(4) - T(5)) \\
 114 &:= 3! \times (1! + 2!) - 4! + 5! &= -T(3) + (T(1) - T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 120 &:= (1! - 3!) \times 4! + 2! \times 5! &= (T(1) - T(3) + T(4) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 122 &:= 5! \times (1! + 3!) + 2! - 6! &= T(5) - T(1) - T(3) \times (T(2) - T(6)) \\
 126 &:= -(1! + 2!) \times 3! + 4! + 5! &= -(T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 130 &:= (-1! + 3!) \times (2! - 5!) + 6! &= T(1) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5)) + T(6) \\
 &:= 4! - (1! + 3!) \times 2! + 5! &= T(4) \times (T(1) - T(3) + T(2) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 131 &:= -2! \times 3! - 1! + 4! + 5! &= -T(2) \times T(3) - T(1) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 132 &:= -1! \times 2! \times 3! + 4! + 5! &= -T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 132 &:= 3! \times (4! + 5! - 2!) - 6! &= (T(3) - T(4)) \times (-T(5) + T(2) - T(6)) \\
 133 &:= 1! - 2! \times 3! + 4! + 5! &= T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 134 &:= -2! \times (3! - 1!) + 5! + 4! &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) - T(4) \\
 135 &:= -1! - 2! - 3! + 4! + 5! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(4) - T(5)) \\
 136 &:= -1! \times 2! - 3! + 4! + 5! &= T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(4) - T(5)) \\
 137 &:= -2! - 3! + 4! + 1! + 5! &= T(2) - T(3) - T(4) \times (T(1) - T(5)) \\
 138 &:= (1! - 2!) \times 3! + 4! + 5! &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 138 &:= (-1! + 4! + 5!) \times 3! - 6! &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) - T(3) - T(6) \\
 140 &:= 1! \times 2! - 3! + 4! + 5! &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 141 &:= 1! + 2! - 3! + 4! + 5! &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 143 &:= -1! + 3! \times (4! + 5!) - 6! &= -T(1) + (-T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 144 &:= (2! \times 3! - 1!) \times 4! - 5! &= T(2) + T(3) + (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= 3! \times (4! + 5! + 6!) - 7! &= T(3) \times (-T(4) - T(5) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 145 &:= 1! + (5! + 4!) \times 3! - 6! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(3) - T(6) \\
 146 &:= 2! + 3! \times (5! + 4!) - 6! &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(5) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 147 &:= -1! - 2! + 3! + 4! + 5! &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 148 &:= -1! \times 2! + 3! + 4! + 5! &= T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 149 &:= -2! + 3! + 4! + 1! + 5! &= T(2) + T(3) - T(4) \times (T(1) - T(5)) \\
 \\
 150 &:= (-1! + 2!) \times 3! + 4! + 5! &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) \times T(4) + T(5)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (1! + 4! + 5!) - 6! &= T(3) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) - T(6) \\
 \\
 151 &:= 2! + 3! + 4! - 1! + 5! &= -T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 152 &:= 1! \times 2! + 3! + 4! + 5! &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 153 &:= 1! + 2! + 3! + 4! + 5! &= -T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 154 &:= (3! - 1!) \times 2! + 4! + 5! &= T(3) + T(1) - T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 155 &:= -1! + 2! \times 3! + 4! + 5! &= (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 \\
 156 &:= 2! \times 3! \times 1! + 4! + 5! &= -T(2) - T(3) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= (2! + 4! + 5!) \times 3! - 6! &= (T(2) + T(4)) \times (-T(5) + T(3) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 157 &:= 2! \times 3! + 4! + 1! + 5! &= T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 158 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 2! + 4! + 5! &= -T(1) + T(3) + T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 160 &:= (4! - 1!) \times 2! - 3! + 5! &= T(4) + (T(1) + T(2) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 162 &:= (1! + 2!) \times 3! + 4! + 5! &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 163 &:= 1! + 5! + 4! \times 2! - 3! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) - T(2) + T(3) \\
 164 &:= (1! + 4!) \times 2! - 3! + 5! &= -T(1) + T(4) \times T(2) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 166 &:= (-1! + 3! \times 4!) \times 2! - 5! &= T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) \times T(2) - T(5) \\
 167 &:= -1! + 2! \times 3! \times 4! - 5! &= -T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 168 &:= 1! \times 2! \times 3! \times 4! - 5! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 &:= (3! + 1!) \times (6! + 4!) - 7! &= (-T(3) - T(1) + T(6)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 169 &:= 1! + 2! \times 3! \times 4! - 5! &= T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 170 &:= (4! \times 3! + 1!) \times 2! - 5! &= T(4) \times (T(3) - T(1) - T(2) + T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 173 &:= 3! - 1! + 4! \times 2! + 5! &= -T(3) - T(1) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(5)) \\
 174 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (-3! + 4!) + 5! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 175 &:= 1! + 3! + 2! \times 4! + 5! &= (T(1) + T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 176 &:= 3! + (4! + 1!) \times 2! + 5! &= (T(3) + T(4)) \times (-T(1) - T(2) + T(5)) \\
 178 &:= 2! \times (-3! - 1! - 4! + 5!) &= T(2) + (T(3) + T(1)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 179 &:= -1! + 2! \times (3! + 4!) + 5! &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 180 &:= (1! \times 3! + 4!) \times 2! + 5! &= (-T(1) \times T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(5) \\
 181 &:= 1! + 2! \times (3! + 4!) + 5! &= T(1) - T(2) \times (T(3) - T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 182 &:= 2! \times (3! + 4! + 1!) + 5! &= (T(2) - T(3) - T(4)) \times (T(1) - T(5)) \\
 184 &:= 2! \times (5! - 1! - 4!) - 3! &= (T(2) + T(5) + T(1)) \times T(4) - T(3) \\
 185 &:= -1! - 3! + 2! \times (-4! + 5!) &= (-T(1) + T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(4) + T(5) \\
 186 &:= (2! + 1!) \times 4! - 3! + 5! &= -T(2) + (-T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(5)) \\
 187 &:= 1! + 2! \times (5! - 4!) - 3! &= T(1) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(3) \\
 188 &:= (1! + 5! - 4!) \times 2! - 3! &= (-T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(4) + T(2)) + T(3) \\
 \\
 192 &:= (-2! - 1! + 3!) \times 4! + 5! &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(3) \times T(4)) + T(5) \\
 &:= (3! + 2!) \times (4! + 7!) - 8! &= (T(3) - T(2) \times T(4)) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\
 \\
 196 &:= 3! - 2! \times (4! + 1! - 5!) &= T(3) \times T(2) \times T(4) + T(1) + T(5) \\
 197 &:= 3! - 1! + (5! - 4!) \times 2! &= (T(3) - T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) - T(2) \\
 198 &:= (2! + 1!) \times 4! + 3! + 5! &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(4) \times T(3)) + T(5) \\
 200 &:= 3! + 2! \times (1! - 4! + 5!) &= (T(3) + T(2) - T(1)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 202 &:= (-1! - 3! + 5!) \times 2! - 4! &= T(1) + T(3) + T(5) \times (T(2) + T(4)) \\
 203 &:= 2! \times (5! - 3!) - 1! - 4! &= T(2) + (T(5) + T(3) - T(1)) \times T(4) \\
 204 &:= (1! \times 3! - 4! + 5!) \times 2! &= (T(1) + T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(2)) \\
 205 &:= -4! + 1! + 2! \times (-3! + 5!) &= T(4) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(3)) + T(5) \\
 206 &:= 2! \times (1! - 4! + 3! + 5!) &= -T(2) - T(1) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5)) \\
 208 &:= -3! - 4! + 2! \times (-1! + 5!) &= (T(3) + T(4) - T(2)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 209 &:= -1! - 3! - 4! + 2! \times 5! &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 210 &:= -1! \times 3! - 4! + 2! \times 5! &= (T(1) + T(3) + T(4) - T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 211 &:= 1! - 3! - 4! + 2! \times 5! &= T(1) - T(3) \times (T(4) - T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 212 &:= 2! \times (1! + 5!) - 3! - 4! &= T(2) - T(1) + (T(5) + T(3)) \times T(4) \\
 215 &:= 4! \times (-2! + 3!) - 1! + 5! &= -T(4) + T(2) \times (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 216 &:= (3! + 2!) \times 5! - 4! - 6! &= -T(3) - T(2) + T(5) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 1! \times 4! \times (3! - 2!) + 5! &= (-T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(2) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 221 &:= 2! \times 5! - 1! + 3! - 4! &= -T(2) + (T(5) - T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \\
 222 &:= 2! \times 1! \times 5! + 3! - 4! &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(4)) \\
 223 &:= 2! \times 5! + 1! + 3! - 4! &= T(2) + (T(5) + T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 228 &:= (3! \times 1! + 5!) \times 2! - 4! &= T(3) \times ((T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) - T(4)) \\
 230 &:= (1! + 3! + 5!) \times 2! - 4! &= (-T(1) + T(3) + T(5) + T(2)) \times T(4) \\
 238 &:= -2! - (1! - 3!) \times 4! + 5! &= -T(2) + T(1) + (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 240 &:= (1! - 2! + 3!) \times 4! + 5! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= 1! \times 5! \times (3! + 2!) - 6! &= (T(1) + T(5) - T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -(3! + 2!) \times (6! - 5!) + 7! &= T(3) + (T(2) - T(6)) \times (T(5) - T(7)) \\
 \\
 242 &:= 2! - (1! - 3!) \times 4! + 5! &= T(2) - T(1) + (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 248 &:= (1! + 5!) \times (2! + 3!) - 6! &= -T(1) + T(5) \times T(2) \times T(3) - T(6) \\
 250 &:= (3! - 1!) \times (2! + 4!) + 5! &= (T(3) + T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 252 &:= (-1! \times 2! + 4!) \times 3! + 5! &= (-T(1) + T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(5)) \\
 253 &:= (-2! + 4!) \times 3! + 1! + 5! &= -T(2) + (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 254 &:= 2! \times (5! + 1! - 3!) + 4! &= (T(2) \times T(5) - T(1)) \times T(3) - T(4) \\
 257 &:= -1! - 3! + 5! \times 2! + 4! &= (-T(1) + T(3) \times T(5)) \times T(2) - T(4) \\
 258 &:= (-2! + 1! + 4!) \times 3! + 5! &= T(2) + (T(1) + T(4) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 259 &:= 1! + 4! - 3! + 2! \times 5! &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(3) \times T(2) \times T(5) \\
 260 &:= (4! - 1!) \times 3! + 2! + 5! &= -T(4) \times T(1) + T(3) \times T(2) \times T(5) \\
 261 &:= -1! - 2! + 4! \times 3! + 5! &= (T(1) - T(2) \times T(4)) \times (T(3) - T(5)) \\
 262 &:= 4! \times 3! - 2! \times 1! + 5! &= T(4) - T(3) \times T(2) \times (T(1) - T(5)) \\
 263 &:= -2! + 1! + 5! + 3! \times 4! &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5) \times T(3)) - T(4) \\
 \\
 264 &:= (3! + 2!) \times 5! + 4! - 6! &= (T(3) + T(2) + T(5)) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 3! \times 4! \times (2! - 1!) + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) - T(1) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 265 &:= 4! \times 3! + 2! - 1! + 5! &= T(4) + (T(3) \times T(2) - T(1)) \times T(5) \\
 266 &:= 2! + 3! \times 4! \times 1! + 5! &= (T(2) + T(3) + T(4)) \times (-T(1) + T(5)) \\
 267 &:= 2! + 1! + 4! \times 3! + 5! &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(5))) \\
 269 &:= -1! + 3! + 4! + 2! \times 5! &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) + T(5)) \\
 270 &:= 1! \times 3! + 4! + 2! \times 5! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) + T(5)) \\
 271 &:= 1! + 3! + 4! + 2! \times 5! &= T(1) + T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) + T(5)) \\
 272 &:= 3! \times (4! + 1!) + 2! + 5! &= (T(3) + T(4)) \times (-T(1) + T(2) + T(5)) \\
 274 &:= 2! \times (5! - 1! + 3!) + 4! &= (T(2) \times T(5) - T(1)) \times T(3) + T(4) \\
 275 &:= -1! + 3! \times (4! + 2!) + 5! &= (-T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 276 &:= 3! \times (2! + 4!) \times 1! + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(2) \times T(4) + T(1) + T(5)) \\
 277 &:= 1! + (3! + 5!) \times 2! + 4! &= (-T(1) + T(3) \times T(5)) \times T(2) + T(4) \\
 278 &:= (1! + 5! + 3!) \times 2! + 4! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) \times T(2) - T(4) \\
 280 &:= (4! - 1! + 5!) \times 2! - 3! &= T(4) \times T(1) + T(5) \times T(2) \times T(3) \\
 281 &:= -1! - 3! + 2! \times (5! + 4!) &= T(1) + T(3) \times T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) \\
 282 &:= 2! \times (4! \times 1! + 5!) - 3! &= T(2) \times (T(4) - (T(1) - T(5)) \times T(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 284 &:= (1! + 5! + 4!) \times 2! - 3! &= -T(1) + T(5) \times (T(4) + T(2) + T(3)) \\
 286 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 4! - 2! + 5! &= T(1) + (T(3) + T(4) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 288 &:= -(1! + 2!) \times (4! + 5!) + 6! &= (T(1) - T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (1! + 2! - 3!) \times (4! - 5!) &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times (T(3) - T(4) \times T(5)) \\
 &:= -3! \times (1! + 2!) \times 4! + 6! &= -T(3) + (T(1) + T(2) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 2! \times (3! \times (4! + 5!) - 6!) &= (T(2) \times T(3) - T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 294 &:= 3! - (2! + 1!) \times (4! - 5!) &= -T(3) + (T(2) - T(1)) \times T(4) \times T(5) \\
 295 &:= 1! + 3! + 2! \times (5! + 4!) &= (T(1) + T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(5) + T(4) \\
 298 &:= 2! \times (3! + 5! - 1! + 4!) &= T(2) \times T(3) \times (T(5) + T(1)) + T(4) \\
 299 &:= -1! + 2! \times (4! + 3! + 5!) &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3) \times T(5)) \\
 300 &:= 1! \times 2! \times (3! + 4! + 5!) &= (T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 301 &:= 1! + 2! \times (4! + 3! + 5!) &= T(1) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3) \times T(5)) \\
 304 &:= (2! + 3!) \times (4! - 1!) + 5! &= (T(2) + T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 306 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (5! - 4! + 3!) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) \times T(4) + T(3) \\
 \\
 312 &:= (1! + 2!) \times 3! \times 4! - 5! &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)) \\
 &:= -3! \times 4! \times 2! - 5! + 6! &= T(3) \times T(4) - (T(2) - T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 318 &:= (2! + 1!) \times (5! - 3!) - 4! &= T(2) \times ((T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(4)) \\
 320 &:= (4! + 1!) \times (2! + 3!) + 5! &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(5)) \\
 330 &:= -3! - 4! + (1! + 2!) \times 5! &= T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(1) + T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 336 &:= -(1! + 2!) \times 5! - 4! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) - T(4))) \times T(6) \\
 &:= -2! \times 5! - 3! \times 4! + 6! &= (-T(2) + T(5) - T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 4! \times (2! + 3! + 1!) + 5! &= (T(4) \times T(2) - T(3)) \times (-T(1) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 342 &:= -(3! + 5!) \times (1! + 2!) + 6! &= T(3) + (T(5) - T(1)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 354 &:= -3! - (2! + 1!) \times 5! + 6! &= T(3) \times T(2) + (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 360 &:= (1! + 2! + 3!) \times 5! - 6! &= (T(1) + T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (3! - 1!) \times 2! \times 4! + 5! &= (-T(3) \times T(1) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 366 &:= 3! - 5! \times (1! + 2!) + 6! &= T(3) + T(5) \times T(1) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 378 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (3! - 5!) + 6! &= (-T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 380 &:= (3! - 2!) \times (5! - 1! - 4!) &= (-T(3) + T(2) \times T(5) - T(1)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 384 &:= -(1! + 3!) \times 4! \times 2! + 6! &= (T(1) \times T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 3! \times 4! + 2! \times 1! \times 5! &= (-T(3) + T(4) \times T(2)) \times (T(1) + T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := 4! - (1! + 2!) \times 5! + 6! & = (T(4) - T(1)) \times T(2) \times T(5) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{385} & := 1! + 3! \times 4! + 2! \times 5! & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{390} & := (1! + 4!) \times 3! + 2! \times 5! & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{408} & := -(1! + 2! \times 3!) \times 4! + 6! & = (T(1) - T(2)) \times (T(3) - T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{414} & := 3! \times (2! \times 4! + 1!) + 5! & = -T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{420} & := (1! + 4!) \times 2! \times 3! + 5! & = (T(1) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 & := -(1! + 4!) \times 2! \times 3! + 6! & = (T(1) + T(4) + T(2) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 & := -2! \times (4! + 5! + 3!) + 6! & = (T(2) + T(4) + T(5)) \times (-T(3) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{426} & := -3! \times (4! \times 2! + 1!) + 6! & = T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) - T(1)) \times T(6) \\
 & := 3! \times (-2! \times 4! - 1! + 5!) & = T(3) - T(2) \times T(4) \times (T(1) - T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{430} & := -(1! + 4! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! & = T(1) + T(4) \times T(5) \times T(2) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{431} & := -4! \times 2! \times 3! - 1! + 6! & = -T(4) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(6) \\
 & := -1! + (-2! \times 4! + 5!) \times 3! & = -T(1) + T(2) \times (T(4) \times T(5) - T(3)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{432} & := -1! \times 2! \times 3! \times 4! + 6! & = (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 & := (-1! \times 2! \times 4! + 5!) \times 3! & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(4) \times T(5) - T(3)) \\
 & := -(1! \times 4! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! & = (T(1) - T(4) - T(5)) \times (T(2) - T(6)) \\
 & := -(2! \times 4! + 6!) \times 3! + 7! & = -T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) \\
 & := 2! \times (-3! + 5!) \times 4! - 7! & = (T(2) + T(3) + T(5)) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := (2! + 3!) \times (4! + 5!) - 6! & = T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 & := -4! \times (1! + 3!) - 5! + 6! & = -T(4) + T(1) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{433} & := 1! - (2! \times 4! - 5!) \times 3! & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(4) \times T(5) - T(3)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{438} & := (2! + 1!) \times (5! + 4!) + 3! & = T(2) \times ((-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(3)) \\
 & := 3! - (4! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! & = T(3) \times T(4) + (T(5) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 & := 3! \times (1! - 4! \times 2!) + 6! & = T(3) \times T(1) \times (T(4) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{444} & := ((1! - 4!) \times 2! + 5!) \times 3! & = T(1) \times T(4) \times T(2) \times T(5) - T(3) \\
 & := -2! \times (5! + 3!) - 4! + 6! & = (-T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := 3! \times (1! - 4!) \times 2! + 6! & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{450} & := -(1! + 4!) \times 3! - 5! + 6! & = -T(1) + T(4) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 & := -2! \times 5! - 3! - 4! + 6! & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times (-T(3) + T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := (1! + 2!) \times (3! + 4! + 5!) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 454 &:= -2! - 4! \times 3! - 5! + 6! &= T(2) + T(4) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 455 &:= -4! - 2! \times 5! - 1! + 6! &= (T(4) + T(2)) \times (T(5) - T(1) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -1! + (3! - 2!) \times 5! - 4! &= -T(1) + T(3) + (T(2) \times T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 456 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 2! \times 4! + 5! &= T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \times T(5) \\
 &:= -3! \times 1! \times 4! + 6! - 5! &= T(3) - (T(1) - T(4) - T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= -1! \times 4! - 2! \times 5! + 6! &= (-T(1) + T(4) \times T(2)) \times T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= -5! - 3! \times (6! + 4!) + 7! &= (-T(5) + T(3) + T(6)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 457 &:= 1! + (3! - 2!) \times 5! - 4! &= T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(5) \times T(4) \\
 458 &:= -4! \times 3! - 5! + 2! + 6! &= -T(4) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 460 &:= (1! + 5!) \times (-2! + 3!) - 4! &= (T(1) - T(5) \times (T(2) - T(3))) \times T(4) \\
 462 &:= (1! - 4!) \times 3! - 5! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -2! \times 5! - 4! + 3! + 6! &= (T(2) + T(5) + T(4) - T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 467 &:= -1! - (3! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 468 &:= -(1! \times 3! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 &:= (2! - 4!) \times 3! - 5! + 6! &= (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\
 469 &:= 1! - (3! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! &= T(1) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 474 &:= -3! \times 1! - 5! \times 2! + 6! &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 480 &:= (-1! + 3!) \times 5! \times 2! - 6! &= (-T(1) + T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (1! - 2! + 3!) \times (-4! + 5!) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= 2! \times 4! \times (1! - 3!) + 6! &= T(2) \times T(4) \times (T(1) - T(3) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -2! \times 5! - 3! \times 6! + 7! &= -(T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(7) \\
 485 &:= -1! - 2! \times 5! + 3! + 6! &= -T(1) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 486 &:= -1! \times 2! \times 5! + 3! + 6! &= (T(1) \times T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 487 &:= 1! - 2! \times 5! + 3! + 6! &= T(1) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 500 &:= (1! - 5!) \times (2! - 3!) + 4! &= (-T(1) + T(5) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) \\
 503 &:= -2! \times 5! + 4! - 1! + 6! &= T(2) + (T(5) + T(4)) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) \\
 504 &:= -(1! + 3! + 2!) \times 4! + 6! &= (-T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= -(3! - 2!) \times 4! - 5! + 6! &= T(3) \times ((-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) - T(6)) \\
 &:= 1! \times 4! - 2! \times 5! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(4) + T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := 3! \times 4! + (2! + 1!) \times 5! & = (T(3) + T(4) \times T(2)) \times (-T(1) + T(5)) \\
 506 & := (1! - 5!) \times 2! + 4! + 6! & = (T(1) + T(5) \times T(2)) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \\
 510 & := 4! - 2! \times 5! + 3! + 6! & = T(4) \times ((-T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3) - T(6)) \\
 516 & := -2! \times (3! + 5! - 4!) + 6! & = -T(2) - T(3) + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 522 & := -3! + (4! - 5!) \times 2! + 6! & = T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(5) - T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 527 & := -1! + 2! \times (4! - 5!) + 6! & = -T(1) + T(2) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 & := -1! - (2! + 3!) \times 4! + 6! & = (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(6)) \\
 528 & := (1! \times 4! - 5!) \times 2! + 6! & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times (-T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 & := -(3! + 2!) \times 4! \times 1! + 6! & = (-T(3) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 & := (2! + 3!) \times (-4! + 6!) - 7! & = T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(4) \times T(6) - T(7)) \\
 529 & := 1! - 2! \times (5! - 4!) + 6! & = T(1) + T(2) + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 534 & := 3! - 2! \times (5! - 4!) + 6! & = T(3) + T(2) + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 540 & := -(3! + 4!) \times 2! - 5! + 6! & = T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(2) - T(5) + T(6)) \\
 & := 2! \times ((1! + 4!) \times 3! + 5!) & = (-T(2) - T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3) \times T(5) \\
 546 & := -2! \times 4! - 3! - 5! + 6! & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 552 & := -1! \times 4! \times 2! + 6! - 5! & = (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(6) - T(5) \\
 & := -2! \times 3! \times 4! + 6! + 5! & = -T(2) + (T(3) + T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 & := -(3! - 1! + 2!) \times 4! + 6! & = T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(6))) \\
 553 & := -2! \times 4! - 5! + 1! + 6! & = T(2) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 558 & := 3! - 5! - 2! \times 4! + 6! & = (T(3) + T(5) - T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := -3! \times (1! + 2! + 4!) + 6! & = T(3) \times T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(4) + T(6)) \\
 564 & := -(2! + 4! + 6!) \times 3! + 7! & = T(2) \times (T(4) \times T(6) + T(3) - T(7)) \\
 & := -3! \times 2! - 5! - 4! + 6! & = T(3) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := -3! \times (4! + 2!) \times 1! + 6! & = T(3) \times (T(4) + (T(2) + T(1)) \times T(6)) \\
 570 & := -1! \times 3! - 4! + 6! - 5! & = (T(1) + T(3) + T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 & := -3! \times (1! + 6! + 4!) + 7! & = (-T(3) \times T(1) + T(6)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 573 & := -3! \times 4! - 1! - 2! + 6! & = T(3) + (T(4) - T(1)) \times T(2) \times T(6) \\
 575 & := 1! + 6! - 2! - 4! - 5! & = (-T(1) + T(6) + T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 576 &:= (2! \times 5! - 3!) \times 4! - 7! &= (T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(3) \times T(4) - T(7)) \\
 &:= (2! \times 5! - 4!) \times 3! - 6! &= T(2) \times T(5) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (2! - 1!) \times 6! - 4! \times 3! &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= (4! + 5!) \times (1! - 2!) + 6! &= (T(4) + T(5) - T(1)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (3! - 2!) \times (4! \times 1! + 5!) &= (T(3) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 579 &:= 1! + 2! - 4! - 5! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) \times T(5) - T(6) \\
 580 &:= (-4! + 1!) \times 3! - 2! + 6! &= T(4) \times (T(1) - T(3) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 587 &:= -1! + 3! \times (2! - 4!) + 6! &= -T(1) + (T(3) \times T(2) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 588 &:= -(1! \times 2!) \times 3! - 5! + 6! &= (T(1) - T(2) \times (T(3) - T(5))) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (-1! \times 4! + 2!) \times 3! + 6! &= (T(1) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 2! \times 3! - 4! - 5! + 6! &= (-T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 3! \times (2! - 4! - 6!) + 7! &= (-T(3) - T(2) + T(4)) \times T(6) \times T(7) \\
 &:= -5! - 3! \times (2! + 6!) + 7! &= (T(5) - T(3) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (2! - 4! \times 1! + 5!) &= T(3) \times (T(2) - T(4)) \times (T(1) - T(5)) \\
 \\
 589 &:= 1! - (4! - 2!) \times 3! + 6! &= T(1) + (T(4) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 594 &:= -(3! + 5!) \times (2! - 1!) + 6! &= (-T(3) + T(5)) \times T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (2! - 4! + 1!) + 6! &= -T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (1! + 2! - 4! + 5!) &= -T(3) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 600 &:= (2! + 3!) \times 6! - 7! - 5! &= (-T(2) - T(3) + T(6) + T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 600 &:= 4! \times (2! - 1! - 3!) + 6! &= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(1)) \times (-T(3) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 5! \times (2! \times 3! - 1!) - 6! &= T(5) \times (T(2) \times T(3) + T(1) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 5! \times (2! \times 4! - 1!) - 7! &= T(5) \times (T(2) + T(4) - T(1) + T(7)) \\
 612 &:= 1! \times 2! \times 3! - 5! + 6! &= (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (2! - 6!) \times 3! - 5! + 7! &= T(2) + T(6) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= -3! \times 2! - 5! + 4! + 6! &= T(3) \times (-T(2) + (T(5) - T(4)) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 618 &:= (1! + 2!) \times 3! - 5! + 6! &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times (T(3) - T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 620 &:= (4! + 1!) \times (2! - 3!) + 6! &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(6)) \\
 621 &:= -1! - 2! - 5! + 4! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 623 &:= -1! - (3! - 2!) \times 4! + 6! &= -T(1) - T(3) + (T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 624 &:= (-1! \times 3! + 2!) \times 4! + 6! &= -T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (-1! + 2!) \times 4! + 6! - 5! &= (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) + T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (1! - 2! + 3!) \times 5! + 4! & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + (T(5) \times T(4))) \\
 & := 3! \times 4! - 2! \times 5! + 6! & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 & := 7! - 5! - 3! \times 6! + 4! & = T(7) \times T(5) - T(3) + T(6) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{625} & := 4! - 5! + 2! - 1! + 6! & = (T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(1) + T(6)) \\
 & := 1! - (3! - 2!) \times 4! + 6! & = T(1) - T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{629} & := -1! - 5! + 4! + 3! + 6! & = -T(1) + (T(5) - T(4)) \times T(3) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{630} & := 1! \times 3! + 4! - 5! + 6! & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 & := -(1! + 2!) \times (3! + 4!) + 6! & = (-T(1) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{631} & := 1! + 3! + 4! - 5! + 6! & = T(1) - T(3) \times (T(4) - T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{646} & := -(1! - 4!) \times 2! + 6! - 5! & = T(1) + T(4) \times T(2) \times T(6) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{648} & := (1! + 2! - 3!) \times 4! + 6! & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 & := 2! \times 1! \times 4! + 6! - 5! & = T(2) \times ((T(1) + T(4)) \times T(6) - T(5)) \\
 & := -(2! + 3!) \times 4! + 5! + 6! & = -T(2) + (T(3) + T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 & := 3! \times 5! - (2! + 1!) \times 4! & = T(3) \times (T(5) - T(2)) \times (-T(1) + T(4)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{650} & := (4! + 1!) \times 2! - 5! + 6! & = T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{654} & := 2! \times 4! + 3! - 5! + 6! & = T(2) + (T(4) + T(3) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 & := 3! - 4! \times (2! + 1!) + 6! & = -T(3) + T(4) \times T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{660} & := (4! + 3!) \times 2! - 5! + 6! & = T(4) \times ((T(3) - T(2)) \times T(5) + T(6)) \\
 & := -2! \times (3! + 4!) \times 1! + 6! & = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{666} & := -3! - 2! \times 4! \times 1! + 6! & = T(3) + (T(2) \times T(4)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{672} & := -(1! + 3!) \times 4! + 5! + 6! & = (T(1) + T(3) + T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 & := 2! \times 4! \times (5! - 1!) - 7! & = -T(2) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times (-T(1) + T(7)) \\
 & := 4! \times (2! + 1!) - 5! + 6! & = (-T(4) + T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(5))) \times T(6) \\
 & := 2! \times (5! - 4! \times 3!) + 6! & = -T(2) + (T(5) + T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 & := -2! \times 4! + 3! \times 1! \times 5! & = (-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{678} & := -2! \times 4! \times 1! + 6! + 3! & = T(2) \times (T(4) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(3)) \\
 \mathbf{680} & := 3! + 6! + 2! \times (1! - 4!) & = (T(3) + T(6) \times T(2) - T(1)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{684} & := -(2! + 4!) \times 3! + 5! + 6! & = (T(2) + T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(5) + T(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -(2! + 6!) \times 3! - 4! + 7! & = (T(2) + T(6) - T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 687 & := -3! - 1! - 4! - 2! + 6! & = -T(3) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(6) \\
 689 & := 1! - 4! - 3! - 2! + 6! & = -T(1) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 690 & := -(1! + 4!) \times 3! + 5! + 6! & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(3) \times T(5) - T(6)) \\
 & := (4! + 3!) \times (1! - 2!) + 6! & = T(4) \times (T(3) \times T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 & := -4! - (1! + 6!) \times 3! + 7! & = T(4) - (T(1) - T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 691 & := -1! - 4! - 3! + 2! + 6! & = T(1) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 693 & := 1! - 4! + 2! - 3! + 6! & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 & := -1! - 4! - 2! + 3! \times 5! & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) \\
 696 & := (-1! + 2! \times 5!) \times 4! - 7! & = -T(1) - T(2) + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 & := -3! \times (6! + 4!) + 7! + 5! & = T(3) \times T(6) + (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 699 & := 3! - 1! - 4! - 2! + 6! & = T(3) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(6) \\
 700 & := -4! \times 1! + 3! - 2! + 6! & = T(4) \times (T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 702 & := -3! \times (2! + 6! + 1!) + 7! & = T(3) + (T(2) + T(6)) \times (T(1) + T(7)) \\
 & := 5! - (4! - 1!) \times 3! + 6! & = (T(5) + T(4) + T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 704 & := 2! + (5! + 1!) \times 3! - 4! & = (T(2) \times T(5) - T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \\
 708 & := 3! \times (2! - 6!) - 4! + 7! & = -T(3) + T(2) \times (T(6) \times T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := -3! \times (4! - 2!) + 5! + 6! & = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6))) \\
 & := -1! \times 4! + 3! \times (2! + 5!) & = (T(1) - T(4) \times T(3)) \times (T(2) - T(5)) \\
 710 & := (1! - 3!) \times (2! - 5! - 4!) & = (-T(1) + T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(5))) \times T(4) \\
 712 & := -2! - (1! + 6!) \times 3! + 7! & = -T(2) + T(1) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 714 & := (1! + 2!) \times 3! - 4! + 6! & = ((T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 & := 2! \times 4! \times 5! - 3! - 7! & = T(2) \times (T(4) \times (T(5) + T(3)) + T(7)) \\
 & := -(1! + 5!) \times 3! + 2! \times 6! & = (T(1) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 & := 3! \times (1! + 2! + 5!) - 4! & = T(3) \times (-T(1) + (-T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4)) \\
 716 & := 2! - (1! + 6!) \times 3! + 7! & = T(2) - T(1) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 717 & := -1! - 2! - 6! \times 3! + 7! & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 718 & := -1! \times 2! - 6! \times 3! + 7! & = T(1) + T(2) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 720 &:= 1! \times 5! \times 2! \times 3! - 6! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -(1! + 2!) \times 3! + 4! \times 5! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= -2! \times 4! \times 6! - 7! + 8! &= (T(2) + T(4) - T(6) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= -(1! + 2!) \times 6! + 5! \times 4! &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 &:= (-3! + 4!) \times 5! - 2! \times 6! &= T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (6! + 5! \times 2!) - 7! &= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 722 &:= 2! \times (4! \times 5! + 1!) - 7! &= -T(2) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(1) + T(7)) \\
 726 &:= 3! \times (2! \times 5! + 1!) - 6! &= (T(3) \times T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 730 &:= (-1! + 3!) \times (2! + 5! + 4!) &= (T(1) - T(3) \times (T(2) - T(5))) \times T(4) \\
 731 &:= (2! - 6!) \times 3! - 1! + 7! &= T(2) + (T(6) + T(3) - T(1)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 732 &:= (2! - 6!) \times 1! \times 3! + 7! &= -T(2) + T(6) \times (T(1) + T(3) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 1! \times 4! - 3! \times (2! - 5!) &= (T(1) + T(4) \times T(3)) \times (-T(2) + T(5)) \\
 &:= 4! - 3! \times (2! + 6!) + 7! &= T(4) \times T(3) + (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 735 &:= -1! - 2! + 4! - 3! + 6! &= (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 736 &:= -2! + (5! - 1!) \times 3! + 4! &= (T(2) \times T(5) + T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \\
 \\
 738 &:= (2! - 6! + 1!) \times 3! + 7! &= T(2) + T(6) \times (T(1) + T(3) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 4! - (1! + 6!) \times 3! + 7! &= -T(4) + (T(1) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 744 &:= 2! \times 3! \times 5! + 4! - 6! &= (T(2) + T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(4) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 4! \times (1! + 5! \times 2!) - 7! &= (T(4) - T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 745 &:= 1! + 4! - 3! \times 6! + 7! &= -T(1) - T(4) + (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 747 &:= 2! + 4! + 1! + 3! \times 5! &= -T(2) + T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 755 &:= -1! + 3! \times 2! + 4! + 6! &= -T(1) + (T(3) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 756 &:= 1! \times 3! \times 2! + 4! + 6! &= (T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (2! - 6!) \times 3! + 4! + 7! &= T(2) \times T(6) \times (-T(3) - T(4) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (2! + 4!) - 5! + 6! &= T(3) \times ((-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 757 &:= 1! + 3! \times 2! + 4! + 6! &= T(1) + (T(3) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 768 &:= (3! \times 4! - 5!) \times 2! + 6! &= (T(3) + T(4)) \times (-T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 &:= (3! + 1!) \times 4! - 5! + 6! &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(4) \times T(5) - T(6)) \\
 &:= 2! \times 4! - 3! \times 6! + 7! &= T(2) \times T(4) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 2! \times 4! + 3! \times 1! \times 5! &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 780 &:= -(4! + 3!) \times 2! + 6! + 5! &= T(4) \times ((T(3) - T(2)) \times T(6) + T(5)) \\
 &:= 2! \times (4! \times 1! + 3!) + 6! &= T(2) \times T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(3) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 786 &:= -3! - 4! \times 2! + 6! + 5! &= T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) \times T(6) + T(5)) \\
 790 &:= -(4! + 1!) \times 2! + 6! + 5! &= T(4) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(6) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 792 &:= (3! + 2!) \times 4! - 5! + 6! &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) - T(6)) \\
 &:= 3! \times 5! + (2! + 1!) \times 4! &= T(3) \times (T(5) - T(2)) \times (T(1) + T(4)) \\
 &:= 4! \times (-2! + 3! - 1!) + 6! &= (T(4) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 794 &:= (1! - 4!) \times 2! + 6! + 5! &= -T(1) + (-T(4) + T(2) \times T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 810 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (4! + 3!) + 6! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 816 &:= (-1! \times 2! + 3!) \times 4! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 &:= 5! \times (-1! + 2!) - 4! + 6! &= (T(5) + T(1)) \times (T(2) \times T(4) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 820 &:= (4! + 1!) \times (-2! + 3!) + 6! &= T(4) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6))) \\
 \\
 828 &:= 2! \times 3! + 5! - 4! + 6! &= (T(2) \times T(3)) \times (T(5) + T(4) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -(2! + 6!) \times 3! + 7! + 5! &= T(2) + (T(6) + T(3) + T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 839 &:= -1! + 5! - 3! \times 6! + 7! &= -T(1) + (T(5) - T(3) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 840 &:= -1! \times 6! \times 3! + 5! + 7! &= (T(1) \times T(6) - T(3) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (1! + 3! - 2!) \times 4! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(3) - T(2)) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (2! + 3!) \times 6! + 5! - 7! &= (T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(6)) - T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (1! + 3! \times 2!) \times 5! - 6! &= (T(1) - T(3) + T(2) \times T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (4! \times 2! + 5!) \times (-1! + 3!) &= T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(1) + T(3)) \\
 \\
 841 &:= 1! - 3! \times 6! + 5! + 7! &= T(1) - (T(3) - T(6) - T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 846 &:= 3! \times (4! - 1! - 2!) + 6! &= T(3) + T(4) \times (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 852 &:= -3! \times (6! - 2!) + 7! + 5! &= (T(3) + T(6)) \times (T(2) + T(7)) + T(5) \\
 854 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 2! + 6! + 5! &= -T(1) + (-T(3) + T(2) \times T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 856 &:= (-1! + 5! + 4!) \times 3! - 2! &= T(1) + T(5) \times (T(4) \times T(3) - T(2)) \\
 858 &:= (1! + 5! + 4! - 2!) \times 3! &= ((-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(2)) \times T(3) \\
 860 &:= 2! + 3! \times (5! - 1! + 4!) &= (-T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(1)) \times T(4) \\
 861 &:= -1! - 2! + 4! \times 3! + 6! &= (-T(1) + (-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 863 &:= -1! + 3! \times (4! - 6!) + 7! &= T(1) - T(3) + (T(4) + T(6)) \times T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 864 & := (-1! + 2!) \times 3! \times 4! + 6! & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 & := (3! + 5! \times 2!) \times 4! - 7! & = -T(3) + T(5) \times (T(2) \times T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := 3! \times (4! + 2! \times 5!) - 6! & = (-T(3) + T(4) \times T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 869 & := -1! + 3! + 5! + 4! + 6! & = (-T(1) + T(3) \times T(5)) \times T(4) - T(6) \\
 870 & := (-1! + 4! + 2! + 5!) \times 3! & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(5) \times T(3)) \\
 875 & := -1! + 6! + 3! \times (2! + 4!) & = (T(1) - T(6) \times T(3)) \times (T(2) - T(4)) \\
 \\
 876 & := 2! \times 3! + 4! + 5! + 6! & = (-T(2) + T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := 3! \times 1! \times (2! + 4!) + 6! & = T(3) \times (-T(1) + (-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(6)) \\
 & := 3! \times 1! \times (2! + 4! + 5!) & = T(3) \times (-T(1) - T(2) + T(4) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 882 & := (1! + 2! + 4!) \times 3! + 6! & = (-T(1) \times T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) \times T(6) \\
 & := 2! \times 4! + 5! - 3! + 6! & = T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) \times T(3) - T(6) \\
 & := 3! \times (1! + 2! + 4! + 5!) & = (T(3) \times T(1)) \times (-T(2) + T(4) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 888 & := (3! - 1! + 2!) \times 4! + 6! & = T(3) \times (T(1) - (T(2) - T(4)) \times T(6)) \\
 & := 2! \times 4! + (3! + 1!) \times 5! & = T(2) + (T(4) \times T(3) - T(1)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 900 & := 2! \times (4! + 3!) + 5! + 6! & = T(2) \times T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 912 & := (2! + 1!) \times 4! + 5! + 6! & = T(2) \times (-T(1) - T(4) + T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 & := (2! + 3!) \times (6! + 4!) - 7! & = (-T(2) + T(3) + T(6)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 914 & := (-4! + 1! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! & = -T(4) + (-T(1) + T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 918 & := 2! \times (5! - 4!) + 3! + 6! & = -T(2) + T(5) \times T(4) \times T(3) + T(6) \\
 924 & := 2! \times (3! + 5! - 4!) + 6! & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 930 & := -4! - 3! + 2! \times 5! + 6! & = T(4) \times (T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(5)) + T(6)) \\
 934 & := -4! + 2! \times (5! - 1!) + 6! & = T(4) + (T(2) \times T(5) - T(1)) \times T(6) \\
 935 & := -1! - 4! + 5! \times 2! + 6! & = -T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) \times T(2) \times T(6) \\
 936 & := -1! \times 4! + 2! \times 5! + 6! & = T(1) - T(4) + T(2) \times T(5) \times T(6) \\
 938 & := -4! + 2! \times (1! + 5!) + 6! & = -T(4) + T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 942 & := 2! \times 5! + 3! - 4! + 6! & = -T(2) + (-T(5) + T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 944 & := (1! + 5!) \times (2! + 3!) - 4! & = -T(1) + T(5) \times (T(2) + T(3) \times T(4)) \\
 946 & := -(1! - 5! + 3!) \times 2! + 6! & = T(1) + T(5) \times (T(3) - T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 948 & := 2! \times (5! + 3!) - 4! + 6! & = T(2) - (T(5) - T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 & := 2! \times (-3! \times 1! + 5!) + 6! & = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 950 & := (1! - 3! + 5!) \times 2! + 6! & = -T(1) + T(3) + T(5) \times T(2) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 952 &:= -3! - (1! - 5!) \times 2! + 6! &= T(3) + T(1) + T(5) \times T(2) \times T(6) \\
 954 &:= -3! + 2! \times 1! \times 5! + 6! &= T(3) + T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 960 &:= (3! + 1!) \times 2! \times 5! - 6! &= -T(3) + (T(1) + T(2) \times T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 2! \times 4! \times (3! - 1!) + 6! &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (2! + 3!) \times (5! + 7!) - 8! &= (T(2) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= -3! \times 6! + 2! \times 5! + 7! &= -T(3) + T(6) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 4! \times (3! - 1!) + 5! + 6! &= T(4) \times ((T(3) - T(1)) \times T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 2! \times (1! - 3!) \times (4! - 5!) &= (T(2) + T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 966 &:= 1! \times 5! \times 2! + 3! + 6! &= (T(1) - T(5) \times (T(2) - T(3))) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 972 &:= 2! \times (3! + 5!) \times 1! + 6! &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(5) \times (T(1) + T(6))) \\
 &:= 2! \times (5! - 3!) + 4! + 6! &= (-T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(3) \times T(4) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 984 &:= 3! \times 1! \times 4! + 6! + 5! &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + (-T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 990 &:= 3! + 2! \times 5! + 4! + 6! &= T(3) \times (-T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 &:= 5! + 3! \times (1! + 4!) + 6! &= T(5) \times T(3) \times T(1) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 1007 &:= -1! + 2! \times 3! \times 4! + 6! &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 1008 &:= 1! \times 2! \times 3! \times 4! + 6! &= T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (2! \times 1! \times 4! + 5!) \times 3! &= (T(2) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= (4! + 5!) \times 2! \times 3! - 6! &= (-T(4) + T(5) + T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 2! \times (4! \times 1! + 5!) + 6! &= (T(2) \times (T(4) + T(1)) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 3! \times (4! \times 2! - 6!) + 7! &= (T(3) \times T(4) - T(2) - T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 1009 &:= 1! + 2! \times 3! \times 4! + 6! &= T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 1020 &:= 3! \times (4! + 1!) \times 2! + 6! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (-T(1) - T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 3! \times ((4! + 1!) \times 2! + 5!) &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(2) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 1056 &:= 2! \times 4! \times (3! + 1!) + 6! &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 2! \times (-5! + 6!) - 3! \times 4! &= (T(2) \times T(5) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \\
 \\
 1080 &:= (1! - 3!) \times (4! - 2! \times 5!) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(2) + T(5)) \\
 &:= 5! \times (3! - 2! - 1!) + 6! &= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6))) \\
 \\
 1140 &:= 2! \times (-1! + 5! - 4!) \times 3! &= (T(2) + T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times T(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := 2! \times (-3! - 5! + 6! - 4!) & = ((T(2) + T(3)) \times T(5) - T(6)) \times T(4) \\
 & := 2! \times (-3! \times (4! + 1!) + 6!) & = (T(2) - T(3) \times T(4)) \times (T(1) - T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1152} & := 3! \times (2! + 1!) \times 4! + 6! & = T(3) \times (T(2) - (T(1) - T(4)) \times T(6)) \\
 & := 3! \times (5! - 2! \times 4!) + 6! & = T(3) \times (-T(5) - T(2) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 & := 2! \times (-3! \times (6! + 4!) + 7!) & = T(2) \times (T(3) - T(6) \times (T(4) - T(7))) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1154} & := (1! + 6! - 4! - 5!) \times 2! & = -T(1) + T(6) \times (T(4) + T(5) \times T(2)) \\
 \mathbf{1164} & := (1! + 5! - 4!) \times 2! \times 3! & = (-T(1) + (T(5) \times (T(4) + T(2)))) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{1170} & := -3! - 4! + 2! \times (6! - 5!) & = (((T(3) \times T(4)) - T(2)) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1176} & := -1! \times 4! + 2! \times (-5! + 6!) & = (T(1) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 & := (3! + 1!) \times (2! \times 4! + 5!) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1182} & := 3! - 4! + 2! \times (6! - 5!) & = (T(3) \times T(4) - T(2)) \times T(6) - T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1188} & := 1! \times 2! \times (-5! - 3! + 6!) & = (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 & := 2! \times (-5! + 3! + 6!) - 4! & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3) \times (T(6) - T(4)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1200} & := -(3! + 4! + 2!) \times 5! + 7! & = -T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 & := (4! - 5!) \times (1! - 3!) + 6! & = T(4) \times (T(5) - (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(6)) \\
 & := 5! \times 1! \times (-2! + 3!) + 6! & = T(5) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6))) \\
 & := (4! - (1! + 3!) \times 2!) \times 5! & = T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(3) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 & := 2! \times (-6! \times 3! + 7! - 5!) & = ((-T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) - T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 & := 2! \times (6! - (3! - 1!) \times 4!) & = (T(2) + T(6)) \times (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1212} & := 2! \times (-5! + 6! - 3!) + 4! & = -T(2) + T(5) \times (T(6) + T(3) \times T(4)) \\
 & := 2! \times 1! \times (-5! + 3! + 6!) & = T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(5) \times (T(3) + T(6))) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1214} & := (1! + 3! + 6! - 5!) \times 2! & = -T(1) + (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(5) \times T(2) \\
 \mathbf{1218} & := 2! \times (-5! + 6!) - 3! + 4! & = T(2) + T(5) \times (T(6) + T(3) \times T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{1230} & := 3! + 2! \times (6! - 5!) + 4! & = (-T(3) \times (T(2) - T(6)) + T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 \mathbf{1242} & := 2! \times (-5! + 4! + 6!) - 3! & = -T(2) - T(5) + T(4) \times T(6) \times T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1248} & := ((3! - 1!) \times 5! + 4!) \times 2! & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(4) + T(2)) \\
 & := 2! \times (5! + 3! \times 4!) + 6! & = T(2) - T(5) + T(3) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1250} & := 2! \times (1! + 6! - 5! + 4!) & = (T(2) + T(1)) \times T(6) \times T(5) - T(4) \\
 \mathbf{1260} & := 2! \times (3! - 5! + 4! + 6!) & = (-T(2) - T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1270} & := (-4! + 6! - 1!) \times 2! - 5! & = T(4) + T(6) \times (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1272 &:= 2! \times 6! - 4! \times (1! + 3!) &= (T(2) + T(6) \times T(4) - T(1)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= 5! - 2! \times (3! \times 4! - 6!) &= T(5) - T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 1278 &:= 2! \times (6! - 4!) + 3! - 5! &= T(2) + T(6) \times T(4) \times T(3) + T(5) \\
 1290 &:= -4! - 3! - 5! + 2! \times 6! &= T(4) \times (T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2)) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 2! \times 6! - 3! \times (1! + 4!) &= (T(2) + T(6) \times T(3)) \times T(1) \times T(4) \\
 &:= 3! \times (5! - 4! - 1!) + 6! &= T(3) \times (T(5) - T(4) \times (T(1) - T(6))) \\
 1296 &:= (1! \times 5! - 4!) \times 3! + 6! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(4) \times T(3) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -1! \times 4! \times 3! + 2! \times 6! &= (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (3! - 2!) \times (4! + 5!) + 6! &= T(3) \times ((T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(6)) \\
 1302 &:= (1! - 4!) \times 3! + 2! \times 6! &= (-T(1) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= -4! + 3! - 5! + 2! \times 6! &= (-T(4) + T(3) \times (T(5) - T(2))) \times T(6) \\
 1308 &:= (5! + 2! - 4!) \times 3! + 6! &= -T(5) + (T(2) + T(4) \times T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 1320 &:= (-2! + 1! + 3!) \times 5! + 6! &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(6)) \\
 &:= -5! \times (1! + 3! + 4!) + 7! &= T(5) \times T(1) \times (T(3) \times T(4) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 5! \times (-3! + 4! - 1!) - 6! &= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 1322 &:= (-1! + 3!) \times 5! + 2! + 6! &= -T(1) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(2) \times T(6) \\
 1324 &:= (-1! + 6!) \times 2! + 3! - 5! &= T(1) + T(6) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) \\
 1326 &:= 2! \times 1! \times 6! + 3! - 5! &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(5))) \\
 1338 &:= -5! - 3! + 4! + (2! \times 6!) &= T(5) + (T(3) \times T(4) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 1344 &:= (3! - 1!) \times 5! + 4! + 6! &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(5) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 1350 &:= 3! + 4! - 5! + 2! \times 6! &= (T(3) \times T(4) + T(5)) \times (-T(2) + T(6)) \\
 1380 &:= (4! + 3! + 6!) \times 2! - 5! &= T(4) \times (T(3) \times T(6) - T(2) + T(5)) \\
 &:= 1! \times 2! \times (6! - 3! - 4!) &= (-T(1) + T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) \times T(4) \\
 1392 &:= -(2! + 5!) \times 4! + 3! \times 6! &= (T(2) - T(5)) \times (T(4) - T(3) \times T(6)) \\
 1404 &:= 2! \times 1! \times (-4! + 6! + 3!) &= (T(2) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(6)) \times T(3) \\
 1410 &:= -(5! + 1!) \times (4! + 3!) + 7! &= T(5) \times ((T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(7)) \\
 &:= -4! + (5! - 1!) \times 3! + 6! &= T(4) \times (T(5) \times T(1) + T(3) \times T(6)) \\
 1416 &:= 2! \times (7! - 3! \times 6!) - 4! &= T(2) \times (T(7) - T(3)) \times T(6) + T(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1428 &:= 3! \times (5! - 2! - 6!) + 7! &= (T(3) \times (T(5) - T(2)) - T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 2! \times (-(1! + 6!) \times 3! + 7!) &= (T(2) - T(1)) \times T(6) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 1430 &:= (1! + 3! + 6!) \times 2! - 4! &= (-T(1) + T(3) \times (T(6) + T(2))) \times T(4) \\
 1438 &:= -(4! + 3!) \times 5! - 2! + 7! &= T(4) + (T(3) + T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 1440 &:= (-2! \times 3! + 4! \times 1!) \times 5! &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 &:= (2! \times 4! + 3!) \times 5! - 7! &= T(2) \times (T(4) \times T(3) + T(5) \times T(7)) \\
 &:= -(2! \times 4! + 3!) \times 6! + 8! &= (T(2) + T(4) + T(3) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 3! \times 5! \times (2! + 1!) - 6! &= T(3) \times (T(5) - T(2)) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 4! \times 2! \times 5! - 3! \times 6! &= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(6)) \\
 &:= -2! \times 6! + 4! \times 1! \times 5! &= T(2) \times (T(6) + T(4) + T(1)) \times T(5) \\
 &:= -3! \times (2! \times 6! + 7!) + 8! &= (-T(3) - T(2) + T(6) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 1450 &:= (-1! - 3! + 6!) \times 2! + 4! &= (T(1) + T(3) \times (T(6) + T(2))) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 1452 &:= (2! + 5! - 6!) \times 3! + 7! &= (T(2) \times T(5) + T(6)) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (5! - 2!) + 6! + 4! &= T(3) \times ((T(5) - T(2)) \times T(6) - T(4)) \\
 &:= 2! \times ((1! - 6!) \times 3! + 7!) &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 1464 &:= (-3! \times 6! + 7!) \times 2! + 4! &= -T(3) + (T(6) + T(7)) \times T(2) \times T(4) \\
 &:= 3! \times (5! - 6!) + 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times (-T(5) - T(6) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 1470 &:= -(5! - 1!) \times (3! + 4!) + 7! &= T(5) \times ((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(7)) \\
 1488 &:= 2! \times (-3! \times 6! + 7! + 4!) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + (T(6) + T(7)) \times T(4)) \\
 \\
 1500 &:= -((3! + 4!) \times (5! - 2!)) + 7! &= (T(3) - T(4)) \times T(5) \times (T(2) - T(7)) \\
 &:= 1! \times 2! \times (6! + 3! + 4!) &= (T(1) + T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) \times T(4) \\
 &:= 2! \times (3! \times (1! + 5!) + 4!) &= (T(2) + T(3) + T(1)) \times T(5) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 1512 &:= 2! \times (6! - 4!) \times 1! + 5! &= T(2) \times T(6) \times (T(4) - T(1) + T(5)) \\
 1530 &:= -3! + 5! - 4! + 2! \times 6! &= T(3) \times (T(5) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6))) \\
 1548 &:= (3! + 6!) \times 2! - 4! + 5! &= T(3) \times (T(6) \times (T(2) + T(4)) - T(5)) \\
 \\
 1560 &:= (-1! + 3! + 2!) \times 5! + 6! &= (T(1) - T(3)) \times (T(2) - T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 &:= (-3! + 1!) \times (6! - 4!) + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(1) - T(6) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 1572 &:= (-2! + 5! + 4!) \times 3! + 6! &= -T(2) + (T(5) + T(4) \times T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 2! \times (6! + 3!) \times 1! + 5! &= -T(2) + T(6) \times (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1578 &:= 2! \times 6! + 4! - 3! + 5! &= T(2) + T(6) \times (T(4) \times T(3) + T(5)) \\
 1584 &:= (5! - 6! + 4!) \times 3! + 7! &= (T(5) + T(6)) \times (T(4) + T(3) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 1! \times 4! \times 3! + 2! \times 6! &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 1585 &:= (4! + 5!) \times 3! + 1! + 6! &= T(4) + T(5) \times (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(6) \\
 1590 &:= 4! + 5! + 3! + 2! \times 6! &= T(4) \times (T(5) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6))) \\
 1620 &:= 2! \times (6! + 4! + 3!) + 5! &= (T(2) - T(6)) \times T(4) \times (T(3) - T(5)) \\
 1680 &:= (2! - 4! - 3!) \times 5! + 7! &= (-T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (2! + 3!) \times (6! + 5!) - 7! &= (-T(2) \times (T(3) - T(6)) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 2! \times (-(1! - 3!) \times 4! + 6!) &= (T(2) - T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 1710 &:= 3! + 4! + 2! \times (5! + 6!) &= T(3) \times (-T(4) \times T(2) + T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 1722 &:= -3! + 2! \times (5! + 4! + 6!) &= (T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(5)) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 1728 &:= 3! \times (4! \times 2! + 5!) + 6! &= (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 2! \times (7! - (6! - 4!) \times 3!) &= T(2) \times (T(7) \times T(6) - T(4)) - T(3) \\
 1740 &:= 2! \times (3! + 6! + 5! + 4!) &= ((T(2) + T(3)) \times T(6) - T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 1764 &:= -(2! + 4!) \times (3! + 5!) + 7! &= ((T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) - T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 1782 &:= (2! + 1!) \times (-5! + 6! - 3!) &= (T(2) - (T(1) - T(5)) \times T(6)) \times T(3) \\
 1800 &:= (-1! - 2! - 3! + 4!) \times 5! &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(4) \times T(5) \\
 &:= 5! \times (1! + 3! + 2!) + 6! &= T(5) \times (-T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 1818 &:= (2! + 1!) \times (6! - 5! + 3!) &= (T(2) - (T(1) - T(6)) \times T(5)) \times T(3) \\
 1890 &:= -(5! + 3!) \times (1! + 4!) + 7! &= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(1)) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\
 1920 &:= 5! \times 2! \times (-1! + 3!) + 6! &= T(5) \times (T(2) - T(1) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 1968 &:= 2! \times (5! + 6! + 4! \times 3!) &= (T(2) + T(5) \times T(6) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 2040 &:= (-3! + 2!) \times 6! - 5! + 7! &= T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(6) \times T(5) + T(7)) \\
 2046 &:= 3! - 5! + (2! + 1!) \times 6! &= (T(3) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 2052 &:= (-2! + 4!) \times (3! + 5!) - 6! &= (-T(2) + T(4) \times T(3)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 2064 &:= 4! \times (-3! + 2! - 5!) + 7! &= (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(2) \times (T(5) + T(7)) \\
 2106 &:= -3! - (2! + 5!) \times 4! + 7! &= T(3) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 2118 &:= -(2! + 5!) \times 4! + 7! + 3! &= T(2) \times ((T(5) + T(4)) \times T(7) + T(3)) \\
 2154 &:= -3! \times 1! + 4! \times 5! - 6! &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6))) \\
 &:= 3! \times (-1! + 5!) + 2! \times 6! &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2156 &:= 2! - 4! \times 5! - 3! + 7! &= (-T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \times T(3)) \times T(7) \\
 2159 &:= -1! + 5! \times 3! + 2! \times 6! &= -T(1) + T(5) \times T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 2160 &:= 1! \times 3! \times 5! \times 2! + 6! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 6! - 5! \times 4! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(6) + T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 &:= (4! + 3!) \times 5! - 2! \times 6! &= T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 5! \times (3! + 4!) \times 2! - 7! &= T(5) \times (T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 &:= 5! \times 4! + 3! \times 6! - 7! &= T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 2161 &:= 1! + 3! \times 5! + 2! \times 6! &= T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 2166 &:= ((3! \times 1!) + (4! \times 5!)) - 6! &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6))) \\
 &:= (3! \times (1! + 5!)) + (2! \times 6!) &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6))) \\
 \\
 2184 &:= ((- (1! - 5!) + 2!) \times 4!) - 6! &= (-T(1) + T(5) \times (-T(2) + T(4))) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (((2! - 1!) - 5!) \times 4!) + 7! &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (4! - ((3! - 2!) \times 6!)) + 7! &= (T(4) \times T(3) - T(2) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 2208 &:= 3! \times 5! + 2! \times (6! + 4!) &= T(3) \times ((T(5) + T(2)) \times T(6) - T(4)) \\
 2268 &:= (2! - 4!) \times (5! + 3!) + 7! &= (T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(3)) \times T(7) \\
 2280 &:= 5! \times (2! - 1! - 4!) + 7! &= T(5) \times (T(2) + T(1)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 2286 &:= 3! + 6! \times (1! + 2!) + 5! &= (T(3) \times T(6) + T(1)) \times (T(2) + T(5)) \\
 2352 &:= 5! + (1! + 2!) \times (4! + 6!) &= (T(5) + T(1)) \times (-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 2394 &:= (4! + 2!) \times 5! - 3! - 6! &= (T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(5)) - T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= -3! + 5! \times (2! - 4!) + 7! &= (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(2) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 2400 &:= (4! + 2!) \times 5! \times 1! - 6! &= T(4) \times (T(2) - T(5)) \times (T(1) - T(6)) \\
 2448 &:= 2! \times (5! + 4!) \times 3! + 6! &= (T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(4) + T(3) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 2520 &:= (1! + 2! + 4!) \times 5! - 6! &= (T(1) - T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (1! + 2! - 4!) \times 5! + 7! &= (-T(1) - T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (2! + 4! - 3! + 1!) \times 5! &= T(2) \times T(4) \times T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(5)) \\
 &:= (-1! - 2! + 3!) \times (5! + 6!) &= (-T(1) + T(2) + T(3)) \times T(5) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 2532 &:= (3! - 5!) \times (4! - 2!) + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(5) \times T(4) \times T(2) - T(7)) \\
 2592 &:= 2! \times (6! - 3! \times (4! - 5!)) &= (T(2) - T(6)) \times (T(3) - T(4) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 2640 &:= -5! \times (2! + 4! - 3!) + 7! &= (T(5) - T(2)) \times T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := 4! \times (-3! - 1!) \times 2! + 5! & = T(4) \times T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2700} & := (1! + 4!) \times (-3! \times 2! + 5!) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times T(3) \times T(2) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{2710} & := -2! + (-3! + 5! - 1!) \times 4! & = (T(2) \times T(3) \times T(5) + T(1)) \times T(4) \\
 \mathbf{2736} & := -(3! + 5!) \times 4! + 6! + 7! & = T(3) + T(5) \times (T(4) \times T(6) - T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2760} & := -5! \times (4! - 3! + 1!) + 7! & = T(5) \times (T(4) + (T(3) \times (T(1) + T(7)))) \\
 & := 4! \times (-3! - 1! + 2! + 5!) & = (T(4) \times T(3)) \times (T(1) + (T(2) \times T(5))) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2844} & := -(2! + 5!) \times (4! - 3!) + 7! & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times (-T(4) + (T(3) \times T(7))) \\
 \mathbf{2850} & := (4! - 1! + 2!) \times (-3! + 5!) & = (T(4) \times (T(1) + (T(2) \times T(3)))) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2880} & := (4! + 3!) \times 1! \times 5! - 6! & = T(4) \times (-T(3) + (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(6)) \\
 & := 1! \times 7! + 6! - 5! \times 4! & = (T(1) - T(7) + T(6) \times T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 & := (2! + 3!) \times 6! - 4! \times 5! & = (-T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 & := -3! \times 5! \times (1! + 2!) + 7! & = T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(1) + T(2) + T(7)) \\
 & := (-4! + 6!) \times 5! - 2! \times 8! & = T(4) \times (T(6) \times (T(5) - T(2)) + T(8)) \\
 & := 2! \times (7! - 3! \times (6! - 5!)) & = (T(2) + T(7) \times T(3) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2928} & := 6! + (2! - 5!) \times 4! + 7! & = (T(6) + T(2)) \times (T(5) \times T(4) - T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{2976} & := (3! - 1!) \times (-5! + 6!) - 4! & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(6) + T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{3000} & := (4! + 3! + 1!) \times 5! - 6! & = T(4) \times (T(3) - (T(1) - T(5)) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{3120} & := (4! + 2! + 3!) \times 5! - 6! & = T(4) \times (T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 & := -5! \times (4! - 2!) + 6! + 7! & = T(5) \times (T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(6)) + T(7)) \\
 & := 5! \times (2! + 3! - 4!) + 7! & = T(5) \times (T(2) \times T(3) \times T(4) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{3150} & := (2! + 4! - 1!) \times (3! + 5!) & = T(2) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{3168} & := 2! \times (3! \times (4! + 5!) + 6!) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{3240} & := 5! \times (4! - 1! - 2!) + 6! & = T(5) \times (T(4) - T(1)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{3360} & := -(1! + 3!) \times 2! \times 5! + 7! & = (-T(1) + T(3) + T(2)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 & := 1! \times 5! \times (4! - 2!) + 6! & = (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{3384} & := 4! + 7! - 2! \times (5! + 6!) & = (T(4) + T(7) \times T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{3432} & := 4! \times (5! - 3! - 1!) + 6! & = (T(4) \times T(5) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{3456} & := (1! \times 5! - 3!) \times 4! + 6! & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{3480} & := -5! + 6! \times 2! \times 3! - 7! & = T(5) - (T(6) \times (T(2) - (T(3) \times T(7)))) \\
 \mathbf{3486} & := 3! - 5! \times (1! - 4!) + 6! & = (T(3) + ((T(5) + T(1)) \times T(4))) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3528 &:= -(2! - 5! + 1!) \times 4! + 6! &= (T(2) + (T(5) \times (T(1) + T(4)))) \times T(6) \\
 &:= -2! \times (6! - 4!) - 5! + 7! &= (-T(2) + T(6)) + (T(4) \times T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= -2! \times (4! + 6!) + 3! + 7! &= (T(2) \times T(4)) + ((T(6) \times T(3)) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 3570 &:= -3! - 4! - 2! \times 6! + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(4) - T(2) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 3576 &:= -3! \times 5! - 4! - 6! + 7! &= T(3) + T(5) \times (T(4) \times T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 4! \times (5! + 1! - 2!) + 6! &= (T(4) \times T(5) - T(1)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 3592 &:= -(1! + 6!) \times 2! - 3! + 7! &= T(1) + T(6) \times (T(2) + T(3) \times T(7)) \\
 3599 &:= 1! + 4! \times 5! - 2! + 6! &= -T(1) + T(4) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 3600 &:= ((-1! + 2!) \times 3! + 4!) \times 5! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(4) \times T(5) \\
 &:= -(3! - 4!) \times 5! + 2! \times 6! &= T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 4! \times 5! \times (1! + 2!) - 7! &= T(4) \times T(5) \times (-T(1) - T(2) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 4! \times 5! \times (2! - 1!) + 6! &= T(4) \times T(5) \times (T(2) \times T(1) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 3601 &:= -1! + 4! \times 5! + 2! + 6! &= T(1) + T(4) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 3606 &:= 3! \times (-5! + 1!) - 6! + 7! &= T(3) \times (-T(5) + (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(7)) \\
 3611 &:= -1! + 2! \times (3! - 6!) + 7! &= -T(1) + (T(2) + T(3) \times T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 3612 &:= (1! \times 3! - 6!) \times 2! + 7! &= (T(1) \times T(3) \times T(6) + T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (2! - 5!) \times 3! - 6! + 7! &= ((T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= -(3! + 6!) \times 2! + 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(6) \times T(2) \times T(4) - T(7)) \\
 \\
 3613 &:= 1! - (6! - 3!) \times 2! + 7! &= T(1) + (T(6) \times T(3) + T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 3624 &:= 4! \times (5! - 1! + 2!) + 6! &= (T(4) \times T(5) + T(1)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 3654 &:= (2! + 5!) \times 4! + 3! + 6! &= ((T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4) - T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 3696 &:= -2! \times 6! - 4! + 5! + 7! &= (T(2) - T(6) + T(4) \times T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 3720 &:= (3! + 1! - 2!) \times (6! + 4!) &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 3744 &:= 3! \times (4! - 5!) + 7! - 6! &= T(3) + (T(4) \times T(5) + T(7)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 3! \times (4! - 5! \times 2!) + 7! &= -T(3) + (T(4) \times T(5) \times (-T(2) + T(7))) \\
 \\
 3770 &:= (4! + 1!) \times (2! + 5!) + 6! &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 3840 &:= 1! \times 5! \times (4! + 2!) + 6! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (3! - 1!) \times (6! + 2! \times 4!) &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(6) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 3846 &:= -2! \times (6! - 5!) + 3! + 7! &= T(2) + T(6) \times (T(5) + T(3) \times T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3864 &:= 2! \times (5! - 6!) + 4! + 7! &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6) + T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 3888 &:= 2! \times (5! - 6! + 4!) + 7! &= T(2) - T(5) \times (T(6) - T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (6! + 4! \times 2! - 5!) &= (T(3) + T(6) \times T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(5)) \\
 4032 &:= -(1! + 3!) \times (4! + 5!) + 7! &= (-T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 2! \times ((5! - 3!) \times 4! - 6!) &= (-T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 4050 &:= (-1! - 4! + 6!) \times 3! - 5! &= T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(6) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 4104 &:= -2! \times 5! - 6! + 4! + 7! &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 &:= -(3! + 2!) \times 5! + 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 4158 &:= 3! \times (-1! - 4! - 2! + 6!) &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(6) \\
 4164 &:= 7! - (5! + 2! + 4!) \times 3! &= (T(7) \times T(5) - T(2)) \times T(4) - T(3) \\
 4175 &:= -1! + 7! - 3! \times (4! + 5!) &= (-T(1) + T(7) \times T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 4176 &:= -3! \times (5! + 4!) \times 1! + 7! &= (-T(3) + T(5) \times T(4)) \times (T(1) + T(7)) \\
 4200 &:= (1! - 2! - 3!) \times 5! + 7! &= (T(1) + T(2) + T(3)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (4! + 3! - 1!) \times 5! + 6! &= T(4) \times (T(3) - T(1) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 4! \times (1! - 3!) - 6! + 7! &= T(4) \times T(1) \times (-T(3) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= -(5! + 7!) \times (1! + 3!) + 8! &= T(5) \times (T(7) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(8)) \\
 4218 &:= -3! - 5! - 6! + 4! + 7! &= (T(3) \times T(5) + T(6)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 4284 &:= -2! \times 3! - 4! - 6! + 7! &= T(2) \times T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= -3! \times (2! + 5!) - 4! + 7! &= (T(3) - T(2) + T(5) \times T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 4290 &:= -(1! + 5!) \times 3! - 4! + 7! &= T(1) \times T(5) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 4320 &:= 1! \times 5! \times (4! + 3!) + 6! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 2! \times (7! + 8!) - 5! \times 6! &= (T(2) \times T(7) + T(8)) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= 2! \times 1! \times (7! - 5! \times 4!) &= (-T(2) + (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 &:= 5! \times (-3! + 4! \times 2!) - 6! &= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times (-T(2) + T(6)) \\
 4344 &:= -3! \times 5! + 4! \times 1! + 7! &= -T(3) + T(5) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(7)) \\
 4350 &:= 3! - 6! + 4! \times 1! + 7! &= (-T(3) + T(6)) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(7)) \\
 4368 &:= (1! + 3!) \times (4! - 5!) + 7! &= (T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 2! \times (4! \times (1! + 5!) - 6!) &= (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4410 &:= -3! + 5! - 4! - 6! + 7! &= (-T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \\
 4428 &:= -3! \times 2! + 5! - 6! + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5) \times (T(6) + T(7))) \\
 \\
 4452 &:= -(2! - 4!) \times 3! - 6! + 7! &= (T(2) \times T(4) \times T(3) - T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 3! \times 2! - 6! + 5! + 7! &= (T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6)) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 3! \times (4! - 5! - 2!) + 7! &= (T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 4464 &:= (4! + 5!) \times (-3! + 2!) + 7! &= (T(4) \times T(5) - T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 4470 &:= 3! + 4! + 5! - 6! + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5) \times (T(6) + T(7))) \\
 4512 &:= 2! \times (5! - 4!) + 7! - 6! &= -T(2) + T(5) \times (T(4) \times T(7) + T(6)) \\
 4536 &:= 2! \times 5! - 6! - 4! + 7! &= (T(2) - T(5)) \times T(6) \times (T(4) - T(7)) \\
 4656 &:= -3! \times 4! - 5! \times 2! + 7! &= T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 4740 &:= -(5! + 3! + 4!) \times 2! + 7! &= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(7))) \\
 4770 &:= -3! - 2! \times 5! - 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 4836 &:= -(3! - 4! + 5!) \times 2! + 7! &= (T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 4860 &:= 2! \times (3! - 5! + 4!) + 7! &= T(2) \times T(3) \times T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 4872 &:= -3! \times 4! \times 2! + 5! + 7! &= (-T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(5))) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (-3! + 1! - 2!) \times 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 4932 &:= -5! - 2! \times 3! + 4! + 7! &= (T(5) + T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 4950 &:= 4! - 5! \times 1! + 3! + 7! &= T(4) \times T(5) \times (-T(1) + T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 4980 &:= (4! + 3!) \times 2! - 5! + 7! &= T(4) \times (-T(3) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(7)) \\
 &:= 1! \times 7! - 2! \times (3! + 4!) &= (-T(1) + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 5010 &:= -4! \times (2! - 1!) - 3! + 7! &= T(4) \times T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(3) \times T(7)) \\
 5012 &:= 1! \times 2! - 3! - 4! + 7! &= (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 5022 &:= 3! \times (2! - 1!) - 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 5030 &:= -4! + (1! + 3!) \times 2! + 7! &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(3) \times T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 5034 &:= 3! \times (1! + 2!) - 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 5040 &:= -(2! \times 4! + 1!) \times 6! + 8! &= (T(2) - T(4)) \times (T(1) - T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (1! + 6! - 3! \times 5!) \times 7! &= (T(1) - T(6)) \times (T(3) - T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 2! \times (3! + 1!) \times 6! - 7! &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 2! \times (4! - 3!) \times 5! + 6! &= T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(3) \times T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 2! \times (5! + 6!) \times 3! - 7! &= (T(2) - T(5)) \times (-T(6) + T(3)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 2! \times (7! - 4! \times 5!) + 6! &= T(2) \times T(7) \times T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -3! \times (7! + 5! + 6!) + 8! &= T(3) \times T(7) \times (T(5) - T(6) + T(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5046 &:= -3! \times (1! + 2!) + 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 5050 &:= 4! - (1! + 3!) \times 2! + 7! &= T(4) \times (T(1) + T(3) \times T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 5058 &:= -3! \times (2! - 1!) + 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times T(2) \times (T(1) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 5068 &:= 1! \times 3! + 4! - 2! + 7! &= (T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) \times T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 5070 &:= 4! \times (2! - 1!) + 3! + 7! &= T(4) \times T(2) \times (T(1) + T(3) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 5100 &:= (3! + 4! \times 1!) \times 2! + 7! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 &:= -(4! + 3!) \times 2! + 5! + 7! &= T(4) \times (T(3) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 5148 &:= 5! + 2! \times 3! - 4! + 7! &= (T(5) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 5160 &:= -6! + (1! + 3!) \times 5! + 7! &= (T(6) - T(1)) \times T(3) \times (T(5) + T(7)) \\
 5202 &:= 2! \times 4! + 5! - 3! + 7! &= (T(2) + T(4) \times T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 5208 &:= 3! \times 4! \times 2! - 5! + 7! &= (T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(5))) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (3! - 1! + 2!) \times 4! + 7! &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 5220 &:= (5! - 3! - 4!) \times 2! + 7! &= T(5) \times T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) + T(7)) \\
 5250 &:= -4! - 3! + 5! \times 2! + 7! &= T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5)) \times (-T(2) + T(7)) \\
 5292 &:= 3! \times (4! - 2!) + 5! + 7! &= (-T(3) + (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 5310 &:= 2! \times 5! + 4! + 7! + 3! &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4) \times T(7)) \times T(3) \\
 5400 &:= (2! + 3! + 1!) \times (6! - 5!) &= T(2) \times T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 5472 &:= 6! - 2! \times 3! \times 4! + 7! &= (T(6) + T(2)) \times T(3) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 5544 &:= -2! \times 5! + 4! + 6! + 7! &= (T(2) + T(5)) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 5568 &:= -2! \times (5! - 4!) + 7! + 6! &= T(2) - (T(5) - T(4) \times T(7)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 5610 &:= (-1! - 4! + 5!) \times 3! + 7! &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 &:= -4! + 6! - 5! - 3! + 7! &= (-T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 5615 &:= -5! - 1! + 6! - 4! + 7! &= T(5) - (T(1) - T(6)) \times T(4) \times T(7) \\
 5616 &:= -(3! + 6! \times 2!) \times 4! + 8! &= (T(3) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 5628 &:= (2! - 4!) \times 3! + 6! + 7! &= (T(2) \times T(4) \times T(3) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (2! - 4! + 5!) \times 3! + 7! &= ((T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(3)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 5640 &:= -4! \times 2! \times 6! - 5! + 8! &= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(5) \times T(8)) \\
 5670 &:= 4! + 3! - 5! + 6! + 7! &= T(4) \times (-T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 5700 &:= -(4! + 3!) \times 2! + 6! + 7! &= T(4) \times (-T(3) \times T(2) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 5712 &:= -2! \times (4! + 8!) + 6! \times 5! &= -T(2) + (T(4) \times T(8) + T(6)) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := -3! \times 6! + 2! \times (-4! + 7!) & = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(2) + T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{5730} & := -4! - 3! + 6! \times 1! + 7! & = T(4) \times (T(3) - T(6) \times (T(1) - T(7))) \\
 \mathbf{5733} & := -1! + 7! - 4! - 2! + 6! & = ((-T(1) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{5736} & := -3! \times 4! + 5! + 6! + 7! & = T(3) - T(4) \times (T(5) - T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{5754} & := -3! \times (6! + 7! + 1!) + 8! & = T(3) \times (-T(6) + T(7) \times (-T(1) + T(8))) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{5760} & := -5! \times 3! \times 4! \times 2! + 8! & = T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(8))) \\
 & := 2! \times 6! \times 3! - 4! \times 5! & = (T(2) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\
 & := -3! \times 1! \times (6! + 7!) + 8! & = (T(3) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 & := 2! \times (6! + 7! - 5! \times 4!) & = (T(2) + T(6) \times T(7) - T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 & := 3! \times (5! \times 1! \times 2! + 6!) & = T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{5784} & := 4! - (6! + 7!) \times 3! + 8! & = T(4) \times (T(6) \times T(7) - T(3)) - T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{5796} & := 2! \times 3! + 4! + 6! + 7! & = (T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 & := (2! + 5!) \times 3! + 4! + 7! & = (-T(2) + (T(5) + T(3)) \times T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{5802} & := -3! + 2! \times 4! + 6! + 7! & = T(3) - (T(2) - T(4) \times T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{5832} & := 5! + 6! - 2! \times 4! + 7! & = T(5) - T(6) \times (T(2) - T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{5855} & := -1! + 6! + 7! - 4! + 5! & = (-T(1) + T(6) \times T(7)) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{5880} & := 5! + 8! - 3! \times (6! + 7!) & = (T(5) + T(8) \times T(3) - T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{5904} & := (4! - 6! - 7!) \times 3! + 8! & = T(4) \times (T(6) \times T(7) + T(3)) - T(8) \\
 & := 2! \times 7! - (6! - 4!) \times 3! & = (T(2) + T(7) \times T(6)) \times T(4) - T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{5905} & := 1! + 6! + 7! + 4! + 5! & = (T(1) + T(6) \times T(7)) \times T(4) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{5916} & := 3! \times (4! + 2!) + 6! + 7! & = T(3) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{5928} & := 2! \times 4! + 7! + 6! + 5! & = (T(2) + T(4) \times T(7)) \times T(6) - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{6024} & := 3! \times 4! + 5! + 6! + 7! & = -T(3) + T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{6048} & := 2! \times (4! + 5!) + 6! + 7! & = ((T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 & := 2! \times (-6! + 3!) \times 4! + 8! & = T(2) \times T(6) \times (T(3) \times T(4) + T(8)) \\
 & := 3! \times ((4! + 5!) \times 2! + 6!) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{6192} & := 2! \times (6! - 5! - 4!) + 7! & = -T(2) + T(6) \times (T(5) + T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{6216} & := 2! \times (-5! + 6!) - 4! + 7! & = (-T(2) + T(5) + T(6) \times T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{6384} & := 2! \times 6! + 4! - 5! + 7! & = (T(2) + T(6) \times T(4) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{6450} & := -4! - 3! + 6! \times 2! + 7! & = T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(6) \times (T(2) + T(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6480 &:= (1! - 4! \times 2!) \times 6! + 8! &= T(1) \times T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 2! \times (3! + 4!) \times 5! - 6! &= T(2) \times T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -2! \times 6! + 5! \times 4! + 7! &= (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (3! + 6!) \times 5! - 2! \times 8! &= (T(3) - T(6)) \times (-T(5) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 6510 &:= 4! + 6! \times 2! + 3! + 7! &= T(4) \times T(6) \times (-T(2) + T(3) + T(7)) \\
 6516 &:= -(3! - 4! - 6!) \times 2! + 7! &= T(3) + T(4) \times T(6) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 6720 &:= (1! \times 6! + 5!) \times 2! + 7! &= (T(1) - T(6)) \times (-T(5) + T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 7056 &:= -(3! - 5!) \times 4! - 6! + 7! &= (-T(3) + T(5) \times T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 4! \times (-3! + 6!) - 2! \times 7! &= (T(4) - T(3)) \times T(6) \times T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 7200 &:= 4! \times 5! - 6! \times 1! + 7! &= T(4) \times T(5) \times (T(6) - T(1) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 4! \times 6! + 3! \times 7! - 8! &= T(4) \times ((T(6) + T(3)) \times T(7) - T(8)) \\
 &:= 3! \times (4! \times 5! + 7!) - 8! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times T(5) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 7344 &:= (3! + 5!) \times 4! - 6! + 7! &= -T(3) + T(5) \times T(4) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \\
 7440 &:= 5! \times (4! - 3! + 2!) + 7! &= T(5) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 7560 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (6! + 5!) + 7! &= (-T(1) \times T(2) + T(6)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (1! + 2! + 3!) \times (5! + 6!) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(5) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 7920 &:= (4! \times 5! - 6!) \times 3! - 7! &= T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 2! \times (6! + 5! \times 3!) + 7! &= (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 8400 &:= (-1! \times 5! - 6! + 7!) \times 2! &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(6) \times (T(7) - T(2)) \\
 &:= (4! - 2!) \times 5! + 7! + 6! &= T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(5) - T(7)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= 5! \times (3! + 4! - 2!) + 7! &= (T(5) \times T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 8520 &:= 6! \times (-1! + 3!) - 5! + 7! &= (T(6) - T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(5) \times T(7)) \\
 8616 &:= 3! \times (6! - 5!) + 7! - 4! &= T(3) + T(6) \times (T(5) \times T(7) - T(4)) \\
 \\
 8640 &:= -(2! \times 5! + 7!) \times 3! + 8! &= (-T(2) + T(5) + T(7)) \times T(3) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (4! + 6!) \times 5! - 2! \times 8! &= T(4) \times (-T(6) + T(5) \times T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 8664 &:= -3! \times (5! - 6!) + 7! + 4! &= -T(3) + T(5) \times (T(6) \times T(7) - T(4)) \\
 8760 &:= 5! \times 1! - 2! \times (6! - 7!) &= T(5) \times (-T(1) - T(2) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 8880 &:= 1! \times 2! \times (-6! + 7! + 5!) &= (T(1) + T(2) + T(6) \times T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 8882 &:= (1! - 6! + 5! + 7!) \times 2! &= -T(1) + T(6) \times (T(5) \times T(7) + T(2)) \\
 9072 &:= (2! \times (6! - 4!) + 5!) \times 3! &= T(2) \times T(6) \times (T(4) \times T(5) - T(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9216 &:= -3! \times (4! + 5! + 7!) + 8! &= (-T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)) \times (T(7) + T(8)) \\
 9234 &:= 3! \times (6! - 1!) - 5! + 7! &= -T(3) + (T(6) + T(1)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 9240 &:= 3! \times 6! \times 1! - 5! + 7! &= (-T(3) + T(6) \times (T(1) + T(5))) \times T(7) \\
 9246 &:= 3! \times (1! + 6!) - 5! + 7! &= T(3) + (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 9324 &:= -(2! - 6!) \times 3! - 4! + 7! &= (-T(2) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(4))) \times T(7) \\
 9360 &:= (4! - 3! + 2!) \times 6! - 7! &= (T(4) + T(3)) \times (-T(2) + T(6) \times T(7)) \\
 9492 &:= 3! \times (4! + 6! - 2!) + 7! &= ((T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 9504 &:= (4! - 7! - 5!) \times 3! + 8! &= ((-T(4) + T(7)) \times T(5) - T(3)) \times T(8) \\
 9576 &:= 2! \times (5! + 7!) - 4! - 6! &= (-T(2) + T(5)) \times (T(7) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 9900 &:= 2! \times (4! - 5! + 3! + 7!) &= T(2) \times T(4) \times T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 9936 &:= -(1! \times 7! + 4!) \times 3! + 8! &= (-T(1) - T(7)) \times T(4) + T(3)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 8! - 5! - 4! - 7! \times 3! &= T(8) \times (-T(5) \times (T(4) - T(7)) + T(3)) \\
 \\
 9984 &:= 4! - 5! - 3! \times 7! + 8! &= (T(4) \times T(5) + T(3)) \times (T(7) + T(8)) \\
 10044 &:= -3! \times (2! + 7!) + 8! - 4! &= -T(3) + (-T(2) + T(7) \times T(8)) \times T(4) \\
 10050 &:= -3! \times (1! + 7!) - 4! + 8! &= T(3) - (T(1) - T(7) \times T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 10080 &:= (1! - 2!) \times 3! \times 7! + 8! &= (T(1) + T(2) + T(3)) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (2! \times 4! - 3!) \times 5! + 7! &= (T(2) \times T(4) - T(3)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (2! + 3! - 1!) \times 6! + 7! &= T(2) \times T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (2! + 6! - 3! \times 5!) \times 7! &= (-T(2) + T(6) + T(3)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (-3! + 4!) \times (5! + 6!) - 7! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 6! \times (-2! \times 4! + 3!) + 8! &= (T(6) + T(2)) \times T(4) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 10110 &:= 3! \times (1! - 7!) + 4! + 8! &= -T(3) + (T(1) + T(7) \times T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 10116 &:= 3! \times (2! - 7!) + 8! + 4! &= T(3) + (T(2) + T(7) \times T(8)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 10224 &:= (-1! \times 7! + 4!) \times 3! + 8! &= ((T(1) + T(7)) \times T(4) - T(3)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= -3! \times 7! + 8! + 5! + 4! &= -T(3) + (T(7) \times T(8) + T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 10260 &:= 2! \times (-3! + 5! - 4! + 7!) &= T(2) \times T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 10674 &:= -3! - 5! + 6! + 2! \times 7! &= T(3) \times (T(5) + T(6) \times T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 10692 &:= -5! + 2! \times (3! + 7!) + 6! &= (T(5) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(7) \times T(6)) \\
 10764 &:= 2! \times (3! - 4! + 7!) + 6! &= T(2) \times T(3) \times (T(4) + T(7) \times T(6)) \\
 10800 &:= 1! \times 6! - 7! \times 3! + 8! &= (T(1) + T(6) + T(7)) \times T(3) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 10920 &:= (4! - 2!) \times 6! + 5! - 7! &= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (1! + 3!) \times (6! + 5!) + 7! &= (-T(1) + T(3) + T(6)) \times T(5) \times T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 11400 &:= -5! + 6! \times (-1! + 4!) - 7! &= T(5) \times (T(6) - T(1)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 11976 &:= (-3! + 6!) \times 4! - 7! - 5! &= T(3) + T(6) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 12240 &:= 4! \times 5! + 6! \times 3! + 7! &= T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 &:= 6! + 2! \times (5! \times 3! + 7!) &= (T(6) + T(2)) \times T(5) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 12600 &:= (1! + 2! - 4!) \times (5! - 6!) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) \times T(5) \times T(6) \\
 12960 &:= -3! \times 7! + 4! \times 5! + 8! &= (T(3) + T(7) - T(4)) \times T(5) \times T(8) \\
 13104 &:= (3! + 5!) \times 4! + 2! \times 7! &= (T(3) + T(5) \times T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(7) \\
 13440 &:= (4! - 2!) \times (6! + 5!) - 7! &= T(4) \times (T(2) \times T(6) - T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 13680 &:= 5! \times 4! + 7! \times 2! + 6! &= T(5) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 15120 &:= (-2! + 4!) \times 3! \times 5! - 6! &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(5) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (2! - 1! - 3!) \times 7! + 8! &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 &:= -(4! + 3!) \times (5! + 6!) + 8! &= T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 3! \times (5! + 6! - 7!) + 8! &= T(3) \times T(5) \times T(6) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 15840 &:= 6! + (1! - 3!) \times 7! + 8! &= (T(6) - T(1)) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 16560 &:= -(2! + 4!) \times 6! - 7! + 8! &= T(2) \times T(4) \times (T(6) \times T(7) - T(8)) \\
 \\
 17280 &:= (2! - 3!) \times 5! \times 6! + 9! &= T(2) \times T(3) \times (T(5) + T(6) \times T(9)) \\
 &:= -(4! + 1!) \times 6! - 7! + 8! &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(6) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= -4! \times (5! \times 2! + 6!) + 8! &= T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 9! - 3! \times (4! \times 6! + 8!) &= (T(9) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 17640 &:= (1! + 2!) \times (6! + 5! + 7!) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 18000 &:= 3! \times 5! \times 4! \times 1! + 6! &= T(3) \times T(5) \times T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -4! \times 5! \times 3! - 7! + 8! &= (-T(4) + T(5) \times (T(3) + T(7))) \times T(8) \\
 &:= -1! \times 7! - 6! \times 4! + 8! &= (T(1) + T(7) + T(6)) \times T(4) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 18144 &:= -(6! - 3!) \times 4! - 7! + 8! &= T(6) \times (T(3) - T(4) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 18720 &:= (3! \times 4! + 2! - 5!) \times 6! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 20304 &:= (2! \times 7! + 4!) \times 3! - 8! &= (T(2) \times T(7) + T(4)) \times T(3) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 21600 &:= -1! \times 6! \times (2! + 4!) + 8! &= (-T(1) + T(6)) \times T(2) \times T(4) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (4! - 3!) \times 2! \times (6! - 5!) &= T(4) \times T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 22320 &:= -(4! - 1! + 2!) \times 6! + 8! &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 23040 &:= (1! - 2!) \times 6! \times 4! + 8! &= (T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) \times T(4) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23328 &:= (2! \times 3! - 6!) \times 4! + 8! &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6) \times T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 23760 &:= (2! - 4! - 1!) \times 6! + 8! &= T(2) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 25200 &:= (1! + 3!) \times 4! \times 5! + 7! &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 &:= -4! \times (6! + 5!) + 7! + 8! &= T(4) \times T(6) \times T(5) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 26628 &:= 3! \times (-2! - 6! + 5! + 7!) &= (T(3) + T(2) \times T(6) \times T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 27360 &:= -6! \times (1! + 4!) + 7! + 8! &= (T(6) - T(1)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 3! \times (4! \times 5! - 7!) + 8! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(5) \times T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 28080 &:= -3! \times 4! \times 5! + 7! + 8! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 28224 &:= 4! \times (3! - 6!) + 7! + 8! &= (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 30180 &:= -(4! + 3! + 7!) \times 2! + 8! &= T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(7) \times T(2) \times T(8)) \\
 30222 &:= 3! + 8! - 4! - 7! \times 2! &= (-T(3) + T(8) \times T(4) \times T(7)) \times T(2) \\
 \\
 30240 &:= -3! \times (6! + 5!) - 7! + 8! &= (-T(3) + T(6) + T(5)) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 2! \times ((5! + 6!) \times 4! - 7!) &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6)) \times T(4) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 30258 &:= -2! \times 7! + 4! + 8! - 3! &= T(2) \times (T(7) \times T(4) \times T(8) + T(3)) \\
 30300 &:= (4! + 3! - 7!) \times 2! + 8! &= T(4) \times (T(3) + T(7) \times T(2) \times T(8)) \\
 30912 &:= 6! - 2! \times (7! + 4!) + 8! &= (T(6) + T(2)) \times T(7) \times (T(4) + T(8)) \\
 33120 &:= 3! \times (4! \times 6! - 7!) - 8! &= T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(6) \times T(7) - T(8)) \\
 33600 &:= -(5! + 6!) \times 2! + 8! - 7! &= T(5) \times (T(6) \times T(2) \times T(8) - T(7)) \\
 34560 &:= -5! \times 6! + (2! + 1!) \times 8! &= T(5) \times (T(6) \times T(2) + T(1)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 35280 &:= -5! \times (6! - 3!) + 4! \times 7! &= T(5) \times T(6) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 9! - (2! + 3!) \times 8! - 7! &= (T(9) - T(2)) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 36288 &:= 3! \times (4! \times 2! - 6!) + 8! &= (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) \times T(6) \times T(8) \\
 37440 &:= (3! - 4!) \times (6! - 7!) - 8! &= (T(3) \times T(4)) \times (T(6) \times T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 38880 &:= 2! \times 6! - 5! \times 4! + 8! &= T(2) \times (T(6) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 5! \times (2! \times 3! - 4!) + 8! &= (T(5) + T(2)) \times T(3) \times T(4) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 40320 &:= 4! \times 7! \times 1! - 2! \times 8! &= T(4) \times T(7) \times (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 2! \times (9! - 8!) - 7! \times 5! &= (-T(2) + T(9)) \times (T(8) + T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 45360 &:= (1! - 2! + 5!) \times 6! - 8! &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) \times T(6) \times T(8) \\
 47520 &:= 5! \times (4! - 3!) + 7! + 8! &= T(5) \times (T(4) \times T(3) + T(7)) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 50400 &:= (-1! \times 3! + 4!) \times 7! - 8! &&= (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 51840 &:= -(3! - 4! + 2!) \times 6! + 8! &&= T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 55440 &:= (5! - 1!) \times 6! - 3! \times 7! &&= T(5) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(3) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 60480 &:= -2! \times (3! + 4!) \times 7! + 9! &&= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(7) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (3! \times (5! + 2!) - 6!) \times 7! &&= T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 4! \times (-5! - 6! + 7!) - 8! &&= T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 &:= 4! \times (-5! + 3! \times 6!) - 8! &&= (-T(4) + T(5) \times T(3)) \times T(6) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 62640 &:= 3! \times (6! \times 4! - 5!) - 8! &&= (T(3) \times T(6) - T(4)) \times T(5) \times T(8) \\
 65520 &:= 3! \times (-5! + 7! - 6!) + 8! &&= T(3) \times T(5) \times (-T(7) + T(6) \times T(8)) \\
 67680 &:= (4! + 3! + 5!) \times 6! - 8! &&= (-T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) \times T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 70560 &:= 3! \times (5! + 7!) - 6! + 8! &&= T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(7) + T(6) \times T(8)) \\
 75600 &:= (-4! \times 2! + 6!) \times 5! - 7! &&= T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(6)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 77760 &:= 2! \times (-6! - 3! \times 5! + 8!) &&= (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) \times T(5) \times T(8) \\
 80640 &:= (4! \times 3! - 5!) \times 7! - 8! &&= (-T(4) + T(3) \times T(5)) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 82800 &:= 4! \times (5! + 7!) - 6! - 8! &&= T(4) \times T(5) \times (T(7) \times T(6) - T(8)) \\
 89880 &:= -5! - 6! + (-3! + 4!) \times 7! &&= (T(5) \times T(6) + T(3)) \times T(4) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 90720 &:= 9! \times 2! - (5! + 3!) \times 7! &&= T(9) \times (-T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3) \times T(7) \\
 &:= 3! \times (4! \times (6! + 5!) - 7!) &&= (T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \times T(5) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 108864 &:= (4! - 5!) \times (3! - 6!) + 8! &&= (T(4) \times T(5) - T(3)) \times T(6) \times T(8) \\
 116640 &:= 3! \times (5! - 8!) - 7! + 9! &&= T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(8) + T(7) \times T(9)) \\
 120960 &:= (-3! + 6!) \times 5! - 7! + 8! &&= T(3) \times T(6) \times T(5) \times (T(7) + T(8)) \\
 129600 &:= (2! \times 6! - 4!) \times 5! - 8! &&= (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(4) \times T(5) \times T(8) \\
 181440 &:= (3! - 2! + 4!) \times 7! + 8! &&= T(3) \times T(2) \times T(4) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 207360 &:= -3! \times 8! + 5! \times 6! + 9! &&= T(3) \times T(8) \times (T(5) + T(6) \times T(9)) \\
 233280 &:= 2! \times (- (6! + 8!) \times 3! + 9!) &&= (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(8) \times T(3) \times T(9) \\
 241920 &:= 7! \times (5! - 4!) - 3! \times 8! &&= T(7) \times T(5) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(8) \\
 264960 &:= -4! \times (6! + 7!) + 9! + 8! &&= T(4) \times (T(6) \times T(7) \times T(9) + T(8)) \\
 272160 &:= (3! - 6!) \times 5! - 7! + 9! &&= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(5)) \times T(7) \times T(9) \\
 339840 &:= 1! \times 9! + 6! \times 4! - 8! &&= (-T(1) + T(9) \times T(6)) \times T(4) \times T(8) \\
 339984 &:= (3! + 6!) \times 4! + 9! - 8! &&= (-T(3) + T(6) \times T(4) \times T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 340560 &:= (4! + 1!) \times 6! + 9! - 8! &&= T(4) \times (T(1) + T(6) \times T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 341280 &:= (4! + 2!) \times 6! + 9! - 8! &&= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6) \times T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 349920 &:= (3! - 4!) \times (6! - 8!) - 9! &&= (T(3) + T(4) \times T(6)) \times T(8) \times T(9) \\
 443520 &:= 4! \times 7! - 8! \times 1! + 9! &&= T(4) \times T(7) \times T(8) \times (-T(1) + T(9)) \\
 453600 &:= (2! + 5! - 4!) \times 7! - 8! &&= T(2) \times T(5) \times T(4) \times T(7) \times T(8) \\
 725760 &:= 7! \times 4! + 3! \times 8! + 9! &&= T(7) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(8) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$816480 := 3! \times (2! \times 8! - 7!) + 9! = T(3) \times T(2) \times T(8) \times T(7) \times T(9)$$

$$1360800 := (4! - 2!) \times (7! + 8!) + 9! = T(4) \times T(2) \times T(7) \times T(8) \times T(9)$$

$$4082400 := (3! + 5!) \times (8! - 7!) - 9! = T(3) \times T(5) \times T(8) \times T(7) \times T(9)$$

7 Fibonacci-Triangular-Type Equality Expressions

In this case we have very few examples, as we considered factorial and Fibonacci values equality expressions following the same order of digits on both sides of the equalities. This we have divided in two subsections. One only with positive sign expressions and another with positive and negative signs expressions.

7.1 Positive Sign Expressions

7.1.1 Two Terms Expressions

$$42 := F(3) \times F(8) = T(3) + T(8)$$

7.1.2 Three Terms Expressions

$$32 := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(6) = T(1) + T(4) + T(6)$$

$$39 := F(1) \times F(4) \times F(7) = T(1) + T(4) + T(7)$$

$$42 := (F(1) \times F(3)) \times F(8) = T(1) \times T(3) + T(8)$$

$$:= F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) = T(3) + T(5) + T(6)$$

$$43 := F(1) + F(3) \times F(8) = T(1) + T(3) + T(8)$$

$$66 := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(8)) = T(4) \times T(2) + T(8)$$

$$105 := F(2) + F(7) \times F(6) = T(2) \times T(7) + T(6)$$

7.1.3 Four Terms Expressions

$$31 := F(1) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) = T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(5)$$

$$32 := (F(1) + F(4) \times F(5)) \times F(3) = T(1) + T(4) + T(5) + T(3)$$

$$40 := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(5) \times F(6) = T(1) + T(2) + T(5) + T(6)$$

$$:= (F(2) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) = T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(6)$$

$$41 := F(1) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(7) = T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(7)$$

$$42 := F(1) \times F(5) \times F(6) + F(3) = T(1) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(3)$$

$$:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(7)) = T(1) + T(4) + T(2) + T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43 &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) &&= T(1) + T(3) + T(5) + T(6) \\ 44 &:= (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(4) + F(3) &&= T(1) \times T(7) + T(4) + T(3) \\ \\ 45 &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(7)) &&= T(1) + T(4) + T(3) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &&= T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) + T(8) \\ \\ 46 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) &&= T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(8) \\ 49 &:= F(2) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6) &&= T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(6) \\ 52 &:= (F(1) + F(2) + F(3)) \times F(7) &&= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\ 54 &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(5) + F(7)) &&= T(1) + T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\ 60 &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(7) + F(6) &&= T(1) + T(4) + T(7) + T(6) \\ 65 &:= F(3) + F(4) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &&= T(3) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\ \\ 66 &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &&= T(1) \times T(4) \times T(2) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(5) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) &&= T(5) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) \\ \\ 67 &:= F(1) + F(4) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &&= T(1) + T(4) \times T(2) + T(8) \\ 68 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) &&= T(1) + T(2) + T(7) + T(8) \\ \\ 69 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) \times F(9) &&= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(1) + F(2) + F(8)) &&= (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\ \\ 70 &:= F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7) + F(8)) &&= (T(3) \times T(1)) + T(7) + T(8) \\ 72 &:= (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &&= T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(8) \\ \\ 73 &:= F(3) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(8) &&= T(3) + T(6) + T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(4) + (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(5) &&= T(4) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(5) \\ &:= F(4) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(9)) &&= T(4) + T(3) \times T(2) + T(9) \\ \\ 76 &:= F(4) + F(5) + F(3) \times F(9) &&= T(4) + T(5) + T(3) + T(9) \\ 77 &:= F(2) + F(7) + F(4) \times F(8) &&= T(2) + T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\ 78 &:= F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(9)) &&= T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(9) \\ 81 &:= F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(8)) &&= T(4) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(8) \\ \\ 82 &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(9) &&= T(1) + T(5) + T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6) + F(9) &&= T(3) + T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(9) + F(2) + F(7) &&= T(3) + T(9) + T(2) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) + F(7) + F(3) \times F(9) &&= T(2) + T(7) + T(3) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84 &:= F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(6) + F(9)) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(9) \\ 86 &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) + F(9) &= T(2) + T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\ 87 &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(6) + F(8)) &= T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\ 89 &:= F(4) + F(5) \times F(7) + F(8) &= T(4) + T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\ 90 &:= F(2) + F(3) \times F(9) + F(8) &= T(2) + T(3) + T(9) + T(8) \\ 91 &:= (F(2) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) + T(7) \\ 91 &:= (F(2) + F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(7) &= T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(7) \\ 96 &:= F(3) \times F(6) \times (F(2) + F(5)) &= (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(5) \\ \\ 105 &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(9) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(6) \times F(2) \times F(7) &= T(1) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) \\ \\ 106 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(7) \times F(6) &= T(1) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) + (F(6) + F(7)) \times F(5) &= T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(5) \\ \\ 108 &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9)) &= T(2) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(9) \\ 109 &:= F(3) + F(4) + F(6) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\ \\ 111 &:= F(3) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(4)) + T(9) \\ \\ 112 &:= F(6) \times F(1) \times (F(2) + F(7)) &= T(6) \times (T(1) + T(2)) + T(7) \\ 114 &:= F(2) + F(6) + F(5) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(8) \\ \\ 115 &:= (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) + F(4) &= T(2) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(4) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9)) + F(8) &= T(3) + T(7) + T(9) + T(8) \\ &:= F(4) + F(6) \times (F(2) + F(7)) &= T(4) + T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) \\ \\ 120 &:= F(4) \times (F(5) + F(2) + F(9)) &= (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\ \\ 126 &:= (F(2) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(5) + F(2) \times F(1)) \times F(8) &= T(5) + T(2) \times (T(1) + T(8)) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6)) + T(9) \\ \\ 130 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(5) \times F(7) &= T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(7)) \\ 136 &:= F(3) \times (F(5) + F(4) \times F(8)) &= T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(8) \\ 147 &:= F(3) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(8)) &= T(3) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\ 162 &:= (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(5)) &= T(2) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(5) \\ 168 &:= F(3) \times (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 171 &:= F(2) + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(3)) = T(2) \times (T(9) + T(4)) + T(3) \\ 174 &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 180 &:= (F(1) + F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5)) \\ &:= F(5) \times F(2) \times (F(3) + F(9)) = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(3)) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 186 &:= F(3) \times F(6) + F(5) \times F(9) = T(3) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \\ 189 &:= (F(2) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) = T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(8) \\ 190 &:= (F(4) + F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) = T(4) + T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5)) \\ 195 &:= F(5) \times (F(4) + F(3) + F(9)) = (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\ 208 &:= (F(2) + F(5) \times F(4)) \times F(7) = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\ 210 &:= (F(2) + F(7) \times F(6)) \times F(3) = T(2) \times T(7) + T(6) \times T(3) \\ 214 &:= F(3) \times (F(4) + (F(6) \times F(7))) = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(6)) + T(7) \\ 216 &:= (F(2) + F(5) + F(8)) \times F(6) = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(6)) \\ 231 &:= (F(1) + F(5) \times F(3)) \times F(8) = T(1) \times T(5) + T(3) \times T(8) \\ 234 &:= F(4) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) = T(4) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 276 &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(6) \times F(9) = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) + F(8) \times F(7) + F(3) = T(2) \times T(8) + T(7) \times T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 300 &:= F(2) + F(7) \times (F(3) + F(8)) = T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) \times T(8) \\ 312 &:= (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) \times F(7) = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(7)) \\ 346 &:= (F(4) \times F(7)) \times F(6) + F(9) = T(4) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(9) \\ 370 &:= F(3) \times F(5) \times (F(9) + F(4)) = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(9)) + T(4) \\ 378 &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(8) = T(2) + T(5) + T(4) \times T(8) \\ 441 &:= (F(3) \times F(6) + F(5)) \times F(8) = (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\ 444 &:= F(3) \times F(1) + F(7) \times F(9) = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(7) + T(9)) \\ 448 &:= F(4) \times F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) = T(4) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\ 479 &:= F(4) + F(9) \times (F(1) + F(7)) = T(4) \times T(9) + T(1) + T(7) \\ 481 &:= F(2) \times F(7) \times (F(4) + F(9)) = T(2) + T(7) + T(4) \times T(9) \\ 510 &:= F(5) \times F(1) \times F(4) \times F(9) = T(5) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(9) \\ 511 &:= F(1) + (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(9) = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\ 525 &:= F(5) \times (F(2) + F(7) \times F(6)) = (T(5) + T(2)) \times T(7) + T(6) \\ 540 &:= F(4) \times (F(9) + F(3)) \times F(5) = T(4) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(5) \\ 546 &:= (F(3) + F(6) \times F(5)) \times F(7) = T(3) \times T(6) + T(5) \times T(7) \\ 615 &:= F(4) + (F(7) + F(5)) \times F(9) = (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(5) + T(9) \\ 624 &:= (F(5) + F(1)) \times F(7) \times F(6) = T(5) + (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(6) \\ 630 &:= F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\ 640 &:= (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(5) \times F(6) = T(4) \times (T(7) + T(5) + T(6)) \\ 783 &:= F(2) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(9) = T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(8) + T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 825 &:= F(5) \times F(4) \times (F(8) + F(9)) = T(5) + T(4) \times (T(8) + T(9)) \\ 832 &:= (F(2) + F(4) \times F(8)) \times F(7) = (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(8) + T(7)) \\ 840 &:= (F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) = T(4) \times (T(8) + T(2) + T(9)) \\ 2145 &:= (F(2) + F(8) \times F(9)) \times F(4) = (T(2) + T(8)) \times (T(9) + T(4)) \\ 2205 &:= F(4) \times F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9)) = (T(4) + T(8) + T(2)) \times T(9) \\ 2346 &:= F(4) \times (F(8) + F(3)) \times F(9) = (T(4) + T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \\ 2352 &:= (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(6) \times T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

7.1.4 Five Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned} 34 &:= F(1) + (F(2) + F(5) \times F(3)) \times F(4) = T(1) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(3) + T(4) \\ 35 &:= (F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) = T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\ 40 &:= (F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) = T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(6) \\ 41 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) = T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(6) \\ 44 &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) = T(1) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) \\ 46 &:= F(1) + (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(5) = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(5) \\ 47 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(7)) = T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(3) + T(7) \\ 48 &:= (F(1) \times F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) = T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(7) \\ \\ 49 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6) = (T(1) \times T(2)) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(5) \times (F(2) + F(6)) = T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(2) + T(6) \\ \\ 50 &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(2) + F(4) \times F(6)) = T(1) + T(3) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(6) \\ \\ 52 &:= (F(2) + F(1)) \times (F(3) + F(4) \times F(6)) = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(3)) + T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= F(3) \times ((F(5) + F(1)) \times F(4) + F(6)) = T(3) + T(5) \times T(1) + T(4) + T(6) \\ \\ 53 &:= (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(5) + F(6) = T(1) + T(3) + T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\ \\ 55 &:= (F(2) + F(4) \times F(6)) \times F(3) + F(5) = T(2) + T(4) + T(6) + T(3) + T(5) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(2) + F(3) + F(6)) = T(1) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) \\ \\ 56 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(4) \times F(5) + F(7)) = T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\ \\ 57 &:= ((F(1) + F(6)) \times F(3) + F(2)) \times F(4) = T(1) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(7)) = T(1) + T(4) + T(2) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) + (F(3) \times F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(6) \\ \\ 58 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(3) \times F(6) + F(7)) = T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \\ 59 &:= F(3) + F(5) + (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(7) = T(3) + T(5) \times T(1) + T(4) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{60} & := (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(4) & = T(3) + T(6) + T(2) \times (T(1) + T(4)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(5) + F(3) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(5) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(6) + F(1) + F(2) + F(3)) & = T(5) + T(6) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{62} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(3) \times F(7) + F(5)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(5) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(5) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = T(3) + T(5) + T(2) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{63} & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(6) \times F(2) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(6) + T(2) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{64} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{65} & := (F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(4) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{66} & := F(1) + F(2) + (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) + F(4) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(3) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{67} & := (F(1) \times F(2)) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(2) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(1) + (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(4)) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{68} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(3) \times F(7) + F(6)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(6) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = T(3) + T(6) + T(2) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{69} & := F(1) + F(5) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{70} & := (F(1) + F(7)) + ((F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(4) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(8) + T(4) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) + T(5) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{71} & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(3) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(6) + T(5) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(6) + F(4) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(2) + T(6) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(4) + F(5) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{72} & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(5) + F(3)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(4) \times F(2) + F(8)) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(2) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(5) \times F(3) + F(6)) = T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(3) + T(6) \\ \mathbf{73} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(7) \times F(3) + F(8) = T(1) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(3) + T(8) \\ & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(6)) + F(7) = T(2) + T(5) + T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \\ & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(8) = T(1) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(4) + T(8) \\ & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\ & := F(1) + F(4) \times (F(2) + F(3) + F(8)) = T(1) + T(4) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(8) \\ & := F(1) + F(4) + F(2) + F(3) \times F(9) = T(1) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(9) \\ \mathbf{74} & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(4) + F(9)) = T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(9) \\ & := F(1) + F(3) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(8) = T(1) + T(3) + T(6) + T(4) + T(8) \\ & := F(1) + F(4) + (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(5) = T(1) + T(4) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(5) \\ \mathbf{75} & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) + F(8) = T(1) \times T(5) + T(2) + T(6) + T(8) \\ & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(2) + F(8)) = T(3) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\ \mathbf{76} & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(7)) = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(7) \\ & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(6) + F(3) \times F(9) = T(1) + T(2) + T(6) + T(3) + T(9) \\ & := F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(2) + F(4) + F(9)) = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(9) \\ & := F(1) \times F(4) + F(5) + F(3) \times F(9) = T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(3) + T(9) \\ & := F(3) + F(6) + F(4) \times (F(2) + F(8)) = (T(3) + T(6)) + T(4) + T(2) + T(8) \\ \mathbf{77} & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) = T(1) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(6) \\ & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) + F(8) = T(1) \times T(4) + T(2) + T(7) + T(8) \\ & := (F(2) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(7) = T(2) + T(4) + T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\ & := F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(3) \times F(9) = T(1) + T(4) + T(5) + T(3) + T(9) \\ & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) + F(7) = T(3) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\ \mathbf{78} & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(9)) = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(9) \\ & := F(1) + F(2) + F(7) + F(4) \times F(8) = T(1) + T(2) + T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\ & := F(1) + F(6) \times (F(3) + F(5)) + F(8) = T(1) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(5) + T(8) \\ \mathbf{79} & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(4) + F(9) = T(2) + T(3) + T(5) + T(4) + T(9) \\ & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(9)) = T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(9) \\ & := F(1) + (F(3) + F(4) + F(2)) \times F(7) = (T(1) + T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(7) \\ & := F(2) + F(4) + F(5) \times (F(3) + F(7)) = T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(3) + T(7) \\ & := F(4) + F(6) + (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(9) = T(4) + T(6) \times T(1) + T(2) + T(9) \\ \mathbf{80} & := (F(1) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(2))) \times F(6) = T(1) + T(4) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(6) \\ & := (F(5) + F(6) + F(7)) \times F(4) + F(3) = T(5) + T(6) + T(7) + T(4) + T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(1) \times F(3) + (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{81} & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(7) + F(3)) + F(8) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(7) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(6)) + F(8) & = T(2) + T(5) + T(3) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(8)) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{82} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) + F(9) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(7) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(8) + F(5) + F(2)) \times F(4) & = T(1) + T(8) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(6) \times F(3) + F(2) + F(5) \times F(7) & = T(6) + T(3) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{83} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(7) + F(5) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(5) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(7) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(2) + T(7) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(3) + T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(7) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = T(2) + T(7) + T(4) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{84} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(5) \times F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(9) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(5)) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(2) + F(8) + F(5)) & = (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(2) + T(8) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{85} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(6) \times F(3)) \times F(5) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(8) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(4) + F(9) & = (T(2) + T(3)) + T(6) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(8) & = T(4) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times F(2) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(7) & = T(6) + T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{86} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) + F(9) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(5) \times (F(2) + F(4) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{87} & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(5) + F(8)) & = T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(7) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(2) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) + (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(6) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(5) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{88} & := (F(1) + F(5) + F(9)) \times F(3) + F(6) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(9) + T(3) + T(6) \\ & := F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) + T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\ & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(1) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(1) + T(6) + T(8) \\ & := F(3) + F(6) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(3) + T(6) + T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\ & := F(5) \times (F(4) + F(2)) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(5) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(9) \\ & := F(6) \times ((F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(5)) & = T(6) \times T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(5) \\ \\ \mathbf{89} & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(9)) \times F(3) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(9) + T(3) + T(7) \\ & := F(1) \times F(5) \times F(7) + F(4) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\ & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(7) + F(2)) + F(5) & = T(3) + T(4) + T(7) + T(2) \times T(5) \\ \\ \mathbf{90} & := (F(2) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(9) & = T(2) + T(3) + T(5) + T(6) + T(9) \\ & := F(6) \times (F(5) + F(2)) + F(3) \times F(8) & = ((T(6) + T(5)) + (T(2) \times T(3))) + T(8) \\ & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(8) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(8) + T(3) + T(9) \\ & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(8) \\ & := F(1) + F(4) + F(5) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\ \\ \mathbf{91} & := (F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) + T(7) \\ & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(9) + T(7) \\ & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(7) \\ & := (F(5) + F(7)) \times (F(3) + F(4)) + F(2) & = T(5) + T(7) + (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) \\ & := F(1) + F(2) + F(8) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(2) + T(8) + T(3) + T(9) \\ \\ \mathbf{92} & := F(1) \times F(2) + (F(5) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(3)) + T(7) \\ & := F(1) + (F(3) \times F(4) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) + T(7) \\ & := F(2) + F(7) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(2) + T(7) + T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\ & := F(4) \times (F(8) + F(2)) + F(3) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(8) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) \\ \\ \mathbf{93} & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(6) + F(3) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(3) + T(8) \\ \\ \mathbf{94} & := (F(2) + F(4) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(9) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \\ & := F(2) \times F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(3)) + T(7) + T(9) \\ & := F(4) \times F(6) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = T(4) + T(6) + T(3) \times T(2) + T(9) \\ & := F(5) \times (F(7) + F(2)) + F(4) \times F(6) & = T(5) + T(7) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) \\ \\ \mathbf{95} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) + F(8) & = T(1) + T(2) + T(4) + T(9) + T(8) \\ \\ \mathbf{96} & := (F(1) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(3)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(6) \\ & := F(1) \times F(6) \times F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5)) & = (T(1) \times T(6) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{97} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(9) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(2) \times F(8) + F(7) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(8) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(9)) \times F(3) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(9) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(5) + F(8) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(5) + F(3) \times F(6)) + F(9) & = T(4) + T(5) + T(3) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = T(5) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{99} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(9) + F(5)) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(9) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(2) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(5) \times F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(6) + F(2)) & = T(5) + (T(3) + T(1) + T(6)) \times T(2) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{100} & := F(7) \times (F(3) + F(5)) + F(2) + F(6) & = ((T(7) + T(3)) + (T(5) \times T(2))) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(2) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(8) + F(9) & = T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(3) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{101} & := (F(7) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) + F(4) & = (T(7) + (T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)))) + T(4) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(7) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(7) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) & = T(4) + T(7) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{102} & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(5) + F(6) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(6)) & = T(3) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(6) + (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(7)) & = T(4) + T(6) \times T(2) + T(1) + T(7) \\
 & := F(5) + (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(8) + F(9) & = (T(5) + T(3)) \times T(1) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{103} & := F(2) + F(6) + F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(2) + T(6) + T(3) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{104} & := (F(1) \times F(2) \times F(5) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4)) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) + F(6) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(7) + F(5) + F(9) & = T(3) + T(4) + T(7) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(4) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{105} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(1) \times F(4) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(2) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(3) + F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{106} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(6) \times F(5) + F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(3) + (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7)) & = T(3) \times T(1) \times (T(2) + T(4)) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(5) \times (F(7) + F(2)) + F(3) + F(9) & = T(5) + T(7) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{107} & := F(2) + (F(6) + F(7)) \times F(5) + F(1) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(5) + T(1) \\
 \mathbf{108} & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(5) + (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) \times T(5) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times ((F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{109} & := F(7) \times F(4) + (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(3) & = ((T(7) + (T(4) \times T(2))) + T(9)) + T(3) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(5) + F(6) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(3)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + F(4) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(7) \times (F(2) + F(4)) + F(5) & = T(3) + T(7) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{110} & := F(1) + F(3) + F(4) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(6) + F(5) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(4) + T(6) + T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{111} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(8) \times F(5) + F(4) \times (F(2) + F(1)) & = (T(8) + ((T(5) + T(4)) \times T(2))) \times T(1) \\
 \mathbf{112} & := (F(1) + F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) + F(8) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(2) \times (F(4) + F(5)) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(5)) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5)) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(3) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(5) + F(6) + F(9) & = T(2) + T(7) + T(5) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{112} & := (F(3) + F(5) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(1) + T(2)) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) + F(6) & = T(4) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(8) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = T(4) + T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(1) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(5) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(7) + F(6) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{114} & := (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(5) \times F(6) + F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5)) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(1) + F(9)) & = T(2) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(1)) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(3) \times F(6)) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4) + T(3)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(6) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(1) + F(4) + F(5) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(4) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + F(6) \times F(2) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = T(3) + T(6) + T(2) \times (T(1) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{115} & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = T(1) + (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) + F(6) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(8) + F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(8) + T(3) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(6) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(6) + F(7) \times F(5) + F(9) & = T(3) + T(6) + T(7) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{116} & := F(1) + F(4) + F(6) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + F(8) + F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(8) + T(3) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{117} & := (F(1) + F(5) + F(2) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(4) + F(8) + F(9)) \times F(3) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(9) + T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{118} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(6) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(6) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) + F(9) & = T(1) \times T(5) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(8)) \times (F(3) + F(4)) + F(6) & = T(1) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{118} & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{120} & := ((F(8) + F(2)) \times F(1) + F(3)) \times F(5) & = T(8) + ((T(2) + T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(5))) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(8) + F(2)) \times F(3) + F(6) & = ((T(9) + T(8)) + (T(2) \times T(3))) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(4) \times F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(2) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times ((F(5) + F(1)) \times F(2) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(1) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{121} & := (F(1) + F(5) \times F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(4)) & = T(1) \times T(5) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(4) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) + F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3)) + T(9) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) \times F(5) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(2) + F(9)) & = T(1) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(4) + (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) \times T(4) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(7)) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5) + T(3)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{122} & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) \times F(4) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{123} & := F(1) + F(7) \times (F(2) + F(6)) + F(5) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(5) + F(9)) & = T(2) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(8) + F(9)) + F(5) + F(6) & = T(3) + T(8) + T(9) + T(5) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(5) + F(2) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{124} & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(5) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(7)) + F(9) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(9) + F(6) + F(7) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(9) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) \times (F(5) + F(7))) + F(6) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(7) + F(5) & = (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(5) \\
 & := F(5) \times F(6) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(5) + T(6) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{125} & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(3) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(1) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(5) + F(8) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(7) + T(5) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{126} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(5) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(4)) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(5) + F(9)) & = T(3) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6) \times F(5)) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3) + T(6)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(6) + F(5) & = T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(1) + F(3)) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(6) \times T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{127} & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(8) & = T(1) + (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(7) \times F(6) + F(2) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(7) + T(6) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(3) \times (F(7) + F(6)) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) \times (F(1) + F(4) \times F(6)) & = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(1)) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) \times (F(1) + F(6) \times F(4)) & = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(1)) + T(6) + T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{128} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{129} & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(2) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(3) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9)) + F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3)) + T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(1) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{130} & := (F(1) + F(5) + F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(5) + F(8) + F(9) & = T(3) + T(7) + T(5) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(5) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{131} & := F(2) + (F(4) + F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{132} & := F(8) \times F(5) + F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = (T(8) + ((T(5) + T(4)) \times T(2))) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(6) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(9) + F(8) & = T(6) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(9) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{133} & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(7) \times F(5)) \times F(3) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(7) + T(5) + T(3) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(6) \times F(2) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(6) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(4) + F(3) \times F(2) \times F(5) \times F(7) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{134} := F(1) + F(5) \times F(3) \times F(7) + F(4) = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{135} & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(5) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(2)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(5) \times (F(1) + F(7) \times F(3)) & = T(2) \times (T(5) \times T(1) + T(7)) + T(3) \\
 & := F(2) + F(6) + (F(4) \times F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(4)) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(8))) & = (T(4) + T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(2)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(6) + F(1) + (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(6) \times (T(1) + T(2)) + T(5) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{136} & := (F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(4)) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(4) \times F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(4)) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(5)) + T(4) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(4) \times F(8)) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(6) \times (F(2) + F(4) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(6) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(3)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + F(5) \times (F(2) + F(3) \times F(7)) & = (T(1) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{137} := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(4) \times F(8)) = T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(8)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{138} & := (F(1) + (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(5)) \times F(4) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(6) + T(5) + T(4)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(7) \times F(3) \times F(5) + F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(3)) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) \times (F(5) + F(2)) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(3) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{139} & := F(1) + F(6) \times F(2) \times F(7) + F(9) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(6) + F(5) \times F(3) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(6) + T(5) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7)) + F(9) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(7) + F(8)) + F(9) & = T(4) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(8) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{140} := (F(1) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(3)) + F(5) = T(1) + T(6) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{141} & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(5) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6)) + T(5) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(3)) + F(4) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(4) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(2))) \times F(4) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(2) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(5) \times F(8) + F(9) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(5) + F(6) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) + F(7) + (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(3) + T(7) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(7) \times (F(2) + F(3)) + F(6)) & = (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{142} & := (F(2) + F(1)) \times (F(8) \times F(4) + F(6)) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(8)) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(5) + F(3) \times F(8)) \times F(4) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(8) + T(4) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(7) \times F(2) + F(9)) \times F(4) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(9) + T(4) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times (F(3) \times F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + F(5) \times (F(2) + F(7))) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(2)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{143} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(5) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(7) \times (F(4) + F(6)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(7) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{144} & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(2) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(3)) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(2) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(3) + F(8)) & = (T(1) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5) + F(4)) \times F(6) \times F(3) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4) + T(6)) + T(3) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(8)) \times (F(3) + F(4)) + F(9) & = T(2) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{145} & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(6) \times F(2) + F(8)) & = T(3) + T(4) + T(6) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(3) \times F(2) \times F(7)) \times F(5) & = T(4) + T(3) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(5)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(5) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(3) \times F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(7) + F(2) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(4) + T(7) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{146} & := F(3) \times F(5) + (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(1) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(3) \times F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{147} & := (F(9) + F(1)) \times F(4) + F(3) \times F(8) & = (T(9) + ((T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3))) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2) + F(4) + F(1)) \times F(8) & = T(3) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(1) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(5) \times F(8) + F(6) + F(9) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(8) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(1) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(6)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(8) + F(2) + F(7) \times F(6) & = T(3) + T(8) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) \times F(1) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(5) \times T(1) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{148} & := F(1) + F(3) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(5) + F(3) + F(4) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(5) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{149} & := (F(3) + F(5) \times F(4)) \times F(6) + F(7) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{150} & := (F(2) + F(7) + F(1)) \times F(5) \times F(3) & = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(1) + T(5) + T(3)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{151} & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(2) \times F(7) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(3) + F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(7) + F(9) & = (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) + F(1) + (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(4) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) + F(2) + F(8) \times (F(3) + F(5)) & = T(4) + T(2) \times (T(8) + T(3)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(5) \times F(7) \times (F(1) + F(2)) + F(8) & = T(5) + T(7) \times T(1) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(5) + (F(7) + F(2)) \times F(6) + F(9) & = T(5) + T(7) + T(2) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{152} & := (F(7) + (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4)) \times F(6) & = T(7) + ((T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(6))) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(7) + F(4) \times F(2) \times F(8)) & = T(3) + T(7) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{153} & := F(2) + (F(1) + F(5) + F(7)) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(7)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(4) \times F(3) + F(7)) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3) + T(7)) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{154} & := (F(1) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(5) + T(2)) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(7)) \times (F(6) + F(2) + F(3)) & = T(1) + (T(7) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(3) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(5) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) \times (F(3) + F(7)) + F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(3)) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(4) \times F(8) + F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(2)) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) \times F(7) + F(9)) + F(6) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(9) + T(6) \\
 & := F(5) + F(7) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(5) + T(7) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{156} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(9) + F(5)) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(9) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(4) \times (F(8) + F(5)) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(4) + T(8)) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(4) \times F(6)) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(3) + T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2) + F(1) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(3) + T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(5) \times (F(7) + F(2)) + F(6)) & = T(3) + (T(5) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(5) + F(9) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{157} & := (F(3) + F(5) \times F(4)) \times F(6) + F(8) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(4) + F(2) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(8) + (F(7) + F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) & = (T(8) + T(7)) + (T(2) \times (T(4) + T(6))) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{159} & := (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(7) + F(3) \times F(8) & = T(6) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(3)) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(3) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(9) + F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(4)) + T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{160} & := (F(1) \times F(5) + F(3)) \times F(8) + F(7) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(8) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(5) \times (F(4) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(6) \times F(3) \times F(5) & = T(1) + (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(5) + F(2) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(4)) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6) + T(7)) + T(4) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(6) \times F(5) + F(7)) + F(2) & = T(4) + T(6) + (T(5) + T(7)) \times T(2) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{162} & := (F(8) + F(1)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) + F(6) & = (T(8) + ((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5))) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(5)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(6) + (F(5) + F(3)) \times (F(8) + F(2)) & = (T(6) + T(5)) + ((T(3) + T(8)) \times T(2)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{163} & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(5)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{164} & := (F(4) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) \times F(5) \times F(7) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{165} & := (F(1) \times F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(6) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(7) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) & = T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(7) + (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{166} & := F(1) + (F(8) \times F(2) + F(9)) \times F(4) & = (T(1) + T(8)) \times T(2) + T(9) + T(4) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(5) \times F(7) + F(2)) + F(9) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(2) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{167} & := F(2) \times F(8) \times F(4) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(8) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{168} & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(3) \times F(2) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3) + F(7) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(7) + T(5)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) \times (F(5) + F(3)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(5)) + T(3) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{169} & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(8) \times (F(4) + F(5)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(6) \times (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(4) & = (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(4) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(1) + F(3) \times F(7)) + F(9) & = (T(5) + T(1)) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{170} & := (F(1) \times F(7) \times F(3) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = T(1) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(6) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 171 & := (F(5) + F(2) + F(3)) \times F(8) + F(4) & = T(5) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(8) + T(4)) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(3) \times F(2) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) + F(1) + F(6) \times F(2) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(2) + (F(5) + F(3)) \times F(6)) & = T(4) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 172 & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(5) \times T(3) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(7) + F(8) + F(9) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + (F(6) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(2) \times (F(5) \times F(7) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5)) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(1) + F(2) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(3) + T(1) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(5) \times F(2) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(5) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 173 & := F(1) \times F(4) + F(8) \times F(6) + F(3) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(8) + T(6) \times T(3) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(9) + F(3)) + F(5) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(9) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 174 & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) + F(6) + F(4) \times (F(8) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(4)) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(9) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(9) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 175 & := (F(1) + F(6) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(5) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(5) + F(8) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(3) + F(6) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$177 := (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(8) \times F(6) = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4) + T(8)) + T(6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 178 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(3) + F(9) \times F(5) & = T(4) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) + F(9) & = T(4) + T(8) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) + (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(3) + T(2) \times (T(8) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(5) \times F(3) + F(6) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(8) + (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(9)) & = T(3) + T(8) + T(1) + T(2) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 180 & := (F(2) \times F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(5)) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(7)) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) & = T(2) + T(5) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(3) \times F(2) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(5) \times (T(3) + T(2)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times ((F(3) + F(2)) \times F(7) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 181 & := F(1) + (F(5) \times F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(5) \times (T(2) + T(3)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(8) \times (F(4) + F(5)) + F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(8) + T(4)) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(6) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(6) + F(5) \times F(2) \times F(9) & = T(4) + T(6) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{182} & := (F(2) + F(6) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{183} & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(6) \times F(5) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(7) + F(6) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(7) + T(6)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(7) \times (F(6) + F(4) \times F(3)) & = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(6) + T(4)) + T(3) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(1) + F(9) + F(2)) \times F(5) & = (T(4) + T(1) + T(9)) \times T(2) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{184} & := (F(2) + F(8)) \times (F(5) + F(4)) + F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(8) + T(5)) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(2) + F(1)) & = (T(4) + T(5) + T(8)) \times T(2) + T(1) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(2) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = (T(3) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{186} & := F(1) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(5) \times F(9) & = (T(1) \times T(3)) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(3) + F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5)) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(6) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(5) + F(7) + F(6) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(7)) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{187} & := F(1) + F(3) \times F(6) + F(5) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(3) \times F(2) + F(8)) \times F(6) & = T(4) + T(3) + T(2) \times (T(8) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{189} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(8)) \times F(6) + F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(8) + T(6)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) \times (F(8) + F(3)) + F(5) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) + F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(9)) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(5) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = T(4) \times T(5) + T(3) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{190} & := ((F(1) + F(4)) \times F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5)) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(3)) \times (F(1) + F(5) + F(7)) & = T(6) \times (T(3) + T(1)) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{191} & := (F(1) + F(8)) \times F(6) + F(3) + F(7) & = ((T(1) + T(8)) + (T(6) \times T(3))) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(4) + F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(4)) + (T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5))) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{192} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = ((T(1) \times T(3)) + (T(5) \times T(4))) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = (T(3) + ((T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5))) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (((T(3) + T(1)) + T(6)) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{195} & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times (((T(1) + T(5)) + T(6)) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4) \times F(3) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times (((T(4) + T(3)) + T(6)) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(2) \times F(7) & = ((T(3) \times T(5)) + T(6)) + (T(2) \times T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(4) + F(3) + F(9)) & = (((T(1) \times T(5)) + T(4)) \times T(3)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times ((F(2) + F(6)) \times F(3) + F(8)) & = (T(5) + ((T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3))) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{196} & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times ((T(3) + T(5)) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(9) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(9)) + (T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5))) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(5) + F(9)) \times (F(3) + F(4)) & = ((T(2) \times (T(5) + T(9))) + T(3)) + T(4) \\
 & := F(2) + F(7) \times F(4) \times F(1) \times F(5) & = (T(2) + T(7)) + ((T(4) + T(1)) \times T(5)) \\
 & := F(3) + F(6) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(9) & = (((T(3) \times T(6)) + T(4)) + T(5)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{198} & := (F(5) + F(7)) \times (F(6) + F(2) + F(3)) & = (((T(5) + T(7)) + T(6)) \times T(2)) + T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{199} & := (F(9) + F(7)) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(8) & = ((T(9) + T(7)) + (T(3) \times T(5))) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(6) + F(4)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) & = ((T(1) \times T(6)) + (T(4) \times T(5))) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{200} & := (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(3) + F(6) \times F(8) & = ((T(4) + T(7)) + (T(3) \times T(6))) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(7) + (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4)) \times F(5) & = ((T(7) + T(1)) + T(6)) + (T(4) \times T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{201} & := F(1) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) \times F(5) & = ((T(1) \times T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(6))) + T(5) \\
 & := F(1) + F(5) \times (F(4) \times F(3) + F(9)) & = (((T(1) + T(5)) + T(4)) \times T(3)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(6) \times (F(1) + F(4) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times (((T(6) \times T(1)) + T(4)) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) + F(2) & = (T(6) \times T(3)) + ((T(4) + T(5)) \times T(2)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{202} & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(8) \times F(2) + F(7) & = (((T(1) + T(6)) + T(8)) \times T(2)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{204} & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(3) \times F(7)) & = ((T(1) \times T(5)) + T(6)) + (T(3) \times T(7)) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(6) + F(8)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) & = (T(2) \times ((T(6) + T(8)) + T(3))) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(5) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(8)) & = (((T(4) + T(5)) + T(2)) \times T(3)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(5) + F(8) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = (((T(4) + T(5)) + T(8)) \times T(2)) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{205} & := F(1) + (F(3) + F(4) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(3) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(5) \times F(7) & = T(3) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(3) \times F(5) + F(7)) + F(8) & = T(6) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{207} & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(5) \times F(3) + F(7)) & = T(2) + T(6) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(9) + F(5) + F(6) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times T(9) + T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times ((F(1) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(1) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{208} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(9) + F(5) + F(7)) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(9)) + T(5) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(8) + F(5)) \times F(3) & = T(4) + T(2) \times T(8) + T(5) \times T(3) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(6) \times F(3) \times F(2) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(6) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) + (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(9) & = T(2) + T(4) \times (T(1) + T(5)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(8) \times F(5) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(8) + T(5)) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{209} & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(9) + F(7)) + F(8) & = T(4) + T(2) \times T(9) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(4) \times F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(4) \times (T(5) + T(2)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(5) + F(4) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{210} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(8)) \times F(6) + F(9) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(7) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) & = (T(1) + T(7) + T(8)) \times T(2) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(6) + F(3)) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = T(5) + T(6) + T(3) \times (T(1) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(5) \times F(8) \times F(3) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(3) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(3) \times F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + (F(6) \times F(2)) \times F(7)) & = T(3) \times T(1) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{211} & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(7) \times F(6)) \times F(3) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(6) \times T(3) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(3) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(9) \times F(4) + F(1)) + F(5) & = T(3) + T(9) + T(4) \times (T(1) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{213} & := F(1) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(9) + F(6) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(2) \times (T(9) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(5) \times F(8) + F(2)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(8) \times T(2) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(5) \times (F(3) + F(6)) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(5) + T(3) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(5) + T(2) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) + F(3) \times F(2) \times F(5) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{214} & := ((F(8) + F(7)) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times F(3) & = (T(8) + T(7)) + ((T(4) + T(5)) \times T(3)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) + F(9) & = T(3) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(4) + F(6) \times F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(4) + T(6)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(9) + (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) & = (T(4) + T(9)) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(2) + F(8)) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(5) + T(2) \times (T(8) + T(6)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{215} & := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(6) \times F(7)) & = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(6)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{216} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(5) + F(8)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(9) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(9) + T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(9) \times F(4)) & = T(3) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(9) + T(4)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(5) + F(1) + F(4) \times F(9)) & = T(3) + T(5) \times (T(1) + T(4)) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{217} & := (F(7) \times F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) + F(1) & = (T(7) + ((T(3) + T(2)) \times T(6))) \times T(1) \\
 & := F(9) \times F(1) \times (F(2) + F(5)) + F(7) & = T(9) + ((T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(7))) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(5) + F(8)) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(1) + F(6) \times (F(2) + F(3) \times F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(6) \times (T(2) + T(3)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(5) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{219} & := F(3) \times F(5) \times F(8) + F(2) + F(6) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(8) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(2) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times F(6) & = T(4) \times T(2) + T(3) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{220} & := (F(4) + F(1)) \times (F(7) + F(3) \times F(8)) & = T(4) + (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(3) \times F(8) + F(7)) & = T(4) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(8) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{221} & := (F(4) \times F(5) \times F(1) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(5) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{222} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) \times F(6) + F(7)) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(6) \times F(3)) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(6)) + T(3) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(5) + F(4) \times F(9)) + F(6) & = T(3) + T(5) \times T(4) + T(9) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{223} & := (F(1) + F(9)) \times F(4) \times F(3) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(9) + T(4) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(3) \times F(4) + F(7) & = T(2) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) + F(7) & = T(5) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(9) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(9) + F(6) \times F(5)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (T(9) + T(6)) + T(5) + T(4) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(6) + F(3)) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = (T(4) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(1) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{224} & := (F(2) + F(4) \times F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(1) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{225} & := F(3) + (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(8) + F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(2)) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{226} & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(8) + F(4) + F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(8) + T(4)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(5) \times (F(4) + F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6) \times (F(1) + F(7))) & = (T(3) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(1)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(6) + (F(9) + F(2)) \times F(4)) & = (T(3) + T(6) + T(9)) \times T(2) + T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{227} & := F(4) + F(6) \times F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = T(4) + T(6) + (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(6) \times F(3) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = T(4) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(2)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{228} & := ((F(1) + F(2)) \times F(9) + F(6)) \times F(4) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(9) + T(6) + T(4)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(8) \times F(4) + F(7)) & = T(3) + T(2) \times (T(8) + T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(4) + F(8) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = (T(4) + T(8) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{229} & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(7) \times F(5) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(7) + T(5) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(1) + F(4) \times F(5)) \times F(7) + F(8) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) + F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(4) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(7) \times (F(4) + F(5)) + F(8) & = T(3) \times T(7) + T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{230} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(7) + F(9) \times F(4)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{231} & := ((F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(9) \times F(3) + F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4) & = T(9) + T(3) \times T(1) \times (T(6) + T(4)) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) + F(8) & = T(5) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) + F(8) & = T(9) \times (T(1) + T(2)) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(8) + (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(8) + T(6)) + T(9) + T(5) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7) \times F(6)) + F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(7)) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) \times F(8) + F(2) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(8) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(8) + (F(6) \times F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = (T(8) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(9) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{232} & := ((F(1) + F(7)) \times F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(7) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) \times (F(4) + F(3) \times F(7)) & = (T(2) + T(6) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{234} & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(2) \times F(3) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{234} & := F(2) + F(8) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(9) & = T(2) + T(8) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(6) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(9))) & = (T(4) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(2) + T(9) \\
 & := F(7) \times (F(3) \times F(2) \times F(5) + F(6)) & = T(7) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{235} & := ((F(1) \times F(2)) \times F(7) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(2) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(3) + T(4) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(9)) + F(2) & = T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(9) \times T(2) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(6) + F(4)) + F(8) & = T(3) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(4) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{237} & := (F(1) + F(7) \times (F(2) + F(5))) \times F(4) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(5) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(2) + F(1) + (F(7) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(7) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(5) + F(4) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{238} & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(6) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = T(3) \times T(6) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) + F(5) \times (F(9) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(9) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(3) + F(5) \times F(4)) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times T(1) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(5) \times (F(9) \times F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(4) + T(5) + T(9)) \times T(2) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{240} & := (F(2) + F(7) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4) + F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(7)) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(9) + F(5)) & = T(3) \times T(4) \times T(2) + T(9) + T(5) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(1) + F(5) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{241} & := F(1) + (F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(3) \times F(5) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(8) \times T(3) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(2) + F(5) + F(1)) \times F(9) & = (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(1) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{242} & := (F(1) + F(8)) \times (F(3) \times F(4) + F(5)) & = T(1) + T(8) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{243} & := (F(2) + F(3) \times F(5) \times F(6)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(6) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{244} & := F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(2) + F(7)) + F(9) & = T(4) + T(5) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(5) + (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(7)) & = T(3) \times (T(5) \times T(1) + T(6)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(6) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(6) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{246} & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(5)) \times F(9) + F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(9) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(9) \times (F(3) + F(5)) + F(6) & = T(2) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(4) \times F(7)) & = T(2) + T(5) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(5) \times F(6) + F(2)) \times F(4) & = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(6)) + T(2) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(9)) \times (F(5) + F(3)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(9) + T(5)) + T(3) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(7) + F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = (T(2) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(9) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times ((F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(5)) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(6) + (F(3) \times F(4) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = T(6) + T(3) \times T(4) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{247} & := (F(2) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(3) + T(6) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3) \times F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(6)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{249} & := F(2) + (F(8) + F(5) \times F(3)) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{250} & := (F(2) + F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(3) + F(6)) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(8) \times T(3) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{251} & := F(9) \times (F(4) \times F(3) + F(1)) + F(7) & = T(9) + T(4) + (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{252} & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) \times (F(1) + F(3)) & = T(2) \times T(4) + (T(8) + T(1)) \times T(3) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(8) + F(5)) & = T(1) \times T(6) + T(3) \times T(8) + T(5) \\
 & := F(2) + F(7) + F(9) \times (F(3) + F(5)) & = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(9) + T(3)) + T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(3) \times (F(7) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) = T(3) \times T(7) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{253} & := (F(1) \times F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) = T(1) + T(4) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{255} & := (F(3) \times F(6) + F(2)) \times F(7) + F(9) = T(3) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(3) \times F(8)) = T(5) + T(2) + T(6) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{256} & := F(2) \times F(3) \times F(6) \times (F(4) + F(7)) = T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{258} & := F(6) \times (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(3) + F(9) = T(6) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(3) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(3)) + F(7) = T(9) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(9)) = T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(8)) = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{259} & := (F(1) + F(5) + F(2)) \times F(9) + F(8) = T(1) + T(5) + T(2) \times (T(9) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(4) + F(2)) \times F(9) + F(8) = T(3) + T(4) + T(2) \times (T(9) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(4) \times F(9) + F(8)) \times F(3) + F(7) = T(4) + T(9) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(4) \times F(6) + F(7)) = (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(5) \times (F(7) + F(9)) + F(8) = T(4) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(9) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{261} & := (F(1) + F(5) + F(4)) \times (F(6) + F(8)) = T(1) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(3) \times F(7)) = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(4)) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{264} & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(3) = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(8) \times T(3) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(3) + F(9)) = T(2) + (T(5) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) \times F(5) + F(2)) \times F(6) = (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(2) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(3) + F(8)) = T(4) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{265} & := F(3) \times F(8) \times (F(1) + F(5)) + F(7) = T(3) \times (T(8) + T(1)) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(7) + F(8) \times (F(6) + F(2) + F(4)) = (T(7) + T(8) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(4) \\
 \mathbf{266} & := F(3) \times (F(8) + F(6) \times (F(1) + F(7))) = T(3) \times T(8) + T(6) + T(1) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{267} & := F(3) + (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(8) + F(9) = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(6)) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{268} & := (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(7) + F(9) = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(4)) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(5) \times F(7)) = (T(1) \times T(4) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(5) \times F(7)) = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(3) + T(5)) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{270} & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(6) + F(9)) = T(1) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(6) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 273 & := (F(1) \times F(4) + F(6) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(5) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(7)) \\
 274 & := F(1) + (F(7) \times (F(5) + F(3)) \times F(4)) & = (T(1) + T(7) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(4) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(5) + F(4)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 275 & := F(1) \times F(4) + F(6) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = T(1) + T(4) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 276 & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(5) \times (F(9) + F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(5) + T(9)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) + F(7) \times F(2) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(7) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(2) \times F(6) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times T(7) + T(2) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 277 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(8) \times F(7) + F(3) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(8) + T(7) \times T(3) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) + (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(8) + T(9) + T(5) \\
 279 & := (F(3) \times F(7) + F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(5)) \times T(1) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(2) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) + F(1) + F(2) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(5) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) \times (F(8) \times F(5) + F(9)) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 280 & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(9)) \times (F(4) + F(5)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(9) + T(4) + T(5)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(6) + (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 282 & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(7) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(4) + T(7)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(6) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(8) + F(1) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(3) \times (T(8) + T(1)) + T(9) + T(5) \\
 283 & := F(3) \times F(2) + F(8) \times F(7) + F(6) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(8)) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 284 & := F(1) \times F(6) + F(4) + F(7) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 285 & := F(2) \times F(1) \times F(7) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(7) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) + F(6) + F(7) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(6) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 286 & := (F(4) \times (F(3) + F(5)) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(2) + T(7)) \\
 287 & := F(1) + F(3) \times F(7) \times (F(4) + F(6)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(7) + T(4)) + T(6) \\
 288 & := (F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(9)) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(9) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(7) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(7) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) + F(2) + F(7) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(3) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(6) + T(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(2) \times F(3) + F(7) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(7) \times T(1) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(1) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(5) + T(2) \times (T(1) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(4)) \times (F(3) \times F(2) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times (T(4) + T(3) + T(2)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(1) + F(8)) \times (F(5) + F(6)) & = (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{289} & := F(4) + F(6) + F(5) + F(7) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(7) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(7) + T(1) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{291} & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(2) + F(6) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6)) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(4) \times F(6) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(9) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{294} & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times F(7) + F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5) + T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4) + F(6) + F(2)) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(6)) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(5) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{296} & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(3) + F(9)) & = T(4) + T(5) + T(1) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{297} & := F(2) + F(3) + (F(7) + F(1)) \times F(8) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(7) + T(1)) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{298} & := F(5) \times F(9) + F(6) \times (F(4) + F(7)) & = T(5) + T(9) + T(6) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{299} & := (F(1) + (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(4) \times (T(6) + T(3)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{300} & := (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(3) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(3) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(7) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) + (F(7) + F(2)) \times F(8) & = (T(3) \times T(4) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(7) \times (F(1) + F(3)) + F(8)) & = (T(5) + T(7) + T(1)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{301} & := F(1) + F(2) + F(7) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{302} & := F(4) + F(7) \times F(1) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = (T(4) + T(7)) \times (T(1) + T(3)) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{304} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) + F(9)) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(9) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(7) + F(5) \times F(8)) \times F(3) & = T(9) + T(7) + T(5) + T(8) \times T(3) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(6) + F(3) \times F(9)) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(6) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(9) + F(4) + F(2)) \times F(1) & = (T(6) + T(9) + T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(1)) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(2) + F(4) + F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(6) + T(2)) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(5) \times (F(4) + F(3)) + F(7)) & = (T(6) + T(5) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{306} & := ((F(2) + F(4)) \times F(3) + F(1)) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) \times (T(1) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(9) + F(4)) + F(3) \times F(5) & = T(6) + T(9) + (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 307 & := F(2) \times F(6) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(3) \times T(8) + T(7) \\
 308 & := (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = T(4) \times (T(6) + T(3) + T(1)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 309 & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(9)) \times F(6) + F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(9) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) + (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) + F(9) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + T(6) \\
 \\
 312 & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(8) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(2) \times F(6) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(7) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(7) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(7) \times (F(2) + F(4) + F(6)) & = (T(3) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 313 & := F(1) + (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 314 & := F(2) + F(1) + F(7) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = T(2) + (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 \\
 315 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(1) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(1) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(4) + F(2) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(3) + (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(9)) \times (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (T(9) \times T(1) + T(3) \times T(4)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(7) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(7) + T(6)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(1) + (F(6) \times F(2)) \times F(7)) & = (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(5) \times ((F(7) + (F(3) \times F(8))) + F(6)) & = (T(5) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(8) + T(6) \\
 \\
 316 & := F(5) \times (F(7) + F(6)) \times F(4) + F(2) & = T(5) + T(7) + T(6) \times (T(4) + T(2)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) + (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(2) + T(3)) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(6) + F(7)) \times F(4) \times F(5) & = (T(1) \times T(6) + T(7) \times T(4)) + T(5) \\
 \\
 317 & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(8) \times F(4) & = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(4) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(5) + F(6) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(3) + F(4) \times (F(1) + F(7) \times F(6)) & = T(3) + T(4) \times (T(1) + T(7)) + T(6) \\
 \\
 318 & := F(4) + (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(6) \times T(1) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) + F(5) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times (T(5) + T(3)) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 319 & := F(3) + (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(7) + F(5) & = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(8)) + T(7) + T(5) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(4) + F(5) & = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(3) + F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 321 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(5) \times F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(4) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(5) + F(8) \times (F(3) + F(7)) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(4) \times F(3) + F(9)) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(9) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{322} & := F(3) \times F(5) + F(6) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = T(3) + T(5) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(5) \times F(8) + F(3)) \times F(4) & = (T(1) + T(5) + T(8)) \times T(3) + T(4) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(6) \times (F(2) + (F(7) \times F(4)))) & = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(2) + T(7)) + T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{324} & := (F(6) + F(2)) \times ((F(4) \times F(5)) + F(8)) & = T(6) \times (T(2) + T(4)) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) + F(2) + F(5) \times F(8)) & = (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(5)) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{325} & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(2)) \times F(7) \times F(5) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(2) + T(7)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) + ((F(7) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(8))) & = T(4) \times T(7) + T(2) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{327} & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(6) \times F(7) + F(5)) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(7)) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{328} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(7)) \times F(8) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(7) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(7) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(4)) \times F(6) & = T(7) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) \times (F(3) + F(4) \times F(7)) & = (T(2) + T(6) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{330} & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(5) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(1) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(6) + (F(1) + F(7)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = (T(6) \times T(1) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{331} & := (F(1) + F(8) \times F(5)) \times F(4) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{333} & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(9) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(9) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(9) + F(7) \times (F(8) + F(3)) & = T(2) \times (T(9) + T(7) + T(8)) + T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{334} & := F(1) + F(7) \times (F(8) + F(3)) + F(9) & = T(1) \times T(7) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{336} & := ((F(4) + F(2)) \times F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(3) + T(6)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(2) \times F(8) & = (T(4) + T(5) \times T(3)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(8) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(2) \times T(3)) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(8) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(8) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(9) + F(8) + F(2)) \times F(4) & = T(3) \times T(9) + T(8) + T(2) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{337} & := (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) + F(7) & = T(3) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) + F(9) \times F(6) + F(4) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times T(9) + T(6) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times F(8) \times (F(4) + F(5)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(8) + T(4)) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{339} & := F(2) + (F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) \times F(3) & = T(2) \times T(5) + (T(6) + T(7)) \times T(3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(4) + F(8) \times F(3) \times F(2) \times F(6) & = (T(4) + T(8)) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{340} & := ((F(4) + F(5)) \times F(1) + F(3)) \times F(9) & = T(4) + T(5) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(8) + F(7)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{341} & := F(4) \times F(1) + F(7) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times (T(1) + T(7)) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{342} & := F(2) + F(8) \times (F(7) + F(4)) + F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(8) + T(7)) + T(4) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(2) \times (F(4) + F(6) \times F(8)) & = (T(3) \times ((T(2) \times T(4)) + T(6))) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{343} & := F(4) \times F(2) + (F(6) + F(3)) \times F(9) & = (T(4) + (T(2) \times T(6))) + (T(3) \times T(9)) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(8) \times F(6)) & = ((T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(8))) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(7) + F(8)) \times (F(3) + F(6)) & = (((T(4) \times T(7)) + T(8)) + T(3)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{344} & := ((F(1) + F(7)) \times F(4) + F(2)) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(7) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(3) + (F(5) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(7) \times F(8) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(4) + T(7) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{345} & := (F(2) + F(9) \times F(5)) \times F(3) + F(4) & = T(2) \times T(9) + (T(5) + T(3)) \times T(4) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) + F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(8) \times F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(8) \times (T(3) + T(2)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{346} & := F(1) \times F(4) \times F(7) \times F(6) + F(9) & = (T(1) \times T(4)) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(5) \times F(9) + F(4)) \times F(3) & = T(1) + T(5) + (T(9) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times F(7) + F(9) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(8) + (F(2) + F(4) \times F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(8) \times T(2) + T(4) \times T(6) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{347} & := F(1) + F(4) \times F(7) \times F(6) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(4) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{348} & := (F(2) + F(5) \times F(9) + F(4)) \times F(3) & = T(2) + T(5) + (T(9) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) + F(5) \times F(3) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{349} & := F(4) \times (F(7) \times F(6) + F(2)) + F(9) & = T(4) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(2) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{351} & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(4) \times (F(9) + F(5)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(4) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(4) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(6) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(3) + F(9)) & = (T(6) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(9)) + T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 352 & := ((F(2) + F(3)) \times F(7) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = T(2) + T(3) + T(7) + T(5) \times T(6) \\
 & := (F(5) \times F(8) + F(6)) \times F(4) + F(7) & = T(5) + T(8) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(7) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = T(1) \times T(7) + (T(3) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(4) + F(9) & = T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(7) \times (F(4) \times F(3) + F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 353 & := F(1) + F(6) \times (F(5) + F(4) \times F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(6) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(7) \times F(4) & = (T(3) + T(1)) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(4) \\
 \\
 354 & := ((F(6) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(9))) + F(8) & = T(6) \times (T(2) + T(4)) + T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + (F(1) + F(8)) \times F(6)) & = (T(3) + T(2)) \times (T(1) + T(8)) + T(6) \\
 \\
 355 & := (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(8) + F(5) \times F(6) & = T(7) + T(3) \times (T(8) + T(5)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) + F(6) \times F(3) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = T(4) + T(6) + (T(3) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 356 & := F(5) + (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = T(5) \times T(6) + T(2) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 357 & := (F(1) + F(8)) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(5) & = T(1) \times T(8) + T(3) + T(6) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 358 & := (F(1) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(5) + F(7) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times ((F(1) + F(8)) \times F(6) + F(4)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(8) + T(6)) + T(4) \\
 \\
 360 & := (F(3) \times F(1) + F(7)) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(7) + T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(7) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(4) \times T(3) + T(9) + T(5)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(8))) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(2) + T(8) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(2) + F(1)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times T(2) \times (T(1) + T(3)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 361 & := F(4) \times (F(7) \times F(6) + F(5)) + F(9) & = T(4) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(6) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(6) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(2) + F(6) \times (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(3)) + T(7) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 363 & := F(2) + (F(7) + F(6) \times F(8)) \times F(3) & = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(6)) + T(8) \times T(3) \\
 \\
 364 & := (F(1) + F(6) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(5) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(2) \times (T(5) \times T(3) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(1) + (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(4)) \times F(7) & = ((T(1) + T(2)) \times T(6)) + (T(4) \times T(7)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(7)) \times (F(3) + F(4) \times F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(7) + (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(7)) \times (F(3) + F(4) \times F(6)) & = T(2) + (T(7) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 365 &:= (F(1) + F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) + F(6) &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(7) + T(8) + T(6) \\
 366 &:= (F(1) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(5) + F(8) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(2) + F(9) \times F(3)) + F(8) &= T(5) + T(2) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(6) + F(5) \times (F(1) + F(9))) &= T(3) + T(6) \times T(5) \times T(1) + T(9) \\
 369 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(4) \times F(9) + F(8)) &= T(2) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(9)) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(3) + F(9)) &= T(2) + T(6) \times T(5) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(7) \times F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) &= T(3) \times (T(7) + T(4) \times T(2)) + T(6) \\
 370 &:= (F(1) \times F(4) + F(9)) \times F(5) \times F(3) &= T(1) \times T(4) + (T(9) + T(5)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(8) + F(7) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(6) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(4) \times F(7) + F(2) + F(9)) &= T(5) + T(4) \times (T(7) + T(2)) + T(9) \\
 371 &:= F(1) + (F(7) + F(4)) \times F(8) + F(9) &= (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(4) + F(9)) \times F(5) \times F(3) &= T(1) + T(4) + (T(9) + T(5)) \times T(3) \\
 372 &:= (F(2) \times F(8) + F(5)) \times F(7) + F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(8) + T(5) + T(7) + T(9)) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(8) \times F(6) + F(2)) + F(9) &= T(3) \times T(8) + T(6) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(9) + F(3) \times (F(1) + F(8) \times F(6)) &= T(9) \times (T(3) + T(1)) + T(8) + T(6) \\
 375 &:= F(2) + (F(5) + F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) \times (T(4) + T(9)) \\
 376 &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(6) \times (F(7) + F(9)) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(4) + F(9) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(4) + T(9) + T(3) + T(5) \times T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(6) \times (F(8) + F(3) \times F(7)) &= (T(1) + T(6) + T(8)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(9) + F(7)) &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(4) + T(9)) + T(7) \\
 377 &:= (F(8) + (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(3)) \times F(7) &= T(8) + T(1) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 378 &:= (F(1) \times F(2) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(8) &= T(1) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) \times F(3) + F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(7)) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(3) \times F(1) \times F(5) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= T(3) + (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(9) + F(6)) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(2)) &= (T(9) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(3)) \times T(2) \\
 379 &:= F(1) \times F(3) + F(7) \times (F(6) + F(8)) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(7) + T(6)) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(7) \times F(4) + F(9) \times (F(3) + F(6)) &= T(7) + (T(4) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(8) &= T(1) + T(5) + T(2) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) + (F(4) + F(3) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(2) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(7)) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(3) + (F(4) \times F(6) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{381} & := F(1) + F(5) \times (F(9) \times F(3) + F(6)) & = (T(1) \times T(5) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{382} & := F(2) \times F(5) + (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(5) \times T(6) + T(8) + T(7) \\
 & := F(6) + (F(1) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(9) & = T(6) + T(1) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{384} & := (F(1) + F(7) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(6) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(1) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(7) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(2) \times T(4)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8)) \times F(4) & = T(3) + T(2) + T(5) + T(8) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(8) + F(5) \times F(9)) & = (T(3) + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{389} & := F(4) + F(6) + (F(5) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(4) + T(6) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(5) + F(6) \times (F(1) + F(7) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times T(6) + T(1) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{390} & := (F(2) \times F(7) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) + F(5) & = T(9) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{391} & := (F(2) + F(7) + F(4)) \times F(8) + F(9) & = (T(2) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(4) \times F(7)) \times (F(3) + F(6)) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{396} & := (F(2) \times F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(3)) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{397} & := F(3) + F(8) + (F(6) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(8) + T(6)) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(6) + F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times (T(4) + T(3)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(7) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(6) & = (T(7) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{399} & := (F(2) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(2) + F(5) \times F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(6) + T(2) \times (T(5) \times T(3) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{400} & := (F(2) + F(7) \times F(4)) \times F(3) \times F(5) & = (T(2) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(1) + F(8) \times (F(7) + F(3) \times F(4)) & = (T(1) + T(8) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(4) \\
 \mathbf{403} & := (F(3) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{405} & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(8) \times F(3)) & = T(2) + (T(6) + T(4) + T(8)) \times T(3) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(1) + F(8) + F(5)) & = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(1) + T(8)) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{406} & := (F(2) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(4) + F(8)) & = T(2) + T(7) + T(5) + T(4) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(9) + F(4) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(9)) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(5) \times (F(9) \times F(3) + F(7)) & = (T(2) + T(5) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(7) \times (F(3) \times F(5) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(7) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{407} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(9) + F(4)) & = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{408} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(1) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(5) \times T(3) + T(1) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(6) + F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(1) + T(4) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{409} & := (F(9) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) + F(7) & = T(9) + (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(7) + F(2)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) & = T(4) \times T(7) + T(2) \times T(8) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(8) + F(6)) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = T(4) \times T(8) + T(6) \times T(1) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{411} & := F(8) \times F(5) + (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = T(8) + T(5) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{414} & := F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(4) + F(6) \times F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(7) + T(4) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{416} & := (F(4) \times (F(6) + F(2)) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(6) \times (T(2) + T(5)) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{417} & := (F(9) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) + F(8) & = T(9) + (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{420} & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = (T(2) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5)) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(3) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times F(1) \times (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = (T(5) \times (T(1) + T(2))) + (T(4) \times T(8)) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = T(5) + (((T(2) + T(3)) \times T(1)) \times T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(3) \times ((T(5) + T(6)) + T(7))) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = ((T(4) + T(3)) \times T(6)) + (T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(5) \times ((T(1) + T(2)) + T(6))) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(8) \times F(5) + F(1) + F(9)) & = (((T(4) \times T(8)) + T(5)) \times T(1)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{423} & := (F(3) \times F(7) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(8) + T(2)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{424} & := (F(5) + F(8)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) + F(6) & = T(5) + T(8) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{426} & := (F(3) \times F(9) + F(4)) \times (F(1) + F(5)) & = T(3) \times (T(9) + T(4) + T(1) + T(5)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(4) \times F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(5) + T(6)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{429} & := ((F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) \times (T(8) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(6) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = T(3) + T(6) \times (T(2) + T(5)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(9) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(4)) + F(8) & = T(9) + T(2) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{430} & := F(5) \times (F(7) \times (F(4) + F(2)) + F(9)) & = T(5) + T(7) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 432 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + F(5) + F(8)) \times F(6) & = T(3) \times T(1) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(6)) \\
 433 & := F(2) + (F(5) + F(7)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 435 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times (F(8) + F(6)) & = T(2) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 441 & := (F(1) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) \times T(3) + T(6)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5) + F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times T(5) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 & := ((F(2) + F(6)) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(6) + T(3)) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(5) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(5) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(6) + F(5) \times F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(6) + F(5) \times F(8) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(6) + T(5)) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 442 & := (F(2) \times F(5) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(6) + F(4)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(6) + T(4) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(1) + (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 444 & := F(1) + F(2) + (F(5) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(2) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 445 & := F(1) + F(4) + F(8) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(8) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 447 & := F(5) + F(3) + F(6) \times (F(9) + F(8)) & = (T(5) + (T(3) \times (T(6) + T(9)))) + T(8) \\
 \\
 448 & := F(1) + F(4) + F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(6) \times (F(5) \times F(4) + F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(6) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 449 & := F(1) + F(4) \times F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 450 & := F(3) + F(6) \times (F(2) + F(9) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(2) + T(9)) + T(8) \\
 451 & := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(3)) + F(7) \times F(9) & = T(4) + T(2) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 453 & := F(1) + F(5) \times F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 454 & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 456 & := (F(3) \times F(8) + F(4) \times F(5)) \times F(6) & = (T(3) + T(8)) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(3) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(5) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 457 & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(7) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(2) + T(9)) \\
 459 & := F(1) + F(7) \times F(9) + F(3) \times F(6) & = (T(1) \times T(7) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(6) \\
 \\
 460 & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(6) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(3) + F(8)) \times (F(1) + F(4)) & = T(5) \times T(3) + (T(8) + T(1)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 462 & := ((F(3) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(4) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(1) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times T(6) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$463 := F(4) \times (F(5) + F(3)) + F(7) \times F(9) = T(4) + T(5) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9))$$

$$465 := (F(1) + F(9)) \times F(7) + F(3) + F(6) = (T(1) + T(9) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(6)$$

$$:= F(2) + (F(7) + F(4)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) = T(2) \times T(7) + T(4) \times T(8) + T(6)$$

$$468 := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) = (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(5) \times T(7)$$

$$:= (F(4) \times F(6) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) = T(4) \times T(6) + T(3) \times (T(5) + T(7))$$

$$:= (F(5) + F(6)) \times F(2) \times (F(3) + F(9)) = T(5) \times T(6) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(9))$$

$$469 := F(2) + F(7) \times (F(5) \times F(4) + F(8)) = T(2) + (T(7) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(8)$$

$$471 := F(1) + F(3) \times F(5) \times (F(7) + F(9)) = T(1) \times T(3) + T(5) \times T(7) + T(9)$$

$$:= F(2) + (F(7) + F(9)) \times F(3) \times F(5) = (T(2) + T(7) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(5)$$

$$472 := F(3) \times (F(1) + F(5) \times (F(7) + F(9))) = T(3) + T(1) + T(5) \times T(7) + T(9)$$

$$474 := F(2) + F(5) + F(7) \times (F(3) + F(9)) = T(2) + T(5) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(9)$$

$$477 := F(2) + F(7) \times (F(9) + F(3)) + F(6) = (T(2) + T(7) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(6)$$

$$477 := F(1) + (F(6) + F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(9) = T(1) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(4) \times T(9)$$

$$478 := F(6) + F(3) \times F(5) \times (F(7) + F(9)) = (T(6) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(7) + T(9)$$

$$480 := (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(9) + F(2) + F(7)) = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + T(2) \times T(7)$$

$$481 := (F(1) \times F(2)) \times F(7) \times (F(4) + F(9)) = T(1) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(4) \times T(9)$$

$$:= (F(8) + F(4) \times F(5) + F(1)) \times F(7) = T(8) + T(4) + T(5) \times (T(1) + T(7))$$

$$:= F(7) \times (F(5) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6)) = (T(7) + T(5) + T(2)) \times T(4) + T(6)$$

$$482 := F(1) \times F(2) + F(7) \times (F(4) + F(9)) = T(1) + T(2) + T(7) + T(4) \times T(9)$$

$$483 := F(3) + F(5) + (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(9) = T(3) \times (T(5) \times T(2) + T(7)) + T(9)$$

$$484 := F(1) + F(3) + F(7) \times (F(4) + F(9)) = T(1) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(4) \times T(9)$$

$$486 := F(3) \times F(5) + (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(9) = T(3) + T(5) \times (T(1) + T(7)) + T(9)$$

$$487 := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(7) \times F(9) = T(1) + T(6) + T(5) \times T(7) + T(9)$$

$$489 := F(5) + (F(7) + F(2)) \times F(9) + F(6) = T(5) \times T(7) + T(2) + T(9) + T(6)$$

$$:= F(5) + F(8) \times F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) = T(5) + T(8) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9))$$

$$492 := (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(7) \times F(9) = T(3) + T(6) + T(5) \times T(7) + T(9)$$

$$495 := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(8) + F(9)) = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(3) + T(8)) + T(9)$$

$$:= F(5) \times (F(3) + F(9) + F(4) \times F(8)) = T(5) \times T(3) + T(9) + T(4) \times T(8)$$

$$496 := (F(4) \times F(5) + F(7) + F(9)) \times F(6) = T(4) \times (T(5) + T(7)) + T(9) + T(6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(3) + (F(2) + F(4) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times T(2) + T(4) \times T(9) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{500} & := (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(9) + F(4) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(7) + T(9) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{502} & := (F(2) + F(4) + F(9)) \times F(7) + F(6) & = T(2) + T(4) \times T(9) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := F(5) + (F(7) + F(1)) \times F(9) + F(8) & = T(5) \times T(7) + T(1) + T(9) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{504} & := F(2) \times F(6) \times (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times ((T(6) + T(1)) \times T(3) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{504} & := (F(2) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(2) + (T(6) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(8) & = (T(4) \times T(5) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{507} & := F(1) + F(3) + F(6) \times F(4) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(6) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(7) \times (F(5) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(2)) & = (T(7) + T(5) + T(6) \times T(3)) \times T(2) \\
 \mathbf{508} & := F(7) \times (F(5) + F(6)) \times F(4) + F(1) & = T(7) + T(5) \times (T(6) + T(4) + T(1)) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(4) \times F(7)) \times (F(6) + F(5)) & = T(2) + T(4) \times (T(7) + T(6)) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{510} & := (F(1) \times F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := ((F(5) + F(2)) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(5) + (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(3)) \times F(9) & = (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{511} & := F(2) + F(4) \times (F(8) + F(7)) \times F(5) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(8) + T(7) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{513} & := (F(3) + F(8) + F(9)) \times (F(1) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times (T(8) + T(9) + T(1)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(1) + F(9) \times F(5)) & = T(2) + (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(9) + T(5) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(5) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times T(5)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) + F(7) \times (F(9) + F(5)) & = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(7) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{514} & := F(4) + F(2) + F(9) \times (F(3) + F(7)) & = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(9)) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{515} & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(9)) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(1) + T(4) \times T(9) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{516} & := (F(3) + F(5) \times F(9)) \times F(1) \times F(4) & = T(3) + T(5) + T(9) \times (T(1) + T(4)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(5) \times F(7) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(5) + F(2) + (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(9) & = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(7)) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{517} & := (F(2) \times F(4)) \times F(8) \times F(6) + F(7) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(8) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(8) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) & = T(8) \times T(3) + T(7) \times T(4) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$518 := (F(4) \times F(1) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) = T(4) \times (T(1) + T(9) + T(2)) + T(7)$$

$$519 := F(3) + (F(7) + F(9)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9) + T(4)) + T(6)$$

$$520 := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times F(3) \times F(7) = T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) \times (T(3) + T(7))$$

$$:= (F(1) + F(4) + F(2)) \times F(6) \times F(7) = T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(7))$$

$$:= F(3) \times (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) \times F(7) = T(3) + T(4) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(7)$$

$$:= (F(4) + F(3) \times F(6) + F(8)) \times F(7) = T(4) + T(3) \times (T(6) + T(8) + T(7))$$

$$522 := (F(2) \times F(7) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(8)) = (T(2) + T(7)) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(8)$$

$$523 := F(2) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times F(9) + F(7) = T(2) \times T(4) \times T(5) + T(9) + T(7)$$

$$525 := ((F(1) + F(3)) \times F(9) + F(4)) \times F(5) = (T(1) \times T(3) + T(9)) \times T(4) + T(5)$$

$$:= ((F(6) \times F(1)) \times F(4) + F(2)) \times F(8) = T(6) + (T(1) + T(4) + T(2)) \times T(8)$$

$$:= (F(1) \times F(5)) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(9)) = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) \times T(2) + T(9)$$

$$525 := (F(1) \times F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(7) \times F(6)) = (T(1) \times T(5) + T(2)) \times T(7) + T(6)$$

$$:= F(5) + F(7) \times (F(3) \times F(4) + F(9)) = T(5) \times T(7) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(9)$$

$$526 := F(1) + (F(6) \times F(7) + F(2)) \times F(5) = T(1) + T(6) + T(7) \times (T(2) + T(5))$$

$$:= F(1) + F(5) \times F(8) \times (F(4) + F(3)) = (T(1) + T(5) + T(8)) \times T(4) + T(3)$$

$$528 := F(6) + (F(2) + F(9) + F(5)) \times F(7) = T(6) \times T(2) + T(9) + T(5) \times T(7)$$

$$531 := (F(2) \times F(4)) \times F(5) \times F(9) + F(8) = T(2) \times T(4) \times T(5) + T(9) + T(8)$$

$$:= F(5) \times (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(9) + F(8) = T(5) \times T(2) + T(3) \times (T(9) + T(8))$$

$$:= F(1) + F(5) \times (F(3) + F(7) \times F(6)) = T(1) \times T(5) \times (T(3) + T(7)) + T(6)$$

$$:= F(2) + F(5) \times (F(7) \times F(6) + F(3)) = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(3)$$

$$532 := F(2) + F(8) + F(9) \times (F(3) + F(7)) = (T(2) + T(8) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(7)$$

$$534 := (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(9) + F(4) + F(8) = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9) + T(4)) + T(8)$$

$$:= (F(3) + (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(6)) \times F(4) = (T(3) + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(6) \times T(4)$$

$$:= F(1) + (F(7) \times ((F(5) + F(9)) + F(3))) = (T(1) + T(7) + T(5) + T(9)) \times T(3)$$

$$535 := (F(4) \times (F(1) + F(9)) + F(3)) \times F(5) = T(4) \times (T(1) + T(9) + T(3)) + T(5)$$

$$:= F(2) \times F(5) \times (F(4) + F(6) \times F(7)) = T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) \times (T(6) + T(7))$$

$$538 := F(7) + F(5) \times (F(9) + F(1)) \times F(4) = T(7) + T(5) + T(9) \times (T(1) + T(4))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 540 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(9) + F(3)) \times F(5) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(9) + F(2)) \times F(5) & = (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(9) + T(2) \times T(5) \\
 541 & := F(1) + F(4) \times (F(9) + F(3)) \times F(5) & = T(1) + T(4) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 543 & := (F(2) + F(5) \times (F(3) + F(9))) \times F(4) & = T(2) + T(5) \times T(3) + T(9) \times T(4) \\
 544 & := F(1) \times F(9) \times (F(4) \times F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(9)) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(7)) & = T(3) + T(4) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 546 & := (F(1) \times F(2)) \times F(7) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(2) \times T(7)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(6) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(5) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(5) \times F(6) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2) + F(5) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(9) + T(7)) \\
 & := ((F(5) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(4) + T(6)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(3) + F(6) \times F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(6) + T(5) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(9) + F(2)) + F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(5) \times (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = (T(2) \times T(5) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(4) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5)) + T(4) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(4) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 547 & := F(1) + (F(3) + F(6) \times F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(5) \times T(7) \\
 549 & := F(2) \times F(5) + F(3) \times F(6) \times F(9) & = (T(2) + T(5) + T(3)) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times F(2) + (F(7) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(5) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(4) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(8) \times F(6) + F(3) + F(7)) & = T(4) \times T(8) + T(6) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(8) + (F(2) + F(5) \times F(7)) \times F(6) & = T(8) \times T(2) + T(5) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 550 & := F(4) + F(2) + F(7) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = T(4) + T(2) \times T(7) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 553 & := (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(4) \times F(5) + F(7) & = (T(3) + T(9)) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7) \times F(8)) + F(5) & = (T(3) + T(1)) \times (T(7) + T(8) + T(5)) \\
 555 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(9) \\
 & := ((F(3) + F(2)) \times F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = (T(3) + T(2) \times T(5)) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(9)) & = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(4)) + T(9) \\
 556 & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(5) \times F(8) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(4) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(9) \\
 559 & := (F(4) + F(9) + F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(4) + T(9) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(5) + F(6) + F(7) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = T(5) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(9) + F(4) \times (F(2) + F(3))) \times F(7) & = T(9) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(3) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{560} & := (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(1) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(7)) \times (F(4) \times F(3) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{561} & := (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(4) \times F(5) + F(8) & = (T(3) + T(9)) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{564} & := (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(5) + (T(2) \times T(3)) \times T(7) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{565} & := (F(1) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(6) + F(7) & = T(1) + T(3) \times (T(9) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(9) \times (F(4) \times F(5) + F(1)) + F(8) & = T(9) + T(4) \times (T(5) + T(1) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(5) + (F(7) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = (T(5) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{567} & := (F(1) + F(3) \times (F(6) + F(5))) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(5) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(5) + (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(3)) \times F(8) & = (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(5) + F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(8) + F(6)) & = T(5) \times (T(3) + T(7)) + T(8) + T(6) \\
 & := F(8) \times (F(3) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(6)) & = (T(8) + T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(4)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{568} & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{570} & := F(3) \times F(7) \times F(8) + F(4) \times F(6) & = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(8) + T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(7) + F(6) \times F(9)) & = T(2) \times T(3) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(1) \times (F(7) + F(6) \times F(9)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(7) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(3) \times F(7) + F(2)) \times F(8) & = (T(4) + T(3) \times T(7)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{572} & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(8) + F(5) & = T(1) + T(6) + T(4) + T(8) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{573} & := F(4) \times F(8) + (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times T(8) + T(7) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(9) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(9) + T(3)) + T(5) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(9) \times F(5) \times F(2) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(9) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{576} & := (F(2) + F(9) + F(1)) \times F(3) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(9) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(6)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(9) \times F(3)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(6) & = T(3) \times T(1) + T(4) \times (T(8) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(5) \times F(4) + F(1)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = T(5) + (T(4) + T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(6) \times (F(5) \times F(4) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(5)) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + (F(7) + F(2)) \times F(5)) \times F(6) & = (T(3) + T(7) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(2) + F(4) + F(9) \times F(3)) & = (T(6) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(9)) \times T(3) \\
 \mathbf{577} & := F(5) + (F(8) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(7) & = T(5) \times T(8) + T(2) + T(3) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 579 &:= F(2) + (F(7) + F(1) + F(4)) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times T(7) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(9) \\
 580 &:= F(3) + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(2) + F(7)) &= T(3) \times T(9) + T(4) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 582 &:= F(4) \times (F(5) + (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(8)) &= (T(4) + T(5) + T(1)) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 584 &:= (F(9) + (F(4) \times F(1)) \times F(7)) \times F(6) &= T(9) + (T(4) + T(1)) \times (T(7) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 585 &:= (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(7) \times (F(4) + F(3)) &= T(6) + (T(2) \times T(7) + T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(3) \times (F(1) + F(8))) \times F(7) &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(8) + T(7)) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(3) \times F(9) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(9) + T(5) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 586 &:= (F(4) + F(7) \times F(8)) \times F(3) + F(9) &= T(4) \times T(7) + T(8) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(8) + F(9) \times (F(5) + F(4))) &= T(3) \times (T(8) + T(9) + T(5)) + T(4) \\
 \\
 588 &:= (F(6) \times F(9) + F(8) + F(1)) \times F(3) &= T(6) + (T(9) + T(8)) \times (T(1) + T(3)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(3)) + T(5) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) + F(4) &= T(3) \times (T(7) + T(5) + T(9) + T(4)) \\
 \\
 594 &:= F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(8) + F(4) \times F(6)) &= T(3) \times (T(7) + T(8)) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6) \times (F(4) + F(9))) &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6)) + T(4) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 595 &:= (F(1) + F(9)) \times (F(6) \times F(3) + F(2)) &= T(1) + (T(9) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(2)) \\
 \\
 598 &:= ((F(4) + F(3)) \times F(5) + F(8)) \times F(7) &= T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(8)) \times F(7) &= T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(6) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(8) + F(4) \times F(6)) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times T(8) + T(4) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 600 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(9)) &= (T(3) + T(7) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 608 &:= F(1) \times F(6) \times (F(8) \times F(4) + F(7)) &= (T(1) + T(6) + T(8)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 609 &:= ((F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(3) + T(2) \times T(6) + T(5) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(5) \times F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(2) + T(5) \times (T(4) + T(7)) + T(8) \\
 \\
 612 &:= F(4) \times (F(9) + F(3) + F(6) \times F(8)) &= T(4) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 \\
 613 &:= F(1) + F(9) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5)) &= (T(1) + T(9)) \times (T(4) + T(2)) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(3) + (F(9) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times T(9) + T(5) \times T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(5) + F(6) \times (F(8) \times F(4) + F(7)) &= T(5) + (T(6) + T(8)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 615 &:= F(1) \times F(4) + (F(7) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= (T(1) \times T(4) + T(7)) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(9) \times (F(1) + F(5))) \times F(4) &= T(2) \times (T(9) + (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(2) + F(5) \times F(6)) &= T(3) \times (T(7) \times T(2) + T(5)) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(4) + (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times T(6) + (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(8) \times F(2) + F(4) \times F(9)) & = T(5) \times T(8) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{616} & := F(1) + F(4) + (F(7) + F(5)) \times F(9) & = T(1) + (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(8) + F(1) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(6) + T(8)) + T(1) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{618} & := (F(3) + (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(9)) \times F(4) & = T(3) \times T(2) + (T(5) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 \mathbf{619} & := F(3) \times (F(9) + F(7) \times F(8)) + F(5) & = T(3) + T(9) + T(7) + T(8) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{624} & := (F(2) + F(4) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(6) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(4) + F(6) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(6) + T(9) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(8) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(8) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(6) \times F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(6) \times (T(2) + T(4) + T(5)) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{625} & := F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(8) + F(6) \times F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(8) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(8) + F(6) \times F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(8) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + F(7) \times F(6) \times F(3) \times F(4) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{627} & := F(4) + (F(5) + F(9)) \times F(3) \times F(6) & = T(4) \times (T(5) + T(9)) + T(3) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{630} & := (F(2) \times F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(4) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(7)) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times ((T(1) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3) \times F(6) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(9) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(6) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(1) \times (T(5) + T(2) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times (T(3) \times T(2) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times ((F(9) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(4)) & = T(3) \times T(9) + (T(5) + T(6)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{631} & := F(1) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{632} & := (F(3) \times F(4) \times F(7) + F(1)) \times F(6) & = T(3) + T(4) + T(7) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{633} & := ((F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) + F(1)) \times F(4) & = T(3) + (T(6) + T(8)) \times (T(1) + T(4)) \\
 & := (F(2) + (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8)) \times F(4) & = T(2) + (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(9))) & = (T(4) + T(2) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{634} & := F(3) \times (F(5) + F(7) \times (F(4) + F(8))) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{636} & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(1) + F(5) \times F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(4) + (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(7) \times F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) & = T(3) \times (T(7) + T(6) \times T(2) + T(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) \times F(8) + F(5) \times F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{637} & := ((F(1) + F(8)) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(8) \times T(3) + T(5) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{638} & := F(1) + (F(9) + F(5) \times F(4)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(9) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{639} & := (F(4) + F(9) \times F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = T(4) \times T(9) + (T(3) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{640} & := F(1) \times F(6) \times (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(4) + T(7) \times T(5) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(4) \times F(8)) \times F(3) \times F(5) & = T(1) \times T(4) + (T(8) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) \times F(5) \times (F(4) + F(7)) & = (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(4) \times F(8) + F(1)) \times (F(3) + F(6)) & = T(4) \times (T(8) + T(1) + T(3) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(6) \times (F(2) + F(7) \times F(4)) & = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(2) \times T(7)) + T(4) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(6) + F(7) \times (F(4) + F(8))) & = T(3) + T(6) \times T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{641} & := F(1) + (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(5) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(4) \times (T(7) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{645} & := F(4) \times (F(3) \times F(8) + F(2)) \times F(5) & = T(4) \times T(3) + (T(8) + T(2)) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times ((F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) + F(5)) & = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(1) + (F(7) + F(4)) \times F(6)) & = T(5) \times (T(1) + T(7)) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(8) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9))) & = T(5) \times T(8) + T(4) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{646} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(7) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(7) + T(4) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{648} & := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times F(6) & = T(4) \times T(1) \times T(3) + T(7) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{651} & := ((F(5) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(4) + T(7)) + T(8) \\
 & := ((F(5) \times F(1)) + (F(7) \times F(3))) \times F(8) & = T(5) \times (T(1) + T(7)) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(1) + F(7) \times (F(6) + F(3) \times F(8)) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(6) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(6) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{652} & := F(1) + (F(5) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(5) + T(3)) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{658} & := (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(7) \times F(3) + F(9) & = T(4) \times T(8) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(3) \times F(8)) & = T(1) \times T(7) + T(5) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{660} & := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(3) \times F(5) & = T(4) \times T(2) + (T(8) + T(3)) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(2) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{663} & := (F(4) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(6)) \times F(7) & = (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(6) \times T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 666 &:= (F(1) + F(6)) \times (F(9) + F(4)) \times F(3) &= (T(1) \times T(6) + T(9)) \times T(4) + T(3) \\
 &:= (F(3) \times F(5) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) &= T(3) \times (T(5) + T(6)) + T(4) \times T(9) \\
 669 &:= (F(9) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) + F(8) &= T(9) + (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 672 &:= F(3) \times F(8) \times (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(6) &= (T(3) \times T(8) + T(1)) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 &:= (F(5) + F(7) \times F(3) + F(1)) \times F(8) &= T(5) \times T(7) + (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(8) \\
 676 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) \times F(7) &= (T(1) \times T(2) + T(5)) \times T(8) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(3) \times (F(6) + F(2)) + F(9)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times (T(6) \times T(2) + T(9)) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(7) \times (F(6) + F(5)) &= T(4) + (T(2) + T(7)) \times T(6) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(3) + (F(6) \times F(4)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= T(3) \times T(6) + T(4) + T(5) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(4) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(6) \times F(8)) &= T(4) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(6)) + T(8) \\
 682 &:= (F(3) \times F(7) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &= T(3) + T(7) + (T(5) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 684 &:= (F(2) + F(5) + F(7)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(7) \times T(3) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(9) + F(3) \times F(8)) &= (T(2) \times T(6) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 688 &:= (F(1) + F(6) + F(9)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) &= (T(1) \times T(6) + T(9)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 690 &:= F(5) \times (F(3) + F(9) \times (F(2) + F(4))) &= (T(5) + T(3) + T(9) + T(2)) \times T(4) \\
 693 &:= F(4) \times (F(1) + F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= (T(4) + T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 702 &:= (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(9)) &= T(1) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 705 &:= F(5) \times F(4) \times (F(7) \times F(2) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(4) + T(7)) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 706 &:= F(9) + F(6) \times (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(8) &= (T(9) + T(6) + T(1)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 712 &:= ((F(1) + F(4)) \times F(8) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(1) + (T(4) + T(8)) \times T(5) + T(6) \\
 714 &:= (F(1) \times F(4) + F(7) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= T(1) + T(4) + T(7) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (F(2) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(5) + F(3) \times F(6) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(5) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 718 &:= F(4) + F(2) + F(9) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(9) + T(6)) + T(7) \\
 720 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(9) \times F(8) + F(5) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(9) + T(8) \times T(5) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times (F(3) + F(9)) &= T(2) \times T(4) \times T(5) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(3) \times (T(7) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(3) + F(7) + F(4)) \times F(6) &= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(7)) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 721 &:= F(2) + F(5) + (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(7) &= (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(8) + T(9) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 722 &:= F(1) \times F(4) + F(5) + F(9) \times F(8) &= T(1) + T(4) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 726 &:= F(4) + F(2) + F(6) + F(9) \times F(8) &= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(9)) + T(8) \\
 727 &:= F(4) + F(3) \times F(5) + F(9) \times F(8) &= T(4) + T(3) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 \\
 729 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) + F(9) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(5) + F(3)) \times F(7) \times F(6) &= T(1) \times T(5) + (T(3) + T(7)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 735 &:= F(4) \times (F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= T(4) \times T(3) + T(5) \times T(1) \times T(9) \\
 738 &:= F(2) + F(3) + F(8) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(8) + T(1) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 741 &:= ((F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(2)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times T(5) + T(6) \times (T(2) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (F(1) + (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6)) \times F(7) &= T(1) \times T(3) + T(5) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 744 &:= F(4) \times (F(5) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times F(6) &= T(4) \times T(5) + T(3) + T(7) \times T(6) \\
 &:= F(3) \times ((F(5) + F(8)) \times F(7) + F(9)) &= T(3) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 745 &:= ((F(1) + F(4)) \times F(9) + F(7)) \times F(5) &= T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(9) + T(7)) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(7) + F(5) + F(9) \times F(8) &= T(3) + T(7) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 \\
 748 &:= ((F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(7)) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(4) + F(5) + F(7)) \times F(9) &= T(2) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(9) \times (F(4) \times (F(3) + F(1)) + F(7)) &= T(9) \times (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(1) + T(7) \\
 \\
 750 &:= F(5) \times (F(3) \times F(6) + F(9)) \times F(4) &= T(5) \times T(3) + (T(6) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 &:= F(5) \times F(4) + F(8) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(4) + T(8) + T(1)) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(9) \times (F(6) + F(4))) &= (T(3) + T(2) + T(9) + T(6)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 751 &:= F(4) + F(9) \times (F(1) + F(7) + F(6)) &= T(4) \times (T(9) \times T(1) + T(7)) + T(6) \\
 753 &:= F(3) + F(4) + (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(9) &= T(3) \times (T(4) + T(2) \times T(8)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 754 &:= (F(1) \times F(4) \times F(6) + F(9)) \times F(7) &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(2) \times F(6) \times F(4) + F(9)) \times F(7) &= T(2) + T(6) + T(4) \times (T(9) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 756 &:= ((F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(5) \times (T(3) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 759 &:= F(2) \times F(4) + (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= T(2) + (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 \\
 760 &:= (F(1) + (F(9) + F(7)) \times F(3)) \times F(6) &= T(1) + T(9) + (T(7) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (F(6) + F(3)) \times (F(7) + F(4) \times F(8)) &= T(6) \times (T(3) + T(7)) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 762 &:= F(1) + F(5) + (F(9) + F(3)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(9) + T(3) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(5) + F(2) + (F(9) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(9)) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{763} & := F(3) + (F(1) + F(8)) \times F(9) + F(7) & = (T(3) + T(1)) \times (T(8) + T(9) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{766} & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(7) + F(9) \times F(8) & = (T(1) \times T(4)) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{767} & := (F(1) + F(8) + F(4) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(8) + T(4) \times (T(9) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{768} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(6) & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(7) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{771} & := F(5) \times F(4) + (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(8) & = T(5) + (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{772} & := F(4) + F(7) + (F(9) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{774} & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(7) \times F(5) + F(8)) & = T(2) + (T(6) + T(7)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{777} & := (F(2) + (F(5) + F(7)) \times F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{780} & := F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{783} & := F(1) \times F(2) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(9) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{784} & := F(1) + F(2) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(8) \times F(9) + F(5) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = T(8) + T(9) \times (T(5) + T(1)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{793} & := ((F(2) + F(6)) \times F(4) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(4) \times (T(9) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{798} & := F(4) + (F(8) + F(3)) \times F(9) + F(7) & = T(4) \times T(8) + T(3) \times (T(9) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{800} & := (F(3) \times F(8) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) & = T(3) + T(8) \times T(6) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{805} & := (F(4) \times F(9) + F(7)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) & = T(4) \times (T(9) + T(7) + T(3)) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{810} & := F(5) + (F(8) + F(3)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times T(8) + T(3) \times T(1) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{814} & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(8)) \times (F(9) + F(4)) & = T(1) + T(2) + (T(8) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{816} & := (F(3) + F(2) + F(6) + F(7)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(4) + F(9)) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(3) + T(4) \times (T(9) \times T(1) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(9) \times (F(6) + (F(5) + F(4)) \times F(3)) & = (T(9) + T(6) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{819} & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(8) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) + T(6) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(8) + F(5) \times F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(6) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(9) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(4) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(7) \times (F(5) + F(3) \times F(6)) & = (T(4) + T(7)) \times (T(5) + T(3)) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{822} & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(8) \times F(7)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(2) \times T(8) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(5) \times F(6) + (F(8) + F(3)) \times F(9) & = T(5) + T(6) \times T(8) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{825} & := F(1) \times F(5) \times F(4) \times (F(8) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(5) + T(4) \times (T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) + F(8) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(3) + T(4) + T(8)) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times F(4) \times (F(8) \times F(2) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times (T(4) + T(8)) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(5) + F(2) + F(7) \times F(4) \times F(8) & = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(7)) + T(4) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 826 & := F(3) + F(5) + F(8) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = T(3) + T(5) \times T(8) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + F(5) \times F(4) \times (F(8) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(5) + T(4) \times (T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(8) \times F(7) + F(3)) \times F(4) & = (T(2) \times T(8) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(4) \\
 \\
 828 & := (F(2) + F(5) \times (F(8) + F(9))) \times F(4) & = T(2) + T(5) + (T(8) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(6) + F(9)) \times F(4) & = T(3) \times T(7) + (T(6) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 829 & := F(9) \times (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(6) + F(7) & = T(9) + (T(1) + T(3) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 830 & := F(4) \times (F(7) \times F(8) + F(1)) + F(6) & = T(4) + T(7) + T(8) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 831 & := (F(3) + F(5) \times (F(8) + F(9))) \times F(4) & = T(3) + T(5) + (T(8) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 832 & := (F(2) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) \times F(7) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6) + F(8) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(6) \times T(8) + T(9) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) \times F(8)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(8) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(6) \times F(7) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 833 & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(4) \times F(8)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(8) + T(7)) \\
 835 & := F(4) + F(7) + F(8) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(7) + T(8) + T(5)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 840 & := ((F(1) + F(3)) \times F(7) + F(2)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(7) \times T(2) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(8) + T(2) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(3) \times (F(4) + F(7)) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(3) + (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(9) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(9) + T(6) + T(5)) \\
 & := (F(4) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(9)) \times F(6) & = T(4) \times (T(2) \times T(3) + T(9) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 841 & := F(1) + (F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(4) \times (T(8) + T(2) + T(9)) \\
 844 & := F(2) + F(8) \times F(6) \times F(5) + F(4) & = (T(2) + T(8)) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(4) \\
 845 & := (F(2) + F(4) \times F(8) + F(1)) \times F(7) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(8) + T(1) + T(7)) \\
 846 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = (T(3) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 847 & := (F(1) + F(6) \times F(8)) \times F(5) + F(3) & = T(1) + T(6) \times T(8) + T(5) \times T(3) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(8) \times F(6)) \times F(5) + F(3) & = T(1) + T(8) \times T(6) + T(5) \times T(3) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) \times (F(6) \times F(8) + F(1)) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(6) \times T(8) + T(1) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) \times (F(8) \times F(6) + F(1)) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(8) \times T(6) + T(1) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) \times (F(1) + F(6) \times F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(1) + T(6) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) \times (F(1) + F(8) \times F(6)) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(1) + T(8) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 850 & := (F(4) + F(8) + F(1)) \times F(2) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times (T(8) + T(1) + T(2) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5) + T(7) + T(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(1) + F(4) \times F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) = (T(1) \times T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{855} & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(5) \times F(9)) = (T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(2) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(5) + (F(2) + F(8) + F(4)) \times F(9) = (T(5) \times T(2) + T(8)) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{856} & := (F(4) \times F(7) + F(9) \times F(3)) \times F(6) = T(4) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{858} & := F(4) \times (F(6) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) = T(4) \times T(6) + (T(5) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{861} & := (F(2) \times F(3) + F(9) + F(5)) \times F(8) = T(2) \times T(3) \times T(9) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(8)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) + F(4) = T(1) \times T(8) + T(5) \times (T(9) + T(4)) \\
 & := F(8) + (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(4) \times F(6) = (T(8) + T(2) + T(9)) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{864} & := F(2) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times (F(9) + F(3)) = (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(9)) + T(3) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3) + F(5) \times F(8)) \times F(6) = T(2) + T(3) + T(5) \times (T(8) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(7) \times (F(2) + F(8))) \times F(4) = T(3) \times T(7) \times T(2) + T(8) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(8) + F(3) + F(7)) \times F(6) = (T(4) + T(8)) \times T(3) + T(7) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{865} & := F(1) + (F(4) + F(5) \times F(8)) \times F(6) = T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) \times (T(8) + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{873} & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(4) \times F(8) + F(9)) = T(2) \times T(6) + T(4) \times (T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{879} & := (F(2) + F(8) \times F(6)) \times F(5) + F(9) = (T(2) + T(8)) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{880} & := F(1) \times F(5) \times F(6) \times (F(2) + F(8)) = T(1) + T(5) + (T(6) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(8) + F(2)) \times F(6) = T(3) + T(4) + T(8) \times (T(2) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(4) \times F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(1) + F(8)) = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(9) + T(1) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{882} & := (F(2) + F(4) \times F(7) + F(3)) \times F(8) = T(2) \times T(4) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5) \times F(1) \times F(6)) \times F(8) = T(3) \times T(5) + (T(1) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{886} & := F(3) + F(7) \times (F(5) + F(4) \times F(8)) = (T(3) + T(7)) \times (T(5) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{891} & := F(2) + (F(4) + F(7) \times F(9)) \times F(3) = T(2) \times T(4) \times T(7) + T(9) + T(3) \\
 \mathbf{897} & := (F(1) \times F(8) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) = (T(1) + T(8)) \times T(3) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(7) \times (F(1) + F(3) \times F(9)) = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(1) + T(3) \times T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{900} & := (F(4) + F(2) + F(8)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(8) + T(3) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4) \times F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) = T(2) \times T(4) \times T(6) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(6) \times F(2) + F(7) \times F(9)) = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{903} & := F(2) \times F(8) \times (F(1) + F(6) + F(9)) = (T(2) + T(8)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 910 &:= (F(5) + F(3) + F(8) \times F(4)) \times F(7) &= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(8)) + T(4) \times T(7) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(4) \times (F(3) + F(8))) \times F(7) &= (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(3) + T(8) + T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$912 := (F(2) + F(7) \times (F(1) + F(9))) \times F(3) = T(2) \times (T(7) + (T(1) + T(9)) \times T(3))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 918 &:= (F(2) + (F(5) + F(6)) \times F(3)) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6) + T(3) \times T(9)) \\ &:= F(9) \times (F(4) \times F(3) + F(7) + F(6)) &= (T(9) + T(4)) \times T(3) + T(7) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 921 &:= F(4) \times F(6) \times F(9) + F(5) \times F(8) &= T(4) \times T(6) + T(9) \times T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(7) \times F(8) + F(9)) &= T(2) \times T(4) \times T(7) + T(8) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 924 &:= (F(2) + F(6) \times F(5) + F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(2) + T(6) + (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times T(1) \times T(7) + T(6) \times T(8) \\ &:= F(2) + F(7) \times (F(4) + F(3) \times F(9)) &= T(2) \times (T(7) + T(4) + T(3) \times T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 936 &:= (F(2) \times F(5) + F(9)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= (T(2) \times T(5) + T(9)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(8) + F(1)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) &= T(3) \times T(8) + (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(9) \\ &:= (F(5) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(3) + F(8)) &= T(5) \times (T(9) + T(2)) + T(3) \times T(8) \\ &:= F(6) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) &= T(6) \times T(3) + (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$937 := (F(9) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) + F(7) = T(9) + (T(6) + T(2)) \times T(8) + T(7)$$

$$945 := (F(9) + F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(8) = T(9) \times (T(2) + T(3)) + T(5) \times T(8)$$

$$946 := (F(1) + F(8)) \times (F(4) + F(5) \times F(6)) = (T(1) + T(8)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(6)$$

$$955 := F(3) \times F(9) \times (F(7) + F(2)) + F(4) = T(3) + (T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(4))$$

$$957 := F(4) \times (F(7) + (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(9)) = (T(4) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(6)) + T(9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 960 &:= (F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(1) + F(5) + F(9)) &= T(4) \times (T(8) \times T(1) + T(5) + T(9)) \\ &:= (F(5) \times F(6)) \times (F(1) + F(3) + F(8)) &= T(5) \times (T(6) + T(1) + T(3) + T(8)) \\ &:= (F(5) \times F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(3) + F(8)) &= T(5) + T(6) \times (T(2) + T(3) + T(8)) \\ &:= (F(6) \times F(3)) \times ((F(4) \times F(7)) + F(8)) &= T(6) \times (T(3) + T(4) + T(7)) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$963 := F(2) + (F(4) + F(9)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) = T(2) + T(4) \times (T(9) + T(5) + T(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 966 &:= (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(8)) &= T(2) \times (T(7) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(8)) \\ &:= (F(4) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(6)) \times F(8) &= T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5)) + T(6) \times T(8) \\ &:= (F(2) + (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(7) \times T(4) + T(8)) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(8)) \times ((F(5) + F(9)) + F(4)) &= T(3) + (T(8) + T(5) + T(9)) \times T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$973 := F(9) \times (F(7) + F(4) \times F(5)) + F(8) = T(9) + T(7) + (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(8)$$

$$984 := (F(2) + F(5) \times F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) = T(2) + T(5) + T(6) \times (T(4) + T(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 987 &:= ((F(2) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(3)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(6) \times T(5) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(5) \times (F(1) + F(6)) + F(3)) \times F(8) &= T(5) \times T(1) + (T(6) + T(3)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 988 &:= (F(4) + F(3) \times F(9) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(9) + T(5)) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(3) + (F(8) + F(6)) \times F(9) &= T(1) + T(3) + T(8) + T(6) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(7) \times (F(2) + F(9) + F(4)) &= T(3) \times (T(7) + T(2) \times T(9)) + T(4) \\
 &:= F(2) + (F(6) + F(4) \times F(7)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(6) + T(4)) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 989 &:= F(4) + (F(7) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(9) &= T(4) + T(7) + T(3) + T(6) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 990 &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(4) &= T(1) \times T(5) \times T(8) + T(9) \times T(4) \\
 &:= (F(5) \times F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(8) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(9) + F(8)) &= T(3) + T(2) + T(6) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) + F(2) + (F(7) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times (T(2) \times T(7) + T(9) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(9)) &= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 992 &:= (F(1) + F(8) + F(4) \times F(9)) \times F(6) &= T(1) + T(8) + T(4) + T(9) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 994 &:= (F(1) + F(7)) \times (F(6) + F(4) \times F(8)) &= T(1) \times T(7) + T(6) \times (T(4) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 1000 &:= (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(6) \times F(7) + F(8)) &= T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 1008 &:= (F(3) \times F(8)) \times (F(4) + F(6) + F(7)) &= (T(3) + T(8)) \times T(4) + T(6) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (F(5) + F(7)) \times (F(8) + F(2) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(7) + T(8) + T(2)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 1009 &:= F(1) + F(8) \times F(3) \times F(6) \times F(4) &= (T(1) + T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) + T(4) \\
 \\
 1011 &:= F(4) + (F(7) + F(9) + F(2)) \times F(8) &= (T(4) \times T(7) + T(9)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(4) + F(6) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(8) &= (T(4) + T(6) \times T(5)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 \\
 1015 &:= (F(5) + F(4) \times F(6)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= T(5) + T(4) + (T(6) + T(1)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(7) \times (F(8) + F(5)) \times F(4) &= (T(2) + T(7) + T(8)) \times T(5) + T(4) \\
 \\
 1017 &:= F(3) + (F(6) + F(8)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(8) \times T(1) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) + (F(8) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) &= (T(3) + T(8)) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 1020 &:= (F(1) + F(2) + F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(9) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(6) \times T(4) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times F(9) &= (T(1) + T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(8) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= (T(2) + T(8)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(2) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(6)) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4)) + T(6) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) \times (T(7) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(6) + F(3)) \times F(2) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times T(6) + T(3) \times T(2) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1023} & := (F(2) + F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) + F(4) & = T(2) + (T(6) + T(8) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(2) + (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1027} & := (F(2) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(8))) \times F(7) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{1032} & := (F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(1) + F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(8) + T(1)) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1033} & := F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(9) + F(7) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(9) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1035} & := (F(2) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(4) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(3) \times (T(9) + T(4)) + T(5)) \\
 & := (F(5) \times F(4)) \times (F(1) + F(3) \times F(9)) & = T(5) \times (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1041} & := F(3) \times F(5) \times F(9) \times F(4) + F(8) & = T(3) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(9) + F(8) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1042} & := F(3) \times (F(1) + (F(5) \times F(6)) \times F(7)) & = T(3) + (T(1) + T(5) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1044} & := (F(1) \times F(8) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = (T(1) + T(8)) \times (T(6) + T(3)) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(9)) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = (T(1) \times T(2) + T(9)) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(9) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(6) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1050} & := (F(4) \times F(6) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times (T(6) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1050} & := (F(1) + F(9) + F(5) \times F(4)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(9)) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(9) + F(6) \times F(3)) \times F(8) & = (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(2) + F(8)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(2) + T(8) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(6) \times F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(1) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(3) + (T(6) + T(1)) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5))) \times F(8) & = (T(9) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(5) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1053} & := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = T(4) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(8) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(5) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1054} & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(8) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(8) + T(6) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1056} & := (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(6) \times F(3) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times ((T(8) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(4)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(9) + F(7)) \times (F(8) + F(2)) & = T(1) \times T(9) + T(7) \times T(8) + T(2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(2) \times (T(5) \times T(6) + T(1) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(2) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(8) \times T(7) + T(2) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1071} & := (F(9) + F(1) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(9) \times (T(1) + T(3)) + T(6) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(2) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(9) + T(2) \times T(3) \times (T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(2) + (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6) \times T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1074} & := F(3) \times F(5) \times F(6) \times F(7) + F(9) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + (F(4) + F(9)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) & = (T(2) + T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(8)) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1086} & := (F(5) + F(2)) \times (F(6) \times F(8) + F(7)) & = T(5) + (T(2) \times T(6)) + T(8) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{1090} & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(9) \times (F(4) + F(7))) & = T(3) \times T(2) \times T(9) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1092} & := (F(9) + F(6)) \times F(1) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = (T(9) + T(6)) \times (T(1) + T(5)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(4) + F(8)) & = (T(9) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1096} & := (F(3) + (F(9) \times F(6))) \times (F(2) + F(4)) & = T(3) + T(9) \times (T(6) + T(2)) + T(4) \\
 \mathbf{1100} & := ((F(4) + F(7)) + F(9)) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times (T(7) + T(9) + T(1) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1104} & := (F(3) + (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(9)) \times F(6) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(2) + T(9) + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{1108} & := F(3) \times (F(9) + (F(6) \times F(5)) \times F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(9) + T(6)) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{1113} & := (F(3) \times F(4) + F(9) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(9) + T(7) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1122} & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1125} & := F(5) \times ((F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(4) + F(8)) & = T(5) \times (T(3) + T(9)) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1131} & := (F(8) \times F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(9) + F(5)) & = T(8) + (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(9) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(5) \times F(8) + F(6) \times F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(5) + T(8) + T(6) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1132} & := F(2) + (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = (T(2) + T(6)) \times (T(8) + T(4)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1134} & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(6) \times (T(2) + T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times T(2) + (T(6) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1134} & := (F(3) \times F(7) + F(1)) \times (F(9) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times T(7) + (T(1) + T(9)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1144} & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(4) \times T(2)) \times T(8) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(9) + F(5)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) + F(7) & = T(9) + (T(5) + T(8)) \times T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + (F(8) + F(6)) \times F(4)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(8) \times (T(6) + T(4)) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(2) + (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(4)) \times F(7) = (T(2) + T(6)) \times T(8) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{1150} & := (F(4) + F(7) + F(9)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) = T(4) \times (T(7) + T(9) + T(3) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1155} & := ((F(5) + F(7)) \times F(4) + F(2)) \times F(8) = T(5) \times (T(7) + T(4) + T(2) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(7) + F(4)) \times (F(8) + F(9)) = T(5) \times (T(7) + T(4) + T(8)) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1164} & := F(2) \times F(9) \times (F(7) + F(8)) + F(6) = (T(2) \times T(9) + T(7) \times T(8)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1170} & := (F(4) + F(6) + F(9)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) = T(4) \times (T(6) + T(9) + T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1176} & := (F(3) + F(8) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) = T(3) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(6) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(7) + F(2)) \times (F(9) + F(6)) = T(3) \times T(7) + (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1197} & := (F(1) + (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6)) \times F(8) = (T(1) \times T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(6) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1212} & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(9) + F(6) \times F(8)) = T(3) + T(4) \times T(9) + T(6) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{1218} & := (F(7) + F(1)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) \times F(4) = T(7) \times T(1) \times T(8) + T(6) \times T(4) \\
 \mathbf{1224} & := (F(2) \times F(3) + F(8) + F(7)) \times F(9) = T(2) + (T(3) + T(8)) \times T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := ((F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) + F(8)) \times F(9) = T(2) + T(3) + T(5) \times (T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{1225} & := F(1) + (F(4) \times F(5) + F(8)) \times F(9) = T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) \times (T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{1251} & := (F(5) \times F(8) + F(9)) \times (F(1) + F(6)) = T(5) \times (T(8) + T(9) + T(1)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1260} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) \times (F(3) + F(6)) = (T(2) + T(5) + T(8) + T(3)) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(5) \times F(4) \times F(3) \times (F(6) + F(9)) = T(5) \times (T(4) \times T(3) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(9)) \times (F(5) \times F(4) + F(8)) = T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5) + T(4) \times T(8)) \\
 & := F(8) \times (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(2) + F(4)) = (T(8) + T(3) + T(7) \times T(2)) \times T(4) \\
 \mathbf{1261} & := F(4) + (F(8) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(9) = T(4) + T(8) + (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1281} & := (F(2) + F(9) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times F(8) = T(2) + T(9) \times T(3) + T(7) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{1292} & := (F(1) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(7)) \times F(9) = T(1) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1302} & := (F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7)) + F(9)) \times F(8) = T(3) \times T(1) + T(7) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(9)) \times (F(5) \times F(3) + F(8)) = T(6) \times (T(9) + T(5) + T(3)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(9)) \times (F(7) \times F(3) + F(5)) = T(6) + T(9) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{1323} & := (F(3) \times F(6) + F(7) + F(9)) \times F(8) = T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) = T(2) \times ((T(6) + T(3)) \times T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(8) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(7) + F(6)) = (T(8) + T(3)) \times (T(2) + T(7)) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1326 &:= (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(6) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= T(3) + (T(1) + T(6)) \times (T(5) + T(9)) \\ &:= F(4) \times F(7) \times (F(5) + F(6) + F(8)) &= (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(5) + T(6) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$1333 := F(4) \times (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(6) + F(7) = T(4) \times T(8) + T(9) \times T(6) + T(7)$$

$$1338 := F(4) \times ((F(7) + F(6)) \times F(8) + F(5)) = (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(6) + T(8) \times T(5)$$

$$1339 := (F(9) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(4)) \times F(7) = T(9) + T(3) + (T(8) + T(4)) \times T(7)$$

$$1344 := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(6) \times F(3) \times F(8) = (T(1) + T(4) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(8))$$

$$:= (F(2) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) \times F(6) = (T(2) + T(4) + T(5) + T(8)) \times T(6)$$

$$:= (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(8) \times F(6) = (T(4) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(8)) \times T(6)$$

$$1347 := (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(7) \times F(9) + F(8) = T(3) + (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(9) + T(8)$$

$$:= F(9) \times F(7) \times (F(2) + F(3)) + F(8) = T(9) + (T(7) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(8))$$

$$1353 := F(4) \times (F(6) + F(2) + F(7) \times F(9)) = (T(4) + T(6)) \times T(2) + T(7) \times T(9)$$

$$1360 := (F(4) + F(1)) \times F(3) \times F(5) \times F(9) = T(4) \times (T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(9))$$

$$:= F(1) \times F(5) \times F(6) \times (F(7) + F(8)) = (T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(6) + T(7) + T(8))$$

$$:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) \times (F(7) + F(8)) = (T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(7) + T(8))$$

$$:= (F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6)) + F(7)) \times F(9) = T(4) \times (T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(9))$$

$$:= (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(9) = T(4) + (T(2) + T(3) + T(6)) \times T(9)$$

$$:= F(9) \times F(5) \times F(3) \times (F(1) + F(4)) = (T(9) + T(5) \times T(3) + T(1)) \times T(4)$$

$$1365 := (F(3) + F(4) \times F(9) + F(1)) \times F(7) = T(3) \times T(4) + T(9) \times (T(1) + T(7))$$

$$:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(1) + F(6) \times F(9)) = T(3) \times T(4) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(9)$$

$$:= F(5) + (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(9) = T(5) \times T(4) + (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(9)$$

$$1366 := F(2) + F(8) \times F(7) \times (F(4) + F(3)) = (T(2) \times T(8) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(3)$$

$$1368 := F(4) + (F(6) \times F(9) + F(2)) \times F(5) = (T(4) + T(6) + T(9)) \times (T(2) + T(5))$$

$$:= F(5) + (F(6) + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(9)) = T(5) \times T(6) + T(8) \times T(7) + T(9)$$

$$:= F(6) \times (F(2) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(9)) = T(6) \times (T(2) + T(3) \times T(4)) + T(9)$$

$$:= F(6) \times (F(2) + F(5) \times (F(7) + F(8))) = (T(6) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(7) \times T(8)$$

$$1371 := F(2) + (F(1) + F(8) \times F(7)) \times F(5) = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(8) + T(7) \times T(5))$$

$$1378 := ((F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) + F(2)) \times F(7) = T(3) + (T(4) + T(8) + T(2)) \times T(7)$$

$$:= (F(1) + (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(4)) \times F(7) = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(9) \times T(4) + T(7)$$

$$1378 := F(4) + (F(8) \times F(7) + F(3)) \times F(5) = (T(4) + T(8)) \times T(7) + T(3) \times T(5)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1380 &:= (F(2) \times F(4) + F(7) \times F(8)) \times F(5) &= T(2) \times T(4) \times T(7) + T(8) \times T(5) \\
 1386 &:= (F(2) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(3) + (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(3) + (F(5) + F(4)) \times F(6)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times (T(5) + T(4) \times T(6)) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(6) + (F(2) + F(5) \times F(8)) \times F(7) &= T(6) \times (T(2) + T(5)) + T(8) \times T(7) \\
 1390 &:= F(2) + (F(9) \times F(7) + F(8)) \times F(4) &= (T(2) + T(9)) \times T(7) + T(8) + T(4) \\
 1392 &:= (F(2) + F(9) + F(7)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= T(2) + T(9) + (T(7) + T(8)) \times T(6) \\
 1404 &:= F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(2) \times F(7) &= T(4) \times T(3) + (T(9) + T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 1407 &:= (F(3) + F(5) \times F(7)) \times F(2) \times F(8) &= (T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(7) + T(2) + T(8)) \\
 1408 &:= F(1) + (F(3) + F(5) \times F(7)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(7) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(4) + (F(6) + F(7) \times F(8)) \times F(5) &= (T(4) + T(6)) \times T(7) + T(8) \times T(5) \\
 1410 &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(7) + F(9)) &= T(3) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(7) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (F(6) + F(1) + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(9)) &= T(6) \times (T(1) + T(8) + T(7)) + T(9) \\
 1425 &:= F(5) \times F(1) \times (F(7) + F(6) \times F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(1) + T(7) + T(6) + T(9)) \\
 1428 &:= (F(4) + F(7) + F(8) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(8) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(5) + F(2) + F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(9) &= T(5) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(4) \times T(9)) \\
 1431 &:= F(2) + F(7) \times F(5) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= T(2) + T(7) \times (T(5) \times T(1) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(4) + (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(9) \times F(8) &= (T(4) \times T(2) + T(1)) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 1440 &:= (F(1) + F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) \times F(6) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(9) + T(5) \times T(6)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(7) \times F(4)) \times (F(9) + F(3)) &= T(2) \times (T(7) + T(4) \times T(9)) + T(3) \\
 1446 &:= F(5) \times (F(6) \times F(9) + F(7)) + F(8) &= T(5) \times (T(6) + T(9) + T(7)) + T(8) \\
 1449 &:= ((F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(7) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(9) \times (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(9) + (T(1) + T(7) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times (F(7) + F(6)) &= (T(1) \times T(3) + T(9)) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 1452 &:= (F(2) + F(7) \times F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= T(2) \times (T(7) \times (T(5) + T(1)) + T(8)) \\
 1470 &:= F(3) \times (F(6) + F(7)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) &= T(3) \times T(6) + T(7) \times (T(2) + T(9)) \\
 1512 &:= (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(8) \times F(6) &= (T(3) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(8)) \times T(6) \\
 1518 &:= (F(3) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(5) \times F(7)) &= T(3) + (T(8) + T(2) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 1530 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times F(9) &= (T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(5)) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(1) \times T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(4) + (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(8)) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times T(1) \times (T(2) \times T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(3) \times (F(6) + F(7))) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(6)) + T(7) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(5) + T(2)) \times (T(6) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1533} & := F(2) \times F(8) \times (F(5) \times F(7) + F(6)) & = (T(2) + T(8) + T(5)) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(5) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(6) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(5) \times F(9) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = (T(4) + T(5) + T(9) + T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1536} & := F(4) + (F(3) \times F(9) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(9) + T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1540} & := (F(1) + F(8)) \times F(5) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(8) + T(5) + T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{1545} & := F(5) \times (F(4) + (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(9)) & = T(5) + (T(4) + T(2) + T(6)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1560} & := (F(4) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) \times F(6) & = T(4) \times (T(3) \times T(5) + T(9) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1561} & := F(2) + (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(5) \times F(7) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(8) \times (T(5) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(2) + F(5) \times F(4) \times F(7) \times F(6) & = (T(2) \times T(5) + T(4)) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1564} & := (F(3) + F(8)) \times (F(5) \times F(7) + F(4)) & = T(3) + T(8) \times (T(5) + T(7)) + T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1575} & := (F(5) \times F(6) + F(2) + F(9)) \times F(8) & = T(5) \times (T(6) + T(2) + T(9) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(6) + F(5) \times F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(3) + T(6) + (T(5) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1590} & := (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(1) + F(5) \times F(8)) & = T(3) + (T(7) + T(1) + T(5)) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{1596} & := (F(1) + (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(7) \times (T(3) + T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1620} & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = (T(1) \times T(6) + T(3)) \times (T(9) + T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{1625} & := F(5) \times (F(4) + F(1) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = (T(5) + T(4)) \times (T(1) + T(8) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{1632} & := F(1) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times F(3) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(4) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1638} & := F(1) \times F(4) \times F(7) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(4) + T(7)) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(9) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(3) \times T(6) + T(9) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(6) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(6) + T(7) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1645} & := (F(2) + F(9)) \times (F(4) \times F(7) + F(6)) & = (T(2) + T(9) + T(4)) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1650} & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(6) \times F(9)) & = (T(1) \times T(5) + T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{1651} & := ((F(1) + F(5)) \times F(8) + F(2)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(5) \times T(8)) \times T(2) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{1656} & := (F(3) \times F(9) + F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = T(3) \times (T(9) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{1659} & := ((F(2) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(9)) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{1665} & := F(5) \times (F(6) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times T(6) + T(2) \times T(4) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1666} &:= (F(3) \times (F(2) + F(7)) + F(8)) \times F(9) &= T(3) \times T(2) + T(7) + T(8) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(6) + F(7) \times F(4)) \times F(9) &= T(3) \times T(6) + T(7) \times (T(4) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6)) \times F(9) &= T(1) + (T(3) + T(4) + T(6)) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1677} &:= (F(3) \times F(8) + F(1)) \times (F(9) + F(5)) &= T(3) + T(8) \times (T(1) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1680} &:= F(3) \times (F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= T(3) \times T(4) + T(8) \times T(1) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(5) \times F(8) \times (F(2) + F(3) + F(7)) &= (T(5) + T(8) + T(2) + T(3)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1690} &:= (F(4) \times F(6) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(7) &= T(4) \times (T(6) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1701} &:= (F(2) \times F(7) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(7) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(5) + F(3) \times F(9) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= (T(5) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(6) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) \times F(3) + F(6)) + F(2) &= T(9) \times T(8) + (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(2) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(5) \times F(9) \times (F(3) + F(6)) &= (T(2) + T(5) + T(9)) \times (T(3) + T(6)) \\
 &:= F(2) + ((F(6) + (F(3) \times F(8))) \times F(9)) &= T(2) \times (T(6) + T(3)) + T(8) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1710} &:= (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(9) \times F(5)) &= (T(3) + T(6) \times T(2) + T(9)) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1716} &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(7) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &= (T(1) + T(5) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(7) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= T(3) \times T(4) \times T(7) \times T(1) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(7) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &= (T(3) + T(4) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1719} &:= (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(8) + F(9) \times F(5)) &= T(2) + T(6) \times (T(8) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1722} &:= (F(2) + F(7) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(7) + T(3)) + T(9) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1734} &:= ((F(3) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(2)) \times F(9) &= T(3) + (T(6) + T(5)) \times (T(2) + T(9)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6) \times F(3)) \times F(9) &= (T(4) + T(2) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1764} &:= (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(4) \times (F(9) + F(6)) &= (T(1) + T(7) + T(4) + T(9)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(2) \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(6)) + T(9) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(8) \times (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(9) + F(6)) &= (T(8) \times T(1) + T(2) + T(9)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1776} &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(7) \times F(9) + F(6) &= (T(1) + T(4) + T(7)) \times T(9) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1800} &:= F(5) \times (F(8) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) &= T(5) \times T(8) + T(3) \times T(4) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1806} &:= (F(3) \times F(9) + F(7) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(3) + T(9) \times T(7) + T(5) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{1809} &:= F(3) + F(7) \times (F(5) \times F(8) + F(9)) &= (T(3) + T(7) + T(5)) \times T(8) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1810} &:= F(4) + F(7) \times (F(9) + F(5) \times F(8)) &= T(4) + T(7) \times T(9) + T(5) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1830} &:= F(4) \times (F(6) \times F(8) + F(7) \times F(9)) &= T(4) \times (T(6) + T(8)) + T(7) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1846} &:= F(7) \times (F(9) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(6)) &= (T(7) + T(9)) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1848} &:= (F(1) + F(8)) \times F(3) \times (F(9) + F(6)) &= (T(1) + T(8) + T(3) + T(9)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1869} &:= F(8) \times (F(5) \times F(7) + F(4) \times F(6)) &= (T(8) + T(5) + T(7) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{1881} &:= F(2) + (F(7) + F(9)) \times F(5) \times F(6) &= (T(2) + T(7)) \times (T(9) + T(5)) + T(6) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{1890} &:= (F(5) + F(2)) \times (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(8) &= T(5) \times (T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(6) + F(4) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= (T(3) + T(6)) \times T(4) + T(9) \times T(8) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{1911} &:= (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) \times F(2) \times F(8) &= (T(3) + T(5) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1932} &:= (F(2) + F(7) \times (F(5) + F(3))) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(7) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1938} &:= (F(2) + (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6)) \times F(9) &= T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{1974} &:= (F(2) \times F(7) + F(9)) \times F(3) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(7) + T(9) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(5) \times F(6)) \times (F(7) + F(9)) &= (T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(6) + T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{2016} &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(5) + T(4) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(5) + F(1)) \times F(6) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times T(5) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(8) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{2040} &:= (F(2) + F(4) + F(6)) \times F(5) \times F(9) &= (T(2) + T(4) + T(6)) \times (T(5) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(5) + F(7)) \times F(4) \times F(9) &= T(3) \times (T(5) + T(7) \times T(4) + T(9)) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{2074} &:= F(9) \times ((F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(7)) &= T(9) \times T(2) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{2100} &:= (F(2) + F(9) + F(5) \times F(7)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(9)) \times (T(5) + T(7)) + T(8) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{2142} &:= (F(3) \times F(8) + F(6) + F(7)) \times F(9) &= (T(3) + T(8)) \times T(6) + T(7) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) &= (T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(6) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{2145} &:= F(4) \times (F(5) + F(6)) \times (F(8) + F(9)) &= (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(8) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(1) + (F(9) \times F(2)) \times F(8)) &= (T(4) \times T(1) + T(9)) \times (T(2) + T(8)) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{2146} &:= F(1) + (F(8) \times F(9) + F(2)) \times F(4) &= (T(1) + T(8)) \times (T(9) + T(2) + T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{2151} &:= (F(3) + F(2) + F(8) \times F(9)) \times F(4) &= T(3) + (T(2) + T(8)) \times (T(9) + T(4)) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{2160} &:= (F(2) + F(5) + F(9) \times F(8)) \times F(4) &= (T(2) \times (T(5) + T(9)) + T(8)) \times T(4) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(5) + (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(7)) &= (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(8) + T(9) \times T(7) \\
 \\ \\
 \mathbf{2163} &:= F(4) \times F(9) \times (F(6) + F(7)) + F(8) &= (T(4) + T(9)) \times T(6) + T(7) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(4) \times F(9)) \times (F(7) + F(6)) &= (T(2) \times T(4) + T(9) + T(7)) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{2166} &:= F(4) \times (F(9) \times F(2) \times F(8) + F(6)) &= (T(4) + T(9)) \times (T(2) + T(8)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{2169} &:= F(4) \times (F(6) + F(7) \times (F(8) + F(9))) &= (T(4) + T(6) + T(7)) \times T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2184} &:= (F(1) + F(4) \times F(9) + F(2)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(4) + T(9)) \times (T(2) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(6) + (F(2) + F(4) \times F(8)) \times F(9) &= (T(6) + T(2)) \times (T(4) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2196} &:= (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(5) \times F(6) + F(8)) &= T(3) \times (T(9) + T(5) \times T(6)) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{2202} &:= F(3) + F(6) \times (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(5) &= (T(3) + T(6)) \times (T(8) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2205} &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9)) &= (T(1) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(2)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(9) \times F(4) + F(3)) \times F(8) &= T(1) \times T(9) + (T(4) \times T(3)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2206} &:= F(1) + F(4) \times F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9)) &= T(1) + (T(4) + T(8) + T(2)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{2208} &:= F(4) \times (F(1) + F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9))) &= (T(4) \times T(1) + T(8)) \times (T(2) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2211} &:= (F(3) + (F(9) + F(2)) \times F(8)) \times F(4) &= T(3) + T(9) \times (T(2) + T(8) + T(4)) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(4) \times F(8) + F(3)) \times F(9) &= (T(1) + T(4) \times T(8)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2215} &:= F(4) + F(3) + (F(5) \times F(7)) \times F(9) &= T(4) + (T(3) + T(5) + T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2220} &:= (F(2) \times F(3) + F(7) \times F(9)) \times F(5) &= (T(2) + T(3) + T(7)) \times (T(9) + T(5)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9)) + F(5)) &= (T(4) + T(8) + T(2)) \times T(9) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2223} &:= F(1) \times F(7) \times (F(4) + F(6) \times F(8)) &= (T(1) + T(7) + T(4)) \times (T(6) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(2) + F(9) \times F(7)) + F(6) &= T(5) + T(2) + T(9) \times (T(7) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (F(5) + F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(8) + F(9) &= T(5) + T(6) \times T(7) + T(8) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2226} &:= ((F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) + F(3)) \times F(8) &= (T(4) + T(5) + T(7)) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(6) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(7) \times F(9) &= T(6) + (T(3) + T(5) + T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2229} &:= F(4) \times (F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9)) + F(6)) &= (T(4) + T(8)) \times (T(2) + T(9)) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{2232} &:= (F(2) + F(7) \times F(8) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= (T(2) + T(7)) \times (T(8) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{2236} &:= (F(1) \times F(3) + F(9) \times F(5)) \times F(7) &= (T(1) + T(3) + T(9)) \times (T(5) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{2241} &:= F(5) \times (F(3) + F(7) \times F(9)) + F(8) &= (T(5) + T(3) + T(7)) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2244} &:= (F(2) \times F(7) \times F(5) + F(1)) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(7) + (T(5) + T(1)) \times T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(7) \times (F(3) + F(4))) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(7) + (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(9)) \\
 &:= F(8) + (F(9) \times F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) &= T(8) \times (T(9) + T(5)) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2250} &:= F(2) \times F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7) \times F(9)) &= T(2) \times T(5) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2268 &:= F(2) \times F(8) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9)) &= T(2) \times (T(8) + (T(4) + T(3)) \times T(9)) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(9)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(5) + T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$2271 := F(5) \times (F(9) \times F(7) + F(6)) + F(8) = T(5) \times T(9) + T(7) \times (T(6) + T(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2289 &:= (F(5) \times (F(3) + F(7)) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= (T(5) + T(3)) \times (T(7) + T(9) + T(8)) \\ &:= F(8) \times (F(5) \times F(2) + F(7) \times F(6)) &= (T(8) + T(5) \times T(2) + T(7)) \times T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2296 &:= (F(1) + F(7) \times (F(2) + F(8))) \times F(6) &= T(1) \times T(7) + T(2) \times T(8) \times T(6) \\ &:= F(8) + F(5) \times (F(9) + F(2)) \times F(7) &= T(8) \times (T(5) + T(9) + T(2)) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2304 &:= (F(5) \times (F(8) + F(9)) + F(7)) \times F(6) &= T(5) + (T(8) + T(9) + T(7)) \times T(6) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(4) \times F(8)) &= (T(3) + T(9) + T(2) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\ &:= F(6) \times (F(3) + F(7) \times (F(2) + F(8))) &= (T(6) + T(3)) \times T(7) \times T(2) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$2314 := ((F(2) + F(8)) \times F(6) + F(3)) \times F(7) = T(2) \times (T(8) \times T(6) + T(3)) + T(7)$$

$$2331 := (F(6) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(9)) \times F(8) = (T(6) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(9) + T(8)$$

$$2340 := F(2) \times F(5) \times F(7) \times (F(3) + F(9)) = (T(2) + T(5) + T(7) + T(3)) \times T(9)$$

$$2346 := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(8) + F(3)) \times F(9) = (T(1) \times T(4) + T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(9))$$

$$2347 := F(1) + F(4) \times (F(8) + F(3)) \times F(9) = T(1) + (T(4) + T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(9))$$

$$2349 := (F(2) + F(9) \times (F(3) + F(8))) \times F(4) = T(2) + (T(9) + T(3)) \times (T(8) + T(4))$$

$$2352 := (F(1) \times F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) \times F(8) = (T(1) \times T(2)) \times (T(7) + T(6) \times T(8))$$

$$2353 := F(1) + (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(1) + (T(2) \times (T(7) + T(6) \times T(8)))$$

$$2355 := (F(4) + F(7) \times (F(3) + F(9))) \times F(5) = T(4) \times T(7) \times T(3) + T(9) \times T(5)$$

$$2355 := F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7) \times F(9) + F(8)) = T(5) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(9) \times T(8)$$

$$2361 := F(4) \times ((F(8) + F(3)) \times F(9) + F(5)) = (T(4) + T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(9)) + T(5)$$

$$2380 := (F(3) + F(7) \times F(5) + F(4)) \times F(9) = (T(3) + T(7)) \times (T(5) + T(4) + T(9))$$

$$2436 := F(3) \times (F(4) \times F(6) + F(9)) \times F(8) = T(3) \times T(4) + (T(6) + T(9)) \times T(8)$$

$$2448 := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) \times F(9) = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4) \times (T(8) + T(9)))$$

$$2457 := ((F(3) + F(8)) \times F(6) + F(5)) \times F(7) = T(3) + (T(8) + T(6)) \times (T(5) + T(7))$$

$$2458 := F(2) + (F(9) + F(5)) \times F(8) \times F(4) = (T(2) + T(9)) \times (T(5) + T(8)) + T(4)$$

$$2496 := F(6) \times (F(2) + F(3) + F(8)) \times F(7) = (T(6) + T(2) \times T(3)) \times (T(8) + T(7))$$

$$2502 := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(7) \times F(8) + F(5)) = T(2) + (T(6) + T(7)) \times (T(8) + T(5))$$

$$2520 := (F(1) + F(2) + F(7)) \times F(8) \times F(6) = ((T(1) \times T(2)) \times T(7) + T(8)) \times T(6)$$

$$:= (F(1) + F(5) + F(9)) \times F(4) \times F(8) = (T(1) \times T(5) + T(9) + T(4)) \times T(8)$$

$$:= F(5) \times F(6) \times (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(8) = T(5) \times ((T(6) + T(1)) \times T(3) + T(8))$$

$$2556 := (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(6) + F(4) \times F(8)) = T(3) \times (T(9) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(8))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2565 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(1) + F(5) \times F(9)) &= T(3) \times T(7) \times T(1) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 2646 &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= (T(2) + T(5) + T(8)) \times (T(6) + T(7)) \\
 2652 &:= (F(5) + F(8)) \times (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(9) &= (T(5) + T(8) + T(1)) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \\
 2673 &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) \times F(9) + F(8) &= T(2) \times T(5) + (T(7) + T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 2691 &:= (F(8) \times F(6) + F(9) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= T(8) \times T(6) + T(9) \times (T(5) + T(7)) \\
 2728 &:= F(9) \times F(5) \times (F(7) + F(4)) + F(6) &= (T(9) + T(5) + T(7)) \times (T(4) + T(6)) \\
 2730 &:= F(2) \times F(7) \times (F(6) + F(3)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(7) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(8))) \\
 2736 &:= (F(1) + F(5) \times F(9) \times F(3)) \times F(6) &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(3) \times T(6)) \\
 2751 &:= F(5) + F(4) \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= T(5) + (T(4) + T(6) + T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 2772 &:= F(4) \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= (T(4) + T(6) + T(9) + T(1)) \times T(8) \\
 2800 &:= F(5) \times (F(2) + F(9)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) &= (T(5) \times T(2) + T(9) + T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 2808 &:= (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times (T(9) + T(2) + T(5) \times T(7)) \\
 2848 &:= (F(4) + F(7)) \times (F(5) \times F(9) + F(6)) &= T(4) + (T(7) + T(5)) \times (T(9) + T(6)) \\
 2856 &:= (F(4) \times F(5) + F(3)) \times F(8) \times F(6) &= (T(4) + T(5) \times T(3) + T(8)) \times T(6) \\
 2871 &:= (F(5) \times F(7) + F(9)) \times (F(6) + F(8)) &= T(5) + T(7) \times (T(9) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 2898 &:= (F(6) + F(3) \times F(5) \times F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(6) \times T(3) \times T(5) + T(7) \times T(8) \\
 2899 &:= F(2) + (F(9) + F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(9) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 2925 &:= F(2) + (F(5) \times F(7) + F(8)) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times T(5) \times (T(7) + T(8)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 2940 &:= (F(1) + F(7)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(5) &= (T(1) \times T(7) + T(6)) \times (T(9) + T(5)) \\
 &:= F(8) \times (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) &= (T(8) + T(3) + T(6) \times T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 2958 &:= F(9) \times (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= (T(9) + T(3)) \times (T(1) + T(8) + T(6)) \\
 3024 &:= (F(1) + (F(7) + F(9)) \times F(4)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(7) + T(9) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 3030 &:= F(5) \times F(4) \times (F(6) \times F(8) + F(9)) &= T(5) + (T(4) + T(6) + T(8)) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 3060 &:= (F(1) + F(6) + F(8)) \times F(4) \times F(9) &= (T(1) + T(6) + T(8) + T(4)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(9) &= (T(3) + T(7)) \times (T(5) \times T(2) + T(9)) \\
 &:= F(5) \times F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(9) &= T(5) \times (T(3) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(9))) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) &= T(4) \times T(2) \times (T(6) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 3150 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(5) \times (F(6) + F(9)) &= (T(3) + T(7) + T(5) + T(6)) \times T(9) \\
 3192 &:= F(8) \times F(6) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(7)) &= (T(8) + T(6) \times T(2) + T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 3234 &:= (F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(4) \times T(6) + (T(2) \times T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 3264 &:= ((F(3) + F(7)) \times F(5) + F(8)) \times F(9) &= (T(3) + T(7)) \times (T(5) + T(8) + T(9)) \\
 3276 &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(7) \times F(8) &= (T(2) \times (T(5) + T(3)) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 3276 &:= F(4) \times (F(6) + F(9)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= (T(4) + T(6) + T(9) + T(5)) \times T(8) \\
 3690 &:= F(5) \times (F(4) \times F(6) + F(8) \times F(9)) &= (T(5) + T(4) + T(6) + T(8)) \times T(9) \\
 3705 &:= F(5) \times F(7) \times (F(3) + F(8) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(7) + T(3) \times T(8)) + T(9) \\
 3718 &:= (F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(8) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= (T(4) \times T(6) + T(8)) \times T(5) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 3744 &:= (F(5) + F(8) + F(7) \times F(9)) \times F(6) &= (T(5) + T(8)) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + T(6) \\
 3780 &:= (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) \times F(2) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times (T(9) + T(5) \times (T(2) + T(8))) \\
 &:= (F(5) \times F(9) + F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= (T(5) + T(9)) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(8) \times (F(9) + F(1) + F(2)) \times F(5) &= T(8) \times (T(9) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5)) \\
 3795 &:= F(5) \times (F(4) + F(3) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= T(5) + (T(4) \times T(3) + T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 3808 &:= F(9) \times F(6) \times F(2) \times (F(1) + F(7)) &= T(9) \times T(6) \times (T(2) + T(1)) + T(7) \\
 3811 &:= F(4) + F(6) \times (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(9) &= T(4) + T(6) + (T(2) \times T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 3843 &:= F(2) \times F(8) \times (F(7) + F(5) \times F(9)) &= T(2) + (T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(5) + T(9)) \\
 3853 &:= F(5) + (F(9) + F(4)) \times F(6) \times F(7) &= T(5) \times (T(9) + T(4) \times T(6)) + T(7) \\
 3915 &:= F(5) \times (F(1) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(9)) &= (T(5) \times T(1)) \times (T(3) \times T(8) + T(9)) \\
 3915 &:= F(5) \times (F(2) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(9)) &= (T(5) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(8)) \times T(9) \\
 3925 &:= (F(4) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(9)) \times F(5) &= T(4) + (T(3) \times T(8) + T(9)) \times T(5) \\
 3933 &:= (F(3) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(5) \times F(9)) &= T(3) \times T(8) \times (T(2) + T(5)) + T(9) \\
 3960 &:= F(5) \times (F(2) + F(8)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(2) + T(8) \times T(3) + T(9)) \\
 3978 &:= (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(1) \times F(7) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(6) + (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(9)) \\
 4080 &:= F(1) \times F(5) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times F(9) &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times (T(4) \times T(6) + T(9)) \\
 4095 &:= (F(1) + F(6) \times F(9)) \times F(4) \times F(5) &= T(1) \times T(6) \times (T(9) + T(4) \times T(5)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(7) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= (T(2) \times T(6) + T(7)) \times T(1) \times T(9) \\
 4110 &:= F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(3) + F(6) \times F(9)) &= T(4) \times (T(5) + T(3) \times (T(6) + T(9))) \\
 4158 &:= (F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(4) \times T(6) \times T(5) + T(7) \times T(8) \\
 4167 &:= (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(8) + F(7) \times F(9)) &= T(2) \times (T(6) \times (T(8) + T(7)) + T(9)) \\
 4200 &:= F(5) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times (F(2) + F(9)) &= T(5) + (T(4) + T(6)) \times T(2) \times T(9) \\
 4284 &:= F(9) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= (T(9) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6))) \times T(7) \\
 4290 &:= F(4) \times F(3) \times F(7) \times (F(8) + F(9)) &= T(4) \times (T(3) \times (T(7) + T(8)) + T(9)) \\
 4320 &:= F(5) \times F(6) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9)) &= (T(5) + T(6) + T(4) \times T(3)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(9) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= (T(5) + T(9) + T(3) \times T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 4368 &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times F(6) \times F(7) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(6) \times T(7) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(5) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(6) &= ((T(5) + T(9)) \times T(2) + T(7)) \times T(6) \\
 4410 &:= (F(2) + F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(3) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(6) \times (T(7) + T(3) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(3) \times (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= T(4) \times ((T(3) + T(2)) \times T(9) + T(8)) \\
 4485 &:= F(5) \times F(7) \times (F(1) + F(3) \times F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(7) + T(1) + T(3) \times T(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4488 &:= F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(5) + F(1)) \times F(9) &= T(3) \times (T(7) + (T(5) + T(1)) \times T(9)) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(5) + F(2)) \times F(9) &= T(3) \times (T(7) + T(5) \times (T(2) + T(9))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4536 &:= (F(1) + F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(8) &= (T(1) \times T(7)) \times (T(3) \times T(6) + T(8)) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times (T(9) \times (T(1) + T(5)) + T(8)) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times ((T(9) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$4590 := F(5) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(9) = (T(5) + T(2)) \times (T(6) \times T(4) + T(9))$$

$$4605 := F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(7) \times F(8) + F(9)) = T(4) \times (T(5) \times T(7) + T(8)) + T(9)$$

$$4680 := (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(6) \times (F(5) + F(9)) = T(3) \times ((T(7) + T(6)) \times T(5) + T(9))$$

$$4704 := F(3) \times (F(7) + F(1)) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(3) \times (T(7) \times T(1) + T(6) \times T(8))$$

$$5145 := (F(5) + F(3)) \times F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9)) = T(5) + (T(3) + T(8) \times T(2)) \times T(9)$$

$$5725 := F(9) \times (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) + F(7) = T(9) + T(4) \times (T(5) \times T(8) + T(7))$$

$$5796 := F(3) \times F(8) \times (F(6) \times F(7) + F(9)) = T(3) \times T(8) \times T(6) + T(7) \times T(9)$$

$$5880 := (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9)) = T(4) \times (T(5) \times T(8) + T(2) + T(9))$$

$$5916 := F(3) \times F(9) \times F(4) \times (F(6) + F(8)) = (T(3) \times T(9) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(8)$$

$$6084 := (F(3) + F(9)) \times (F(2) + F(6) \times F(8)) = T(3) \times (T(9) + T(2)) \times T(6) + T(8)$$

$$6264 := ((F(3) + F(8)) \times F(9) + F(2)) \times F(6) = (T(3) \times T(8) + T(9)) \times (T(2) + T(6))$$

$$6552 := F(6) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(8) \times F(7) = (T(6) \times T(3) + T(2) \times T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$6804 := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(8) = ((T(2) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(9)) \times T(8)$$

$$6864 := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(8)) \times F(6) \times F(7) = (T(4) + T(1)) \times (T(8) + T(6) \times T(7))$$

$$7170 := F(3) \times F(5) \times (F(9) \times F(8) + F(4)) = (T(3) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(8)) \times T(4)$$

$$7176 := F(4) \times F(6) \times F(7) \times (F(3) + F(8)) = T(4) \times T(6) \times (T(7) + T(3)) + T(8)$$

$$7650 := F(5) \times (F(4) + F(8) \times F(3)) \times F(9) = (T(5) + T(4)) \times (T(8) + T(3) \times T(9))$$

$$7686 := F(3) \times (F(5) \times F(9) + F(7)) \times F(8) = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(9) \times T(7)) + T(8)$$

$$7696 := F(3) \times F(6) \times F(7) \times (F(9) + F(4)) = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(7) \times T(9)) + T(4)$$

$$7956 := F(3) \times (F(6) + F(1)) \times F(7) \times F(9) = T(3) \times (T(6) + (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(9))$$

$$:= (F(5) + F(8)) \times (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(9) = (T(5) + T(8)) \times (T(6) + T(2) \times T(9))$$

$$8160 := F(3) \times F(6) \times F(4) \times F(5) \times F(9) = (T(3) \times T(6) + T(4)) \times (T(5) + T(9))$$

$$8316 := (F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(8) = ((T(4) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(9)) \times T(8)$$

$$8398 := (F(3) \times F(6) + F(4)) \times F(9) \times F(7) = T(3) \times (T(6) + T(4)) \times T(9) + T(7)$$

$$8568 := (F(6) + F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) \times F(9) = T(6) \times (T(2) + T(4) \times T(8) + T(9))$$

$$9291 := F(2) + F(9) \times F(7) \times F(8) + F(6) = (T(2) \times T(9) + T(7)) \times (T(8) + T(6))$$

$$9384 := (F(3) + F(7) \times F(8) + F(1)) \times F(9) = (T(3) \times T(7) + T(8)) \times (T(1) + T(9))$$

$$9792 := ((F(2) + F(8)) \times F(7) + F(3)) \times F(9) = T(2) \times (T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(3) + T(9))$$

$$9828 := (F(1) \times F(3) + F(9)) \times F(8) \times F(7) = ((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(9) + T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$:= (F(2) \times F(9) + F(3)) \times F(8) \times F(7) = (T(2) \times T(9) + T(3) \times T(8)) \times T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{10584} &:= (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(8) \times (F(2) + F(7)) = (T(3) \times T(9) + T(8) \times T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{10710} &:= (F(1) + F(7) \times F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(9) = (T(1) \times T(7) + T(6) \times T(4)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{10731} &:= (F(2) + (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(9)) \times F(8) = T(2) + (T(7) + T(3) \times T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{10836} &:= (F(5) \times F(9) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(8) = T(5) \times T(9) \times (T(3) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{10944} &:= (F(8) \times F(7) \times F(5) + F(4)) \times F(6) = (T(8) + T(7)) \times (T(5) \times T(4) + T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{11025} &:= (F(9) + F(1)) \times F(8) \times (F(3) + F(7)) = T(9) \times (T(1) + T(8) \times T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{11088} &:= (F(5) \times F(7) + F(2)) \times F(8) \times F(6) = (T(5) \times T(7) + T(2) \times T(8)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{11340} &:= F(5) \times F(8) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(9)) = T(5) \times (T(8) + T(4) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{11424} &:= F(2) \times F(9) \times F(8) \times (F(4) + F(7)) = (T(2) + T(9) + T(8) \times T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(6) \times (F(7) + F(2)) \times F(9) = (T(4) \times T(6) + T(7)) \times (T(2) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{11466} &:= F(8) \times F(7) \times (F(3) + F(5) \times F(6)) = (T(8) + (T(7) + T(3)) \times T(5)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{11760} &:= F(5) \times (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(5) \times T(1) \times (T(7) + T(6) \times T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{12988} &:= F(9) \times (F(5) + (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(7)) = (T(9) + T(5) \times T(6)) \times T(8) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{13104} &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(6) \times F(7) \times F(8) = ((T(1) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times F(7) \times F(8) = ((T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) + T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(8) \times (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(7) \times F(6) = (T(8) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(7)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{13650} &:= F(5) \times F(7) \times (F(6) + F(3)) \times F(8) = T(5) \times (T(7) + T(6) \times (T(3) + T(8))) \\
 \mathbf{16320} &:= F(9) \times F(6) \times (F(4) \times F(7) + F(8)) = (T(9) + T(6) \times T(4)) \times (T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{17640} &:= F(4) \times F(6) \times F(8) \times (F(2) + F(9)) = T(4) \times T(6) \times (T(8) + T(2) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{19890} &:= (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(5) \times F(7) \times F(9) = (T(1) + T(6) + T(5) \times T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{22848} &:= F(3) \times F(8) \times F(9) \times (F(4) + F(7)) = (T(3) + (T(8) + T(9)) \times T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{53550} &:= F(5) \times F(9) \times (F(7) + F(3)) \times F(8) = (T(5) + T(9) \times T(7)) \times (T(3) + T(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

7.2 Positive and Negative Signs Expressions

7.2.1 Two Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{3} &:= F(2) + F(3) = -T(2) + T(3) \\
 \mathbf{8} &:= -F(7) + F(8) = -T(7) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{11} &:= F(4) + F(6) = -T(4) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

7.2.2 Three Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1} &:= -F(2) \times F(3) + F(4) = -T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(4) - F(5) = T(3) + T(4) - T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2 &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) \\ &:= -F(2) \times F(4) + F(5) &= -T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3 &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) &= -T(1) - T(3) + T(4) \\ &:= -F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) &= T(2) \times T(3) - T(5) \\ &:= -F(2) \times F(5) + F(6) &= -T(2) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= F(4) \times (-F(1) + F(3)) &= T(4) - T(1) - T(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(4) &= -T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(6) + F(7) &= -T(2) - T(6) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$5 := F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) = T(1) - T(3) + T(4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(4) \\ &:= F(1) - F(6) + F(7) &= -T(1) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) + F(5) &= -T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7 &:= -F(1) - F(7) + F(8) &= -T(1) - T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) + F(3) \times F(4) &= T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8 &:= -F(1) \times F(7) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(5) &= -T(1) - T(3) + T(5) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(4) + F(5) &= T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9 &:= -F(1) + F(3) \times F(5) &= -T(1) \times T(3) + T(5) \\ &:= F(1) - F(7) + F(8) &= T(1) - T(7) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10 &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times F(5) &= T(1) - T(3) + T(5) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(4) + F(6) &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(7) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11 &:= F(1) \times F(4) + F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(4) + F(5) &= T(3) - T(4) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12 &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) &= T(2) + T(5) - T(3) \\ &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(6) &= T(1) - T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(6) + F(8) &= -T(2) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(8) + F(9) &= T(2) - T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) - F(4) + F(7) &= -T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14 &:= (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(3) = -T(1) + T(6) - T(3) \\ &:= F(1) - F(6) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(6) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15 &:= (F(2) \times F(4)) \times F(5) = T(2) \times T(4) - T(5) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(3) \times F(6) = -T(1) \times T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(7) = -T(2) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(3) - F(8) + F(9) = T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16 &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times F(6) = T(1) - T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= F(4) + F(5) + F(6) = T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17 &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(7) = -T(1) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(5) + F(7) = T(2) \times T(5) - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 18 &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(8) = -T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6)) = -T(3) + T(2) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(3) \times F(6) + F(9) = -T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(2) + F(8) = -T(3) \times T(2) + T(8) \\ &:= F(4) \times F(7) - F(8) = T(4) - T(7) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20 &:= -F(2) - F(7) + F(9) = T(2) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) - F(4) + F(8) = -T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$21 := F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) = T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(7))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23 &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(8) = -T(2) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) - F(7) + F(9) = T(3) - T(7) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) = -T(2) + T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(3) \times F(5) + F(9) = -T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(5) \times F(3) + F(9) = -T(5) - T(3) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(6) + F(9) = T(1) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times F(7) = T(2) - T(3) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$26 := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(7) = T(1) - T(2) + T(7)$$

$$27 := F(2) - F(6) + F(9) = T(2) - T(6) + T(9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29 &:= -F(1) \times F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(4) + F(9) &= -T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 30 &:= (F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(5) &= T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\ &:= F(1) - F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) \times T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= F(5) \times (-F(3) + F(6)) &= T(5) - T(3) + T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32 &:= F(2) - F(4) + F(9) &= -T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(4) + F(7)) &= T(3) \times T(4) - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$35 := (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(5) = -T(1) + T(6) + T(5)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36 &:= -F(1) + F(4) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) + F(9) &= -T(2) - T(3) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38 &:= -F(1) + F(4) \times F(7) &= T(1) \times T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) + F(4) + F(9) &= T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$39 := -F(2) + F(5) \times F(6) = T(2) + T(5) + T(6)$$

$$41 := -F(1) + F(3) \times F(8) = -T(1) + T(3) + T(8)$$

$$42 := F(3) \times (F(6) + F(7)) = T(3) \times (-T(6) + T(7))$$

$$48 := (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(6) = -T(5) + T(2) \times T(6)$$

$$60 := F(3) \times F(9) - F(6) = -T(3) + T(9) + T(6)$$

$$63 := F(4) \times (-F(7) + F(9)) = -T(4) + T(7) + T(9)$$

$$64 := (-F(5) + F(7)) \times F(6) = T(5) + T(7) + T(6)$$

$$91 := (-F(2) + F(6)) \times F(7) = T(2) \times T(6) + T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 105 &:= (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(4) &= T(2) \times (T(9) - T(4)) \\ &:= F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= T(5) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$180 := (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) = T(3) \times (T(9) - T(5))$$

7.2.3 Four Terms Expressions

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &:= F(1) \times F(3) - F(5) + F(4) &= T(1) - T(3) + T(5) - T(4) \\ &:= (F(1) - F(3) + F(2)) \times F(5) &= (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(2) + T(5) \\ &:= (F(2) - F(4) + F(3)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) - T(8) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) - F(4) &= T(1) + T(2) + T(3) - T(4) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(5) - F(6) &= T(1) \times T(3) + T(5) - T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(2) + F(3) - F(4)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) - T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(5) - F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5) - T(6)) \\
 \mathbf{0} & := F(3) \times F(6) + F(5) - F(8) & = (T(3) - T(6) + T(5)) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4) - F(5)) \times F(9) & = -T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(3) - F(5)) \times F(6) & = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5) - T(6)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(5) - F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times (T(5) + T(6) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(5) + F(6) + F(8) - F(9) & = (T(5) + T(6) - T(8)) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(5) + F(6) - F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(5) - T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(6) - F(8) + F(7)) & = (T(5) + T(6) - T(8)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1} & := -F(1) \times F(3) + F(6) - F(5) & = T(1) + T(3) - T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) - F(5) & = -T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(3) - F(4) & = -T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) + F(4) - F(5) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) - T(5) \\
 & := (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(3) - F(7) & = -T(1) \times T(6) - T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) + F(5) - F(6) & = -T(2) + T(4) + T(5) - T(6) \\
 & := -(F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) + F(7) & = -(T(2) \times (T(5) - T(3))) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1} & := F(2) + F(6) + F(7) - F(8) & = -T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(3) - F(5) - F(7) + F(8) & = -T(3) + T(5) + T(7) - T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) - F(7)) \times F(4) + F(9) & = -T(3) - T(7) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := -(F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) + F(8) & = T(4) - T(2) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(7) + F(2) + F(8) - F(9) & = T(7) + T(2) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(6)) - F(8) & = T(3) + T(4) + T(6) - T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2} & := -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) + F(5) & = -T(1) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 & := -F(1) \times F(2) - F(3) + F(5) & = -T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times F(5) - F(7) & = -T(1) - T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(1) \times F(4) - F(6) + F(7) & = -T(1) + T(4) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(5) - F(6) & = -T(1) - T(2) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(3) - F(6) + F(7) & = T(1) - T(3) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) - F(3)) \times F(4) + F(5) & = T(1) + T(3) + T(4) - T(5) \\
 & := -F(2) - F(3) - F(4) + F(6) & = -T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2} & := -F(2) - F(3) - F(6) + F(7) & = T(2) + T(3) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 & := -F(3) \times F(4) - F(5) + F(7) & = T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) - T(7) \\
 & := F(3) + F(4) + F(5) - F(6) & = T(3) - T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) + F(6) - F(7) & = -T(3) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 & := -F(4) - F(6) - F(8) + F(9) & = -T(4) + T(6) + T(8) - T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(3) + F(4)) & = T(1) - T(2) - T(3) + T(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= -F(2) + F(4) \times F(6) - F(8) &= -T(2) - T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(2) - F(3)) \times (-F(5) + F(4)) &= T(2) - T(3) + T(5) - T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) - T(5) \\ &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(5) + F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(2) - F(4) + F(5) &= T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(6) + F(7) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= (-F(1) + F(7)) \times F(3) - F(8) &= T(1) - T(7) - T(3) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(1) - F(4)) \times F(5) + F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) - F(4) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(1) \times T(4) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) \times F(3) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) - T(6) + T(7)) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times F(6) - F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(4) - T(6)) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) \times F(4) - F(3) + F(6) &= T(2) \times T(4) - T(3) - T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{3} &:= -F(2) \times F(5) - F(7) + F(8) &= T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) - T(8) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) - F(8) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) - T(8) \\ &:= (F(2) - F(3)) \times F(5) + F(6) &= T(2) + T(3) + T(5) - T(6) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) - F(4) + F(5) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4) - T(5)) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(4) - F(5) + F(7) &= T(3) + T(4) + T(5) - T(7) \\ &:= F(4) + F(6) + F(7) - F(8) &= -T(4) + T(6) + T(7) - T(8) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(4) - F(6)) + F(7) &= T(3) - T(4) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(3) - F(6)) + F(8) &= T(4) \times T(3) - T(6) - T(8) \\ &:= F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(7)) - F(8) &= T(4) - T(5) - T(7) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) - F(6) + F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(2) - F(3) + F(5) &= T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) - T(5) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(2) - F(5) + F(6) &= T(1) - T(2) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(3) + F(6) &= T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(4) - F(5) + F(7) &= T(1) - T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= (-F(1) + F(5)) \times F(4) - F(6) &= T(1) \times T(5) + T(4) - T(6) \\ &:= F(1) - F(3) - F(4) + F(6) &= -T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{4} &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) - F(5) &= T(2) + T(3) + T(4) - T(5) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(2) - T(3) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(5) - F(7) + F(8) &= -T(2) + T(5) + T(7) - T(8) \\ &:= -(F(3) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(7) &= T(3) - T(2) \times T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) + F(4) \times F(6) - F(8) &= -T(1) - T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) \times F(5) + F(7) &= -T(2) - T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) \times F(7) - F(9) &= -T(2) - T(4) - T(7) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) &= T(1) - T(2) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(7) - F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(1) - F(2) + F(4)) \times F(5) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) - F(2) + F(4) &= (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) - T(4) \\
 &:= (F(1) - F(3)) \times F(4) + F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= (F(1) - F(4)) \times F(6) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(4) - F(5) + F(6) &= T(1) + T(4) + T(5) - T(6) \\
 \\
 5 &:= -F(2) \times F(4) - F(7) + F(8) &= T(2) + T(4) + T(7) - T(8) \\
 &:= -F(2) - F(3) - F(5) + F(7) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) - T(7) \\
 &:= -F(2) - F(3) - F(7) + F(8) &= T(2) - T(3) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(8) - F(4) - F(9) &= T(3) - T(8) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(3) + F(5) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \\
 &:= -F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5)) + F(8) &= -T(3) - T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 6 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) + F(3) &= -T(1) + T(2) + T(4) - T(3) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(3) - F(5) + F(7) &= -T(1) - T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(4) + F(2) + F(6) &= (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) - T(6) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(7) + F(8) &= T(1) - T(2) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(2) + F(6) &= (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4) - F(8) &= T(1) - T(6) - T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(4) + F(6) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 \\
 6 &:= -F(2) \times F(3) - F(7) + F(8) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) - T(7) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(4) - F(5) + F(6) &= -T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(5) \times F(6) - F(9) &= -T(2) - T(5) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(3) - F(5) + F(6) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(5)) - T(6) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(8)) \times F(3) - F(9) &= T(2) - T(8) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(4) - F(5) + F(7) &= T(2) - T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(4) - F(7) + F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(7) - T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) - F(9) &= -T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 6 &:= -(F(3) + F(5)) \times F(2) + F(7) &= T(3) \times T(5) - T(2) \times T(7) \\
 &:= -F(3) - F(5) - F(6) + F(8) &= T(3) + T(5) + T(6) - T(8) \\
 &:= -F(6) + F(2) - F(8) + F(9) &= -T(6) + T(2) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(4) \times F(7) - F(9) &= -T(1) - T(4) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(3) + F(5)) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) \times F(6) + F(8) &= -T(2) - T(3) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(8) + F(4) \times F(6)) &= T(3) \times T(8) - T(4) \times T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) + F(5) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(4) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(4) + F(6) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) - F(2) + F(5) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(2) + T(5) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(5) - F(8) + F(9) &= T(1) + T(5) + T(8) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) - F(3) - F(5) + F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(3) - F(4) + F(6) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) - T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(4) - F(5) + F(6) &= T(2) + T(4) + T(5) - T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(4) + F(5) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= -F(3) \times F(4) - F(8) + F(9) &= T(3) + T(4) + T(8) - T(9) \\
 &:= (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) - F(7) &= -T(4) + T(2) \times T(5) - T(7) \\
 \\
 8 &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) + F(5) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= (-F(1) - F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(4) + F(7) &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(1) - F(3)) \times F(5) + F(7) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(1) - F(4)) \times F(7) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(4) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(2) \times F(3) \times F(7) + F(9) &= -T(2) - T(3) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(2) \times F(4) - F(3) + F(7) &= T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) - T(7) \\
 &:= (F(2) \times F(4) - F(3)) \times F(6) &= T(2) - T(4) - T(3) + T(6) \\
 \\
 8 &:= (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(5) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= ((F(3) - F(4)) \times F(7)) + F(8) &= T(3) + T(4) + T(7) - T(8) \\
 &:= -F(3) + F(5) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) - T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(4) - F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= -T(4) + T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (F(4) - F(5)) \times F(7) + F(9) &= T(4) + T(5) + T(7) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) \times F(4) &= T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \\
 &:= -F(3) - F(4) \times F(6) + F(9) &= -T(3) - T(4) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 9 &:= (F(1) \times F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) &= T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) - T(4) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) + F(5) &= T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(6) &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(3) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(2) - F(5) + F(7) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(5) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(3) + F(7) &= -T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(4) + F(6) &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) - T(6) \\
 \\
 9 &:= -F(1) + F(5) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(1) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 &:= -F(2) \times F(3) + F(4) + F(6) &= (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) - T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(4) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(6) - T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= -(F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) + F(8) &= -T(2) \times (T(5) - T(3)) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(4) + F(7) &= -T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(5) - F(8) + F(9) &= T(2) + T(5) + T(8) - T(9) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) - F(8) &= T(3) \times T(4) - T(5) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{9} &:= F(3) \times F(4) - F(5) + F(6) &= T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) - T(6) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(5) + F(4) + F(7) &= T(3) - T(5) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times (-F(3) + F(5)) &= T(2) \times T(4) - T(3) - T(5) \\ &:= F(2) + F(3) \times F(8) - F(9) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) - T(9) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (-F(5) + F(6)) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(4) + F(6)) - F(7) &= T(3) + T(4) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(2) - F(5)) + F(8) &= T(4) \times T(2) + T(5) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) - F(3) + F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) + F(5) &= -T(1) + T(3) - T(4) + T(5) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(4) + F(5) &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times (T(4) - T(5)) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(5) + F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(7) + F(8) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(3) - F(6) + F(8) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) - F(5) + F(7) &= T(2) - T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) - F(7) + F(8) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{10} &:= F(2) \times F(5) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(2) \times (T(5) - T(6)) + T(7) \\ &:= (-F(3) \times F(4) + F(6)) \times F(5) &= T(3) + T(4) - T(6) + T(5) \\ &:= F(4) + F(3) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(4) \times (-T(3) - T(6) + T(7)) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(4) + F(6)) &= T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) - T(6) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(2) \times F(3)) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(1) - F(7)) + F(9) &= -T(3) - T(1) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) \times (-F(9) + F(4) \times F(7)) &= -T(3) \times T(9) + T(4) \times T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{11} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(7) &= T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(6) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) + F(6) &= -T(1) + T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(6) + F(8) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(8) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(4) + F(5) &= T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(5) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(4) + F(7) &= -T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(1) - F(4)) \times F(5) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{11} &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) - F(7) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(3) - F(7) + F(8) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(5) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(2) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(5) + F(3) + F(7) &= T(2) \times T(5) - T(3) - T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(4) - F(6) + F(7) &= T(3) \times T(4) - T(6) - T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(2) \times F(6) - F(7) &= -T(4) + T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) \times F(5) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(4) \times F(6) + F(9) &= -T(2) - T(4) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(4) - F(6)) + F(8) &= T(3) - T(4) - T(6) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{12} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) - F(6) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) - F(8) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(5) + F(6) &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times (T(5) - T(6)) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(3) - F(4) + F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) \times F(3) &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(4) + T(3) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(4) + F(7) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) - T(7) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(2) + F(6) &= (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) - T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{12} &:= -F(1) - F(4) - F(5) + F(8) &= T(1) - T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) - F(3) + F(5) + F(6) &= T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= -(F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) - T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(5) - F(6) &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) - T(6) \\
 &:= -F(2) - F(6) - F(7) + F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(6) + T(7)) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(5) + F(6) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) - T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(6) + F(8) &= T(2) - T(3) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(8) + F(9) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(2) - F(4) + F(7) &= T(3) \times (T(2) \times T(4) - T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{12} &:= (-F(3) + F(7)) \times F(4) - F(8) &= -T(3) - T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(4) + F(6)) \times F(5) - F(7) &= -T(4) - T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (-F(2) + F(5)) &= (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) - T(5) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) \times F(5) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(4) \times F(5) &= T(1) + T(3) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) \times F(5) + F(8) &= -T(2) - T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(5) - F(3)) &= (-T(2) - T(4) + T(5)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(1) - F(6) + F(7)) &= T(3) - T(1) - T(6) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{13} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(6) + F(8) &= T(1) - T(2) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(8) + F(9) &= T(1) + T(2) - T(8) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (F(1) \times F(3) - F(2)) \times F(7) &= (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(2) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(4) + F(6) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(5) + F(6) &= T(1) + T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= (F(1) - F(6)) \times F(4) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(6) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(3) + F(4) + F(6) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{13} &:= (-F(2) - F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= -T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(7) + F(8) - F(9) &= -T(3) + T(7) + T(8) - T(9) \\
 &:= (F(3) - F(4)) \times F(8) + F(9) &= -T(3) + T(4) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(7) - F(5) - F(8) &= -T(4) - T(7) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(4) + F(7) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(2) \times F(3) + F(4) \times F(5) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) - T(5) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) &= T(1) + T(2) + T(5) - T(3) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(6)) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(2) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{14} &:= -F(1) \times F(3) - F(5) + F(8) &= -T(1) - T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(4) + F(6) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(4) + F(7) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(8) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(4) - F(3) + F(7) &= (-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) - T(7) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(5) &= T(2) + T(3) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(3) + F(4) + F(6) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(4) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{14} &:= F(2) - F(4) - F(5) + F(8) &= T(2) - T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(3) - F(5) + F(6) + F(7) &= T(3) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) \times F(5) &= -T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(3) \times F(4) + F(8) &= (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(8)) - F(9) &= -T(4) + T(5) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(4) - F(5)) \times (F(2) - F(6)) &= -T(4) + T(5) \times T(2) - T(6) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(4) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) &= -T(2) + T(4) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(1) - F(7) + F(8)) &= T(3) \times T(1) - T(7) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{15} &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) \times F(5) &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) + F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(3) - F(8) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) - F(3) - F(5) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(6) &= -T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) + F(6) &= T(2) + T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(1) + F(5) + F(6) &= T(2) \times (-T(1) - T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(5) &= (-T(2) - T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (-F(2) + F(7)) \times F(4) - F(8) & = -T(2) - T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) - F(3) + F(4) + F(7) & = T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{15} & := -F(2) + F(4) - F(6) + F(8) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) - T(8) \\
 & := F(2) - F(5) - F(3) + F(8) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) - T(8) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(6) - F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(6) - T(7)) + T(8) \\
 & := (-F(3) - F(6) + F(7)) \times F(5) & = (-T(3) - T(6) + T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 & := -F(4) \times F(6) + F(5) + F(9) & = T(4) \times (T(6) - T(5)) - T(9) \\
 & := -F(5) \times F(6) + F(8) + F(9) & = -T(5) + T(6) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(5) - F(4) - F(8) + F(9) & = T(5) \times (T(4) + T(8) - T(9)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (-F(4) + F(6)) & = T(2) \times (-T(3) - T(4) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) & = -T(3) + T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := -F(1) + (-F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(3) \times (-F(7) + F(8)) & = T(1) + T(3) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{16} & := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) + F(7) & = T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(7) & = (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) + F(5) + F(6) & = T(1) \times T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(2) - F(4) + F(8) & = (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(2) + F(5) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) - F(8) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) - F(3)) \times F(5) + F(8) & = T(1) - T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) - F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) & = -T(1) + T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{16} & := -F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) + F(7) & = -T(2) + T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) - F(8) + F(9) & = -T(2) + T(4) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) - F(7) + F(8) & = T(2) + T(6) + T(7) - T(8) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(7)) \times F(3) - F(6) & = T(2) + T(7) + T(3) - T(6) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(3) - T(4)) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(5)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(1) - T(2)) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5)) & = -T(2) - T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 & := F(1) - F(4) \times (F(6) - F(7)) & = -T(1) + T(4) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{17} & := -F(1) \times F(2) + F(5) + F(7) & = T(1) + T(2) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(2) - F(5) + F(8) & = -T(1) - T(2) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(2) - F(3) + F(8) & = -T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(6) & = T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(6) & = T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(4) + F(6) + F(7) & = T(1) \times T(4) - T(6) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= F(2) + F(6) + F(8) - F(7) &= T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) - T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(5) + F(7) &= (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(5) - T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(4) + F(8) &= -T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) - F(6) + F(4) + F(8) &= T(2) \times T(6) - T(4) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{17} &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) - F(7) &= T(3) \times T(4) - T(5) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(3) + F(4) - F(5) + F(8) &= T(3) - T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(4) + F(2) - F(8) + F(9) &= -T(4) + T(2) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) \times F(6) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(3) \times F(6) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(7) \times F(4) - F(8) &= -T(1) - T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(4) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(5)) - T(4) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(6) + F(3) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times (T(6) - T(3)) - T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) \times (F(7) - F(8)) &= T(2) + T(3) - T(7) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{18} &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(5) + F(7) &= T(1) + T(2) \times T(5) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(1) \times F(2) - F(3) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(9) &= -T(1) \times T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times F(7) - F(8) &= T(1) \times T(4) - T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) \times F(4) + F(6) + F(7) &= T(1) + T(4) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(5) + F(6) &= T(1) \times T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\ &:= -(F(1) + F(2)) \times F(6) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(2) \times T(6) - T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(5) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(5) + F(7) &= -T(1) + T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{18} &:= F(2) \times F(3) \times F(5) + F(6) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(2) \times F(3) \times F(6) + F(9) &= (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(6) - T(9) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) - F(5) + F(8) &= T(2) - T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times F(7) - F(8) &= T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) - T(8) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(5) - F(6) + F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(5) - T(6)) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(5) - F(8) + F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8) - T(9)) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(7) - F(6) &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(7) - T(6)) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(7) - F(8) &= -T(3) + T(2) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\ &:= (-F(3) + F(1)) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(4)) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{18} &:= (-F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) + F(7) &= T(3) \times (-T(4) - T(5) + T(7)) \\ &:= (-F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) - F(6) &= T(4) + T(5) - T(7) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (-F(3) + F(6)) &= T(1) - T(4) + T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) \times F(6) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(5)) &= T(1) \times T(3) - T(2) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(5) &= -T(1) - T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(4) \times F(6) - F(5) &= T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) - T(5) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(5) + F(8)) - F(9) &= -T(3) + T(5) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(6) + F(3) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) &= T(6) + T(3) + T(8) - T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{19} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(8) &= T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(4) \times F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(4) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(7) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(4) + F(8) &= -T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(5) + F(7) &= T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(2) \times F(5) + F(4) + F(8) &= T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) - T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) - F(7) &= -T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) - F(7) &= -T(2) + T(5) - T(6) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{19} &:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) - F(8) &= -T(3) + T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(4) + F(6) - F(7) + F(8) &= -T(4) + T(6) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(5) \times F(6) + F(7) - F(9) &= T(5) + T(6) + T(7) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) - F(3) \times F(6) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(4) \times F(7) - F(8) &= T(1) + T(4) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(2) \times F(5) + F(4) \times F(6) &= T(2) - T(5) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6)) &= T(1) - T(3) + T(2) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(4) + (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(6) &= T(4) \times (T(1) + T(2)) - T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{20} &:= (F(1) \times F(2) + F(4)) \times F(5) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) - F(7) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(6) + F(7) &= -T(1) + (T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(7))) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) + F(7) &= T(1) + T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(3) - F(4) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(5) + F(2) + F(7) &= (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) - T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(1) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) &= T(1) - T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 &:= (-F(2) - F(6) + F(7)) \times F(5) &= T(2) \times T(6) - T(7) - T(5) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(7) + F(9) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(7) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{20} &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(5) + F(7) &= -T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(3) \times F(4) - F(6) + F(9) &= T(3) - T(4) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(7) + F(3) - F(8) &= T(4) \times (-T(7) - T(3) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(1) - F(4) \times F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) \times T(4) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(4) + F(7)) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(2) \times F(3)) \times (-F(4) + F(7)) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) &= T(2) + T(4) - T(6) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= F(2) + F(4) + F(3) \times F(6) &= T(2) - T(4) + T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(5) + F(7)) - F(9) &= T(4) \times (-T(5) - T(7) + T(9)) \\ &:= F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(5) + F(6)) &= -T(3) - T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{21} &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) &= (T(1) \times T(2)) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\ &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(7) + F(9) &= T(1) + T(2) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= (F(1) \times F(3) - F(2)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) \times F(5) - F(6) + F(9) &= T(2) \times T(5) + T(6) - T(9) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(6) + F(5) &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(6) - T(5)) \\ &:= F(2) + F(3) + F(5) + F(7) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) - T(5) + T(7)) \\ &:= (-F(2) - F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= -T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(4) - F(8) &= T(2) - T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) + F(7) &= (T(2) - T(3)) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{21} &:= (F(2) - F(3)) \times F(7) + F(9) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) - T(9) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(4) - F(6) + F(9) &= T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) - T(9) \\ &:= (F(3) - F(4)) \times F(7) + F(9) &= -T(3) + T(4) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(4) + F(8) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(3) + F(5)) &= T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) - T(5) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(4) \times F(6) &= (-T(2) - T(3) + T(4)) \times T(6) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(4) + F(8) &= -T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \\ &:= -F(3) + F(4) \times F(5) + F(6) &= (T(3) + T(4) - T(5)) \times T(6) \\ &:= -F(6) + F(4) \times F(8) - F(9) &= T(6) \times (T(4) + T(8) - T(9)) \\ &:= F(1) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(5) &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(4) + T(5) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) \times (F(4) - F(7)) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{22} &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(6) + F(7) &= T(1) - T(2) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(4) + F(8) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(7) &= (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) - T(7) \\ &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(7) &= -T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(5) - F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(7) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(3) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) - F(6) &= T(3) + T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times (T(4) - T(6)) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times F(5) + F(7) &= T(2) + T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(4) + F(6)) &= -T(2) - T(3) + T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= F(2) + (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(4) &= T(2) - T(3) + T(5) + T(4) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{23} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(3) - F(7) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(3) - T(7) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= F(1) - F(3) + F(4) + F(8) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(1) + F(4)) \times F(5) + F(7) &= T(1) \times T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times F(5) + F(6) &= -T(2) - T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(5) \times F(3) + F(7) &= T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) - T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(4) + F(8) &= T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{23} &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(6) + F(7) &= T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 &:= -F(4) - F(6) + F(7) + F(8) &= T(4) + T(6) + T(7) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(5) \times F(7) - F(6) - F(9) &= -T(5) - T(7) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(4) + F(3) \times F(7) &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(3) \times F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(3) \times (F(4) - F(6)) + F(7) &= T(3) + T(4) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{24} &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) \times F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(2) + T(3) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(8) &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(3) \times F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= (-F(1) - F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(5) + F(8) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(6) &= -T(1) - T(3) + T(4) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{24} &:= F(1) + F(3) - F(7) + F(9) &= T(1) + T(3) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(2) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(2) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= -F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) + F(8) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(4) - F(7) + F(9) &= -T(2) + T(4) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(2) \times F(6) - F(3) + F(9) &= T(2) \times T(6) + T(3) - T(9) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(3) - T(4)) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) - F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(2) \times T(4) + T(5) - T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{24} &:= (F(3) + F(1) + F(5)) \times F(4) &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(5) - T(4)) \\
 &:= F(3) + F(2) + F(6) + F(7) &= T(3) \times (-T(2) - T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(4) - F(8) &= T(3) - T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) &= -T(1) - T(3) + T(2) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(7)) &= T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(3) \times F(7) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) - F(4) + F(3) \times F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (-F(7) + F(8)) &= (T(2) - T(3)) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5)) + F(6) &= T(3) \times T(4) - T(5) - T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{24} &:= F(3) \times (F(6) + F(8)) - F(9) &= -T(3) + T(6) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(6) - F(7)) + F(9) &= T(3) \times (T(6) + T(7) - T(9)) \\
 &:= -F(4) + F(5) \times F(6) - F(7) &= -T(4) - T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(5) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6) - T(7)) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(2) - F(6) + F(8)) &= T(3) + T(2) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(3) + (F(4) - F(2)) \times F(7) &= -T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (-F(5) - F(6) + F(8)) &= T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) - T(8) \\
 &:= -F(6) + F(3) \times (-F(5) + F(8)) &= -T(6) - T(3) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{25} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(5) + F(8) &= T(1) + T(2) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2) + F(4)) \times F(5) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 &:= -(F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(9) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) - T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(4) + F(6) + F(8) &= T(1) \times T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(4) + F(8) &= T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(6) + F(4) + F(7) &= T(2) \times T(6) - T(4) - T(7) \\
 &:= (F(3) \times F(1) + F(4)) \times F(5) &= (T(3) - T(1)) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{25} &:= F(3) - F(4) + F(5) + F(8) &= -T(3) + T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) - F(3) \times F(5) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) \times F(7) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(5) \times (-F(4) + F(6)) &= -T(1) + T(5) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(5) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) &= T(2) + T(5) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5)) + F(7) &= -T(3) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) &= T(1) - T(2) + T(3) + T(6) \\
 &:= -F(4) + F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7)) &= -T(4) + T(3) + T(1) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{26} &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) \times F(7) &= T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(6) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(2) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(4) + F(6) + F(8) &= T(1) + T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(4) - F(3)) \times F(7) &= (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(3) - T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(5) + F(8) &= -T(1) + T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(2) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{26} &:= -F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) + F(8) &= -T(2) + T(6) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= -(F(2) + F(4)) \times F(3) + F(9) &= -T(2) - T(4) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) \times F(6) &= T(1) - T(3) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(6) + F(8)) &= -T(1) + T(2) \times T(6) - T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (-T(8) + T(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & := (-F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(5) + F(6)) & = -T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\ & := F(3) \times (F(5) - F(7) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(5) - T(7) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27} & := F(1) \times F(2) - F(6) + F(9) & = T(1) \times T(2) - T(6) + T(9) \\ & := -F(1) - F(2) - F(5) + F(9) & = -T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(9) \\ & := -F(1) - F(2) + F(6) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(6) - T(8) \\ & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(6) - F(5) & = T(1) - T(4) + T(6) + T(5) \\ & := -F(1) + F(3) + F(5) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\ & := -F(2) \times F(3) - F(5) + F(9) & = T(2) - T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\ & := -F(2) \times F(3) + F(6) + F(8) & = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(6) - T(8) \\ & := F(2) + F(3) + F(4) + F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) - F(8) & = -T(2) + T(5) - T(6) + T(8) \\ & := -F(2) + F(3) - F(6) + F(9) & = -T(2) + T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\ & := -F(2) + F(3) + F(5) + F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) - T(8) \\ & := F(2) - F(4) + F(6) + F(8) & = -T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\ & := F(5) \times F(6) + F(8) - F(9) & = T(5) + T(6) + T(8) - T(9) \\ & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = -T(1) + T(4) - T(2) + T(6) \\ & := -F(2) + F(5) \times F(4) + F(7) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) - T(7) \\ & := (-F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(4) & = -T(2) + T(3) \times (T(5) - T(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{27} & := F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) - T(6) \\ & := F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(6)) + F(7) & = T(3) - T(2) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\ & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(7)) - F(5) & = -T(3) - T(4) + T(7) + T(5) \\ & := F(2) - F(3) \times (F(8) - F(9)) & = T(2) \times T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \\ & := F(2) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(6)) & = -T(2) - T(3) + T(5) + T(6) \\ & := F(3) - (F(6) - F(7)) \times F(5) & = (T(3) \times (-T(6) + T(7))) - T(5) \\ & := F(4) - F(3) \times (F(2) - F(7)) & = -((T(4) - T(3)) - T(2)) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{28} & := -F(1) \times F(2) - F(5) + F(9) & = T(1) - T(2) - T(5) + T(9) \\ & := -F(1) \times F(2) + F(6) + F(8) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(6) - T(8) \\ & := F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) + F(8) & = T(1) + T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\ & := F(1) + F(2) - F(6) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(2) - T(6) + T(9) \\ & := -F(1) - F(3) - F(4) + F(9) & = -T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\ & := -F(2) - F(6) + F(4) + F(9) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(4) - T(9) \\ & := -F(2) + F(4) + F(5) + F(8) & = -T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{28} & := F(3) + F(5) + F(6) + F(7) & = -T(3) - T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\ & := (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(5) + F(6) & = T(4) - T(2) \times (T(5) - T(6)) \\ & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (-F(2) + F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(4) - T(2) + T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(2) + F(3) \times F(4) + F(8) & = -T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(3) + F(5)) & = -T(2) + T(4) + T(3) + T(5) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(4) + F(3) \times F(7) & = (-T(2) + T(4) - T(3)) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(7)) + F(6) & = (T(3) - T(4)) \times (-T(7) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(3) - (F(4) - F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(3) + T(4) - T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{29} & := -F(1) \times F(3) - F(4) + F(9) & = -T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) - F(6) + F(9) & = -T(1) + T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(3) + F(8) & = -T(2) - T(4) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) & = -T(3) + T(2) \times T(6) - T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(7) - F(8) + F(9) & = T(4) + T(7) + T(8) - T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) + F(3) \times F(7) & = -T(2) + T(4) - T(3) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{29} & := F(2) \times F(5) + F(4) \times F(6) & = T(2) + T(5) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) + F(7) + F(5) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (T(7) - T(5)) - T(4) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5)) + F(7) & = T(3) + T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) & = -T(1) + T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(5) \times (-F(3) + F(6)) & = -T(1) + T(5) - T(3) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(2) + (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) - T(4) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(5) \times F(3) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times T(5) - T(3) - T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{30} & := F(1) \times F(2) + F(6) + F(8) & = (T(1) - T(2)) \times (T(6) - T(8)) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(3) - F(2) + F(9) & = (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\
 & := F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(8) & = -T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(3) - F(5) + F(9) & = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 & := F(1) - F(3) - F(4) + F(9) & = T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(3) \times F(5) \times F(4) & = (T(2) \times T(3) - T(5)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{30} & := (F(2) \times F(3) + F(6)) \times F(4) & = (-T(2) \times T(3) + T(6)) \times T(4) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(6) - T(4)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(4) + F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(4)) - T(8) \\
 & := -F(3) + F(4) - F(5) + F(9) & = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) - T(9) \\
 & := -F(3) + F(4) + F(6) + F(8) & = T(3) \times (-T(4) - T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(6) + F(2) - F(7) + F(9) & = -T(6) + T(2) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{30} & := F(1) \times F(5) \times (-F(3) + F(6)) & = T(1) \times T(5) - T(3) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(3) + F(7)) & = -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(3) \times F(5) + F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(5) \times (-F(3) + F(6)) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) - T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= F(2) + F(5) + F(6) \times F(4) &= (-T(2) - T(5) + T(6)) \times T(4) \\ &:= F(2) - F(7) + F(3) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(7) - T(3)) - T(8) \\ &:= F(5) \times (-F(3) - F(7) + F(8)) &= T(5) \times (-T(3) - T(7) + T(8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{31} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(5) \times F(7) - F(9) &= -T(1) + T(5) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= (-F(1) + F(4)) \times F(5) + F(8) &= T(1) \times T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) \times F(7) + F(5) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) - T(5) \\ &:= -F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) \times F(4) &= T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) + T(4) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6)) + F(7) &= -T(3) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(6)) + F(8) &= T(3) + T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(1) - F(5) \times (F(3) - F(6)) &= T(1) + T(5) - T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(7)) &= -T(1) - T(3) + T(4) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32} &:= (F(1) \times F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \\ &:= (-F(1) \times F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(2) - F(4) + F(9) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(7) + F(8) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) - F(4) + F(9) &= T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= (F(3) - F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(3) - T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= F(4) \times F(6) - F(5) + F(7) &= T(4) - T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{32} &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(4) + F(7)) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) - T(7) \\ &:= F(1) + F(5) \times F(7) - F(9) &= T(1) \times T(5) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times (-F(5) + F(7)) &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(1) - F(4)) \times (F(5) - F(8)) &= T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(4) + F(3) \times F(6) + F(7) &= -T(4) + T(3) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\ &:= F(4) + F(3) \times F(8) - F(7) &= (T(4) - T(3)) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \\ &:= -F(5) - F(3) + F(4) \times F(7) &= T(5) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{33} &:= F(1) \times F(2) - F(3) + F(9) &= (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(4) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(5) + F(7) &= -T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) - F(4) + F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(3) - T(4)) + T(9) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(5)) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(2) \times (-T(5) - T(4) + T(8)) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(5) + F(6) + F(8) &= T(2) + T(5) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) + F(5) - F(6) + F(9) &= -T(3) + T(5) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(4) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5) - T(4)) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) &= (T(2) - T(3)) \times (T(4) - T(6)) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(6) + F(3) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(6) + T(3) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{33} &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(7)) + F(5) &= -T(3) + T(2) \times (T(7) - T(5)) \\
 &:= F(3) + F(5) \times F(7) - F(9) &= T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) - T(9) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(6)) &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(4)) - T(6) \\
 &:= F(3) - F(6) + F(4) \times F(7) &= -T(3) + T(6) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(5) + F(7)) - F(8) &= T(4) + T(5) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) - (F(2) - F(5)) \times F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(2) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) &= T(1) \times T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(7)) &= T(1) - T(3) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(3) \times (F(5) - F(8)) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(3) + F(5) \times (-F(2) + F(6)) &= -T(3) + T(5) + T(2) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{34} &:= F(3) - F(5) + F(4) + F(9) &= -T(3) - T(5) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) \times F(5) + F(4) \times F(7) &= T(1) + T(5) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(5) + F(4) \times F(8) - F(9) &= T(5) + T(4) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(5) \times (-F(2) + F(6)) &= T(1) + T(5) - T(2) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(1) - F(4) + F(8)) &= (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(5) + F(7)) &= -T(3) - T(2) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) &= T(3) - T(2) + T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(6) + (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(7) &= T(6) \times T(2) - T(1) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{35} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(2) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(6) - F(7) &= T(1) - T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= (F(1) - F(3) + F(6)) \times F(5) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (T(6) - T(5)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(3) - F(5) + F(9) &= -T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(5) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) \times F(7) + F(6) &= (T(1) - T(3)) \times (-T(7) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{35} &:= (-F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(4)) &= T(2) \times (T(6) - T(3)) - T(4) \\
 &:= F(6) + F(2) + F(3) \times F(7) &= T(6) \times (-T(2) + T(3)) - T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(4) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) &= T(1) \times T(4) - T(2) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) &= T(2) + T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(7)) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) - T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) - F(3) \times (F(5) - F(8)) &= -T(4) - T(3) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(8) - F(2) - F(7)) &= (-T(5) + T(8)) \times T(2) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{36} &:= F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) + F(9) &= -T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(5) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(3) &= (T(1) + T(5) - T(4)) \times T(3) \\
 &:= -F(2) - F(5) + F(6) + F(9) &= -T(2) + T(5) - T(6) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= -F(3) \times F(4) + F(6) + F(9) &= T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) - T(9) \\ &:= F(3) + F(5) + F(6) + F(8) &= -T(3) - T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(7)) &= -T(1) - T(3) + T(5) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{36} &:= F(1) \times F(4) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) &= T(1) + T(4) - T(2) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(3)) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) &= -T(1) + T(3) + T(2) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(6) - F(3)) &= (-T(1) \times T(5) + T(6)) \times T(3) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(7) &= -T(2) - T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) &= (-T(2) - T(3) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(1)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) &= T(2) \times (-T(1) - T(5) + T(7)) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(4) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(1) + F(6)) &= T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(1) + T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{36} &:= (-F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(5) + F(7)) &= T(2) - T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(4) + F(5) \times F(6) &= T(2) \times T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times (-F(3) + F(6)) &= T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(3) + T(6)) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(5) + F(3) \times F(8) &= (-T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3) - T(8) \\ &:= (F(2) - F(7)) \times (-F(6) + F(5)) &= T(2) \times (T(7) - T(6)) + T(5) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7)) + F(6) &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(7) - T(6)) \\ &:= F(5) \times (F(2) + F(7)) - F(9) &= -T(5) + T(2) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(5) - F(8) + F(9)) &= T(3) \times (T(5) + T(8) - T(9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{37} &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(3) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(2) - T(3) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) + F(9) &= T(1) + T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(4) - F(2) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(2) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times F(6) + F(7) &= T(2) \times T(4) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) + F(9) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) - F(4) + F(5) + F(9) &= -T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(8) + F(6) - F(7) &= -T(3) + T(8) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(4) - F(2)) \times F(6) + F(8) &= T(4) + T(2) \times T(6) - T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) &= T(1) - T(3) \times (T(5) - T(6)) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5)) + F(8) &= T(3) + T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(7)) &= -T(1) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) \times (F(4) - F(8)) &= -T(2) - T(3) + T(4) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{38} &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(6) + F(7) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(6) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) - F(5) + F(6) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(5) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) + F(4) + F(7) + F(8) &= T(2) \times T(4) - T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) + F(4) + F(9) &= -T(2) + T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(1) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(7) & = -T(1) - T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{38} & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(3) + F(8)) & = -T(1) - T(2) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(2) + F(5) \times F(6) & = -T(1) + T(2) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(1) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(1) + (-F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(1) - T(3) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(2) + (-F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\
 & := F(3) - F(4) \times (F(1) - F(7)) & = T(3) \times (T(4) + T(1)) - T(7) \\
 & := F(4) - F(5) \times (F(2) - F(6)) & = -T(4) - T(5) + T(2) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{39} & := -F(1) \times F(6) + F(7) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(6) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(4) + F(9) & = T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := (-F(1) - F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = -T(1) - T(2) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := (-F(2) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(2) - T(3)) \times (T(5) - T(7)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(7) + F(8) + F(5) & = T(2) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(4) + F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4)) - T(8) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) + F(9) & = T(2) + T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{39} & := (F(3) - F(1)) \times F(5) + F(9) & = T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(5)) - T(9) \\
 & := -F(4) + F(6) + F(7) + F(8) & = T(4) + T(6) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(2) - F(4)) \times F(7) & = -T(5) + T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := -F(1) \times F(2) + F(5) \times F(6) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) - T(6) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times T(4) - T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(5) + F(6)) & = -T(2) + T(3) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (-F(6) + F(8)) & = -T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) - F(4)) + F(5) \times F(6) & = (-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{39} & := -F(4) \times F(1) + F(3) \times F(8) & = T(4) - T(1) - T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(5) - F(3)) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) & = -T(5) + T(3) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := -F(1) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(4) - T(6) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) & = T(1) \times T(3) - T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(6) \times (F(4) + F(3)) & = T(2) \times (T(6) - T(4)) + T(3) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(5) - F(7) + F(8)) & = -T(4) - T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(7)) & = -T(4) + T(3) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(5) + F(3) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(5) \times (T(3) - T(1)) - T(8) \\
 & := -F(5) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = -T(5) + T(3) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{40} & := (F(1) \times F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(6) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) + F(4) + F(9) & = -T(1) + T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4) + F(7) & = T(1) + T(6) - T(4) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (-F(3) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times F(6) &= -T(3) + T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(6) - F(5) + F(8) &= T(4) - T(6) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(4) \times F(7) - F(9)) \times F(6) &= T(4) \times (T(7) - T(9) + T(6)) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(2) + F(4) \times F(7) &= -T(1) + T(2) + T(4) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{40} &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(3) \times F(8) &= T(1) - T(2) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) - F(4) + F(3) \times F(8) &= T(1) \times T(4) - T(3) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6)) + F(7) &= T(4) \times (-T(2) - T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (F(4) - F(5)) \times (F(1) - F(8)) &= -T(4) + T(5) - T(1) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(7) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) - (F(3) - F(5)) \times F(7) &= T(2) - T(3) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(6) + F(7)) &= -T(3) - T(2) + T(6) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{41} &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(5) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(9) &= T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(5) - F(6) + F(9) &= -T(4) - T(5) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) \times F(4) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) &= -T(1) + T(3) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(3) + F(4) \times F(7) &= -T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(3) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= -F(2) + (F(6) + F(7)) \times F(3) &= T(2) \times T(6) - T(7) + T(3) \\
 &:= F(3) - (F(5) - F(6)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times T(5) - T(6) - T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) - F(4) \times (F(6) - F(8)) &= -T(3) - T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(4) + F(3) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= T(4) - T(3) + T(1) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{42} &:= (-F(1) \times F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) &= -T(1) - T(2) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(1) \times F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(1) - T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(6) + F(7) + F(8) &= -T(1) - T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(3) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(4) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 &:= (-F(1) - F(5) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(2) - F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= -T(2) - T(3) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(3) + F(5) + F(9) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{42} &:= (F(2) + F(4) - F(3)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(4)) \times T(3) - T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(6) - F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(6) + T(5) - T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) + F(9) &= T(2) \times T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(7) - F(5) + F(8) &= T(3) \times (T(7) + T(5) - T(8)) \\
 &:= -F(3) - F(4) + F(7) + F(9) &= T(3) \times (-T(4) - T(7) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (-F(4) + F(5)) \times F(2) \times F(8) &= T(4) \times T(5) - T(2) \times T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= F(4) + F(7) - F(6) + F(9) &= -T(4) + T(7) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= (-F(6) - F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(6) \times (T(4) + T(7) - T(8)) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= -T(1) - T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{42} &:= F(1) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(7) &= ((T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4)) - T(7) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(5)) - T(6) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(1)) \times (-F(7) + F(9)) &= T(2) \times (T(1) + T(7)) - T(9) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= T(2) - T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(5) \times F(6) &= (-T(2) - T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times (-F(2) + F(6)) &= T(3) \times T(4) + T(2) - T(6) \\ &:= (F(4) - F(5)) \times (F(7) - F(9)) &= T(4) + T(5) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(6) \times F(2) + F(7)) &= T(3) \times T(6) - T(2) \times T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{43} &:= F(1) + F(6) + F(7) + F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) + F(4) + F(5) + F(9) &= T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(4) + F(7) + F(9) &= -T(2) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(6) &= -T(2) + T(4) + T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times (T(5) - T(4)) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) - (F(2) - F(4)) \times F(8) &= -T(1) \times T(2) + T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= -T(1) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(4) - F(3) \times (F(2) - F(8)) &= T(4) - T(3) + T(2) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44} &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(9) \\ &:= F(3) + F(4) + F(5) + F(9) &= -T(3) - T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= (-F(3) + F(6)) \times F(7) - F(9) &= T(3) + T(6) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) \times F(8) &= -T(1) + T(2) + T(3) + T(8) \\ &:= (-F(1) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &= T(1) + T(4) - T(2) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times (-F(3) + F(7)) &= T(1) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(8) &= -T(2) - T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{44} &:= (F(2) - F(5)) \times (F(3) - F(7)) &= (-T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(4) + F(3) \times F(9) - F(8) &= -T(4) + T(3) \times (T(9) - T(8)) \\ &:= (-F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &= -T(4) + T(5) + T(2) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) - (F(2) - F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times T(2) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(1) + F(6) + F(7)) &= -T(3) + T(1) + T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(3) + (F(5) - F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times T(5) - T(4) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{45} &:= (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(5) &= (-T(1) - T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) \\ &:= (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(2) \times F(5) &= (-T(1) + T(6)) \times T(2) - T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times F(6) + F(8) &= T(2) \times T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(5) &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(6) + F(8) &= (T(2) - T(3)) \times (T(6) - T(8)) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(9)) \times F(3) - F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(9) + T(3) - T(8)) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(3) + F(6)) \times F(5) &= T(2) + T(3) + T(6) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{45} &:= (-F(2) + F(8)) \times F(3) + F(5) &= T(2) \times (T(8) - T(3) - T(5)) \\
 &:= -F(3) \times F(2) + F(7) + F(9) &= T(3) + T(2) \times T(7) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(4) + F(5) + F(9) &= (T(3) + T(4) - T(5)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(5) + F(2) + F(9) &= -T(3) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(6) - F(5) + F(9) &= T(3) - T(6) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(3) - F(6) + F(8) + F(9) &= T(3) \times T(6) - T(8) - T(9) \\
 &:= (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(6) + F(7) &= T(4) + T(2) \times T(6) - T(7) \\
 &:= -F(5) \times F(3) + F(8) + F(9) &= T(5) \times (-T(3) - T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{45} &:= F(1) + F(3) \times F(5) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(1) + F(9)) - F(8) &= (T(3) - T(1)) \times (T(9) - T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(1) + F(6)) &= T(3) \times (T(4) + T(1)) - T(6) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) &= -T(3) + T(4) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 &:= -F(3) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(7) &= T(3) + T(6) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(3) - F(6) + F(8)) &= T(4) \times T(3) + T(6) - T(8) \\
 &:= -F(4) + (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(4) - T(1) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(5) - F(3) \times (F(1) - F(8)) &= (T(5) - T(3)) \times T(1) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{46} &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(3) + F(9) &= T(1) + T(5) \times T(3) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(8) &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(5) + F(3) \times F(8) &= T(1) + T(5) - T(3) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times F(7) + F(8) &= -T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(3) + F(5) \times F(6) &= T(4) - T(3) \times (T(5) - T(6)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{47} &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times F(7) + F(8) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(7) + F(8) &= -T(1) + T(2) \times T(7) - T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(6) &= -T(1) - T(5) + T(2) \times T(6) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(6) \times F(3) \times F(4) &= T(2) \times T(6) - T(3) - T(4) \\
 &:= F(5) + (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(8) &= T(5) - T(1) - T(2) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(5) + (F(4) + F(2)) \times F(7) &= (T(5) + T(4)) \times T(2) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{48} &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(2) \times F(6) &= -T(1) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(6) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(1) + T(6) - T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(1) + F(7) + F(9) &= T(2) \times (-T(1) - T(7) + T(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= (F(2) + F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(6) &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(4)) + T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(5) + F(6) + F(9) &= -T(2) - T(5) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(5) + F(4) &= T(2) \times (T(6) - T(5) + T(4)) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(5)) + T(6) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(8)) \times F(3) + F(6) &= -T(2) + T(8) - T(3) + T(6)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{48} &:= F(3) \times F(9) + F(1) - F(8) &= T(3) \times (T(9) - T(1) - T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(2) + F(4)) \times F(6) &= T(3) \times (-T(2) - T(4) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (-F(3) - F(5) + F(7)) \times F(6) &= T(3) \times (T(5) - T(7) + T(6)) \\
 &:= F(5) \times F(6) - F(7) + F(8) &= (T(5) - T(6)) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\
 &:= -F(6) + F(2) + F(8) + F(9) &= T(6) - T(2) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) \times F(7) + F(8) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= -T(1) + T(2) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times (-F(7) + F(8)) &= -T(1) - T(5) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(5) + F(3) \times F(8) &= (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) - T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{48} &:= F(2) \times F(3) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(3) \times F(7) + F(8) &= (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(7) - T(8) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (-F(5) + F(8)) &= T(2) - T(3) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(6)) + F(9) &= -T(3) \times T(2) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times (-F(7) + F(8)) &= -T(3) - T(4) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(7)) &= -T(3) + T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (F(4) + F(1)) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(2)) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(6) - F(2)) + F(7) &= -T(5) - T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (-F(5) + F(6) + F(8)) &= T(3) - T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (-F(5) - F(7) + F(9)) &= -T(4) - T(5) + T(7) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{49} &:= (F(1) \times F(4)) \times F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) - T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(7)) \times F(5) - F(8) &= T(1) \times T(7) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) - F(4) &= T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) + T(4) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(7) + F(4) + F(9) &= T(2) \times T(7) + T(4) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(6) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) - T(6) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(5) + F(2)) \times F(6) &= T(1) - T(5) + T(2) \times T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= -T(2) + T(3) + T(4) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{50} &:= (F(2) \times F(4)) \times F(8) - F(7) &= T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(8)) - T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) + F(6) &= (T(2) - T(4)) + T(8) + T(6) \\
 &:= (F(4) - F(1) + F(6)) \times F(5) &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(6) - T(5)) \\
 &:= F(4) - F(6) + F(8) + F(9) &= -T(4) - T(6) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(6) + F(3) \times F(8) &= -T(1) + T(6) - T(3) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= F(1) + F(4) \times F(5) + F(9) &= -T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(5) \times (-F(4) + F(7)) &= -T(2) + T(5) + T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(3) + (-F(1) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= T(3) + T(1) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(3) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(4)) - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{51} &:= -F(2) - F(4) + F(8) + F(9) &= -T(2) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(6) + F(3) \times F(8) &= T(1) \times T(6) - T(3) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(3) \times F(6)) \times F(4) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6) - T(4)) \\ &:= F(2) + F(6) + F(8) \times F(3) &= T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) + T(3) \\ &:= F(2) - F(7) + F(4) \times F(8) &= -T(2) + T(7) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) + (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times (-T(1) - T(4) + T(7)) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= -T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(8) \\ &:= F(2) + F(5) \times (F(3) + F(6)) &= ((-T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3)) - T(6) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(2) - F(5) + F(8)) &= ((T(4) \times T(2)) - T(5)) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{52} &:= (-F(1) \times F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) \\ &:= (F(2) - F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= T(2) + T(3) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times T(4) - T(3) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(2) - F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times T(5) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(5) - F(4)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times T(5) - T(4) - T(7) \\ &:= F(5) \times F(7) + F(8) - F(9) &= T(5) + T(7) - T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) + F(4) \times F(8) - F(7) &= T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) + T(7) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(5) - F(7) + F(9)) &= -T(3) - T(5) + T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(6) + F(3) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= T(6) - T(3) + T(1) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{53} &:= -F(1) \times F(3) + F(8) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) \\ &:= F(2) + F(8) - F(4) + F(9) &= T(2) \times T(8) - T(4) - T(9) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) + F(7) &= T(3) \times T(4) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(3) + F(6) + F(7) + F(9) &= T(3) \times T(6) - T(7) - T(9) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(6) + F(4) \times F(8) &= T(3) + T(6) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(1) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(4) \times (F(5) + F(7)) &= T(1) \times T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(7) + F(4) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= T(7) - T(4) - T(1) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{54} &:= -F(1) \times F(2) + F(9) + F(8) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(9) - T(8) \\ &:= F(1) - F(3) + F(8) + F(9) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) \\ &:= (F(2) - F(6) + F(9)) \times F(3) &= T(2) \times (-T(6) + T(9) - T(3)) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(8) - F(1) + F(7) &= T(3) \times (T(8) + T(1) - T(7)) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= -F(2) + F(7) + F(3) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(7) + T(3) - T(8) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6)) &= T(3) \times (T(4) \times T(2) - T(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{54} &:= (F(3) - F(5)) \times (F(4) - F(8)) &= (-T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) - T(8) \\ &:= -F(4) - F(6) + F(5) \times F(7) &= -T(4) + T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(1) + (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(5) &= (T(1) - T(4)) \times (-T(6) + T(5)) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(5) \times (F(4) + F(6)) &= T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4)) - T(6) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(1) + F(5) + F(8)) &= T(3) \times T(1) \times T(5) - T(8) \\ &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5) + F(8)) &= T(3) - T(2) + T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) &= (T(3) - T(2)) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(3) \times F(5) + F(6)) &= T(4) \times T(3) + T(5) - T(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{55} &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(8) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(3) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\ &:= (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4) + F(9) &= -T(1) + T(6) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) + F(9) &= T(2) - T(6) + T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(4) + F(9) &= T(3) \times T(5) + T(4) - T(9) \\ &:= F(4) \times F(2) \times F(8) - F(6) &= T(4) + T(2) \times (T(8) - T(6)) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(5) \times (-F(3) + F(7)) &= T(2) \times (T(5) - T(3)) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(7) + F(3) \times F(8) &= -T(2) + T(7) - T(3) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(7) \times F(2) + F(3) \times F(9) &= T(7) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(9) \\ &:= F(4) + F(3) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= T(4) - T(3) + T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(5) \times (F(4) \times F(6) - F(7)) &= -T(5) + T(4) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\ &:= F(7) - (F(1) - F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(7) + T(1) - T(4) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{56} &:= (-F(2) + F(5) + F(4)) \times F(6) &= T(2) \times T(5) - T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= (-F(4) + F(8)) \times F(5) - F(9) &= -T(4) + T(8) - T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) \times F(8) + F(7) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \\ &:= F(1) - F(5) \times (F(3) - F(7)) &= (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(3) - T(7) \\ &:= F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(4) + F(7)) &= T(6) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{57} &:= F(2) \times F(3) + F(8) + F(9) &= T(2) - T(3) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(8) + F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(4) - T(8) + T(9)) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(7)) \times F(4) + F(8) &= T(2) + T(7) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) \times F(7) - F(4) + F(9) &= -T(3) + T(7) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(9) &= T(1) - T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times (-F(5) + F(9)) &= T(2) - T(3) + T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= F(5) - F(3) \times (F(6) - F(9)) &= -T(5) + T(3) + T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= F(7) + F(3) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= T(7) - T(3) - T(1) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(7) + F(3) \times (F(2) + F(9)) &= (T(7) + T(3)) \times T(2) - T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 58 & := F(3) \times F(8) + F(7) + F(4) & = T(3) \times (T(8) - T(7)) + T(4) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(5) + F(9)) & = T(1) - T(2) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(2) \times F(5) + F(4) \times F(8) & = -T(2) + T(5) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(6) - F(7) + F(9)) & = T(3) - T(6) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) - F(5) \times (F(3) - F(7)) & = (-T(4) + T(5)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(5) + (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(5) + T(1) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 59 & := (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(5) - F(8) & = T(4) + T(7) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(6) + F(3) \times F(9) & = -T(1) + T(6) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(4) \times F(6) + F(9) & = T(2) - T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(3) \times F(4) + F(5) \times F(7) & = T(3) + T(4) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(6) \times (-F(4) + F(7)) - F(8) & = -T(6) + T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = -T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(6) \\
 \\
 60 & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (T(6) - T(5)) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(4)) \times F(7) + F(9) & = -T(2) - T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) + F(6) & = T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(6) + F(3) + F(9) & = -T(4) \times T(6) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(5) + F(6) + F(7) + F(9) & = T(5) \times (T(6) + T(7) - T(9)) \\
 & := -F(1) \times F(6) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(1) \times T(6) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(5) \times F(6) + F(8) & = T(2) \times T(5) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (-T(3) - T(4) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(7) + F(3)) & = T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) + T(3) \\
 \\
 60 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(3) + F(6)) & = T(2) \times T(5) - T(3) + T(6) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(7) + F(3)) & = (-T(2) - T(5) + T(7)) \times T(3) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (-F(2) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(2)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) - F(5)) \times (F(1) - F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(1)) - T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) - F(5)) \times (F(2) - F(8)) & = T(3) + T(5) + T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := F(7) \times (F(3) + F(2)) + F(8) & = T(7) \times T(3) - T(2) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (-F(1) - F(4) + F(9)) & = T(3) - T(1) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) - F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6) + F(8)) & = T(3) - T(2) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(6) + (-F(4) + F(5)) \times F(9) & = T(6) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) - T(9) \\
 \\
 61 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(7) & = -T(2) + T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) + F(8) & = -T(3) + T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(1) - F(6) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(6) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(9)) & = T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(5) + F(4) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(5) + T(4) \times T(1) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{62} & := -F(1) \times F(2) + F(8) \times F(4) & = (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(8) - T(4) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(3) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(1) - F(3) + F(5) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(5) - T(7) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(4) \times (-F(7) + F(9)) & = -T(1) - T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(4) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(3) + F(6) \times (-F(7) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(6) - T(7) - T(8) \\
 & := -F(4) + F(5) \times (-F(6) + F(8)) & = -T(4) + T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{63} & := (-F(1) - F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(4) - F(2)) \times F(8) & = (-T(1) + T(4)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := (-F(2) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(2) - T(3)) \times (T(5) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) + F(8) + F(9) & = T(2) - T(6) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(7) + F(4) + F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(7) - T(4)) - T(9) \\
 & := (-F(5) \times F(3) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(5) - T(3) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(2) - F(4)) \times F(8) & = -T(5) + T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(9)) \times F(3) - F(8) & = T(6) \times (T(9) - T(3) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(1) - T(4)) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(4) \times (-F(7) + F(9)) & = -T(1) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{63} & := -F(2) \times F(5) + F(3) \times F(9) & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(3) - T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(6)) & = T(3) \times (T(5) - T(1)) - T(6) \\
 & := (-F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(3) - T(5)) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\
 & := -F(4) + F(2) + F(5) \times F(7) & = -T(4) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = (-T(5) + T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(6) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(6) \times (-F(5) + F(7)) & = -T(1) + T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(2) + (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = T(2) - T(4) \times (T(5) - T(6)) \\
 & := -F(3) + F(5) \times F(2) \times F(7) & = -T(3) - T(5) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 & := -F(5) + (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = T(5) \times T(1) + T(2) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{64} & := F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) + F(9) & = -T(3) + T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := (-F(3) - F(4) + F(7)) \times F(6) & = -T(3) + T(4) \times (T(7) - T(6)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(6) \times (-F(5) + F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (-F(3) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times (-F(5) + F(8)) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(2) - F(4) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(8) + F(3)) - F(5) & = T(4) - T(8) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(1) - F(4) \times (F(7) - F(9)) & = T(1) - T(4) + T(7) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$:= -F(2) + (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7) = T(2) \times T(4) + T(3) + T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65 &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(7) = (T(1) - T(3)) \times (T(5) - T(7)) \\ &:= (-F(2) \times F(4) + F(6)) \times F(7) = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(6)) - T(7) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(7) = T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(7) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(5) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) = -T(1) - T(5) + T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(8) = -T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) = -T(3) - T(4) + T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(5) + F(4) \times F(7) + F(8) = -T(5) + T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\ &:= F(1) - F(6) \times (F(5) - F(7)) = T(1) + T(6) + T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(4) + (F(1) + F(2)) \times F(9) = -T(4) \times (T(1) - T(2)) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(5) + F(3) \times (F(1) + F(9)) = T(5) + T(3) - T(1) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 66 &:= -F(3) + F(7) + F(9) + F(8) = T(3) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) - T(8) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(9)) = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(8) = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(2) + F(8)) = -T(3) + (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(8) \\ &:= -F(3) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(8) = T(3) \times (-T(5) - T(4) + T(8)) \\ &:= F(1) - F(5) \times (F(8) - F(9)) = -T(1) \times T(5) + T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(7) \times F(2) \times F(5) = (-T(1) + T(7)) \times T(2) - T(5) \\ &:= F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(7) + F(8)) = T(3) \times (T(2) - T(7) + T(8)) \\ &:= F(3) + (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) = T(3) \times T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(2) - F(7) + F(9)) = -T(4) + T(2) + T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(6) - F(3) \times (F(5) - F(9)) = T(6) \times T(3) - T(5) - T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 67 &:= F(3) \times F(2) + F(5) \times F(7) = -T(3) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(4) \times (-F(3) + F(7)) + F(9) = (T(4) - T(3)) \times T(7) - T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + (-F(4) + F(5)) \times F(9) = -T(2) + T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times (F(7) + F(8)) = -T(2) + T(3) + T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) - (F(4) - F(6)) \times F(7) = T(3) \times T(4) - T(6) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 68 &:= (F(4) \times F(5) - F(7)) \times F(9) = T(4) - T(5) + T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) + F(1) + F(5) \times F(7) = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(5)) - T(7) \\ &:= F(3) \times (-F(5) + F(7) \times F(4)) = T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) - T(4) \\ &:= F(6) - F(4) \times (F(1) - F(8)) = T(6) + T(4) + T(1) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 69 &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(8) = -T(2) + T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) + F(7) + F(8) + F(9) = T(2) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) + T(9) \\ &:= (F(6) - F(2)) \times F(5) + F(9) = -T(6) + T(2) \times T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) + F(4) + F(5) \times F(7) = T(2) \times (T(4) - T(5) + T(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &:= F(3) \times (F(9) - F(2)) + F(4) &= -T(3) + T(9) + T(2) \times T(4) \\
 &:= -F(3) - F(9) + F(8) \times F(5) &= T(3) \times (T(9) - T(8)) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(5) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(8) &= T(5) \times (-T(2) + T(4)) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(1) - (F(4) - F(5)) \times F(9) &= -T(1) + T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(1) + F(3) \times (F(7) + F(8)) &= -T(1) + T(3) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(1) + F(5) \times (F(2) + F(7)) &= -T(1) \times T(5) + T(2) \times T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(3) - F(7) + F(9)) &= -T(4) + T(3) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(5) - F(6) \times (F(7) - F(8)) &= T(5) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) - T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{70} &:= (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times F(5) &= T(1) - T(6) + T(3) \times T(5) \\
 &:= F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(2) + F(7)) &= (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(6) + F(4) \times F(8) &= T(2) + T(6) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) &= T(3) \times (T(4) - T(2)) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) + F(3) + F(5) \times F(7) &= T(4) \times (-T(3) - T(5) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (-F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= T(4) + T(5) \times T(1) + T(9) \\
 &:= (-F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(1) + F(7)) &= T(4) \times (-T(6) \times T(1) + T(7)) \\
 &:= F(6) - F(3) \times (F(4) - F(9)) &= T(6) - T(3) + T(4) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{71} &:= (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) - F(7) &= -T(2) + T(4) + T(8) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(4) + F(5) \times F(6) + F(9) &= -T(4) + T(5) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(8) + F(2)) + F(5) &= -T(4) + T(8) + T(2) \times T(5) \\
 &:= F(1) + (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(5) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(7) + T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{72} &:= (-F(2) + F(7)) \times F(3) \times F(4) &= T(2) \times (T(7) + T(3) - T(4)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(6) &= T(3) \times (T(1) - T(4) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (F(1) + F(5)) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) &= -T(1) + T(5) \times T(2) + T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(6) &= T(2) + T(3) \times T(5) - T(6) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(5) \times F(8) - F(9) &= T(2) \times (T(5) - T(8) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= T(2) \times (T(3) \times T(4) - T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(2) - F(5)) \times (F(4) - F(8)) &= (-T(2) + T(5) - T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(5) + F(3) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times (-T(5) - T(3) + T(9)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) &= (T(4) - T(3)) \times (-T(2) + T(6)) \\
 &:= F(3) + F(5) \times (F(1) + F(7)) &= T(3) \times (-T(5) - T(1) + T(7)) \\
 &:= -F(4) + F(5) \times (F(3) + F(7)) &= T(4) + T(5) \times T(3) - T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{73} &:= (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(7) + F(8) &= -T(1) + T(4) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) + F(9) &= T(3) \times T(5) + T(7) - T(9) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(9)) &= T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(5) - (F(2) - F(4)) \times F(9) &= T(5) + T(2) + T(4) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(5) + F(3) \times F(4) \times F(7) &= -T(5) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(5) + F(3) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = T(5) - T(3) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{74} & := (-F(1) + F(8)) \times F(3) + F(9) & = -T(1) + T(8) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = -T(1) + T(2) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(7) + F(8)) & = -T(3) + T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{75} & := (F(2) \times F(3) + F(7)) \times F(5) & = -T(2) + T(3) \times (T(7) - T(5)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(8) - F(1) + F(9) & = -T(3) + T(8) \times T(1) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(6) + F(3) \times F(9) & = (-T(1) + T(6)) \times T(3) - T(9) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(7) + F(4) \times F(8) & = T(1) + T(7) + T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(6) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(2) + T(6) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (-F(1) - F(6) + F(9)) & = T(4) - T(1) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (-F(6) - F(2) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(6) - T(2) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(3) - F(6) + F(8)) & = T(5) \times T(3) + T(6) - T(8) \\
 & := F(5) \times (-F(1) + F(3) \times F(6)) & = (T(5) + T(1)) \times T(3) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{76} & := F(1) \times F(3) \times F(8) + F(9) & = T(1) - T(3) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := (-F(1) + F(4)) \times F(9) + F(6) & = T(1) \times T(4) + T(9) + T(6) \\
 & := (-F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) + F(9) & = T(4) - T(5) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{77} & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(6) + F(7) & = (-T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) - T(7) \\
 & := -F(1) + ((-F(3) + F(6)) \times F(7)) & = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(6) - T(7) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(4) \times (-F(6) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{78} & := (F(1) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(7) & = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := (-F(1) + F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(7)) \times F(5) + F(6) & = T(2) \times T(7) + T(5) - T(6) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(3) + F(9) & = T(2) + T(8) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (-F(6) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (-F(6) + F(9)) & = -T(2) + T(3) \times T(6) - T(9) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(2)) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) & = T(5) + T(2) \times T(8) - T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (-F(2) + F(6) \times F(5)) & = (T(3) - T(2)) \times T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(5) - F(7) + F(9)) & = -T(4) + T(5) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{79} & := F(2) - F(4) \times (F(6) - F(9)) & = T(2) + T(4) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(2) + (-F(4) + F(7)) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(2) + (F(7) + F(4)) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times T(7) + T(4) - T(5) \\
 & := F(7) - F(3) \times (F(1) - F(9)) & = T(7) + T(3) \times T(1) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{80} & := F(4) \times F(9) - F(1) - F(8) & = T(4) \times (T(9) - T(1) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(6) \times (F(7) - F(4)) & = (T(1) - T(6) + T(7)) \times T(4) \\
 & := (F(1) - F(5)) \times (F(2) - F(8)) & = -T(1) + T(5) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(7) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(7) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(7) \times F(4)) \times F(3) & = T(2) \times T(7) - T(4) + T(3) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(5)) - T(7) \\
 & := F(6) \times (-F(2) - F(3) + F(7)) & = (T(6) - T(2)) \times T(3) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{81} & := F(1) \times F(4) \times F(9) - F(8) & = (T(1) - T(4)) \times (-T(9) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(9) - F(8) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(9) - T(8)) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(4)) \times F(9) + F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(4) + T(9) - T(7)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(5) - F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(8) - T(5)) - T(9) \\
 & := F(5) + F(6) + F(3) \times F(9) & = (-T(5) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) - F(6) \times (F(4) - F(7)) & = T(2) \times T(6) - T(4) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) + F(5) \times F(3) \times F(6) & = -T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 & := -F(8) + (F(6) - F(5)) \times F(9) & = T(8) \times T(6) - T(5) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{82} & := -F(2) + F(6) \times F(7) - F(8) & = -T(2) + T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(6) - F(1) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times T(6) + T(1) - T(9) \\
 & := -F(5) + F(4) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(5) + T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(7) + F(5) \times (-F(3) + F(8)) & = T(7) + T(5) \times T(3) - T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{83} & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) - F(6) & = T(3) \times T(5) - T(7) + T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{84} & := (-F(1) \times F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(2)) \times (-T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 & := (-F(1) - F(6) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = -T(1) + T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6) - F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times T(6) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) - F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(3) - T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(8)) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(4)) \times (-F(7) + F(9)) & = T(1) + T(4) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(9) + F(6)) & = T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(9)) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{84} & := (-F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = (-T(2) - T(5) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(2) - F(5)) \times (F(7) - F(9)) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(7)) - T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = (-T(3) + T(4) - T(1)) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times (-F(1) + F(7)) & = T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(1) + T(7)) \\
 & := (-F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(5) - T(6) - T(9) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(3)) \times (-F(2) + F(7)) & = (-T(5) + T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(6) - F(3)) \times (F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(6) - T(3) \times T(2)) \times T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(3) \times (F(8) + F(9) - F(7)) & = (-T(3) - T(8) + T(9)) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) - F(6) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{86} & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(7) + F(8) & = T(3) - T(4) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(4) + F(8)) - F(9) & = T(5) - T(4) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{87} & := (-F(1) + F(9)) \times F(3) + F(8) & = T(1) \times T(9) + T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = -T(2) + T(3) \times T(6) - T(8) \\
 & := F(7) + F(6) \times F(5) + F(9) & = -T(7) \times T(6) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 & := -F(2) + (-F(3) + F(7)) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(7) + F(3) \times F(6)) & = (-T(4) + T(7)) \times T(3) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{88} & := -F(1) + F(8) + F(3) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(8) + T(3) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(6)) \times (-F(5) + F(7)) & = T(4) \times (T(6) - T(5)) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(6)) \times (-F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(4) - T(6)) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\
 & := -F(4) + (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(4) - T(3)) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(6) \times (-F(1) - F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(6) - T(1)) \times T(2) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{89} & := (-F(1) + F(4)) \times F(9) + F(8) & = -T(1) + T(4) \times (T(9) - T(8)) \\
 & := (F(4) - F(2)) \times F(9) + F(8) & = -T(4) + T(2) \times T(9) - T(8) \\
 & := -F(7) + (F(2) + F(3)) \times F(9) & = -T(7) + T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{90} & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(6) - T(3) + T(5)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(5) \times (F(8) - F(4)) & = (T(2) \times T(5) - T(8)) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(6) - T(5) \\
 & := -F(7) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(9) & = (-T(7) + T(2) \times T(4)) \times T(9) \\
 & := -F(1) + (-F(2) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = -T(1) + T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(8) + F(6) \times F(4)) & = (-T(3) + T(8) - T(6)) \times T(4) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(1) - F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(4) - T(1)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(2) - F(5) + F(9)) & = (-T(4) - T(2) + T(5)) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{91} & := (-F(1) \times F(2) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = ((T(1) \times T(2)) \times T(6)) + T(7) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(2) - F(3) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(6) + T(7) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(2) - T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(7)) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(3) - F(4)) \times F(7) & = -T(6) + (-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(5) \times F(8) - F(7) & = T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(2) - F(5) \times (F(4) - F(8)) & = T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{92} & := (F(3) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(4)) & = -T(3) + T(8) \times T(2) - T(4) \\
 & := F(1) - (F(2) - F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{93} & := (F(2) + F(3)) \times (-F(4) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(4)) + T(9) \\
 & := F(2) - F(7) + F(5) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(5)) - T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(7) \times F(3) + F(5)) & = (-T(4) + T(7)) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 & := -F(4) + (F(7) - F(2)) \times F(6) & = (T(4) + T(7)) \times T(2) - T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{94} & := F(4) \times (F(8) - F(2)) + F(9) & = T(4) + T(8) + T(2) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(6) + F(4) \times F(7)) & = T(3) \times (T(6) - T(4)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{95} & := F(4) - F(7) + F(8) \times F(5) & = T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(1) + F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(7) - T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{96} & := (-F(2) + F(5)) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(4)) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = (T(3) - T(1)) \times T(5) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(8)) & = (-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + F(4) \times F(9) - F(6) & = (T(3) - T(4)) \times (-T(9) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(5) - F(6)) \times (F(3) - F(9)) & = T(5) + T(6) \times T(3) - T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(1) + F(7) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times (-T(1) - T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{97} & := -F(3) - F(5) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times T(5) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{98} & := -F(1) - F(5) + F(6) \times F(7) & = (T(1) - T(5)) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\
 & := F(3) - F(6) \times (F(1) - F(7)) & = T(3) \times T(6) \times T(1) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{99} & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) + F(6) & = T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times (-F(3) + F(7)) & = T(1) + T(6) \times T(3) - T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(5) + F(9)) + F(8) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(9) - T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + F(4) \times F(8) + F(9) & = (-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(8) - T(9) \\
 & := F(3) + F(8) \times F(5) - F(6) & = -T(3) \times T(8) + T(5) \times T(6) \\
 & := -F(3) - F(1) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(4)) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(3) - F(2) + F(4) \times F(9) & = -T(3) + T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(9)) \\
 & := (-F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = -T(3) + T(7) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 & := F(3) - F(5) + F(4) \times F(9) & = -T(3) + T(5) \times T(4) - T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (-F(6) + F(9)) + F(8) & = (T(4) - T(6)) \times (-T(9) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(5) - F(6)) \times (F(2) - F(9)) & = -T(5) - T(6) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{100} & := -F(1) - F(2) + F(9) \times F(4) & = (-T(1) + T(2)) \times T(9) + T(4) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(8)) \times (F(3) + F(4)) & = T(2) \times (T(8) - T(3)) + T(4)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &:= F(4) \times (F(1) + F(8)) + F(9) &= T(4) \times (T(1) - T(8) + T(9)) \\ &:= F(4) \times (F(2) + F(9)) - F(5) &= T(4) + T(2) \times (T(9) - T(5)) \\ &:= -F(4) - F(2) + F(6) \times F(7) &= T(4) \times (T(2) - T(6) + T(7)) \\ &:= -F(5) + (-F(6) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(5) + T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{101} &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(6) \times F(7) &= T(2) + T(3) \times T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= F(6) \times (-F(4) + F(7)) + F(8) &= T(6) - T(4) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\ &:= -F(4) + F(6) \times F(2) \times F(7) &= T(4) + T(6) \times T(2) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{102} &:= (F(1) \times F(2) + F(3)) \times F(9) &= (-T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \\ &:= F(2) \times F(1) \times F(4) \times F(9) &= T(2) \times (-T(1) - T(4) + T(9)) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(4) \times F(9) &= -T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(8)) \times F(5) - F(6) &= T(2) \times T(8) + T(5) - T(6) \\ &:= (F(2) - F(4) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= -T(2) + T(4) \times T(5) - T(9) \\ &:= (F(3) \times F(7) + F(6)) \times F(4) &= T(3) \times (T(7) - T(6) + T(4)) \\ &:= (-F(3) + F(7) - F(6)) \times F(9) &= T(3) \times T(7) - T(6) - T(9) \\ &:= (F(5) \times F(2) - F(3)) \times F(9) &= -T(5) + T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(9)) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(1) + F(7) \times F(6) &= T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(7)) + T(6) \\ &:= (F(2) + F(3)) \times (F(7) + F(8)) &= T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(7)) + T(8) \\ &:= F(4) \times (-F(6) + F(3) \times F(8)) &= (-T(4) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{103} &:= -F(1) + F(6) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) &= T(1) + T(6) + T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= T(2) \times (T(4) + T(5)) + T(7) \\ &:= F(4) - F(5) \times (F(2) - F(8)) &= T(4) - T(5) + T(2) \times T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{104} &:= (F(1) + F(6) - F(2)) \times F(7) &= -T(1) + T(6) + T(2) \times T(7) \\ &:= (F(3) - F(1)) \times F(6) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times (T(1) + T(6)) - T(7) \\ &:= F(1) \times F(3) + F(4) \times F(9) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(4) \times F(9) &= -T(1) + T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(9)) \\ &:= (F(4) + F(1)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(5)) - T(8) \\ &:= (F(4) + F(2)) \times (F(9) - F(6)) &= -T(4) + T(2) \times T(9) - T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7)) &= -T(1) + T(5) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(8) \times (F(3) + F(4)) &= T(2) \times T(8) + T(3) - T(4) \\ &:= F(5) - F(4) \times (F(1) - F(9)) &= T(5) \times T(4) - T(1) - T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{105} &:= (-F(1) + F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(8) &= (T(1) - T(3)) \times (T(5) - T(8)) \\ &:= (-F(1) - F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(3)) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) \\ &:= (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(5) &= T(1) \times T(6) \times (-T(4) + T(5)) \\ &:= (-F(2) \times F(4) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) - T(4)) \times (T(6) - T(8)) \\ &:= (-F(2) + F(6) - F(3)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times T(6) + T(3) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(3) - F(5) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times T(5) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(8) + F(6) + F(9) & = T(4) \times (T(8) - T(6)) - T(9) \\
 & := F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = T(1) \times T(5) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{105} & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = T(2) \times (-T(4) \times T(1) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(8) \times (F(7) - F(6)) & = (-T(2) + T(8) - T(7)) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(4) \times F(9) & = (T(2) - T(3)) \times (T(4) - T(9)) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(3) + F(7) \times F(6) & = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(3) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (T(5) + T(4)) - T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (-F(2) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(5) - T(2) \times (T(3) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(2) + F(6) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) & = T(2) + T(6) + T(8) + T(9) \\
 & := F(4) - (F(5) - F(6)) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{106} & := -F(1) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(5) \times T(4) - T(9) \\
 & := F(1) + (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(4) & = T(1) + T(2) \times (T(9) - T(4)) \\
 & := F(1) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = T(1) - T(5) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{107} & := -F(2) + (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(9)) - T(4) \\
 & := F(3) - F(5) \times (F(7) - F(9)) & = T(3) \times T(5) - T(7) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{108} & := (F(2) + F(1) + F(9)) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (T(1) + T(9) - T(4)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(7) + F(8)) \times F(4) & = T(3) \times (-T(7) + T(8) + T(4)) \\
 & := (-F(1) + F(7)) \times (F(2) + F(6)) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(6) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(5) \times F(8) & = (T(2) \times T(3) - T(5)) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(5) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(2) + T(5) \times T(4) - T(9) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(5) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(2) - T(5) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(3) \times (F(5) + F(7)) & = -T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := F(4) - (F(6) - F(7)) \times F(8) & = (T(4) + T(6) - T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(7) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = (T(4) - T(7)) \times (-T(6) + T(5)) \\
 & := F(6) - F(5) \times (F(2) - F(8)) & = (T(6) - T(5) - T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{110} & := F(5) + F(4) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = -T(5) - T(4) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{111} & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = T(3) - T(2) \times (T(4) - T(9)) \\
 & := (-F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = T(3) + T(5) \times T(4) - T(9) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(3) - T(5) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{112} & := (-F(3) + F(4) + F(7)) \times F(6) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(7) - T(6)) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(3) \times F(7) + F(9) & = T(4) - T(3) \times (T(7) - T(9)) \\
 & := F(7) \times F(6) + F(5) + F(4) & = T(7) \times (-T(6) + T(5) + T(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(7)) & = (-T(4) + T(5) - T(1)) \times T(7) \\
 & := -F(5) + (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = (T(5) + T(1)) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{113} & := -F(3) + F(7) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times T(7) - T(4) - T(9) \\
 & := F(4) + F(5) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(5) - T(1) - T(8) \\
 & := F(4) + F(5) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = -T(4) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{114} & := F(3) \times F(5) \times F(6) + F(9) & = T(3) \times T(5) - T(6) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{115} & := F(5) \times (F(4) - F(1) + F(8)) & = T(5) \times T(4) + T(1) - T(8) \\
 \mathbf{116} & := F(3) \times (-F(5) + F(4) \times F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(5) - T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{117} & := (F(1) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) - T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(7)) \\
 & := (-F(1) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(7) & = -T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(7) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(5) \times F(8) + F(7) & = -T(2) + T(5) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(2) + T(3)) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(5)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{119} & := F(1) + F(5) \times F(8) + F(7) & = -T(1) + T(5) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \\
 & := F(4) \times F(5) + F(7) \times F(6) & = (-T(4) + T(5)) \times T(7) - T(6) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(5) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) - T(6) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(6) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{120} & := (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(5) & = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) \times F(4)) \times F(6) \times F(5) & = (-T(2) - T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(8)) \times F(3) \times F(4) & = T(2) \times (T(8) - T(3) + T(4)) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(9) - F(2)) + F(8) & = T(4) \times (T(9) + T(2) - T(8)) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(2)) \times (-F(1) + F(8)) & = T(5) - T(2) \times (T(1) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(1) + F(3) + F(8)) & = (T(5) - T(1)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := F(6) \times (-F(3) \times F(4) + F(8)) & = T(6) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{122} & := -F(4) + F(8) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(4) \times (T(8) - T(6)) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{123} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) - F(4) & = T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8) - T(4)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(8) + F(4) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(8) - T(4)) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{124} & := (-F(2) + F(8) \times F(4)) \times F(3) & = T(2) \times T(8) + T(4) + T(3) \\
 & := F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(5) \times F(7)) & = -T(3) + T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{125} & := (-F(1) + F(3) \times F(7)) \times F(5) & = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(7) - T(5)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 126 & := (-F(1) + F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(3) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(8)) \times F(6) - F(9) & = T(2) \times (T(8) + T(6)) - T(9) \\
 & := (-F(3) - F(5) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(3) - T(5) \times (T(7) - T(8)) \\
 & := (F(6) \times F(5) - F(9)) \times F(8) & = T(6) \times (T(5) - T(9) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(2) - F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(6) \times (-T(2) \times T(4) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(6) - F(2) - F(1)) \times F(8) & = T(6) - T(2) \times (T(1) - T(8)) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(4) \times (F(9) + F(6)) & = T(2) \times (-T(4) + T(9)) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) & = (-T(3) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 127 & := -F(4) + F(3) \times F(7) \times F(5) & = (T(4) - T(3)) \times T(7) + T(5) \\
 128 & := (F(1) + F(4) \times F(5)) \times F(6) & = -T(1) + T(4) \times T(5) - T(6) \\
 \\
 129 & := F(4) \times F(6) + F(5) \times F(8) & = (-T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(3) \times F(5) \times F(7) & = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(5) + T(7)) \\
 & := -F(2) + (F(3) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(2) \times (-T(3) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := -F(2) + (F(9) - F(6)) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times T(9) - T(6) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(4) + T(1)) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 \\
 130 & := (-F(1) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times F(7) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) \\
 & := (-F(4) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times F(7) & = T(4) \times (-T(6) + T(3) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(4) - F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(8)) & = T(4) \times (T(7) + T(6) - T(8)) \\
 \\
 132 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = (T(3) - T(4)) \times (T(2) - T(8)) \\
 & := -F(7) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(7) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) - T(8) \\
 \\
 133 & := F(4) \times F(5) \times F(6) + F(7) & = (-T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(7) \\
 \\
 135 & := (F(2) + F(7) \times F(3)) \times F(5) & = (-T(2) + T(7)) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 & := -F(4) + F(6) \times F(7) + F(9) & = (T(4) + T(6) - T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(5) & = (T(4) \times T(2) - T(6)) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(2) - F(6) + F(9)) & = (-T(5) - T(2) + T(6)) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (-F(3) + F(6) + F(8)) & = (T(5) - T(3)) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 136 & := (F(1) + F(2) + F(3)) \times F(9) & = T(1) - (T(2) - T(3)) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(1) - F(3) + F(5)) \times F(9) & = T(1) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 & := (-F(2) - F(6) + F(7)) \times F(9) & = T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5) \times F(7)) & = T(3) - T(4) \times (T(5) - T(7)) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(5) - F(2) + F(7)) & = (T(6) + T(5)) \times T(2) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{138} & := -F(2) + F(5) \times F(8) + F(9) & = T(2) - T(5) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) + (F(5) - F(2)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times T(5) + T(2) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{140} & := -F(2) + (F(7) + F(9)) \times F(4) & = (-T(2) - T(7) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{141} & := F(4) \times F(5) \times F(6) + F(8) & = (-T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + F(5) \times F(8) + F(9) & = T(3) - T(5) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times (T(2) + T(7)) - T(9) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) \times F(9) - F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(8) \times F(3) + F(5)) & = (-T(4) + T(8)) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 & := F(7) - F(6) \times (F(5) - F(8)) & = (T(7) - T(6)) \times T(5) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{143} & := (F(5) + F(4) \times F(3)) \times F(7) & = -T(5) - T(4) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(7) - F(3)) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) & = -T(7) + T(3) \times T(8) - T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{144} & := (-F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) - F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5)) - T(8) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(7) + F(3)) \times F(6) & = -T(4) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(6) \\
 & := (F(1) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = (-T(1) + T(5) - T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(2) \times F(6) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) & = (-T(2) + T(6)) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = (T(2) + T(5)) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 & := (-F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(8) + F(4)) & = -T(3) + (-T(6) + T(8)) \times T(4) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(9)) \times (-F(2) + F(5)) & = -(T(3) - (T(9) \times T(2))) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{144} & := F(4) \times (F(1) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = ((T(4) + T(1)) \times T(5)) - T(6) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(1) + F(8)) + F(9) & = (T(5) + T(1)) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(8) \times F(3) + F(4) \times F(9) & = -T(8) + ((-T(3) + T(4)) \times T(9)) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(5) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = (T(2) \times (T(5) + T(6))) + T(8) \\
 & := F(6) \times (-F(2) - F(3) + F(8)) & = ((T(6) - T(2)) \times T(3)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(6) + (F(1) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = (T(6) \times (-T(1) + T(4))) - T(9) \\
 & := F(6) + (F(2) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = -T(6) + (T(2) \times (T(4) + T(9))) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{145} & := (F(4) \times F(8) - F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(4) - (T(8) - T(9)) \times T(5) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(3)) \times (-F(5) + F(9)) & = T(4) + T(3) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{147} & := (F(1) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times (-T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := (-F(2) - F(5) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (-T(5) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = (T(2) - T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(8)) \\
 & := (F(3) \times F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = -T(3) + T(2) \times (T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(2) - F(3)) \times F(8) & = T(6) + T(2) \times (T(3) + T(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(2) + F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(2) - (T(3) - T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(5)) \times (F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times (-T(6) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(6) \times (-F(1) + F(8)) - F(7) & = T(6) \times (-T(1) + T(8) - T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{149} & := F(6) + F(4) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = -T(6) + T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{150} & := (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(6) - F(9) & = T(3) \times T(8) - T(6) - T(9) \\
 & := F(1) - F(8) + F(9) \times F(5) & = (T(1) - T(8) + T(9)) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(4) - (F(1) - F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times T(1) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(6) + F(3) \times F(8)) & = (T(4) + T(6)) \times T(3) - T(8) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times (-T(3) - T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(5) \times (-F(2) - F(4) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times (T(2) + T(4)) - T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{152} & := (-F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) - F(7) & = T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5)) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{153} & := -F(3) - F(7) + F(6) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times T(7) + T(6) - T(8) \\
 & := F(2) - F(6) \times (F(3) - F(8)) & = -T(2) \times T(6) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{156} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(7) & = T(2) - T(5) + T(3) \times T(7) \\
 \mathbf{157} & := -F(7) + (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(7) \times (-T(3) + T(4)) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{158} & := F(4) + F(6) \times F(8) - F(7) & = -T(4) + T(6) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{160} & := (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(8) + F(7) & = (T(1) - T(6)) \times (-T(8) + T(7)) \\
 & := F(5) \times (-F(4) + F(2) + F(9)) & = T(5) + T(4) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{161} & := (-F(1) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(8)) & = -T(1) + T(6) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(6) + (-F(8) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(6) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{162} & := F(4) \times (F(7) + F(9)) + F(8) & = (T(4) - T(7)) \times (-T(9) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(3) - F(6) \times (F(1) - F(8)) & = T(3) \times T(6) \times T(1) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) - F(6) \times (F(2) - F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(6) \times T(2) - T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{164} & := -F(4) - F(1) + F(6) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times (-T(1) + T(6)) - T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{165} & := -F(1) \times F(4) + F(6) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(4)) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := -F(2) - F(3) + F(6) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(1)) \times (F(8) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(8)) - T(9) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(2)) \times (F(9) + F(8)) & = -T(3) + T(2) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(4) - F(3) + F(5) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times (T(3) + T(5)) - T(9) \\
 & := (F(4) - F(6)) \times (F(1) - F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(6) \times T(1) - T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(5) \times F(1) \times (-F(2) + F(9)) & = -T(5) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(7) - F(2) + F(8)) & = (T(5) + T(7)) \times T(2) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{167} & := F(7) \times F(5) + F(4) \times F(9) & = -T(7) + T(5) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 & := -F(3) + (F(8) - F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times T(8) - T(6) - T(7) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{168} & := F(2) \times F(1) \times F(6) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 & := (-F(3) + F(4)) \times F(6) \times F(8) & = -T(3) + T(4) \times T(6) - T(8) \\
 & := (F(3) - F(1)) \times F(6) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times (T(1) + T(6)) + T(8) \\
 & := -F(2) \times F(3) + F(9) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(4)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(2) - T(4)) \times (T(6) - T(9)) \\
 & := -F(1) + (F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = (-T(1) \times T(5) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 & := -F(1) + (-F(6) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = (T(1) \times T(6)) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \\
 & := -F(2) + (-F(8) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = (-T(2) - T(8) + T(9)) \times T(7) \\
 & := -F(3) + F(5) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = (T(3) + T(5)) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{169} & := (F(1) \times F(5) + F(6)) \times F(7) & = T(1) - (T(5) - T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 & := (-F(1) \times F(6) + F(8)) \times F(7) & = T(1) + T(6) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{170} & := (-F(1) - F(3) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = -T(1) + T(3) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(1) + F(2)) \times F(9) & = -T(4) + (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(4) - F(3)) \times F(5) \times F(9) & = -T(4) + T(3) \times (-T(5) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(7) \times F(2) - F(6)) \times F(9) & = -T(7) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(1) + F(2) + F(6) \times F(8) & = -T(1) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{171} & := F(2) \times F(4) + F(6) \times F(8) & = -T(2) + T(4) \times T(6) - T(8) \\
 & := F(2) + F(3) + F(6) \times F(8) & = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times (T(6) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{172} & := F(3) \times F(9) + F(6) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times (T(9) - T(6)) + T(7) \\
 \mathbf{173} & := -F(4) + F(6) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times T(6) - T(1) - T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{175} & := (-F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(6) + T(1)) - T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{176} & := (F(1) + F(6)) \times F(8) - F(7) & = (T(1) + T(6)) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(5)) \times (F(1) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times (T(5) - T(1)) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{177} & := (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) + F(3) & = -T(2) + (T(9) - T(5)) \times T(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{178} & := -F(4) + F(6) \times F(8) + F(7) & = T(4) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(7) - F(5) \times (F(2) - F(9)) & = T(7) + T(5) + T(2) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{179} &:= -F(1) + (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times (T(9) - T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{180} &:= (F(1) \times F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) &= T(1) \times T(3) \times (T(9) - T(5)) \\
 &:= (F(3) \times F(5)) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) &= -T(3) + T(5) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(6)) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) &= (-T(3) + T(6) - T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) + F(6) + F(5) \times F(9) &= (-T(3) + T(6)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 &:= (-F(4) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) &= T(4) \times (-T(6) - T(3) + T(9)) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (-F(1) + F(4) + F(9)) &= (T(5) - T(1) - T(4)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (-F(2) + F(4) + F(9)) &= T(5) + T(2) \times (T(4) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{181} &:= F(1) + (F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) &= T(1) + T(3) \times (T(9) - T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{183} &:= (-F(3) + F(6)) \times F(9) - F(8) &= -T(3) + T(6) \times (T(9) - T(8)) \\
 &:= F(3) + F(7) + F(6) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times T(7) - T(6) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(2) + F(9)) + F(6) &= -T(5) + T(2) \times (T(9) + T(6)) \\
 &:= F(7) + (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(9) &= (T(7) + T(4)) \times T(3) - T(9) \\
 \mathbf{184} &:= F(6) \times (-F(1) + F(4) + F(8)) &= (T(6) + T(1)) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 \mathbf{185} &:= F(1) \times F(5) \times (F(4) + F(9)) &= (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{186} &:= (-F(2) + F(9)) \times F(5) + F(8) &= T(2) \times T(9) + T(5) + T(8) \\
 \mathbf{189} &:= (F(1) + F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) - T(4)) \times (T(5) - T(8)) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(3) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= T(2) \times (T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(6) + F(3) - F(1)) \times F(8) &= -T(6) + T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(3) \times F(5)) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(3)) \times (-T(5) + T(8)) \\
 &:= -F(3) + F(5) \times F(9) + F(8) &= (T(3) + T(5)) \times (T(9) - T(8)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(6) - F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(4) \times T(6) + T(5) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(6) \times (F(1) + F(8)) + F(7) &= T(6) \times (T(1) + T(8) - T(7)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(3) \times F(9)) &= T(4) \times T(5) - T(3) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(5) + F(6) \times (F(3) + F(8)) &= T(5) \times (T(6) - T(3)) - T(8) \\
 \mathbf{192} &:= (F(2) + F(3) + F(8)) \times F(6) &= -T(2) + T(3) \times T(8) - T(6) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(7)) \times F(3) \times F(6) &= T(2) + T(7) \times T(3) + T(6) \\
 \mathbf{193} &:= -F(3) + F(7) \times F(4) \times F(5) &= T(3) \times T(7) + T(4) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{195} &:= (F(3) + F(6) + F(5)) \times F(7) &= (T(3) - T(6)) \times (T(5) - T(7)) \\
 &:= (F(5) + F(8)) \times F(6) - F(7) &= T(5) \times (-T(8) + T(6) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (F(6) \times F(3) - F(1)) \times F(7) &= T(6) + T(3) \times (T(1) + T(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := (F(3) + F(4)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 \mathbf{198} & := (F(4) - F(8)) \times (F(3) - F(7)) & = T(4) + T(8) \times T(3) - T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(7) \times F(5) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times T(7) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 \mathbf{199} & := -F(4) + F(6) \times F(8) + F(9) & = T(4) - T(6) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{200} & := (-F(1) + F(8)) \times F(3) \times F(5) & = -T(1) + T(8) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{202} & := -F(6) + (-F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(6) \times T(4) + T(7) - T(8) \\
 \mathbf{204} & := (-F(3) \times F(2) + F(6)) \times F(9) & = T(3) + T(2) \times (T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(1) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(3) \times (-T(1) - T(4) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(6) \times F(1) - F(3)) \times F(9) & = -T(6) + (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(4) - F(5)) \times F(9) & = -T(6) + (-T(4) + T(5)) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(3) \times (-F(4) + F(5) \times F(8)) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 \mathbf{205} & := (F(3) + F(7) \times F(4)) \times F(5) & = (-T(3) + T(7)) \times T(4) - T(5) \\
 \mathbf{207} & := (F(2) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(4) & = -T(2) + T(3) \times (T(9) - T(4)) \\
 & := -F(2) + F(7) \times F(3) \times F(6) & = (T(2) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(6) \\
 & := -F(2) + (F(8) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = -T(2) \times T(8) + T(5) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{208} & := (F(4) - F(2)) \times F(6) \times F(7) & = T(4) \times (-T(2) + T(6)) + T(7) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times (-T(5) + T(7)) \\
 \mathbf{210} & := (-F(1) + F(4)) \times F(5) \times F(8) & = T(1) \times T(4) \times (-T(5) + T(8)) \\
 & := (-F(1) + F(7) - F(3)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 & := (-F(2) - F(3) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (T(3) + T(7) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(5) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = (-T(4) + T(5)) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 & := (-F(4) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times F(8) & = T(4) \times (-T(6) + T(3) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(4) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times (-T(4) \times T(1) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times F(8) \times (-F(6) + F(7)) & = (T(3) - T(8)) \times (T(6) - T(7)) \\
 & := F(6) \times (F(1) + F(8)) + F(9) & = T(6) \times (T(1) - T(8) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(2) + F(6) \times F(7)) & = T(3) \times (T(2) \times T(6) - T(7)) \\
 & := F(3) + F(6) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = -T(3) + (T(6) - T(5)) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + F(7) \times (F(8) - F(5)) & = (T(3) - T(7) + T(8)) \times T(5) \\
 \mathbf{216} & := (F(1) + F(8) + F(5)) \times F(6) & = T(1) \times T(8) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\
 & := (-F(3) - F(5) + F(9)) \times F(6) & = (T(3) - T(5)) \times (-T(9) + T(6)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = (-T(2) + T(6)) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := (F(7) - F(1)) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) & = T(7) \times (-T(1) + T(4)) - T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5) \times F(8)) & = T(3) - T(4) \times (T(5) - T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{218} & := (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(8) - F(7) & = T(4) \times T(6) + T(8) - T(7) \\
 \mathbf{219} & := (F(3) \times F(9) + F(5)) \times F(4) & = -T(3) + T(9) \times (T(5) - T(4)) \\
 \mathbf{220} & := F(5) \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(9)) & = -T(5) + T(4) \times T(7) - T(9) \\
 \mathbf{222} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = -T(2) + (T(5) - T(4)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{223} & := -F(6) + (F(7) - F(3)) \times F(8) & = -T(6) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{225} & := F(5) \times (F(4) + F(6) + F(9)) & = -T(5) + T(4) \times (-T(6) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{229} & := -F(5) + F(7) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) & = -T(5) + T(7) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 \mathbf{230} & := F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9) \times F(4)) & = (T(3) - T(7) + T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{231} & := (-F(3) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(8) & = T(3) - T(5) \times (T(6) - T(8)) \\
 & := (F(6) \times F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = -T(6) + (-T(2) + T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(1) + F(3)) \times F(8) & = -T(6) + (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(8) \\
 & := -F(6) + F(7) \times F(8) - F(9) & = -T(6) + T(7) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{232} & := (F(3) \times F(7) + F(4)) \times F(6) & = -T(3) + T(7) + T(4) \times T(6) \\
 & := F(1) - (F(3) - F(7)) \times F(8) & = (T(1) + T(3)) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{234} & := (-F(3) + F(6)) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = T(3) \times (T(6) - T(4) + T(7)) \\
 & := (F(1) \times F(7)) \times (-F(4) + F(8)) & = (-T(1) + T(7)) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) & = (-T(2) + T(6)) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 & := (-F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = T(3) \times (-T(6) + T(5) + T(9)) \\
 & := -F(2) + (F(7) + F(9)) \times F(5) & = T(2) \times (T(7) + T(9)) + T(5) \\
 & := F(4) + (F(7) - F(3)) \times F(8) & = -T(4) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 & := F(7) \times (-F(3) \times F(6) + F(9)) & = T(7) \times T(3) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{237} & := -F(2) + F(9) \times (F(3) + F(5)) & = (-T(2) + T(9)) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{238} & := (-F(1) - F(5) + F(7)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) - T(5)) \times (T(7) - T(9)) \\
 & := (F(7) - F(3) \times F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(7) - T(3) \times (T(4) - T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{240} & := (-F(1) - F(4) + F(9)) \times F(6) & = (T(1) \times T(4)) \times (T(9) - T(6)) \\
 & := (F(3) + F(6)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = -T(3) + T(6) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 & := F(5) \times (F(1) + F(7) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times (-T(1) - T(7) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{241} & := (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(9) + F(4) & = T(1) - (T(6) - T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{242} & := (-F(4) + F(8)) \times F(7) + F(6) & = -T(4) + T(8) \times (T(7) - T(6)) \\
 & := F(4) + F(7) \times F(8) - F(9) & = -T(4) + T(7) \times (-T(8) + T(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 243 &:= (-F(2) + F(6)) \times F(9) + F(5) &= T(2) \times (T(6) + T(9) + T(5)) \\
 246 &:= F(3) \times (F(4) \times F(9) + F(8)) &= -T(3) \times (T(4) - T(9)) + T(8) \\
 &:= -F(3) + (-F(4) + F(9)) \times F(6) &= T(3) + T(4) \times (T(9) - T(6)) \\
 247 &:= (F(2) + F(8) - F(4)) \times F(7) &= T(2) - T(8) + T(4) \times T(7) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(7) \times (-F(3) + F(8)) &= T(2) + T(7) + T(3) \times T(8) \\
 248 &:= (-F(1) - F(3) + F(9)) \times F(6) &= -T(1) + T(3) \times T(9) - T(6) \\
 &:= F(6) \times (-F(4) + F(7) + F(8)) &= (T(6) + T(4)) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 250 &:= -F(3) + F(8) \times (-F(1) + F(7)) &= T(3) \times (T(8) + T(1)) + T(7) \\
 &:= F(4) - F(7) \times (F(3) - F(8)) &= T(4) \times T(7) + T(3) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(4) + F(7) + F(9)) &= T(5) + T(4) \times T(7) - T(9) \\
 252 &:= (-F(1) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) - T(5) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(3) + F(9)) &= T(2) - T(6) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 &:= F(2) - F(8) + F(9) \times F(6) &= (T(2) - T(8) + T(9)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= F(7) \times (F(1) + F(8)) - F(9) &= T(7) \times T(1) \times (-T(8) + T(9)) \\
 &:= F(5) - F(7) \times (F(3) - F(8)) &= (-T(5) + T(7) - T(3)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= -F(6) + F(7) \times (-F(1) + F(8)) &= (-T(6) + T(7)) \times T(1) \times T(8) \\
 255 &:= -F(1) + (F(9) - F(3)) \times F(6) &= (T(1) + T(9)) \times T(3) - T(6) \\
 256 &:= -F(4) - F(7) + F(6) \times F(9) &= T(4) \times T(7) + T(6) - T(9) \\
 &:= F(6) \times (-F(4) + F(1) + F(9)) &= T(6) \times T(4) + T(1) + T(9) \\
 259 &:= F(4) - F(6) \times (F(3) - F(9)) &= T(4) - T(6) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 260 &:= (-F(4) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= -T(4) \times T(7) + T(5) \times T(8) \\
 261 &:= F(5) - F(6) \times (F(3) - F(9)) &= (T(5) + T(6)) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 262 &:= -F(4) - F(6) + F(7) \times F(8) &= T(4) - (T(6) - T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) - (F(2) - F(8)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times (T(2) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 264 &:= (-F(1) \times F(2) + F(9)) \times F(6) &= (T(1) + T(2)) \times (T(9) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (F(3) - F(4) + F(9)) \times F(6) &= (-T(3) + T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(6)) \\
 &:= (F(2) - F(9)) \times (F(5) - F(7)) &= T(2) \times (T(9) + T(5) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (-F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= T(3) \times (T(7) + T(4)) + T(8)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 267 & := -F(2) \times F(5) + F(6) \times F(9) & = -T(2) + T(5) \times T(6) - T(9) \\
 & := -F(5) + (-F(7) + F(8)) \times F(9) & = T(5) - T(7) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\
 & := -F(5) + F(6) \times (F(7) + F(8)) & = T(5) - (T(6) - T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 269 & := F(5) - F(6) \times (F(1) - F(9)) & = T(5) \times T(6) - T(1) - T(9) \\
 \\
 270 & := -F(4) + F(2) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(4) \times (T(2) - T(6) + T(9)) \\
 & := -F(5) + F(4) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(5) + T(4) \times T(6) + T(9) \\
 \\
 271 & := -F(2) + F(9) \times (F(8) - F(7)) & = T(2) \times (T(9) + T(8)) + T(7) \\
 \\
 272 & := (-F(1) \times F(5) + F(7)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(5)) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := (-F(3) - F(4) + F(7)) \times F(9) & = (T(3) + T(4)) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := -F(4) + F(3) + F(8) \times F(7) & = T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) - T(7) \\
 \\
 273 & := (F(6) \times F(3) + F(5)) \times F(7) & = T(6) - (T(3) - T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 & := (F(6) - F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(7) & = T(6) - (T(1) - T(4)) \times T(7) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(6)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = T(2) + T(6) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 & := F(3) - F(2) + F(9) \times F(6) & = T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(9)) + T(6) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(7)) \times (-F(8) + F(9)) & = T(6) - T(7) \times (T(8) - T(9)) \\
 \\
 276 & := F(2) \times F(7) \times F(8) + F(4) & = -T(2) \times T(7) + T(8) \times T(4) \\
 & := -F(1) + F(9) \times F(6) + F(5) & = (T(1) + T(9)) \times (T(6) - T(5)) \\
 & := F(4) + F(8) \times (F(5) + F(6)) & = (T(4) + T(8)) \times (-T(5) + T(6)) \\
 \\
 280 & := (F(1) + F(9)) \times (F(8) - F(7)) & = (T(1) + T(9) - T(8)) \times T(7) \\
 & := F(4) + F(5) + F(6) \times F(9) & = T(4) + T(5) \times T(6) - T(9) \\
 \\
 282 & := F(3) \times (F(7) + F(9)) \times F(4) & = -T(3) \times T(7) + T(9) \times T(4) \\
 283 & := -F(7) + F(6) \times (F(4) + F(9)) & = T(7) + T(6) \times T(4) + T(9) \\
 \\
 285 & := F(5) \times F(4) \times (-F(3) + F(8)) & = -T(5) + T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(5) + F(6) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times (T(6) + T(1)) - T(9) \\
 \\
 288 & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times (-F(3) + F(9)) & = -T(2) + T(6) + T(3) \times T(9) \\
 & := (F(7) - F(1)) \times (F(4) + F(8)) & = T(7) \times (-T(1) + T(4)) + T(8) \\
 & := F(3) + F(7) \times (F(2) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(7) \times T(2) - T(8)) \\
 \\
 290 & := (-F(4) + F(7)) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(6) + T(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 294 &:= (F(1) + F(6) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= ((T(1) + T(6)) \times T(5)) - T(8) \\
 &:= -F(5) + F(7) \times (F(3) + F(8)) &= (T(5) + T(7)) \times T(3) + T(8) \\
 \\
 297 &:= F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(6) \times F(7)) &= T(4) + T(5) \times T(6) - T(7) \\
 \\
 304 &:= (-F(2) + F(4) \times F(7)) \times F(6) &= T(2) + T(4) \times T(7) + T(6) \\
 &:= (F(4) + F(7)) \times (-F(3) + F(8)) &= T(4) \times (T(7) + T(3)) - T(8) \\
 \\
 306 &:= (F(2) - F(5) + F(7)) \times F(9) &= (T(2) + T(5)) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) \\
 &:= (-F(3) + F(5)) \times F(9) \times F(4) &= T(3) - (T(5) - T(9)) \times T(4) \\
 \\
 309 &:= (-F(1) + F(7) \times F(6)) \times F(4) &= T(1) + T(7) \times (T(6) - T(4)) \\
 \\
 310 &:= -F(3) + F(7) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= -T(3) + T(7) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 311 &:= -F(1) + (F(7) \times F(4)) \times F(6) &= (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(4) \times F(6) \times F(7) &= T(2) - (T(4) - T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 312 &:= (-F(3) - F(6) + F(9)) \times F(7) &= T(3) \times (-T(6) + T(9) + T(7)) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(5) \times F(8)) \times F(4) &= (T(2) - T(5)) \times (-T(8) + T(4)) \\
 &:= (F(2) - F(7)) \times (F(6) - F(9)) &= -T(2) + (T(7) - T(6)) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 313 &:= F(2) + (F(7) \times (F(4) + F(8))) &= -T(2) + T(7) \times T(4) + T(8) \\
 \\
 314 &:= F(3) + F(4) \times F(6) \times F(7) &= T(3) + (-T(4) + T(6)) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 315 &:= (-F(1) + F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= -T(1) + T(4) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(5) \times F(4) \times F(8) &= -T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(5) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= (T(3) + T(5)) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(5) \times (F(3) + F(1)) \times F(8) &= (T(5) - T(3)) \times (-T(1) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(5) \times F(4) \times (-F(7) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(7)) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(2) + F(7) \times F(6)) &= (-T(4) - T(2) + T(7)) \times T(6) \\
 &:= F(4) + F(6) \times (F(5) + F(9)) &= T(4) \times (T(6) + T(5)) - T(9) \\
 \\
 317 &:= F(5) + F(7) \times (F(4) + F(8)) &= -T(5) - T(7) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 325 &:= F(5) \times (F(4) + F(3)) \times F(7) &= -T(5) + T(4) \times (T(3) + T(7)) \\
 \\
 330 &:= F(3) \times (-F(1) + F(9)) \times F(5) &= (T(3) + T(1)) \times T(9) + T(5) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(8) \times F(6) - F(4)) &= (T(3) - T(8)) \times (-T(6) + T(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 331 &:= -F(5) + (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= T(5) + T(4) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 333 &:= -F(4) + (F(8) \times F(3)) \times F(6) &= T(4) \times T(8) - T(3) - T(6) \\
 335 &:= -F(2) + (F(7) + F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(2) - T(7) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 336 &:= (-F(2) + F(4)) \times F(8) \times F(6) &= -T(2) + T(4) \times T(8) - T(6) \\
 &:= (F(3) \times F(1)) \times F(6) \times F(8) &= T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (-F(5) + F(7) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= -T(5) \times T(7) + T(6) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(3) \times (F(4) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= (T(3) + T(4)) \times (-T(5) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(6) \times (F(1) + F(7)) &= (-T(4) + T(6) + T(1)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(7) + F(8)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) &= T(7) \times (T(8) + T(6) - T(9)) \\
 \\
 338 &:= F(3) + (F(7) + F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(3) - T(7) + T(4) \times T(8) \\
 339 &:= F(2) + F(7) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= (-T(2) + T(7)) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 342 &:= F(3) \times (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= T(3) \times (-T(2) + T(5) + T(9)) \\
 344 &:= F(6) + (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) &= (T(6) - T(4)) \times T(7) + T(8) \\
 352 &:= (F(7) + F(4)) \times (F(1) + F(8)) &= T(7) + (T(4) - T(1)) \times T(8) \\
 360 &:= (-F(2) + F(8)) \times (F(7) + F(5)) &= T(2) \times (T(8) - T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 361 &:= (-F(4) + F(7)) \times F(9) + F(8) &= T(4) \times T(7) + T(9) + T(8) \\
 365 &:= F(5) \times (F(4) \times F(7) + F(9)) &= (T(5) - T(4)) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 369 &:= -F(5) + (F(7) - F(3)) \times F(9) &= T(5) \times T(7) - T(3) - T(9) \\
 370 &:= (F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) + F(9) &= T(4) \times (T(7) - T(8) + T(9)) \\
 375 &:= -F(3) + F(7) \times (-F(5) + F(9)) &= (-T(3) + T(7)) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 376 &:= -F(1) + F(7) \times (-F(5) + F(9)) &= T(1) + T(7) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 377 &:= F(7) \times (F(4) \times F(8) - F(9)) &= -T(7) + T(4) \times T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 378 &:= (F(6) + F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(8) &= T(6) \times (-T(2) \times T(3) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(6) + F(7) - F(4)) \times F(8) &= T(6) \times (-T(7) + T(4) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(2) + F(7) \times (-F(5) + F(9)) &= T(2) + T(7) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 \\
 390 &:= (-F(4) + F(9) - F(2)) \times F(7) &= T(4) \times (-T(9) + T(2) \times T(7)) \\
 &:= (F(3) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(8)) &= T(3) + T(7) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(4) \times F(5) \times (-F(6) + F(9)) &= T(4) \times (T(5) - T(6) + T(9)) \\
 &:= F(7) \times (F(1) - F(5) + F(9)) &= (T(7) + T(1)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 \\
 399 &:= (F(1) + F(7) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= (T(1) + T(7)) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 &:= (-F(5) \times F(4) + F(9)) \times F(8) &= -T(5) + T(4) \times T(9) - T(8) \\
 \\
 403 &:= -F(5) + (-F(1) + F(7)) \times F(9) &= (T(5) + T(1)) \times T(7) - T(9) \\
 405 &:= F(5) \times (F(4) \times F(9) - F(8)) &= (T(5) - T(4)) \times (T(9) + T(8)) \\
 408 &:= (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(3) \times F(9) &= T(2) + (T(5) - T(3)) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 420 &:= (-F(1) + F(7) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= T(1) \times T(7) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(7) + F(3) + F(5)) \times F(8) &= T(7) \times (-T(3) - T(5) + T(8)) \\
 424 &:= F(6) + (F(9) - F(3)) \times F(7) &= (T(6) + T(9)) \times T(3) + T(7) \\
 432 &:= (F(3) + F(9)) \times (-F(1) + F(7)) &= T(3) \times (T(9) - T(1) + T(7)) \\
 &:= F(4) - (F(1) - F(9)) \times F(7) &= T(4) \times (T(1) + T(9)) - T(7) \\
 437 &:= -F(1) \times F(5) + F(7) \times F(9) &= (-T(1) + T(5)) \times T(7) + T(9) \\
 439 &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) &= T(1) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 441 &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(7) \times F(9) &= T(2) + T(3) \times (T(7) + T(9)) \\
 450 &:= F(2) \times F(6) + F(7) \times F(9) &= (T(2) - T(6) + T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= -F(5) + F(7) \times (F(1) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(7) - T(1)) + T(9) \\
 &:= -F(5) + F(7) \times (F(2) + F(9)) &= (-T(5) + T(7) - T(2)) \times T(9) \\
 452 &:= -F(4) + (F(2) + F(9)) \times F(7) &= T(4) \times (T(2) + T(9)) - T(7) \\
 462 &:= (F(4) + F(6)) \times F(3) \times F(8) &= (-T(4) + T(6)) \times (T(3) + T(8)) \\
 468 &:= (-F(1) + F(9) + F(4)) \times F(7) &= -(T(1) - T(9)) \times T(4) + T(7) \\
 &:= (-F(2) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) &= T(2) + T(7) \times T(5) + T(9) \\
 480 &:= F(4) \times (-F(3) + F(9)) \times F(5) &= (T(4) + T(3)) \times (T(9) - T(5)) \\
 483 &:= (F(6) \times F(4) - F(2)) \times F(8) &= T(6) \times (-T(4) - T(2) + T(8)) \\
 485 &:= F(5) \times (F(8) \times F(4) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times T(8) - T(4) - T(9) \\
 486 &:= F(5) \times F(7) \times F(6) - F(9) &= T(5) \times T(7) + T(6) + T(9) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(9) \times F(5) - F(6)) &= T(4) \times T(9) + T(5) + T(6) \\
 489 &:= F(4) \times F(9) \times F(5) - F(8) &= (-T(4) + T(9)) \times T(5) - T(8) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (-F(5) + F(6) \times F(8)) &= (T(4) + T(5)) \times T(6) - T(8) \\
 495 &:= F(4) \times F(5) \times (-F(2) + F(9)) &= T(4) \times T(5) \times T(2) + T(9) \\
 497 &:= -F(7) + F(5) \times F(4) \times F(9) &= -T(7) + (T(5) \times (-T(4) + T(9))) \\
 504 &:= (F(1) + F(3)) \times F(6) \times F(8) &= (-T(1) - T(3) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= F(2) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times F(8) &= (T(2) - T(4) + T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(7) - F(2)) \times F(3) \times F(8) &= T(7) \times (-T(2) \times T(3) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (F(7) - F(2)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) &= T(7) \times (T(2) \times T(6) - T(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(6) \times (-F(5) + F(3) \times F(9)) & = T(6) \times (-T(5) - T(3) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{505} & := (-F(4) + F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(5) & = T(4) \times (T(6) + T(7)) + T(5) \\
 \mathbf{509} & := F(4) \times F(6) \times F(8) + F(5) & = -T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \times T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{510} & := (-F(1) + F(8) - F(5)) \times F(9) & = (T(1) + T(8)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\
 & := (-F(2) + F(4) + F(7)) \times F(9) & = (T(2) \times T(4)) \times (-T(7) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(4) \times (F(3) + F(6) \times F(8)) & = T(4) \times (-T(3) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{519} & := -F(2) + F(6) \times F(7) \times F(5) & = (-T(2) + T(6)) \times T(7) + T(5) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{525} & := (F(6) \times F(4) + F(1)) \times F(8) & = T(6) \times (-T(4) - T(1) + T(8)) \\
 & := (F(2) + F(6) \times F(7)) \times F(5) & = (T(2) \times T(6) - T(7)) \times T(5) \\
 & := F(5) \times F(4) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = T(5) \times (-T(4) \times T(1) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{540} & := F(4) \times F(5) \times (F(3) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(5) - T(3) + T(9)) \\
 & := F(3) \times (F(8) \times F(7) - F(4)) & = (T(3) - T(8)) \times (-T(7) + T(4)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{546} & := F(2) \times F(7) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(2) + T(7) \times T(6) - T(9) \\
 \mathbf{552} & := (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(4) \times F(6) & = T(3) + (T(8) - T(4)) \times T(6) \\
 \mathbf{557} & := F(7) - (F(5) - F(8)) \times F(9) & = -T(7) + T(5) \times T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{567} & := (F(2) + F(6)) \times F(8) \times F(4) & = -T(2) + (T(6) + T(8)) \times T(4) \\
 & := (F(2) - F(6) + F(9)) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times T(6) \times (T(9) - T(8)) \\
 & := (F(5) \times F(6) - F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(5) + T(6) \times T(7) - T(8) \\
 & := (F(6) + F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(8) & = T(6) \times (T(1) - T(4) + T(8)) \\
 & := F(7) \times (F(6) + F(9)) + F(8) & = (T(7) - T(6)) \times (T(9) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{575} & := (F(4) \times F(9) + F(7)) \times F(5) & = -T(4) + T(9) \times (T(7) - T(5)) \\
 \mathbf{576} & := (F(3) + F(9)) \times (-F(5) + F(8)) & = T(3) \times (T(9) + T(5) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{588} & := (-F(2) + F(9) - F(5)) \times F(8) & = T(2) + T(9) + T(5) \times T(8) \\
 & := (F(7) + F(2)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) & = T(7) \times (-T(2) - T(6) + T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{624} & := F(3) \times F(6) \times (F(5) + F(9)) & = -T(3) + T(6) \times (-T(5) + T(9)) \\
 & := (F(4) + F(8)) \times (-F(6) + F(9)) & = (T(4) - T(8)) \times (T(6) - T(9)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{630} & := (-F(4) + F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(9)) & = T(4) \times (T(8) \times T(2) - T(9)) \\
 & := (F(5) + F(7)) \times (F(1) + F(9)) & = (-T(5) + T(7) + T(1)) \times T(9) \\
 & := F(8) \times (F(2) - F(5) + F(9)) & = (T(8) + T(2)) \times T(5) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 633 &:= F(8) + (F(5) + F(7)) \times F(9) &= (T(8) - T(5)) \times T(7) + T(9) \\
 637 &:= F(7) \times (F(4) \times F(5) + F(9)) &= -T(7) - T(4) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 638 &:= (F(1) + F(8)) \times (-F(5) + F(9)) &= -T(1) - T(8) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 646 &:= (F(1) + F(7) + F(5)) \times F(9) &= -T(1) - T(7) + T(5) \times T(9) \\
 672 &:= (F(7) + F(4)) \times F(3) \times F(8) &= T(7) \times (T(4) \times T(3) - T(8)) \\
 675 &:= -F(5) + (F(8) - F(2)) \times F(9) &= T(5) \times T(8) + T(2) \times T(9) \\
 680 &:= (F(4) + F(1)) \times F(9) \times F(5) &= -T(4) + (T(1) + T(9)) \times T(5) \\
 690 &:= F(5) \times (F(6) \times F(7) + F(9)) &= T(5) \times (T(6) + T(7)) - T(9) \\
 693 &:= F(8) \times (F(2) - F(3) + F(9)) &= T(8) \times T(2) \times T(3) + T(9) \\
 708 &:= -F(2) - F(5) + F(9) \times F(8) &= -T(2) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 710 &:= F(1) - F(5) + F(9) \times F(8) &= -T(1) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 711 &:= F(3) - F(5) + F(8) \times F(9) &= (T(3) + T(5)) \times T(8) - T(9) \\
 714 &:= (F(6) - F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(9) &= T(6) \times (-T(1) - T(4) + T(9)) \\
 717 &:= -F(3) + F(5) + F(9) \times F(8) &= T(3) + T(5) \times T(9) + T(8) \\
 \\
 720 &:= (-F(4) + F(8)) \times F(5) \times F(6) &= T(4) \times (T(8) + T(5) + T(6)) \\
 &:= -F(3) + F(8) \times F(9) + F(6) &= (T(3) - T(8)) \times (-T(9) + T(6)) \\
 &:= F(5) + (F(8) + F(9)) \times F(7) &= -T(5) \times T(8) + T(9) \times T(7) \\
 \\
 735 &:= F(5) \times (-F(1) + F(6)) \times F(8) &= T(5) - (T(1) - T(6)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 756 &:= (-F(2) + F(7)) \times F(4) \times F(8) &= (T(2) + T(7) - T(4)) \times T(8) \\
 &:= (F(7) - F(1)) \times F(4) \times F(8) &= T(7) \times (T(1) - T(4) + T(8)) \\
 &:= F(3) \times F(8) \times (F(5) + F(7)) &= (T(3) + T(8) - T(5)) \times T(7) \\
 &:= F(6) + F(9) \times (F(2) + F(8)) &= (-T(6) + T(9) - T(2)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 795 &:= F(7) + (F(3) + F(8)) \times F(9) &= T(7) \times (-T(3) + T(8)) - T(9) \\
 803 &:= F(4) \times F(6) \times F(9) - F(7) &= (-T(4) + T(6)) \times (T(9) + T(7)) \\
 810 &:= F(4) \times (-F(3) + F(6) \times F(9)) &= T(4) \times (T(3) \times T(6) - T(9)) \\
 \\
 816 &:= (F(3) + F(2)) \times F(6) \times F(9) &= T(3) - (T(2) - T(6)) \times T(9) \\
 &:= (-F(5) + F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) &= T(5) + T(6) \times T(8) + T(9) \\
 \\
 819 &:= (F(6) + F(7)) \times (F(5) + F(9)) &= -T(6) + T(7) \times (-T(5) + T(9)) \\
 827 &:= F(5) \times F(6) \times F(8) - F(7) &= T(5) \times (T(6) + T(8)) - T(7) \\
 \\
 840 &:= F(5) \times F(1) \times F(6) \times F(8) &= T(5) \times (-T(1) + T(6) + T(8)) \\
 &:= (-F(1) + F(8)) \times (F(6) + F(9)) &= (T(1) - T(8)) \times (T(6) - T(9)) \\
 &:= F(4) \times (F(9) + F(2)) \times F(6) &= (-T(4) + T(9)) \times (T(2) + T(6))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & := F(6) \times (F(3) + F(4)) \times F(8) & = T(6) \times (-T(3) + T(4) + T(8)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{846} & := (F(8) - F(4)) \times (F(7) + F(9)) & = T(8) - (T(4) - T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{861} & := (-F(2) + F(6) + F(9)) \times F(8) & = -T(2) + (-T(6) + T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{882} & := F(3) \times (F(6) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = -T(3) \times T(6) + T(7) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{899} & := (-F(4) + F(9)) \times (F(6) + F(8)) & = -T(4) + T(9) \times T(6) - T(8) \\
 \mathbf{962} & := (F(5) \times F(6) + F(9)) \times F(7) & = T(5) \times (T(6) + T(9)) - T(7) \\
 \mathbf{966} & := (-F(2) + F(9) - F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(2) - T(9) + T(7) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{986} & := (F(3) \times F(7) + F(4)) \times F(9) & = T(3) - T(7) \times (T(4) - T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{1008} & := (F(2) + F(5)) \times F(8) \times F(6) & = (-T(2) + T(5) + T(8)) \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1320} & := F(5) \times (F(9) - F(1)) \times F(6) & = (T(5) + T(9)) \times (T(1) + T(6)) \\
 & := F(4) \times (-F(3) + F(7) \times F(9)) & = T(4) \times T(3) + T(7) \times T(9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1323} & := F(8) \times F(4) \times (-F(7) + F(9)) & = T(8) \times (T(4) + T(7)) - T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1326} & := (-F(4) + F(8) \times F(3)) \times F(9) & = (-T(4) + T(8)) \times (T(3) + T(9)) \\
 \mathbf{1344} & := (F(7) \times F(5) - F(2)) \times F(8) & = T(7) \times (T(5) - T(2) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1350} & := F(5) \times (-F(3) + F(6) \times F(9)) & = (T(5) - T(3) + T(6)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1407} & := (-F(2) + F(3) \times F(9)) \times F(8) & = T(2) - (T(3) - T(9)) \times T(8) \\
 \mathbf{1598} & := (F(3) \times F(7) + F(8)) \times F(9) & = T(3) - T(7) + T(8) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{1680} & := F(6) \times (-F(4) + F(7)) \times F(8) & = T(6) \times T(4) \times (-T(7) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{1911} & := F(7) \times (F(6) - F(2)) \times F(8) & = (T(7) + T(6)) \times (T(2) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{2184} & := F(2) \times F(7) \times F(6) \times F(8) & = T(2) \times (-T(7) + T(6) \times T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{2205} & := F(5) \times F(8) \times (-F(7) + F(9)) & = (-T(5) + T(8) - T(7)) \times T(9) \\
 \mathbf{2520} & := (F(3) + F(7)) \times F(6) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times T(7) \times (-T(6) + T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{4368} & := F(3) \times F(7) \times F(6) \times F(8) & = T(3) \times (-T(7) + T(6) \times T(8)) \\
 \mathbf{6552} & := F(4) \times F(6) \times F(7) \times F(8) & = (T(4) \times T(6) - T(7)) \times T(8) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{10920} & := F(5) \times F(7) \times F(6) \times F(8) & = T(5) \times (-T(7) + T(6) \times T(8))
 \end{aligned}$$

7.3 Five-Terms Expressions

Due to high quantity of numbers, this shall be completed later on.

8 Interesting Results

In this section, we present some interesting results obtained from all values given in section 4.1.

8.1 Fibonacci Values: Multiplication

Here we have **selfie expressions** where only multiplication operation is used with Fibonacci sequence values.

$$42 := F(3) \times F(8) = T(3) + T(8)$$

$$2 := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) = -T(1) - T(2) + T(3)$$

$$10 := F(1) \times F(3) \times F(5) = T(1) - T(3) + T(5)$$

$$15 := F(2) \times F(4) \times F(5) = T(2) \times T(4) - T(5)$$

$$16 := F(1) \times F(3) \times F(6) = T(1) - T(3) + T(6)$$

$$30 := F(3) \times F(4) \times F(5) = T(3) \times (-T(4) + T(5))$$

$$39 := F(1) \times F(4) \times F(7) = T(1) + T(4) + T(7)$$

$$15 := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(4) \times F(5) = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) - T(5)$$

$$26 := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(3) \times F(7) = T(1) + T(2) - T(3) + T(7)$$

$$30 := F(2) \times F(3) \times F(5) \times F(4) = (T(2) \times T(3) - T(5)) \times T(4)$$

$$40 := F(1) \times F(2) \times F(5) \times F(6) = T(1) + T(2) + T(5) + T(6)$$

$$102 := F(2) \times F(1) \times F(4) \times F(9) = T(2) \times (-T(1) - T(4) + T(9))$$

$$120 := F(2) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times F(5) = (-T(2) - T(4) + T(6)) \times T(5)$$

$$168 := F(2) \times F(1) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(2) \times (-T(1) + T(6) + T(8))$$

$$315 := F(2) \times F(5) \times F(4) \times F(8) = -T(2) \times T(5) + T(4) \times T(8)$$

$$336 := F(3) \times F(1) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(3) \times (-T(1) + T(6) + T(8))$$

$$504 := F(2) \times F(4) \times F(6) \times F(8) = (T(2) - T(4) + T(6)) \times T(8)$$

$$510 := F(5) \times F(1) \times F(4) \times F(9) = T(5) + (T(1) + T(4)) \times T(9)$$

$$840 := F(5) \times F(1) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(5) \times (-T(1) + T(6) + T(8))$$

$$2184 := F(2) \times F(7) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(2) \times (-T(7) + T(6) \times T(8))$$

$$4368 := F(3) \times F(7) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(3) \times (-T(7) + T(6) \times T(8))$$

$$6552 := F(4) \times F(6) \times F(7) \times F(8) = (T(4) \times T(6) - T(7)) \times T(8)$$

$$10920 := F(5) \times F(7) \times F(6) \times F(8) = T(5) \times (-T(7) + T(6) \times T(8))$$

8.2 Fibonacci Values: Addition

Here we have **selfie expressions** where only the operation of addition is used with Fibonacci sequence values.

$$3 := F(2) + F(3) = -T(2) + T(3)$$

$$11 := F(4) + F(6) = -T(4) + T(6)$$

$$8 := F(1) + F(3) + F(5) = -T(1) - T(3) + T(5)$$

$$12 := F(1) + F(4) + F(6) = T(1) - T(4) + T(6)$$

$$16 := F(4) + F(5) + F(6) = T(4) - T(5) + T(6)$$

$$17 := F(1) + F(4) + F(7) = -T(1) - T(4) + T(7)$$

$$25 := F(1) + F(4) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(4) + T(8)$$

$$38 := F(2) + F(4) + F(9) = T(2) - T(4) + T(9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(4) = T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \\
 9 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(5) = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(3) - T(5) \\
 11 &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(4) + F(5) = T(1) \times T(3) - T(4) + T(5) \\
 12 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) + F(6) = -T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(6) \\
 13 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(4) + F(6) = -T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 14 &:= F(2) + F(3) + F(4) + F(6) = -T(2) + T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 17 &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(6) = T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\
 20 &:= F(1) + F(5) + F(2) + F(7) = (T(1) + T(5)) \times T(2) - T(7) \\
 22 &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(7) = -T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\
 25 &:= F(2) + F(6) + F(4) + F(7) = T(2) \times T(6) - T(4) - T(7) \\
 27 &:= F(2) + F(3) + F(4) + F(8) = T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \\
 28 &:= F(3) + F(5) + F(6) + F(7) = -T(3) - T(5) + T(6) + T(7) \\
 30 &:= F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(8) = -T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\
 36 &:= F(3) + F(5) + F(6) + F(8) = -T(3) - T(5) + T(6) + T(8) \\
 38 &:= F(2) + F(4) + F(7) + F(8) = T(2) \times T(4) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 39 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(4) + F(9) = T(1) + T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 40 &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(4) + F(9) = -T(1) + T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\
 42 &:= F(2) + F(3) + F(5) + F(9) = -T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 43 &:= F(1) + F(6) + F(7) + F(8) = -T(1) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\
 43 &:= F(2) + F(4) + F(5) + F(9) = T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(9) \\
 44 &:= F(3) + F(4) + F(5) + F(9) = -T(3) - T(4) + T(5) + T(9) \\
 48 &:= F(2) + F(5) + F(6) + F(9) = -T(2) - T(5) + T(6) + T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

8.3 Fibonacci Values: Addition and Subtraction

Here we have **selfie expressions** where only the operations of addition and subtraction are used Fibonacci sequence values.

$$\begin{aligned}
 8 &:= -F(7) + F(8) = -T(7) + T(8) \\
 4 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(4) = -T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) \\
 &:= -F(2) - F(6) + F(7) = -T(2) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 6 &:= F(1) - F(6) + F(7) = -T(1) - T(6) + T(7) \\
 &:= -F(2) + F(3) + F(5) = -T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \\
 7 &:= -F(1) - F(7) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 9 &:= F(1) - F(7) + F(8) = T(1) - T(7) + T(8) \\
 10 &:= -F(1) + F(4) + F(6) = -T(1) - T(4) + T(6) \\
 &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(7) = -T(2) \times T(3) + T(7)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12 &:= -F(2) - F(6) + F(8) = -T(2) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(8) + F(9) = T(2) - T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) - F(4) + F(7) = -T(3) - T(4) + T(7)\end{aligned}$$

$$14 := F(1) - F(6) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(6) + T(8)$$

$$\begin{aligned}15 &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(7) = -T(2) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(3) - F(8) + F(9) = T(3) - T(8) + T(9)\end{aligned}$$

$$17 := -F(2) + F(5) + F(7) = T(2) \times T(5) - T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}18 &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(8) = -T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(2) + F(8) = -T(3) \times T(2) + T(8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}20 &:= -F(2) - F(7) + F(9) = T(2) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(3) - F(4) + F(8) = -T(3) - T(4) + T(8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23 &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(8) = -T(2) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) - F(7) + F(9) = T(3) - T(7) + T(9)\end{aligned}$$

$$25 := -F(1) - F(6) + F(9) = T(1) - T(6) + T(9)$$

$$27 := F(2) - F(6) + F(9) = T(2) - T(6) + T(9)$$

$$29 := -F(3) - F(4) + F(9) = -T(3) - T(4) + T(9)$$

$$30 := F(1) - F(5) + F(9) = -T(1) \times T(5) + T(9)$$

$$32 := F(2) - F(4) + F(9) = -T(2) - T(4) + T(9)$$

$$36 := -F(1) + F(4) + F(9) = T(1) - T(4) + T(9)$$

$$0 := F(5) + F(6) + F(8) - F(9) = (T(5) + T(6) - T(8)) \times T(9)$$

$$\begin{aligned}1 &:= F(1) + F(2) + F(3) - F(4) = -T(1) \times T(2) - T(3) + T(4) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) + F(4) - F(5) = T(1) \times T(3) + T(4) - T(5) \\ &:= F(2) + F(4) + F(5) - F(6) = -T(2) + T(4) + T(5) - T(6) \\ &:= F(2) + F(6) + F(7) - F(8) = -T(2) \times T(6) + T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(5) - F(7) + F(8) = -T(3) + T(5) + T(7) - T(8)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2 &:= -F(1) - F(3) - F(6) + F(7) = T(1) - T(3) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) - F(4) + F(6) = -T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) - F(6) + F(7) = T(2) + T(3) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= F(3) + F(4) + F(5) - F(6) = T(3) - T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= F(3) + F(5) + F(6) - F(7) = -T(3) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(4) - F(6) - F(8) + F(9) = -T(4) + T(6) + T(8) - T(9)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 3 &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(6) + F(7) = -T(1) - T(2) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) - F(4) - F(6) + F(7) = T(1) \times T(4) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(4) - F(5) + F(7) = T(3) + T(4) + T(5) - T(7) \\ &:= F(4) + F(6) + F(7) - F(8) = -T(4) + T(6) + T(7) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4 &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(3) + F(6) = T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) - F(3) - F(4) + F(6) = -T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(4) - F(5) + F(7) = T(1) - T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(6) + F(7) = T(2) - T(3) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(5) - F(7) + F(8) = -T(2) + T(5) + T(7) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5 &:= F(1) + F(3) - F(2) + F(4) = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(2) - T(4) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(4) - F(5) + F(6) = T(1) + T(4) + T(5) - T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(3) + F(5) = -T(1) - T(2) - T(3) + T(5) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) - F(5) + F(7) = T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) - F(7) + F(8) = T(2) - T(3) - T(7) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 6 &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(4) + F(6) = T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(7) + F(8) = T(1) - T(2) - T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(2) + F(6) = (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(2) + T(6) \\ &:= F(2) - F(4) - F(5) + F(7) = T(2) - T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(5) - F(6) + F(8) = T(3) + T(5) + T(6) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 7 &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(4) + F(6) = -T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) + F(3) - F(2) + F(5) = T(1) - T(3) - T(2) + T(5) \\ &:= F(1) - F(3) - F(5) + F(7) = -T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(5) - F(8) + F(9) = T(1) + T(5) + T(8) - T(9) \\ &:= F(2) + F(4) - F(5) + F(6) = T(2) + T(4) + T(5) - T(6) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(4) + F(5) = -T(2) \times T(3) + T(4) + T(5) \end{aligned}$$

$$8 := -F(1) - F(2) - F(4) + F(7) = (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(4) + T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 9 &:= -F(1) + F(5) - F(6) + F(7) = T(1) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(4) + F(6) = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(4) - T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(3) + F(7) = -T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(4) + F(7) = -T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(5) - F(8) + F(9) = T(2) + T(5) + T(8) - T(9) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(5) + F(4) + F(7) = T(3) - T(5) - T(4) + T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 10 &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(5) + F(7) = -T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(7) + F(8) = -T(1) + T(2) - T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(3) - F(6) + F(8) = T(1) - T(3) - T(6) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 11 &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(4) + F(7) = -T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(6) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(2) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(8) + F(9) = -T(1) + T(2) - T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) + F(3) - F(7) + F(8) = -T(2) + T(3) - T(7) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) + F(5) - F(6) + F(7) = T(2) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(5) + F(3) + F(7) = T(2) \times T(5) - T(3) - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12 &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(4) + F(7) = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(4) - T(7) \\ &:= F(1) - F(3) + F(5) + F(6) = T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(4) - F(5) + F(8) = T(1) - T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(5) + F(6) = T(2) \times T(3) + T(5) - T(6) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(6) + F(8) = T(2) - T(3) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(8) + F(9) = -T(2) + T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$13 := -F(1) - F(3) + F(4) + F(7) = T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14 &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(8) + F(9) = -T(1) + T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(4) + F(7) = -T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(4) - F(5) + F(8) = T(2) - T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(3) - F(5) + F(6) + F(7) = T(3) + T(5) + T(6) - T(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15 &:= -F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(6) = -T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(6) \\ &:= F(1) - F(3) - F(5) + F(8) = -T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) - F(6) + F(8) = T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) - T(8) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(4) + F(7) = T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(5) - F(3) + F(8) = T(2) \times T(5) + T(3) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 16 &:= F(1) + F(3) - F(8) + F(9) = T(1) + T(3) - T(8) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(5) + F(7) = T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(4) + F(8) = (T(1) - T(2)) \times T(4) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17 &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(3) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(2) \times T(3) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(4) + F(6) + F(7) = T(1) \times T(4) - T(6) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(5) + F(7) = (-T(2) + T(3)) \times T(5) - T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(4) + F(8) = -T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= F(2) - F(6) + F(4) + F(8) = T(2) \times T(6) - T(4) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$:= -F(3) + F(4) - F(5) + F(8) = T(3) - T(4) - T(5) + T(8)$$

$$18 := F(1) + F(2) - F(5) + F(8) = -T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(5) + F(7) = T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(4) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(7) + F(9) = -T(1) + T(2) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= F(4) + F(6) - F(7) + F(8) = -T(4) + T(6) - T(7) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20 &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(5) + F(7) = -T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) - F(7) + F(9) = -T(2) + T(3) - T(7) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21 &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(4) + F(8) = T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(3) + F(4) + F(8) = -T(2) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22 &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(7) + F(9) = -T(1) + T(3) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(4) + F(8) = -T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 23 &:= F(1) - F(3) + F(4) + F(8) = -T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(6) + F(7) = T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) - T(7) \\ &:= F(2) - F(3) + F(4) + F(8) = T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(4) - F(6) + F(7) + F(8) = T(4) + T(6) + T(7) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24 &:= F(1) + F(3) - F(7) + F(9) = T(1) + T(3) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(5) + F(8) = (T(1) + T(2)) \times T(5) - T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(4) + F(8) = T(1) + T(3) \times T(4) - T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(4) + F(6) + F(8) = T(1) \times T(4) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) - F(4) + F(5) + F(8) = -T(3) + T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 27 &:= -F(1) + F(3) + F(5) + F(8) = T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) + F(6) + F(8) = T(1) \times T(2) \times T(6) - T(8) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(2) - F(5) + F(9) = -T(1) \times T(2) - T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) - F(6) + F(9) = -T(2) + T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) - F(4) + F(6) + F(8) = -T(2) \times T(4) + T(6) + T(8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 28 &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(6) + F(9) = T(1) + T(2) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(3) - F(4) + F(9) = -T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(4) + F(5) + F(8) = -T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(8) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(6) + F(4) + F(9) = T(2) \times T(6) + T(4) - T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29 &:= F(1) + F(3) - F(6) + F(9) = -T(1) + T(3) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= F(4) + F(7) - F(8) + F(9) = T(4) + T(7) + T(8) - T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 30 &:= -F(1) + F(3) - F(5) + F(9) = (-T(1) + T(3)) \times T(5) - T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(3) - F(2) + F(9) = (T(1) - T(3)) \times T(2) + T(9) \\ &:= F(1) - F(3) - F(4) + F(9) = T(1) - T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(3) + F(4) - F(5) + F(9) = T(3) \times T(4) + T(5) - T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$32 := -F(2) + F(3) - F(4) + F(9) = T(2) - T(3) - T(4) + T(9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33 &:= F(1) + F(2) - F(4) + F(9) = T(1) - T(2) - T(4) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(5) + F(6) + F(8) = T(2) + T(5) - T(6) + T(8) \\ &:= F(3) + F(5) - F(6) + F(9) = -T(3) + T(5) - T(6) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$34 := F(3) - F(5) + F(4) + F(9) = -T(3) - T(5) + T(4) + T(9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36 &:= -F(1) - F(3) + F(5) + F(9) = T(1) \times T(3) - T(5) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) - F(5) + F(6) + F(9) = -T(2) + T(5) - T(6) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37 &:= F(1) + F(4) - F(2) + F(9) = -T(1) - T(4) + T(2) + T(9) \\ &:= F(2) - F(4) + F(5) + F(9) = -T(2) + T(4) - T(5) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38 &:= F(1) - F(5) + F(6) + F(9) = -T(1) + T(5) - T(6) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(1) - F(6) + F(7) + F(9) = T(1) \times T(6) - T(7) + T(9) \\ &:= -F(2) + F(3) + F(4) + F(9) = -T(2) + T(3) - T(4) + T(9) \end{aligned}$$

$$39 := -F(4) + F(6) + F(7) + F(8) = T(4) + T(6) - T(7) + T(8)$$

$$41 := -F(1) + F(4) + F(5) + F(9) = T(1) + T(4) - T(5) + T(9)$$

$$42 := F(4) + F(7) - F(6) + F(9) = -T(4) + T(7) - T(6) + T(9)$$

$$43 := -F(2) - F(4) + F(7) + F(9) = -T(2) \times T(4) + T(7) + T(9)$$

$$45 := -F(3) - F(6) + F(8) + F(9) = T(3) \times T(6) - T(8) - T(9)$$

$$49 := -F(2) + F(7) + F(4) + F(9) = T(2) \times T(7) + T(4) - T(9)$$

$$50 := F(4) - F(6) + F(8) + F(9) = -T(4) - T(6) + T(8) + T(9)$$

$$51 := -F(2) - F(4) + F(8) + F(9) = -T(2) \times T(4) + T(8) + T(9)$$

$$53 := F(2) + F(8) - F(4) + F(9) = T(2) \times T(8) - T(4) - T(9)$$

$$:= -F(3) + F(6) + F(7) + F(9) = T(3) \times T(6) - T(7) - T(9)$$

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References

- [1] H. HEINZ, Narcissistic Numbers, <http://www.magic-squares.net/narciss.htm>.
- [2] H.E. DUDENEY, Amusements in Mathematics, EBD E-Books Directory.com, 1917.
- [3] J.S. MADACHY, Mathematics on Vacations, Charlers Scriber's Son, New York, 1966.
- [4] KNOTT, R., The Mathematical Magic of the Fibonacci Numbers, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Fibonacci/fibmaths.html>
- [5] KNOTT, R., Fibonacci and Lucas Number Calculator, <http://www.maths.surrey.ac.uk/hosted-sites/R.Knott/Fibonacci/fibCalcX.html>
- [6] I.J. TANEJA, 2017 - Mathematical Style, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Article 03, pp.1-17, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a03.pdf>.
- [7] I.J. TANEJA, Hardy Ramanujan Number - 1729, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Article 06, pp.1-50, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a06.pdf>.
- [8] I.J. TANEJA, Factorial-Type Selfie Expressions With Fibonacci and Triangular Values, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 114, pp. 1-52, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a114.pdf>.
- [9] I.J. TANEJA, Fibonacci-Triangular-Type Selfie Expressions - I, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 122, pp. 1-76, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a122.pdf>.
- [10] I.J. TANEJA, Fibonacci-Triangular-Type Selfie Expressions - II, RGMIA Research Report Collection, **20**(2017), Art. 123, pp. 1-68, <http://rgmia.org/papers/v20/v20a123.pdf>.
- [11] I.J. TANEJA, Palindromic-Type Palindromes - I, **Zenodo**, Open Access, January 15, 2019, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2541174>.
- [12] I.J. TANEJA, Triangular-Type Selfie Numebrs, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 17, 2019, pp. 1-91, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2567571>
- [13] I.J. TANEJA, Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 18, 2019, pp. 1-116, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2571472>.
- [14] I.J. TANEJA, Fibonacci Sequence and Selfie Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 19, 2019, pp. 1-233, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2572044>.
- [15] I.J. TANEJA, Same Digits Equalities Expressions, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 19, 2019, pp. 1-182, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2573194>.
- [16] I.J. TANEJA, Factorial-Power Selfie Expressions, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 20, 2019, pp. 1-115, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2573569>.

- [17] I.J. TANEJA, Simultaneous Representations of Selfie Numbers in Terms of Fibonacci and Triangular Numbers, **Zenodo**, Open Access. February 20, 2019, pp. 1-115, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2574136>.
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